

**The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on The Entrepreneurial
Intentions of Students: An Exploration of Nigerian Universities**

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**“I certify that all material in this thesis which is not my own is duly acknowledged. I
have read and understood the section in the programme handbook dealing with
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Author's Declaration

No portion of this work referred in the thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other University or other institute of learning.

Abstract

Entrepreneurship education (EE) has become a key component of higher education, particularly for fostering entrepreneurial intentions among students. Research shows that effective EE not only imparts theoretical knowledge but also develops critical skills such as creativity, innovation, and risk management, essential for business success (Nabi et al., 2017; Kuratko & Morris, 2018). Despite the growth in entrepreneurship education programmes (EEPs), there is limited understanding of their impact, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. This study investigates how EE shapes students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigerian universities, focusing on teaching methods, university support, and their effects on students' skills and intentions.

Using an explanatory sequential design, the study employed in-depth interviews with 9 EE lecturers and a cross-sectional survey of 306 students. The qualitative phase revealed challenges like outdated curriculum, large class sizes, insufficient institutional support, and limited practical learning, all of which hinder the development of entrepreneurial mindsets. Quantitative findings showed that university support and experiential teaching methods significantly influence students' entrepreneurial intentions by improving attitudes and perceived behavioural control. However, societal norms and family pressures also serve as barriers.

The study proposes a framework for assessing the effectiveness of EEPs, which includes programme design, institutional support, stakeholder engagement, and impact evaluation. The findings highlight the need for context-specific curriculum updates, enhanced support structures, and policy alignment to address Nigeria's unique socio-economic challenges. Theoretically, this research adds to the body of knowledge regarding Theory of planned behaviour by emphasizing the need for context-specific adaptations of EE in developing countries. It also challenges existing EE models, typically based on Western frameworks, and provides valuable insights for Nigerian policymakers aiming to improve EE and foster economic growth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship education, Entrepreneurial intentions, University support, Teaching methods, Nigerian universities, educators, Theory of planned behaviour, subjective norms, personal attitudes, perceived behavioural control

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List of Abbreviations

EE	Entrepreneurship Education
EEPs	Entrepreneurship Education Programmes
EI	Entrepreneurial Intentions
TBP	Theory of Planned Behaviour
NUC	National University Commission

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter begins with an overview of the study's context. It will further convey the rationale for the study and its importance. This study presents an overview of its research aims and objectives to shed light on the relevant issues addressed. Additionally, the foundational elements of the rationale emphasize critical concerns in the study. The research's contribution to knowledge is also emphasized. This chapter will then be accompanied by a clear summary of the thesis structure.

1.1 Background of the study

Economic growth has continually been a central focus for researchers in the social sciences, comprising economics, finance, and entrepreneurship. Researchers have identified a connection between economic growth and poverty alleviation through entrepreneurship and technological advancement (McClosky, 2017; Ahlstrom, 2015; Bloom, Sadun & Van Reenen, 2016). Entrepreneurship's role in poverty reduction and economic development research has become an increasingly important area in management studies (Brunton Ahlstrom & Obloj, 2013; Brunton, Ahlstrom & Li, 2016; Chen, Zhou & Yang, 2019) as entrepreneurship has a beneficial effect on economies worldwide, whether they are developed or developing (Aidis, 2005). Studies indicate that entrepreneurship represents a specific form of both unplanned and intentional action, which can enhance economic performance through employment creation, innovation, and development (Karimi et al., 2016; Milana and Wang, 2017).

The significant youth unemployment rates in developing nations, particularly among university graduates, present significant issues because of market saturation and a shortage of available jobs (Longe, 2017). The incorporation of entrepreneurship education (EE) into the ever-changing curriculum of HEIs is of paramount importance, particularly in developing nations. (Li & Matlay, 2005; Pulka, Rikwentishe, & Ibrahim, 2015). Research indicates that EE is one of the most effective methods for facilitating graduates' transition from academia to the workforce (Santos, Roomi, & Linan, 2019; Nwokolo, Akpa, & Onwuka, 2017). According to Katz (2003) and Matlay (2005), this subject has emerged as a primary focus in public policy across developed countries as well as emerging ones. EE enables schools and educational institutions promote entrepreneurship as a legitimate career path, cultivate an entrepreneurial

mindset among young individuals and promote the cultivation of essential entrepreneurial skills and mindsets. As a result, this approach significantly influences both entrepreneurial intentions and the corresponding entrepreneurial actions (Lackéus, 2018; Nabi et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2019)

The goal of EE is to foster students and graduates with the entrepreneurial mindset and skills needed to recognize societal gaps and requirements, generate creative business ideas, and implement those ideas into real-world solutions (QAA, 2018; Shaver & Commarmond, 2019). In essence, the objective is to develop the capacity to envision and develop concepts. Graduates should be able to spot opportunities in business and establish projects, whether by starting new companies or helping already existing ones expand. Entrepreneurship education prepares students for careers in startups, established firms, charities, NGOs, the government, and businesses (QAA, 2012). EEPs are increasingly acknowledged for their essential contribution to fostering entrepreneurial mindsets and behaviours (Kuratko, 2016).

However, to have the most significant possible impact, these programmes must go beyond conventional business models and be thoughtfully planned and organized to guarantee successful results (Lackéus, 2018). Entrepreneurship education promotes students' academic achievement and contributes to their local economies in developing economies. Students develop entrepreneurship awareness, an entrepreneurial attitude, and abilities from an early age to identify opportunities, solve social problems, and boost the economy. This methodology emphasizes practical skills and theoretical understanding to prepare students for entrepreneurship.

In many developing economies, these stages of entrepreneurial development are less well supported and developed than in more advanced economies. Students frequently need help with these stages due to capital shortages, infrastructure issues, and policy support. Therefore, entrepreneurship education in these places must also address these structural constraints to equip students with resilience and adaptation (GEM, 2020; Fayolle, 2013). According to Nabi & Liñán (2011), further research in underdeveloped countries can greatly enhance comprehension and throw more light on the challenges surrounding students' and graduate entrepreneurial goals. Social psychology research continually demonstrates that attitudes significantly impact intention and behaviour (Ajzen, 1991; Armitage & Conner, 2001). In this regard, educational methods or approaches that influence students' attitudes have a higher impact on entrepreneurship education than traditional abilities learning. Attitudes, being

adaptable, can be formed by educators and the learning environment, mainly when it stimulates entrepreneurial behaviour and thought (Nabi et al., 2017; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

This study is set in Nigeria, a developing country in Africa, that possesses abundant human and material resources that present considerable opportunities for growth and development. However, the actual situation reveals a contrasting scenario. Even after more than six decades of political autonomy and a wealth of natural resources, a significant number of Nigerians continue to live in poverty. The gap shows how complicated socio-political and economic issues have slowed the country's progress, preventing its tremendous resources from bringing wealth to its population. Nigeria continues to be the biggest economy in Africa as of 2023, with a GDP of over \$477 billion in 2022. The country's population has reached approximately 224 million, It is now the most populous country in Africa and the seventh most popular country in the world. Nigeria holds a youthful demographic, with approximately 54% of its population aged between 15 and 64 years and roughly 27% categorized as youth (World Bank, 2023; IMF, 2023). Despite its considerable economic potential, Nigeria continues to encounter ongoing challenges associated with unemployment and poverty. The nation experiences spatial inequality, with certain regions exhibiting performance levels akin to middle-income countries, whereas others lag the average of low-income nations. The government has experienced sluggish growth attributed to external shocks, including the COVID-19 pandemic, decreased oil production, and inflation, which peaked at 31.7% in 2024, marking a 24-year high (IMF, 2023). Guerrero (2013) characterises countries such as Nigeria as frontier economies, distinguished by their vast natural resources and inexpensive labour. This data underscores the significance of entrepreneurship and education in fostering sustainable economic growth, particularly in the context of Nigeria's youthful population and their capacity for innovation and financial contribution.

Matanmi and Awodun (2005) assert that dealing with unemployment and poverty in Nigeria calls for an enhanced emphasis on fostering entrepreneurship. The persistence of these challenges is primarily attributed to inadequate capacity building, a lack of understanding, and insufficient support for entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurship plays a significant part in reducing unemployment, especially for young graduates. Therefore, providing students with entrepreneurial skills is essential for addressing this challenge. In today's business contexts, employers are progressively looking for graduates with entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and capabilities which will offer a competitive advantage in an unpredictable environment (Boyles, 2012). Oseni, McGee, and Dabalén (2015) argue that the existing curriculum in Nigerian

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) primarily aims to cultivate civil servants instead of fostering competitive entrepreneurs. The gap shows how important it is for students to learn how to think like entrepreneurs to do well in today's competitive marketplace.

Many studies highlight that entrepreneurship is teachable, with education significantly influencing entrepreneurial intentions and mindsets (Neck and Greene, 2011). Entrepreneurship education serves as an effective mechanism for fostering entrepreneurial activity among students. Education is seen as an essential driver for economic growth, especially in regions such as Africa, where development is necessary for poverty alleviation (World Bank, 2023). This perspective supports the notion that education is a transformative tool for economic empowerment and development, especially in economically disadvantaged societies. In rural and peripheral areas of the UK, education is regarded as essential for community upliftment and the promotion of economic activity (Carter & Jones-Evans, 2012). Kourilsky and Walstad (2007) argue for the early introduction of EE within the school system, noting that schools typically prepare students primarily for salaried employment instead of entrepreneurial activities. This is a matter of concern, as educational institutions are insufficiently preparing students with the requisite knowledge for economic development. The increasing acknowledgment of the significance of EE has resulted in its swift advancement within educational institutions globally (Gurol & Astan, 2006). Hisrich, Peters, and Shepherd (2010) reinforce this view, arguing that EE is crucial for nurturing entrepreneurs. Increasing recognition of the importance of EEPs in HEIs. Also, Volkmann and Audretsch (2017) emphasize the need to cultivate entrepreneurial skills to drive economic growth and innovation. Well-structured EE within HEIs can prepare students to successfully manage the challenges of today's entrepreneurial environment, allowing nations like Nigeria to tap into the potential of their youth for sustained economic development.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The global financial crisis and Nigeria's ongoing economic difficulties stimulated the Federal Government to formally acknowledge the importance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in achieving economic recovery and national growth on a formal basis (Nwekeaku, 2013; Adebayo, Ibrahim & Oke, 2021). In collaboration with higher education institutions, the government has acknowledged entrepreneurship's role in facilitating economic transformation and has actively promoted the pursuit of entrepreneurial ventures among undergraduates. The National Universities Commission (NUC) mandated a two-semester entrepreneurship course for undergraduates in Nigeria in 2006. This programme's stated goal was to provide recent

university graduates with the knowledge and attitude necessary to start their own businesses and innovate in existing ones (Epoch & Edet, 2011; NUC, 2006).

Despite these attempts, the adoption of entrepreneurship education still needs to improve among Nigerian graduates, especially in the Southeast and South-Eastern regions (Siyanbola, Aderemi, Egbetokun & Sanmi, 2009; Okolie, Nwosu & Elom, 2022). The disparity between policy objectives and real entrepreneurship results has prompted concerns regarding the efficacy of these programs in equipping graduates for the entrepreneurial environment. Global trends indicate that nations or regions that promote more entrepreneurs typically realize enhanced economic advantages, as entrepreneurs facilitate value creation by identifying new markets and economic opportunities (Ahmed & Hoffman, 2012; Pitan & Adedeji, 2021). Despite these attempts, the adoption of entrepreneurship education is still notably low among Nigerian graduates, especially in the South-South and South-Eastern regions (Siyanbola et al., 2009; Okolie et al., 2022). The gap between policy intentions and real entrepreneurial outcomes has prompted concerns regarding the efficacy of these programs in equipping graduates for the entrepreneurial environment. Global trends indicate that nations or regions that promote a higher number of entrepreneurs typically realize enhanced economic advantages, as entrepreneurs facilitate value creation through the identification of new markets and economic opportunities (Ahmed & Hoffman, 2012; Pitan & Adedeji, 2021). The mismatch between educational outcomes and labour market requirements remains, with underemployment also constituting a notable concern. In 2021, reports indicated that a significant number of graduates are underemployed, with around 22.8% of the workforce engaged in positions below their qualifications or in part-time roles that do not fulfil their expectations (NBS, 2020). Addressing this challenge has emerged as a significant concern for policymakers, given that rising unemployment and underemployment rates undermine the nation's socio-economic stability.

The impact of EE on students' entrepreneurial attitudes has been examined across developed nations (Packham, Packham, Jones, Miller, Pickernell & Thomas, 2010; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Studies like Yatu and Shamsudeen (2018) show there is a significant lack of extensive study in developing economies such as Nigeria. Furthermore, numerous studies (Hussain, Bhuiyan & Bakar, 2010; Nabi & Liñán, 2011) demonstrate that factors which relates to the context, including cultural and socio-economic elements, can significantly impact the dynamics of entrepreneurship education's effect on students (Akinbola, Ogundipe & Agboola, 2020; Mbeteh, 2018). This underscores the need for more investigation into the operation of

EE within the Nigerian context and its possible modification to better address the requirements of students in the present landscape.

Other studies have indicated clear evidence of stakeholders' growing interest and dedication to promoting entrepreneurship as a viable career alternative, particularly in industrialized nations. Nevertheless, likened to developing countries, research indicates that emerging economies have made significant progress in leveraging the advantages of entrepreneurship and EE to promote entrepreneurial initiatives and economic growth (Smallbone, Welter & Ateljevic, 2014). Emerging economies experience institutional problems, insufficient financing, and customs that may discourage risk-taking and innovation (Acs, Szerb & Autio, 2017). Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African nations have structural and systemic constraints that hinder EEPs (Edoho, 2016). In many developing nations, entrepreneurial education emphasizes theory rather than practice, which limits its potential to motivate entrepreneurial activity or build the skills needed to start and scale enterprises (Nabi et al., 2017). These regions have promising entrepreneurial potential. As globalisation increases and emerging nations integrate into the global economy, entrepreneurship's role in innovation and economic stability becomes clearer. Well-designed entrepreneurship education programs can empower students to start businesses, especially in resource-constrained conditions (Gielnik, Zacher & Frese, 2015).

According to Fiet (2001), there is a need to be more specific about how we educate our entrepreneurs. When educational theories and teaching methods are combined with entrepreneurship studies, it might help students develop more entrepreneurial skills and meet the learning goals set for EE. (Fayolle, 2013). Various studies have highlighted the ambiguity and need for more agreement regarding optimal approaches to teaching entrepreneurship education (EE). One perspective suggests that the diversity in teaching methods is closely linked to differing assumptions about the definition of EE and the intended learning outcomes for students in entrepreneurship courses (Benneth, 2005). Hannon (2006) notes that different beliefs about education affect how teachers do their jobs in the classroom. Different learning outcomes in environmental education require different teaching methods and approaches to be successful. The literature review on entrepreneurship education indicates a need for a more comprehensive understanding of the current teaching methods employed by university faculty and the effectiveness of these practices (Fayolle, 2013). Entrepreneurship educators must integrate innovative teaching approaches, necessitating an exploration of the criteria and rationale behind their selection and application of pedagogical methods. Ultimately, the emphasis in education is shifting from teaching to learning. Researchers should focus on how

entrepreneurship should be learned rather than how it should be taught (Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2014).

The necessity for entrepreneurship educators to possess knowledge of effective pedagogical methods for fostering entrepreneurial thinking and skills in university students is increasing. This is considering the recognised complexity and uncertainty inherent in entrepreneurship education (Neck & Greene, 2011) and its positive influence on participants' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship (Mueller, 2011). Entrepreneurship education is expected to be well established, involving an established framework and specific concepts. Studies note that this case differs, as certain areas require further investigation to yield effective results. University entrepreneurship programmes have been established for over a decade, and further research is necessary, especially regarding these courses' types, objectives, and outcomes (Kuratko & Morris, 2018). This supports Fiet's (2001) suggestion for increased clarity in entrepreneurial education. Several critical aspects of entrepreneurship education inform the study's objective. The initial aspect encountered by the researcher during the review of literature on EE pertains to the question highlighted by Kuratko (2005): 'What should be taught in EE, and way it can be taught?'

Recently, Nigerian HEIs have notably increased the availability of EEPs. These initiatives are expected to yield positive outcomes; however, additional evaluation of their effectiveness remains necessary (Sofoluwe, Shokunbi, Raimi, & Ajewole, 2013). This study aims to address this gap by exploring how EE in Nigerian universities influences students' entrepreneurial intentions, focusing specifically on the challenges educators face and the skills and competencies students develop through these programs. Utilizing a mixed-method approach, the research will explore the effectiveness of teaching methods, the role of university support, and how these factors collectively contribute to fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students.

1.3 Justification of Research

Entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in boosting economies, creating jobs, and fostering innovation on a worldwide scale. Most research on the efficacy of EEPs in fostering entrepreneurial mindsets and ambitions has been conducted in developed economies (Bosma et al., 2020; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). These economies like the US, UK or Canada have established ecosystems that promote EE through access to resources, infrastructure, and a supportive institutional framework. These countries benefit from robust educational

infrastructure, supportive ecosystems, and a well-established entrepreneurial culture. Emerging economies, such as Nigeria, differ significantly in these areas. Factors such as institutional weaknesses, socio-economic instability, and cultural constraints often hinder the successful implementation of EE (Naudé, 2010; Bruton et al., 2013).

Agbim (2018) states that entrepreneurship is being increasingly viewed to address Nigeria's high rates of youth unemployment, especially among recent graduates. Despite government initiatives and policy reforms designed to enhance entrepreneurship education across various levels, a gap exists in empirical evidence concerning the effectiveness of these programmes in fostering entrepreneurial outcomes. Recent studies indicate that although entrepreneurship education is being introduced in Nigerian universities, it may need to be improved in structure, support, and practical emphasis necessary to influence students' entrepreneurial intentions significantly (Adedokun et al., 2020). This emphasizes how crucial it is to understand the difficulties students and educators encounter when providing and acquiring the positive effects of entrepreneurship education in this unique context.

Understanding how context-specific elements, like teaching methods and pedagogy, access to institutional support, and the current economic circumstances, influence students' entrepreneurial development is one of the primary objectives behind this study. Studies demonstrate that when integrated with practical experience, educational settings can significantly improve students' confidence in their entrepreneurial skills, which is essential for turning goals into tangible entrepreneurial activities (Liñán & Chen, 2009). In Nigeria, the difference between how entrepreneurship is taught in schools and the practical reality of initiating a business frequently results in students being inadequately equipped for entrepreneurial activity (Okeke-Uzodike & Subban, 2015). Examining this disparity and determining methods to reconcile it is necessary to improve entrepreneurship education's efficacy in the Nigerian HEIs.

In addition, the socio-economic barriers that exist in emerging economies, including limited access to funding, inadequate institutional frameworks, and a lack of mentorship opportunities, hinder students' capacity to translate entrepreneurial intentions into actual goals (Brixiová, Ncube & Bicaba, 2020; Miao, Qian & Ma, 2017; Gibson & Vaart, 2014). These challenges frequently hinder the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education, as students encounter considerable difficulties in obtaining the resources and networks essential for initiating successful ventures (Urban, 2019; Smith, McElwee & Dodd, 2016). This research investigates

barriers within the Nigerian context to offer insights on personalizing entrepreneurship education to the specific needs of Nigerian students. The findings will guide educational policy reforms prioritizing practical, hands-on learning, mentorship, and resource accessibility, thereby improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Kew, Herrington, Litovsky & Gale, 2013). This approach may facilitate students' transition from entrepreneurial intentions to actionable ventures, notwithstanding the challenging economic landscape. This study is timely as Nigeria's economy evolves. With the government's efforts to initiate initiatives to broaden the economic base beyond oil and foster innovation-driven growth, entrepreneurship has influenced economic policy discussions (World Bank, 2020). The study on EE will improve policy suggestions and provide insights for universities, educators, and government. An evidence-based understanding of these programmes impact can guide the designing and implementation of EE tailored to Nigeria's socio-economic realities, fostering a new generation of entrepreneurs who can contribute to national development (Nabi et al., 2017).

In Nigeria, despite the incorporation of EE as a mandatory component of undergraduate programmes since 2006, its execution and effects vary significantly across different geopolitical regions. National statistics reveal a persistently high rate of graduate unemployment, with scant evidence that EE alone has influenced entrepreneurial results (Agbonlahor, 2016). A comprehensive mixed-methods investigation conducted in public universities discovered that although EE is implemented, critical challenges such as its relevance to local economies, insufficient funding, and poor institutional coordination consistently hinder its efficacy (Iweh, Yukongdi & Bhujel, 2021). These results highlight a disparity between policy objectives and the impact at the student level, underscoring an urgent need for research that explores how EE operates within Nigeria's unique institutional and socio-economic landscape. By including universities across all three southern zones, this study captures both ends of the implementation spectrum: the relatively robust environment in the South-West and the constrained EE landscapes in the South-East and South-South. This design allows for a nuanced analysis of how institutional strength, curriculum relevance, and local entrepreneurial ecosystems converge or fail to in shaping students' intentions and perceived capabilities. While EE is a national policy in Nigeria, its delivery and outcomes vary substantially across regions. The southern regions host a significant proportion of the country's universities and student population (NUC, 2023). These zones present diverse institutional landscapes, making them ideal for a comparative investigation. According to JAMB (2022),

over half of all university admissions in Nigeria occur in southern institutions, which positions these regions as a focal point for understanding student experiences with EE. Conversely, universities in the South-East (e.g., Enugu, Ebonyi) and South-South (e.g., Rivers, Delta, Calabar) regions have garnered significantly less academic focus, despite hosting a considerable share of Nigeria's higher education sector. Akuegwu and Nwi-ue (2016) indicate that EE in South-South universities is plagued by minimal interaction with the entrepreneurship culture: inadequate facilities, limited application of the curriculum, and low student confidence in launching ventures. Likewise, a study in the South-East identified systemic shortcomings such as a lack of trained EE faculty, funding deficiencies, and outdated curricula leading to students who are disengaged and ill-prepared for entrepreneurial careers (Nwachukwu & Okpo, 2018).

Furthermore, the selection of universities in these three southern zones is grounded in their contrasting levels of institutional development and entrepreneurial ecosystem maturity. The South-West is home to some of Nigeria's most established universities, characterised by relatively better infrastructure, stronger university industry linkages, and broader exposure to entrepreneurial ecosystems (Adeeko, 2023). Including institutions from the South-West, South-East, and South-South allows the study to engage with the complexities of EE implementation within Nigeria's decentralised and regionally diverse higher education system.

Ultimately, the incorporation of universities from the Southern regions facilitates more balanced and policy-relevant findings. Rather than generalizing the challenges and outcomes of EE across the entire country, this approach recognizes that students' learning experiences and entrepreneurial growth are profoundly influenced by their institutional and regional contexts. This geographical spread enriches the analytical scope of the study and aligns with its broader goal: to generate evidence-based recommendations for designing effective and equitable EE frameworks that reflect Nigeria's diverse educational landscape.

In conclusion, this study seeks to address the current gap in the literature while also providing valuable policy recommendations to improve the entrepreneurial ecosystem within the country. By gaining a comprehensive insight into the unique challenges and opportunities present in Nigerian universities, the study can contribute to creating a more effective and contextually appropriate entrepreneurship education framework.

1.4 Research Aims and Objectives

The main aim of the research is to thoroughly examine the effect of entrepreneurship education programmes in Nigerian universities on students' entrepreneurial intention to determine the effectiveness on their outcomes. In addition, evaluating the connection between educational curriculum and real-world industry challenges can help identify ways to improve these programs to prepare students for entrepreneurial success. This study will help explain how universities influence Nigeria's entrepreneurial ecosystem and generate policy recommendations to enhance EE.

1.4.1 Research Objectives

The specific objectives include:

RO1: To critically investigate how entrepreneurship educators define Entrepreneurship Education and teaching methods.

RO2: to critically investigate the challenges confronting EE learning in Nigeria from the educator's viewpoint.

RO3: To critically identify skills, competencies, and capabilities students develop from participating in EEPs.

RO4: To critically explore the effectiveness of teaching approaches for entrepreneurial learning in Nigerian Universities to foster entrepreneurial intentions among students.

RO5: To develop a framework for the effective assessment of entrepreneurship programmes in Nigerian universities

1.4.2 Justification of Research Objectives

RO1: To critically investigate how entrepreneurship educators define Entrepreneurship Education and teaching methods. Through a critical examination of the definition and delivery of entrepreneurship education by entrepreneurship educators at Nigerian universities, this research seeks to determine if the pedagogical approaches now in use meet the demands of students. The resources and methods employed in lectures are directly affected by educators' various viewpoints about what makes for good entrepreneurship education (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Better knowledge of these concepts can assist in identifying how well entrepreneurship education adapts to build real-world entrepreneurial abilities (Neck & Corbett, 2018). Given the ever-changing nature of entrepreneurship, it is crucial to comprehend various perspectives

held by educators regarding the best ways to teach to keep the curriculum up-to-date and applicable.

RO2: to critically investigate the challenges confronting EE learning in Nigeria from the educator's viewpoint. This study will shed light on the challenges that educators in Nigerian universities encounter when teaching entrepreneurship. Previous studies show that educators in emerging economies like Nigeria face restrictions such as low resources, inadequate training, and outdated curriculum that inhibit entrepreneurial skill development (Adejumo, Oladipupo & Ajiboye, 2020). Understanding these obstacles from educators' perspectives helps identify areas for improvement and ensures that entrepreneurship education programs meet students' and the economy's needs (Isaacs, Visse, Friedrich, & Brijlal, 2007).

RO3: To critically identify the skills, competencies, and capabilities students develop from participating in EEPs. This objective is to assess the skills and competencies students develop through entrepreneurial education programmes. The research will establish whether these programs provide students with entrepreneurial abilities, including opportunity awareness, risk management, and innovation, by critically examining their competencies (Cope, 2005). About curriculum quality and practical application, entrepreneurship education can significantly improve students' ability to handle real-world entrepreneurial challenges (Gielnik et al., 2015). This objective will evaluate these skills' relevance to Nigerian entrepreneurship.

RO4: To critically explore the effectiveness of teaching approaches for entrepreneurial learning in Nigerian Universities to foster EI among students. By exploring the effectiveness of various teaching approaches used in Nigerian universities, as part of the aim of this study, it will evaluate how different teaching methods affect students' desire to become entrepreneurs. Methods like experiential learning, project-based activities, and case studies have demonstrated their effectiveness in boosting entrepreneurial intentions by offering practical exposure and hands-on experience (Neck & Greene, 2011). In many developing countries, the most common form of teaching continues to be traditional lecture-based teaching, which may not adequately motivate or prepare students for success in entrepreneurship (Rideout & Grey, 2013). This study will explore the extent to which Nigerian universities are employing teaching methods that encourage entrepreneurial mindsets and intentions, which are crucial for cultivating a culture of innovation and self-employment.

RO5: To develop a framework for the effective assessment of entrepreneurship programmes in Nigerian universities. This study develops a framework for evaluating entrepreneurship

education programmes to help policymakers and educators improve the field. Many Nigerian institutions need institutional entrepreneurship programme assessment methods, making it difficult to quantify their impact on students' entrepreneurial desires and outcomes (Nabi et al., 2017). A well-designed framework allows for systematic evaluation and reveals successes and areas for improvement. This would help match educational programs with Nigeria's changing economic landscape, where entrepreneurship drives improvements. This framework would not only help universities assess the effectiveness of their programmes but would also enable policymakers to ensure that EE contributes meaningfully to the country's economic development goals (Ihugba, Odi, Njoku, 2013; Adebayo, 2019).

1.4.3 Research Questions

RQ1: How do Entrepreneurship Educators define EE? And what teaching methods are utilized?

RQ2: What are the challenges confronting EE Learning from the educator's viewpoint?

RQ3: What are the skills, competencies, and capabilities developed from participating in Entrepreneurship Education Programmes in Nigeria?

RQ4: What are the teaching approaches most effective for teaching entrepreneurship in Nigerian Universities?

RQ5: What strategies can enhance entrepreneurship education in Nigeria to effectively develop the necessary entrepreneurial skills and intentions among students?

1.5 Scope of Study

This study seeks to examine how EEPs in Nigerian universities influence students' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The research will examine the structure of these programmes, the teaching methods employed, and the results regarding the skills, competencies, and entrepreneurial mindsets cultivated in students. In addition, the challenges encountered by educators in providing EE will be explored, the extent to which these programmes correspond with the requirements of students, and the wider Nigerian entrepreneurial environment. With a focus on Nigeria's South-South, South-East, and South-West regions. In addition, it aims to enhance academic and policy dialogues regarding advancing entrepreneurship education within Nigerian universities (Pulka et al., 2015; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

The research employs a mixed-method strategy, which involves combining qualitative and quantitative data to understand the subject comprehensively. Educators from Nigerian

universities participated in semi-structured interviews via Zoom during the initial phase. This method enabled a comprehensive examination of the difficulties and experiences encountered by educators in the delivery of EE. It also provided valuable insights into their viewpoints on curriculum design, teaching methodologies, and institutional support (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The utilisation of interviews is in adherence to previous research that has illustrated the importance of obtaining educators' perspectives when assessing the efficacy of EEPs (Isaacs et al., 2007). During the second phase, a quantitative survey was conducted among students and university graduates in the chosen regions utilizing Microsoft Forms. The survey included open-ended questions, facilitating the acquisition of comprehensive data regarding students' entrepreneurial intentions, the abilities cultivated through entrepreneurship programs, and their perceptions of university support (Neck & Greene, 2011). Open-ended questions facilitated a deeper understanding of how these programmes influence entrepreneurial success on students and graduates. This online method allowed for an expanded reach, promoting student involvement throughout the designated zones.

The study is grounded on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), which acts as the conceptual foundation for the survey design. The TBP is commonly used in the field of entrepreneurship to explore the connections among attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, and entrepreneurial intentions (Ajzen, 1991; Kautonen et al., 2015). Furthermore, TBP informed the quantitative analysis by examining the impact of educational programmes on the attitudes of students towards entrepreneurship, perceived social norms and their confidence in successfully starting and managing businesses (Liñán & Chen, 2009). The use of qualitative and quantitative data yields a comprehensive framework for evaluating the impact of EE within Nigeria, presenting valuable theoretical insights alongside practical suggestions for policy enhancement and educational reform.

1.6 Contribution to Knowledge

This research's first noteworthy addition is its capacity to provide context-specific insights into teaching entrepreneurship firstly in a developing economy and secondly at Nigerian institutions, emphasizing the South-South, South-East, and South-West areas. Although global studies on EE have primarily focused on developed economies, there has been significantly less exploration into the operation of these programmes in emerging markets such as Nigeria. This study examines the influence of local factors, such as University support and teaching methods, on the delivery and outcomes of EE in various Nigerian regions. The contextual approach has significance as the entrepreneurial landscape in Nigeria is influenced by factors

that differ from those in developed countries, such as institutional limitations, socio-economic challenges, and cultural attitudes towards entrepreneurship (Acs et al., 2017). Nigerian students encounter barriers, including limited access to financing, inadequate funding and assistance systems, and socio-cultural expectations that could hinder risk-taking or entrepreneurial activities (Abam, 2018). This research examines regional variations in the perception, delivery, and reception of South-South, South-East, and South-West programs. Understanding these differences is essential for identifying localised barriers and opportunities influencing entrepreneurial intentions among educators and students.

The second contribution of this study is the utilisation of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as a conceptual framework to comprehend students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigerian universities. The TPB is a crucial framework for forecasting intentional behaviour by examining the interaction of attitudes, subjective standards, and perceived behavioural control in influencing human intentions (Ajzen, 1991). This research expands the TPB by integrating university support and pedagogical methods as additional variables to assess their influence on students' entrepreneurial attitudes and behaviours. The inclusion of these contextual enhances the research by illustrating the broader educational environment that shapes students' entrepreneurial intentions. University support, encompassing access to entrepreneurial resources, mentorship, and practical opportunities, significantly influences students' perceived behavioural control, which reflects their belief in their capacity to become entrepreneurs (Saeed et al., 2015). Furthermore, instructional approaches promoting active learning and practical experience are essential for improving attitudes toward entrepreneurship and enhancing students' perceptions of entrepreneurial competence (Neck & Greene, 2011). This research utilizes the TPB to elucidate the interplay between contextual factors and psychological drivers affecting entrepreneurial intentions in emerging economies, enhancing the theoretical comprehension of EE's significance and providing a framework for future studies in analogous contexts. Incorporating university support and pedagogy into the TPB model facilitates a thorough examination of the elements influencing students' entrepreneurial intentions, establishing a foundation for additional research in other developing economies (Kautonen, Van Gelderen & Fink, 2015).

The third significant contribution is establishing a systematic framework for assessing EEPs in Nigerian universities. According to Nabi et al. (2017), a significant obstacle facing higher education institutions in Nigeria is the lack of official assessment methods to gauge how EE has affected students' aspirations to become entrepreneurs and abilities. Without a framework,

educators and policymakers face challenges in evaluating the effectiveness of programmes in achieving their objectives or supporting national economic goals. This study addresses the identified need by developing a framework that integrates essential elements, including instructional strategies, institutional support, and programme results, facilitating a more systematic assessment of these initiatives. The framework holds significant relevance in emerging economies such as Nigeria, where entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth and decreasing youth unemployment (Oseni et al., 2015). Aligning the evaluation framework with Nigeria's social and economic requirements ensures that the results possess both academic value and practical relevance. This framework serves as a tool for ongoing improvement, allowing universities to regularly evaluate their EEPs, pinpoint areas for enhancement, and modify their strategies to better prepare students with the skills and mindsets required for success in the entrepreneurial environment. This contribution is essential for establishing a sustainable entrepreneurship ecosystem in Nigeria, necessitating a strong connection between education, market demands, and the country's broader economic objectives (Sánchez, 2013; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

1.7 Structure of Thesis

This thesis comprises seven chapters, each providing a detailed analysis of the effect of EE on the EI of students in Nigerian universities. The structure facilitates an organized progression of information, beginning with the introduction of the research context, followed by the presentation of findings, and concluding with implications and recommendations.

The thesis begins with Chapter 1: Introduction, establishing the groundwork for the study by detailing the background and context of EE in Nigeria. The focus is on the research problem of unemployment and the potential role of EE in addressing this challenge, in addition to a description of the study's aims and questions. This section gives the brief overview of the research methods used for the study and outlines the theoretical framework, finishing with an insight into the chapters that follow.

Chapter 2 examines the current literature on EE globally and in Nigeria. It reviews studies related to the issues outlined in Chapter One, refining and identifying research questions. The chapter examines entrepreneurship, education, and the support systems needed to enhance entrepreneurial capacity within the economy. By conducting a literature review on EE, this section aims to provide both methodological and theoretical insights for the study, clarifying the research challenges identified. Additionally, Chapter 2 critically assesses evidence related

to EE, entrepreneurial intentions, and Ajzen's TBP. It discusses teaching methodologies, university support, and pedagogical approaches in EE. The review highlights research gaps, particularly in emerging economies like Nigeria, and proposes how this study will address these gaps.

Chapter 3 outlines the methodological frameworks established to address the research problem. This chapter defines the philosophical stance of the study, followed by the adopted method. The researcher determined that a mixed-method strategy would yield the best results for this study, and the rationale for this choice is provided; therefore, this chapter establishes its implementation at different stages of the research process. Additionally, the method section describes the procedures for developing the data collection tools, sample strategies, data analysis procedures, and ethical considerations for this study.

Chapter 4 outlines the Data Presentation and Analysis, which has 2 parts. The first part focuses on the qualitative data collected from the interviews with educators, presenting the findings through thematic analysis. This chapter explores key themes such as the definition of EE, the perceived role of EE in Nigeria, challenges educators face, the teaching methods used, and the identification of university support available for students. The second part focuses on the open-ended responses from the surveys.

Chapter 5 includes the quantitative data from the survey, which use descriptive and inferential statistics to examine the influence of EE on students' entrepreneurial goals.

Chapter 6 provides an in-depth exploration of the findings, synthesising the analyses from Chapters 4 and 5. linking the results to the research objectives and the literature discussed in Chapter 2. This chapter examines the implications of the findings concerning EE in Nigerian universities, focusing on the effectiveness of teaching methods and institutional support in promoting entrepreneurial intentions. The results of the qualitative data will be combined with the quantitative data. Additionally, this chapter will develop a framework for assessing the effectiveness of EE in Nigerian universities.

Chapter 7 provides a conclusion and recommendations. This chapter presents a summary of the key findings of the research and analyses their significance in relation to the research questions formulated. This chapter presents recommendations aimed at enhancing EE in Nigerian universities, focussing on curriculum design, pedagogical approaches, and institutional support structures. The study acknowledges its limitations and proposes potential

avenues for future research, specifically advocating for the expansion of the framework established in this thesis to other regions or countries with similar socio-economic contexts.

1.8 Summary of Chapter

Entrepreneurship education programmes' (EEPs) effects on Nigerian university students' entrepreneurial goals are examined in this chapter. It begins by explaining the research's background and reasoning, emphasizing entrepreneurship's growing importance in Nigeria's unemployment crisis. Considering the elevated unemployment rate, particularly among university graduates, EE has been positioned as an essential tool for encouraging entrepreneurial intentions and reducing reliance on conventional job options. The chapter describes the research challenge, highlighting the lack of attention in Nigerian university EEPs efficacy studies. Despite Nigerian government initiatives to integrate entrepreneurship into university curriculum, there is no empirical evidence on how well these programmes prepare students for entrepreneurial jobs. The research aims to determine how these programmes affect students' entrepreneurial goals and what skills and competencies they acquire. This research is grounded in Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour.

Lastly, the chapter also briefly describes the research technique, which will include qualitative educator interviews and a quantitative student survey. This strategy will help instructors and students understand how entrepreneurship education programs are presented and perceived. The introductory chapter finishes with the thesis structure, defining the chapters' substance and focus.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

The literature review examines fundamental concepts for understanding entrepreneurship education (EE) and entrepreneurial intentions (EI). The review of the development of entrepreneurship theory subsequently engages in an in-depth analysis of the importance of entrepreneurial education in enhancing entrepreneurial skills. This study examines various pedagogical approaches, including traditional and experiential learning methods, and the challenges encountered by environmental education in Nigeria. Furthermore, foundational theories such as Theory of Planned Behaviour and Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model are examined to contextualize the study's conceptual framework. Finally, the chapter highlights limitations in the current literature to highlight the study's unique contribution.

2.1 The Concept and Evolution of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship has a long and storied history, with its roots tracing back to the early 18th century. The term "entrepreneur" was first introduced by the Irish economist Richard Cantillon in his seminal work "Essai sur la Nature du Commerce en Général" (1755). Cantillon defined an entrepreneur as an individual who undertakes the risk of buying goods at certain prices to sell them at uncertain prices. This early definition highlighted the entrepreneurial role in market stabilization by assuming risk and uncertainty. Over time, the definition and measurement of entrepreneurship have undergone significant evolution, incorporating new concepts and categories. Scholars in the field argue that entrepreneurship is a complex phenomenon, characterized by diverse definitions and interpretations (Desai, 2016; Szerb, Smith, and Johnson, 2017). The diversity in definitions and measures of entrepreneurship has contributed to a lack of clarity in the literature regarding its role in the process of economic growth. Recognizing the multidimensional nature of entrepreneurship, some studies have sought to delineate boundaries within the field, aiming to clarify "what is not entrepreneurship" (Bruyat & Julien, 2001; Busenitz, West, Shepherd, Nelson, Chandler, and Zacharakis, 2003).

Ferreira, Fernandes, and Ratten (2015) draw attention to the impact of other disciplines, such as strategic management, which makes it more challenging to draw boundaries within the subject of entrepreneurship. Studies like Davidsson (2016) have shown an overlap between entrepreneurship and small business. However, important studies such as those done by Birch

(1979; 1987), have shown that new entrepreneurial endeavours with the potential to be innovative and growth-oriented, as opposed to small businesses in general, are the main source of new jobs being created. A paradigm changes from appreciating small businesses to appreciating the significance of new venture entrance was brought about by Birch's research (Haltiwanger, Jarmin, and Miranda, 2013; Davidsson, 2016). However, recent studies (Gupta & MacMillan, 2018; Van Praag & Versloot, 2019) recognize the role of entrepreneurship in corporations, highlighting it as a form of intrapreneurship. Entrepreneurship is defined by Wiklund et al. (2011) as the introduction of new economic activity, regardless of the type of economic agent involved. Lastly, it is important to note yet another important area of overlap between entrepreneurship and innovation in the literature. Based on Davidsson (2003), the multiplicity of definitions of entrepreneurship is a result of the concept's complexity. Academics have attempted to describe entrepreneurship in terms of (i) personal traits, which are characteristics that people are born with; (ii) actions, which are the steps taken to recognize and take advantage of possibilities for profit (Kirzner, 1983); and (iii) results, which are the achievements or failures of new businesses.

In addition, researchers have also defined entrepreneurship based on the economic domain, i.e., commercial and social entrepreneurship (Estrin, Mickiewicz, and Stephan, 2016). Also, as discussed earlier, researchers have questioned whether entrepreneurship is only related to small firms or whether it also happens in other organizational contexts, and whether the term is linked to the purpose, growth, innovation, and success of the venture. Baumol (1968) highlighted the difficulties of defining and measuring the impact of entrepreneurs, asserting that: *“the entrepreneur is at the same time one of the most intriguing and one of the most elusive characters in the cast that constitutes economic analysis”*. (p.48)

There are four methods to assist scholars in defining entrepreneurship as identified by Casson and Wadeson (2007, p. 240). To be considered an entrepreneur, they contend, one must consider an individual's function which includes creativity and risk-taking abilities, the role which includes ownership, and personal qualities which include attitudes and behaviours which includes leadership abilities. It is considered that both the role and the function are influenced by the individual's traits. The unique behaviour of the entrepreneur is then linked to the role, function, and personal traits that are taken together.

In addition, the study of entrepreneurship is highlighted by Shane and Venkataraman (2000) who propose a framework that emphasizes the role of opportunities, individuals, and resources

in entrepreneurial behaviour. Their framework aligns with Casson and Wadeson's approach by considering personal characteristics (individuals) and actions (opportunities and resources) as central to understanding entrepreneurship. Both Casson and Wadeson (2007) and Shane and Venkataraman (2000) contribute to the understanding of entrepreneurship by highlighting the interplay between personal characteristics, the actions, and the role of entrepreneurs within their ventures.

The definition of entrepreneurship encompasses a variety of individual-level decisions, including those made regarding self-employment (Blanchflower, 2000), the creation of new firms (Gartner, 1988; Reynolds et al., 2005), the perception of opportunities (Shaney and Venkataraman, 2000), and the discovery of new market opportunities (Kirzner, 1973).

2.1.1 Evolution of Entrepreneurship Theory

Entrepreneurship has evolved alongside the economic theory from its 18th-century conception to its 21st-century understanding. Early economists like Richard Cantillon introduced risk-taking and resource allocation, which shaped modern entrepreneurship. The scholars later integrated entrepreneurship with economic principles like innovation, competition, and market equilibrium. The global economy changed entrepreneurship ideas from classical to modern, emphasizing innovation, opportunity recognition, and entrepreneurs' role in disrupting and stabilizing economies. Entrepreneurial schools of thought have emerged in the 20th and 21st centuries, shedding light on how entrepreneurs drive economic growth and innovation. This section will trace the history of entrepreneurial thought from early classical economists to modern theorists and classify these concepts into the different schools of thought that have impacted our knowledge of entrepreneurship. The table below summarizes these developments:

Table 1: Summary of the Evolution of Entrepreneurship Theory

School of Thought	Contributor	Key Definition/Contribution
French Classical School of Thought	Richard Cantillon (1680-1734)	Defined the entrepreneur as a risk-taker and arbitrageur, buying at known prices and selling at uncertain ones. introducing the idea of risk-bearing as a key entrepreneurial function. This early formal description set the stage for later discussions on the entrepreneur's role in economic systems (Thorsteinson, 2021).
	Francois Quesnay (1694-1774)	focused on the distribution of wealth within an economy and the output of various social classes, particularly entrepreneurs. The basis for comprehending the role of the entrepreneur in resource management and wealth creation in a systematized economy was established by Quesnay's <i>Tableau Economique</i> . (Thorsteinson, 2020).
	Anne-Robert- Jacques Turgot (1727-1781)	emphasized entrepreneurs' role in economic progress through innovation and resource allocation, and his work shaped classical economics. He updated Cantillon's theories about entrepreneurship and stated that capital ownership and entrepreneurship constitute distinct concepts (Pittaway, 2012).
	Jean- Baptiste Say (1767-1832)	Described the entrepreneur as a coordinator of production factors who creates value by transferring resources from low to high productivity. Foss & Klein, 2012) Say developed Cantillon's concepts from risk to innovation and resource organization
The British Classical School of Economic Thought	Adam Smith (1723-1790)	Defined entrepreneurs as part of the broader economic system, allocating resources for optimal production guided by the "invisible hand." Smith's <i>Wealth of Nations</i> highlights the role of entrepreneurship in wealth creation and economic efficiency (Schumacher, 2011).
	David Ricardo (1772-1793)	Developed the theory of comparative advantage, which focuses on how businesses and countries should allocate their resources to get the most out of trade and output by focusing on areas where they are relatively more efficient. This leads to increased international trade and economic growth (Irwin, 2019).
	James Mill (1773-1836)	contributed to classical economics by supporting the labour theory of value, free trade, and limited government involvement. He did this by saying that market competition and rational self-interest would lead to the best economic results (Saito, 2018).

	John Stuart Mill (1806-1873)	distinguished entrepreneurs from capitalists by identifying the entrepreneur as the key decision-maker and risk-bearer in business. He emphasized the entrepreneur's crucial role in driving economic progress through innovation and management (Kelly, 2019)
The Neoclassical School of Economic Thought	Marie-Esprit-Leon Walras (1834-1910)	developed a general equilibrium theory state that entrepreneurs balance supply and demand by reallocating resources, which is crucial in competitive markets. This made entrepreneurs crucial to market dynamics and resource allocation (Backhouse, 2021).
	Alfred Marshall (1842-1924)	saw the entrepreneur as the driver of the market's supply and demand, optimizing production with resources. His Principles of Economics demonstrated the importance of entrepreneurs' innovation and resource management in market competition and economic growth (Groenewegen, 2019).
	Carl Menger (1840-1921)	emphasized entrepreneurs' importance in coordinating output by understanding and acting on market signals. His subjective theory of value was built on his argument that traders are very important in setting prices and allocating resources because they can judge value and change supply to meet demand (Boettke and Leeson, 2015)
Austrian School of Economic Thought	Joseph Schumpeter (1883-1950)	Introduced the idea of "creative destruction," which says entrepreneurs change the economy by bringing new products to markets that destroy old industries and replace them with new ones. His theory stressed how important entrepreneurs are for bringing about rapid economic growth (Garrouste, 2016).
	Israel Kirzner (1930-)	Define entrepreneurship as finding and exploiting opportunities, especially in market turmoil. He believed entrepreneurs discover inefficiencies and link supply and demand to restore market balance (Foss & Klein, 2012).
Schumpeterian School of Thought	Joseph Schumpeter (1883-1950)	placed the entrepreneur as a key leader in new ideas and economic growth, with the job of bringing new goods, services, and ways of doing things to the market. His idea of "creative destruction," in which new ideas from entrepreneurs destroy old businesses to make room for new ones, is still very important to modern theories of entrepreneurship and economic growth (Audretsch, 2012)
Keynesian Economics	John Maynard Keynes (1883-1946)	emphasised that aggregate demand is what causes economic cycles, and that entrepreneurship is key to handling changes
		in the economy and creating more jobs. Keynes emphasized government action, but he also recognized the need for entrepreneurship to create jobs and demand (Bateman, 2016).

Source: Compiled by researcher

2.2 The Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

Literature extensively explores the argument on whether entrepreneurs are made or born, leading to whether entrepreneurship can be taught (Fiet, 2001a). Initial study posited that entrepreneurs are born rather than nurtured; however, contemporary scholars increasingly advocate the perspective that entrepreneurship can be imparted. Drucker (1985) contends that 'Entrepreneurship is not magic, it is not mystical, and it has nothing to do with DNA.' It is a discipline; like any discipline, it may be acquired. Kuratko (2003) claimed that the debate over whether or not entrepreneurship can be taught is out of date. The assumptions underpin current developments in the academic discourse (Fayolle et al., 2006; Nabi & Linan, 2011) about the best way of teaching it.

The discussion surrounding EE began in 1938, spearheaded by a pioneer educator from Japan's Kobe University, Professor Shigeru Fuji. The first Master of Business Administration (MBA) programme in Entrepreneurship, which he helped develop, began in February 1947 at Harvard University with 188 students enrolled and after some time, EE spread to many people. (Mbeteh & Pellegrini, 2022). Additionally, it is also important to mention that EE increased primarily because many governments and institutions identified it as a source of creativity and employment development (Vasper & Gartner, 1997). The International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the United Nations Development Programmes (UNDP) are two well-known organisations that have expanded their offerings of EEPs globally as a result (Valerio et al., 2014).

Apart from the history of diffusion, researchers concluded that entrepreneurial education is a multifaceted concept (Linan, 2004; Fayolle and Gailly; Pellegrini et al., 2021). Fayolle et al. (2006) specifically defined EE as any educational programme or process aimed at cultivating entrepreneurial attitudes and skills, which entails the cultivation of specific personal attributes. The definition of entrepreneurship has been expanded to include sociocultural, political, and educational fields. While the idea of entrepreneurship programmes has gained widespread recognition since the 1970s and 1980s, research on what exactly qualifies as an EEP differs widely within disciplines. While other places concentrate on inspiring students in academic institutions to launch new businesses (Nielsen & Gartner, 2017). Some studies focus prioritise the development of students' skills through a project-based learning approach (Zhao, 2012), while others concentrate on value creation (Lackeus & Middleton, 2015).

Despite different definitions, entrepreneurship education programmes have become essential for acquiring the skills to succeed. However, the lack of consistency has led to disputes about the concept (Josien & Sybrowsky, 2013). Amid differences in the definition of entrepreneurship education programmes, the definition possesses two key themes: value creation and creativity (Laukeus, 2015). These different definitions of EE may have been because of the teaching approach. For example, the curriculum, instructions, and skill development serve as the guidelines for EEPs that concentrate on teaching about entrepreneurship. EEPs that focus on teaching through entrepreneurship are guided by an experimental approach, otherwise referred to as the learning-by-doing approach, as the name implies; they involve students in practical work to build entrepreneurial spirits (Zhao, 2012).

In this set of introductory concepts, it is essential to recognise the distinctions between entrepreneurship education and training programmes. The former emphasises the comprehension and enhancement of an individual's ability to engage in entrepreneurial behaviours, skills, and attributes across various contexts (Gibb, 2005). According to Jones and English (2004), entrepreneurial education provides individuals with the ability to recognise commercial opportunities, as well as the confidence, knowledge, and skills necessary to capitalise on them. The target audience is people under 18 and Secondary and HEIs students. Entrepreneurship Training Programmes aim to develop the necessary knowledge and skills to initiate or manage a business (Volkman et al., 2009). These programmes target both aspiring entrepreneurs, including vulnerable, unemployed, or inactive individuals, as well as those with innovation-driven or opportunistic ideas, and current entrepreneurs, such as small business with the possibility for significant growth (Valerio et al., 2014)

2.2.1 The Importance of Entrepreneurship Education

In the last twenty years, entrepreneurship has become one of the most powerful economic drives globally (Urbano & Aparicio, 2019). This rise has been accompanied by significant growth in entrepreneurship education. Colleges and universities offering entrepreneurship courses have expanded from just a few in the 1970s and by 2021, this number had escalated even more, with more than 3,000 institutions globally offering dedicated entrepreneurship programmes. reflecting the rising demand for entrepreneurial skills in both developed and emerging markets (World Economic Forum, 2021; Katz, 2022). Some studies in this field, particularly psychology, have greatly enhanced the comprehension of the factors that encourage entrepreneurial activity. Research has predominantly centered on personality traits such as the Big Five (Bazkiaei et al., 2020; Ashourizadeh et al., 2014), but other studies have

explored the impact of environmental factors and antecedents on entrepreneurship (Baum et al., 2001; Beaver, 2003). These studies recognize entrepreneurship education (EE) as a key factor that motivates individuals to pursue self-employment and enter the entrepreneurial sector. Therefore, effective entrepreneurship programmes have the potential to enhance entrepreneurial outcomes.

Entrepreneurship Education (EE) is widely acknowledged for promoting entrepreneurial intentions and developing an entrepreneurial attitude in students (Neneh, 2012; Nabi et al., 2017). As the ongoing debate on the teachability of entrepreneurship in academic environments continues, there is an increasing agreement that specific entrepreneurial skills such as problem-solving, creativity, leadership, and risk-taking can be developed through formal education (Liñán & Fayolle, 2015). This growing viewpoint recognizes that although specific entrepreneurial attributes might come from intrinsic features, education can significantly contribute to cultivating the cognitive and practical skills essential for entrepreneurship. Studies further suggest that certain external factors, such as family background, professional experience, and access to high-quality education, can substantially increase the tendency for entrepreneurship (Nabi et al., 2017). In addition, being around successful entrepreneurs in one's family or community frequently enhances entrepreneurial inclination (Chlosta et al., 2012). Some other factors like, geographic location, particularly in major cities with access to entrepreneurial ecosystems, can offer essential networks and opportunities that promote successful entrepreneurship (Audretsch & Belitski, 2017). An analytical review of the nature vs nurture debate indicates an increasing quantity of literature supporting the view that entrepreneurs can be nurtured rather than born (Henry et al., 2015).

Studies have been conducted in different countries that have examined the link with EE and EI frequently highlighting the function of self-efficacy as a moderating element. For instance, a study by Oosterbeek, Van Praag & Ijsselstein (2010) conducted in the Netherlands showed that entrepreneurship education did not considerably increase students' chances of starting their businesses. According to their findings, EE may reduce EI, most likely due to an absence between students' expectations and the realities of entrepreneurial activities. However, they also recognized the complex relationship and the need for more study on mediating elements like self-efficacy. A study conducted in Malaysia by Zainudin, Awang & Rahman (2017) found that EE positively affected students' intentions to start their businesses. Still, this effect was mediated mainly by self-efficacy and perceived behavioural control. Even though EE equips students with entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, the authors concluded that students' self-

efficacy, or the confidence they gained in their capacity to carry out entrepreneurial tasks, drove entrepreneurial behaviour.

Similar results were found in a study by Zhang et al. (2014) in China, which linked EE to entrepreneurial inclinations through the significant influence of self-efficacy. They discovered that students were more likely to consider starting their businesses if they had higher levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which were developed through practical EEPs. This result corresponds with a study conducted in Uganda, where Oyyugi (2015) found that self-efficacy played a significant role in the relationship between EI and EE. This claim was further supported by a study done in South Africa by Fatoki and Chindoga (2011), which demonstrated that EE had a favourable effect on entrepreneurial self-efficacy, encouraging university students to pursue their entrepreneurial goals. They pointed out that although EE can offer the theoretical groundwork, students are more likely to pursue entrepreneurship when they develop the self-confidence that they can accomplish it.

According to Oosterbeek et al. (2010), US and European policymakers started to see entrepreneurship as a critical strategy for promoting innovation and increased economic growth. EE has emerged as an vital component of this strategy, with a prevalent belief that it can foster entrepreneurial mindsets and, in turn, stimulate economic outcomes like growth and innovation. This viewpoint is reinforced by Van Praag and Versloot's (2007) findings, which indicate that entrepreneurial activities are crucial in job creation, enhancing productivity, and encouraging technological advancements.

Over the years, governments have been interested in EE worldwide as they address issues of economic stagnation and unemployment. Entrepreneurship education is now regard as a possible driver for economic recovery and sustainable development due to its capacity to promote innovation, self-sufficiency, and the establishment of new enterprises (OECD, 2020; World Bank, 2021). The increasing prevalence of entrepreneurship programs indicates the importance of entrepreneurship's significant contribution in addressing market challenges and fostering economic growth through innovation and competitiveness (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2022). Current EEPs aim to teach students how to start and run enterprises. These programmes increasingly emphasize experiential learning, innovation, and problem-solving, prompting students to cultivate an entrepreneurial attitude (Maritz, Jones & Shwetzzer, 2020). These educational frameworks integrate entrepreneurial thinking across many fields, enabling students to transform concepts into sustainable businesses (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

2.2.3 Entrepreneurship Learning in HEIs

Entrepreneurial success has always been linked to human capital factors like education, experience, and specialized knowledge (Marvel, Davis & Sproul, 2016). Incorporating entrepreneurial education in universities can be done in diverse ways, depending on institutional objectives and structures. Meyer, Gnyawali, and Messersmith (2017) identified two principal methods for incorporating EE in higher education, the first being the focused approach which emphasizes a particular faculty or academic topic, offering customized entrepreneurship training to students and individuals within that field of study. On the other hand, the unified model integrates EE across diverse disciplines, engaging students from many academic fields and promoting multidisciplinary collaboration and innovation (Wright, Siegel & Mustar, 2017). Though EE has many different agendas and purposes, there is still disagreement over the most accurate way to evaluate its efficiency, particularly in reaching the intended outcomes. Numerous evaluations of entrepreneurship education programmes (Neck et al., 2014; Edelman, Manolova & Brush, 2016) and courses (Jones, Matlay & Maritz, 2017) reveal a lack of consistency and significant diversity regarding aims, teaching philosophies, content, pedagogy, and outcomes. The differences have resulted in disputes, and there is less agreement on standardizing or evaluating these factors across various educational settings (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). In addition, the differences complicate the comparison of entrepreneurship program efficacy and the development of benchmarks for the most effective practices.

The implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum in universities is supported due to its ability to provide graduates with an in-depth knowledge of entrepreneurship, develop an entrepreneurial mindset, and prepare them for job markets, whether as entrepreneurs or managers of new ventures (Jones & Matlay, 2011).

On the other hand, some studies argue that rather than teaching functional, applicable skills, a large portion of the EE provided in HEIs focuses on creating awareness. When looking at entrepreneurship programmes and their educational materials, Katura and Dakung (2014) found a big disconnect between what students learn in the classroom and the difficulties they encounter in the actual world. The disconnect between theoretical knowledge and hands-on experience diminishes the efficacy of entrepreneurship education in equipping students for real-world challenges. In a comparable context, Honig (2004) pointed out that entrepreneurship courses frequently fall short in providing the experiential learning aspect, which is essential for cultivating the practical skills needed for business creation. Similarly, a study by Nowiński,

Haddoud, Lancaric, Egerova, and Czegledi (2020) revealed that while entrepreneurial education fosters skills and knowledge, its effectiveness in fostering entrepreneurial intentions is inconsistent, with some students feeling less motivated to start businesses after participation.

Studies recognized the need for change because of the limitations that existed and proposed a major shift in the focus and paradigm of EE. Fayolle and Klandt (2006) recommended educators should go beyond just teaching entrepreneurial concepts to Highlight the cultivation of entrepreneurial mindsets and practices. Due to a shift in the market, it is important to foster the mindset of students to recognize opportunities and adapt to the job market. Gibb (2005) noted that Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) primarily emphasize knowledge content and academic concepts in entrepreneurship education, while insufficient attention is given to cultivating personal behaviours, skills, and attributes essential for entrepreneurial success. The Quality Assurance Agency (2018) highlights this disconnect, noting that university entrepreneurship courses are predominantly theoretical and frequently lack a practical component that fosters entrepreneurial behaviour. Consequently, an evident imbalance exists in entrepreneurship education, wherein the promotion of entrepreneurial behaviours a fundamental element of entrepreneurial learning is frequently overlooked (Gibb, 2002). Teaching students to identify opportunities and respond to changing market conditions is essential, as these skills are vital for entrepreneurs and all professionals in today's rapidly evolving economy (Morris et al., 2021). Furthermore, the majority of HEIs neglect to specify precisely which behavioural attitudes they hope to promote in their entrepreneurial programmes. Despite the identification of these behaviours, few institutions provide specific strategies for their development. Piperopoulos and Dimov (2015) emphasize that numerous universities continue to depend on conventional teaching methods, including lectures, case studies, and projects, which may not effectively foster entrepreneurial mindset behaviour.

In developing economies, high-quality entrepreneurship education is somewhat undefined (Vesper & Gartner, 1997). Entrepreneurship education is an interventional strategy for building entrepreneurial potential but monitoring its efficiency and impact is essential for tracking the development and analyzing effectiveness (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012) in developed countries like the UK and EU, where frameworks like *EntreComp* guide curriculum development and learning activities (Bacigalupo et al., 2016), entrepreneurship education's impact has been assessed. However, Nigeria lacks such frameworks. The lack of organized measurement techniques in many developing nations makes it challenging to evaluate EEPs, leaving them unexplored. Most entrepreneurial education research focuses on developed nations, leaving

emerging markets understudied. Context-specific frameworks to evaluate the outcomes and impact of EEPs are needed in Nigeria (Nabi et al., 2017; Ezeani, 2018).

2.2.4 The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education

In order to foster an entrepreneurial mindset and behaviour in student, EE has become an essential component of modern educational systems. Multiple studies emphasize the significance of EEPs in fostering entrepreneurial mindsets and skills. Evaluating the impact of EEPs poses several challenges, particularly in identifying the most suitable metrics and methodologies. Some studies debate the effectiveness of EE, with some studies reporting positive outcomes, such as increased entrepreneurial intentions, while others indicate non-significant or adverse effects (Abbas, Perera & Cheah, 2020; Pidduck, Clark & Lumpkin, 2021). This inconsistency as noted by Zhang et al., (2022) is frequently linked to short-term evaluation methods, which may need to adequately reflect the programme's long-term impact. Research conducted by Kwapisz, Hechavarría, and Rivera (2022) and Xiang, Liang, and Zhu (2022) indicates that entrepreneurship education necessitates more extensive, theory-based investigation to enhance knowledge about developing entrepreneurial behaviours.

Within the HEIs, particularly as nations seek to promote economic development, job creation, and innovation, studies indicate that EE fosters entrepreneurial intentions and provides students with essential skills and a mindset conducive to success in entrepreneurial activities. Nowiński et al. (2020) demonstrate that EE markedly improves students' self-efficacy, raising their likelihood of engaging in entrepreneurial activities. This finding aligns with existing research indicating that EEPs facilitate the development of essential competencies, including opportunity recognition, resource management, and creative problem-solving (Duong, 2021). With regards to the development of skills, EE equips students with essential business skills, encompassing financial knowledge, marketing strategies, business planning, and decision-making in uncertain environments. Sanchez (2013) indicates that students receiving entrepreneurship education exhibit enhanced proficiency in vital entrepreneurial skills, including opportunity recognition, resource management, and leadership. This knowledge enables individuals to navigate the complexities and difficulty in launching and maintaining a business.

In addition, EE enhances economic development through the promotion of new venture creation, which in turn stimulates job creation and innovation. Audretsch (2012) suggests that EE fosters economic growth by cultivating a new wave of entrepreneurs who will introduce

innovative ideas, products, and services in the market. EE significantly influences entrepreneurial behaviours, having the right mindset and attitude is crucial to ensure skills are applied effectively. The studies conducted by Neneh (2012) on Small and Medium sized Enterprises highlights that success in today's economy requires more than just skill development; it also depends on cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset and attitude. The behaviour of individuals can serve as an indicator of EE's effectiveness, making it critical for policymakers and HEIs to assess its impact. Despite extensive research in this area, Nabi et al. (2017) indicate that much of the investigation continues to emphasise subjective, short-term outcomes while frequently neglecting the actual pedagogical approaches employed.

2.2.5 Global Perspective on Entrepreneurship Education

There is a global movement to encourage more students to choose careers in venture development. Entrepreneurship education programs (EEPs) are increasingly growing at institutions across America, Europe, Asia, and more recently, Africa (Crammond, 2020). Governments, educational institutions, and policymakers recognize that encouraging youth entrepreneurship is essential for the development of an economy. These programmes teach students to become entrepreneurs who can establish businesses and create jobs and value. In today's changing employment market, entrepreneurship education gives graduates abilities like innovation, problem-solving, and critical thinking, which boosts competitiveness beyond economic growth. Entrepreneurship education boosts graduates' employability by instilling an entrepreneurial perspective that is useful in many professional fields, according to Nabi and Holden (2008). Education must change to generate resilient economies and prepare young people for the job market (Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2015). Entrepreneurship education is growing as more universities incorporate experiential learning and practical training, developing future generations of entrepreneurial thinkers who can adapt to global economic issues. Universities are essential in promoting entrepreneurship, and there is growing evidence linking economic growth to entrepreneurship programmes.

The United States is recognized as the global leader in entrepreneurship education. however, before the 1970s, only a few universities provided formal programmes, with Harvard Business School being among the first to offer entrepreneurship courses disguisedly. The late 20th century they marked a significant expansion, pushed by the growth of small businesses and an enhanced understanding of entrepreneurship's contribution to economic development. During this period, universities established dedicated entrepreneurship programmes, particularly from the 1970s to the 2000s, as educators and policymakers acknowledged entrepreneurship's

potential to drive innovation, create jobs, and enhance economic resilience (Kuratko & Morris, 2018; Honig & Samuelsson, 2021). The global surge in entrepreneurship education is not only about satisfying student curiosity but also aligns with efforts to stimulate economic growth, especially in the wake of technological advancements and global competition (Neck et al., 2021).

Yahya, Mansor, and Mumtaz (2019) in a study of business undergraduates in Lebanon establish a strong link between EE and EI. The study examined how family history, personality attributes, and EE affected students' entrepreneurial goals and found that those with more EE had higher entrepreneurial intentions. The results showed that enhanced EE positively affects students' intention to start businesses (Yahya et al., 2019). Other research supports this link between EE and entrepreneurial intentions. A systematic review of 73 research by Bae et al. (2014) found that EE boosts students' entrepreneurial behaviours across settings. In addition, Nabi et al. (2018) found experiential learning in EE increases students' entrepreneurial ambitions. Pulka, Amino, And Rano (2021) found that EE boosts self-confidence and skill acquisition in Nigerian university students, further supporting the link between entrepreneurial pursuits. These studies indicate that entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial goals are consistent across educational and cultural environments.

China and South Korea use EE to boost technical innovation and economic growth. Zhang et al. (2022) claim that Chinese students with EE had higher entrepreneurial intentions, notably in technology and creativity. The region's concentration on digital entrepreneurship and tech-driven companies is crucial to China's goal of becoming a worldwide technology leader (Xiang et al., 2022). Universities in South Korea have partnered with tech companies and incubated young entrepreneurs to promote technology innovation. The Creative Economy Initiative in South Korea supports entrepreneurship by promoting AI, biotech, and fintech businesses (Oh, Choi & Park, 2018). Entrepreneurship competitions and accelerator programmes have grown in both nations, allowing students to apply their abilities in real life. These efforts promote creativity and enable students to transfer from the classroom to the entrepreneurial ecosystem, helping Asian technology businesses proliferate (Li, He & Zhao., 2021).

Structured frameworks like EntreComp, highlighting core qualities including creativity, vision, and motivation, have shaped European entrepreneurship education. EntreComp, created by the European Commission, provides educators, corporations, and policymakers with a framework to promote entrepreneurial thinking in new and existing businesses (Bacigalupo et al., 2016).

This comprehensive strategy teaches problem-solving, innovation, management, and opportunity identification to students of all ages. Many European countries have integrated entrepreneurship education into their higher education systems to boost economic growth, innovation, and job creation. Finland and Denmark, for instance, have long promoted entrepreneurial learning through collaborations between universities, enterprises, and government agencies to help students start and run businesses (Gibb, 2011). In Germany, vocational education and training (VET) integrates entrepreneurial training with actual practice. The Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy's EXIST program has funded, mentored, and provided resources to promote startup culture, notably technology and innovation (EXIST, 2020). French higher education institutions like Pépité France encourage student entrepreneurs to develop innovative business models by providing mentoring, funding, and a network of resources (Riesco, 2019).

In Africa, EE addresses youth unemployment, poverty, and economic diversification. A continent with one of the youngest populations needs entrepreneurship to boost self-employment and economic growth, which several African nations are realizing. Despite these efforts, African entrepreneurial education programs must overcome significant obstacles. Inadequate cash access for young entrepreneurs is a significant obstacle to these programmes' success. Despite entrepreneurial training, many young Africans need help to raise funds for their firms. Due to a lack of financing and institutional support, many higher education institutions and government programmes struggle to help students become entrepreneurs (Ezeani, 2018). Despite this, there are encouraging indications of advancement. Since its founding, the Tony Elumelu Foundation has funded, trained, and mentored over 10,000 African entrepreneurs. African governments are pushing EE. These programmes give youths the skills, networks, and resources required for their success (Elumelu Foundation, 2022). Another significant project is the African Development Bank's Youth Entrepreneurial and Innovation Trust Fund, which provides money and strengthens youth entrepreneurial ecosystems across Africa. Rwanda and Kenya have also moved to incorporate entrepreneurship education into their curriculums, encouraging entrepreneurial thinking in children (Mutebi, Were & Mboya, 2020). Despite advances, entrepreneurship education in Africa will likely reach its full potential when more coordinated efforts are undertaken to remove structural and financial hurdles to young entrepreneurs' success. This requires public-private collaborations, educational institution capacity-building, and capital access.

2.3 Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the area of EE has experienced significant increase in recent decades, driven by the realisation that entrepreneurship is an important tool for promoting economic growth, tackling youth unemployment, and alleviating poverty. As more graduates encounter restricted job prospects in conventional industries, the emphasis on entrepreneurship education has emerged as a key component of Nigeria's higher education policy. This initiative seeks to give students essential skills, knowledge, and mindset to establish businesses and make meaningful contributions to the economy.

Since Nigeria returned to civilian rule in 1999, entrepreneurship and enterprise development has grown in popularity. This era emphasized economic diversification and small and medium companies (SMEs) as essential catalysts for economic growth. Studies, including Oghojafor et al. (2011), identify 1964 as when the federal government-initiated organizations and agencies to promote SMEs, while contemporary advancements underscore entrepreneurship's dynamic political and economic importance. The initiative to transition Nigeria to a diversified economy, diminishing its dependence on oil, has been essential in government policy and socio-economic reforms in recent years (Akinbami & Olowu, 2021; Ezenwakwelu et al., 2020).

The initial attempts primarily focused on human resource development to uphold Nigeria's newly attained independence. Apprehensions over appointing individuals to government positions once held by colonial administrators prompted the implementation of policies focused on enhancing human capital (Aladekomo, 2004). Following the oil boom of the 1970s, the focus transitioned to reconstructing the economy to promote social and economic development. The emphasis on entrepreneurship became integral to a comprehensive plan to alleviate poverty and generate possibilities beyond the oil sector (Osuagu & Agbim, 2020). In recent years, entrepreneurs assuming significant roles in determining policy and government (Adeoye & Ayodele, 2021). The transition from perceiving entrepreneurship as a marginal endeavour to recognizing it as an integral component of Nigeria's economic framework signifies a profound comprehension of its contribution to promoting innovation and economic resilience.

Nigeria's efforts to promote entrepreneurship and business growth have traditionally focused on external support measures, such as establishing microfinance banks, offering tax incentives for investors, providing import duty exemptions, and launching poverty reduction initiatives. The initiatives were designed to deliver financial and infrastructural assistance to SMEs,

fostering economic activity in urban and rural regions. Initiatives like the World Bank's SME loan schemes and various government-supported financial interventions aim to provide entrepreneurs capital and financial support, especially in agriculture and manufacturing industries (Olawale & Garwe, 2010).

However, as Mitra et al. (2011) point out, these attempts have mainly overlooked the significance of EE in shaping students' entrepreneurial mindsets HEIs. Although numerous government initiatives are designed to support SMEs, there has been a lack of emphasis on cultivating entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, and competencies in undergraduate students. Entrepreneurship education was not incorporated as a vital part of career development for university graduates. Rather than promoting innovative thinking and inspiring students to investigate various entrepreneurial opportunities, higher education institutions concentrated mainly on equipping graduates for conventional job positions, neglecting the possibilities that entrepreneurship presents as a legitimate career choice (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

Although entrepreneurship education has gained significant traction across many advanced countries, it is still in a developing stage in Nigeria. Many universities nationwide adopt various approaches to EE, frequently integrating it into vocational and technical training programmes. Although important, the emphasis on skill acquisition does not continually cultivate the entrepreneurial mindset necessary to stimulate innovation and the creation of businesses, which is crucial for enhancing entrepreneurial performance across various fields (Akhuemonkhan, Raimi & Sofoluwe, 2013). This approach may constrain the broader possibilities of entrepreneurship education, which should fundamentally encourage creativity, risk-taking, and proactive business thinking, Nigeria is encountering an increasing issue of graduate unemployment, The number of university graduates continuously exceed the available recognised job opportunities. Garba (2012) emphasized that shifting the educational system to focus on entrepreneurship development is essential for tackling this issue. Entrepreneurship, often regarded as equivalent to launching new ventures, serves as an essential avenue for self-employment and the generation of jobs. Consequently, there is an increasing emphasis on EE to enable graduates to generate their opportunities instead of depending on conventional employment paths. When executed effectively, it could serve as a fundamental approach to decreasing unemployment and promoting economic development in Nigeria.

A systematic study of Nigerian EE by Yatu et al. (2018) found a growing body of studies. The assessment noted that much of the published work needs to be more valid and is often not in ranked journals, indicating a need for more rigorous and thorough investigations. This disparity shows that Nigerian universities struggle to embed entrepreneurship education. In response to these difficulties, the Federal Government mandated all tertiary education authorities to promote entrepreneurship among young Nigerians. In July 2004 a workshop was conducted by the National Institutions Commission (NUC) to integrate entrepreneurial education into Nigerian institutions to address these curricular gaps. This workshop created a draft entrepreneurial studies curriculum that many universities adopted to create their programmes (Nwokolo et al., 2017). A number of educational institutions have launched EEPs to combat rising graduate unemployment by teaching students how to start and run enterprises. These initiatives encourage graduates to pursue self-employment (Ojeifo, 2013). Entrepreneurship education also helps reduce unemployment and boosts national economic growth by training job creators rather than job seekers (Adeoti & Oladele, 2020).

2.3.1 Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria Universities

The origin of education has always been traced back to the colonial era. Nigeria's education system began during colonial times when educational practices suited the colonial administration. This education prepared Nigerians, including clerks, translators, and administrative officials, for administration duties. Rather than entrepreneurial or technical skills, basic literacy, and clerical skills were chosen to help Nigerians maintain colonial governance without becoming economically independent (Aladekomo, 2004; Geeky Nigeria, 2023). Studies argue the system lacked practical, professional, and entrepreneurial education that could have prepared Nigerians to establish and operate their businesses (Obiorah & Nwakamma, 2022). This legacy of limited educational scope went on after independence, making it difficult for Nigeria to establish a self-reliant and entrepreneurial education system.

Oghojafor et al., (2011) noted Nigeria faces persistent challenges including poverty, unemployment, infrastructure deficits, and corruption, which hinder its development this may be due to the mono-cultural nature of the economy, which is heavily reliant on oil, exacerbates these issues. Prior to the recent implementation of EEPs, entrepreneurial training initiatives predominantly concentrated on vocational education, which aimed to cultivate specific skill sets for a position rather than promoting entrepreneurial thought (Nkechi et al., 2012). This was particularly evident during Nigeria's military dictatorship from 1966 to 1999, when the central government had control over economic and political activities, significantly restricting

opportunities for entrepreneurship and market-driven growth. The oil boom of the 1970s resulted in significant dependence on oil, while entrepreneurial development received minimal focus (Akpan et al., 2012).

The National Universities Commission (NUC) serves as a principal regulatory authority in Nigeria and regulates university education administration and quality assurance within the nation. Founded in 1962, the NUC is accountable for developing academic programmes, establishing university standards, accrediting courses, and ensuring that Nigerian universities adhere to global best practices in higher education. The commission is essential in overseeing universities to ensure compliance with the minimum academic standards required for producing highly skilled graduates (NUC, 2023). The NUC is responsible for developing curriculum in diverse academic disciplines, establishing new universities, and advising the Nigerian government on funding and policy frameworks essential for advancing higher education. The core mandate includes accreditation, which entails assessing the quality of university programmes to ensure alignment with international standards (Babalola, 2019). The NUC promotes research and innovation, urging universities to contribute to national development through scholarly activities and advanced research. The National Universities Commission (NUC) was authorised by the 1988 Act No. 48 to set minimum academic standards for Nigerian universities, resulting in the Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS), which promotes a flexible and innovative, outcome-based curriculum to improve graduates' global competitiveness and entrepreneurial skills (Okojie, 2008).

In 2023, Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) transitioned to the Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS). This shift is aimed at modernizing the Nigerian university curriculum to address the requirements of the present-day economy. CCMAS places a stronger emphasis on interdisciplinary learning, entrepreneurship, and the development of practical skills rather than purely theoretical knowledge. It also allows universities to customize 30% of their curriculum to address local needs while maintaining 70% of the standardized content set by the NUC (NUC, 2023; Independent, 2023). This change shows the NUC's commitment to making Nigerian universities innovative and competitive, educating students for the global economy.

Considering elevated unemployment rates among Nigerian university graduates, A national survey conducted by the National University Commission (NUC) and Education Trust Fund (ETF) in 2004 indicated that Nigerian graduates were viewed as average in competencies such

as innovation, leadership, and creativity; however, they rated weakly in essential skills such as literacy, oral communication, and problem-solving skills vital for entrepreneurial success. To address the skills gap, the Federal Government of Nigeria required all HEIs to incorporate Entrepreneurial Education into their curriculum beginning in the 2007/2008 academic session (Aliu, 2008). This resulted in the creation of entrepreneurship centers at numerous universities to provide students with the entrepreneurial skills they need in the contemporary labour market (Okoye et al., 2022). This initiative demonstrates the increasing acknowledgment of the significance of entrepreneurial education in promoting economic growth and tackling the unemployment issues confronting Nigerian graduates.

The result of the initiative led to institutions establishing Entrepreneurship development Centres to support targeted innovations and empower graduates with appropriate skills (Edokpolor, 2022). The Federal Government of Nigeria has established various schemes in collaboration with stakeholders to improve entrepreneurship skills among Nigerian students and graduates. The agencies responsible for supporting the schemes include the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), the Student Industrial Working Experience Scheme (SIWES), Vocational and Technical Training, Agricultural Training, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Training (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014; Onuma, 2016; Oboreh & Nnebe, 2019). These inclusive programmes give students from all backgrounds life skills and entrepreneurship chances at being successful.

The issue of contextual and conceptual understandings around uniformity in teaching "How, Who, and What" in entrepreneurship has not been settled, according to Israel & Johnmark (2014), despite regulatory and policy support for entrepreneurship education in universities. This is mostly because different people who are organizing entrepreneurial programmes have different perspectives. Examining the viewpoints of educators, student entrepreneurs, programme developers, and evaluators as examples. The way that universities teach entrepreneurship varies; some universities in Nigeria offer it as a stand-alone course or as a non-obligatory module within business courses (Israel & Johnmark, 2014).

Studies on EE in Nigeria have suggested the functionalist disciplinary approach is often used as the primary pedagogy employed in EE within Nigerian higher education institutions. This approach primarily emphasizes theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurship but does not effectively cultivate the enthusiasm and drive required for entrepreneurial action. The teaching style mainly focuses on addressing problems in students' understanding of business concepts

rather than fostering an entrepreneurial mindset (Ifedili & Ofoegbu, 2011; Ubogo 2013; Udu, 2014; Nabi et al, 2017). Consequently, students frequently complete their studies with theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurship but lack the practical skills and motivation to set up their endeavours or innovate within established businesses. The approach confines students to passive learning, typically conveyed through lectures instead of experiential methods like project-based learning or business simulations, which are more effective in promoting entrepreneurial intention.

2.3.2 Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

When it comes to EE in Nigeria, literature states they are a lot of challenges. These challenges range from, structural, leadership, and curriculum challenges. Numerous studies investigate entrepreneurial education in Nigeria, focussing on its problems. Yatu et al. (2018) conducted a thorough assessment and found most studies on EE in Nigeria focuses on the problems of EE. Literature frequently highlights human resources as a significant challenge that hinders the success of EE in Nigeria.

Recent research indicates Nigerian HEIs emphasize teaching "about entrepreneurship" rather than instructing "for entrepreneurship," a crucial distinction for cultivating entrepreneurial potential. Entrepreneurship education includes academic discourse on business principles, economic contributions, and case studies, whereas learning for entrepreneurship emphasizes skill acquisition, practical implementation, and mindset development. Akinyemi et al. (2020) contend that Nigerian universities emphasize theoretical knowledge, leading to a curriculum lacking practical experiences or real-world involvement, limiting students' ability to use their expertise in entrepreneurial settings. In a similar vein, the pedagogical approach employed by numerous educators, which emphasizes fundamental and theoretical aspects of business plan writing, has faced significant criticism and is regarded as deficient in the existing literature (Ifedili & Ofoegbu, 2011). Different teaching methods are often used in different schools, resulting in diverse outcomes because there is no consensus on which educational approaches should be universally implemented. Students' success in EE programmes may be directly impacted by the effectiveness or lack of different approaches (Eze, Ezenwafor & Obidile, 2016). Ineffective teaching methods can limit students' capacity for entrepreneurship and lead to poor performance, especially when they are not in line with the local environment. The lack of skilled educators in entrepreneurship who can render the course engaging and focused on practical outcomes, as opposed to the prevailing focus on theoretical instruction, (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012) represents a significant issue. Furthermore, an absence of skilled EE instructors

in many universities, as these lecturers lack the requisite expertise and entrepreneurial background to properly mentor students (Obaji & Olugu, 2022).

Ubogu (2013) argued that inadequate funding for quality entrepreneurship education in Nigeria constitutes a significant issue. The period from 1990 to 2000 revealed a significant deficiency in proprietor funding, compelling university administrators to increase the enrolment of low-quality students in satellite campuses and remedial programs, primarily to generate revenue from tuition (Akpan & Etuk, 2020). Onyeachu (2008) emphasizes that adequate funding is essential for ensuring quality in entrepreneurship education. This funding should cover teachers' salaries, the construction of new classrooms, the renovation of existing school buildings, internet facilities, and the acquisition of equipment, furniture, and instructional materials. The lack of facilities for entrepreneurial skill training is common in literature of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. These facilities include suitable learning resources, labs, and workshops. (Ubogu, 2013; Gyuse, 2019). Facilities improve student learning; hence universities require them. Unfortunately, Nigerian universities have inadequate facilities. Therefore, this development suggests that Nigerian entrepreneurial education may lack quality. Ubogu (2013) and Obed and Ubogu (2020).

A further major obstacle is the lack of finance, which restricts the resources available for EE, including infrastructure, tools, and teaching materials (Titus & Jacinta, 2018). Many studies believe that more funding has hindered the growth and quality of university entrepreneurship education courses. The National Universities Commission (NUC) and other regulatory organizations worry that limited funding impedes the development of infrastructure and support systems needed for hands-on, practical entrepreneurship training (Olokundun et al., 2018). Poor financial support has led to unsatisfactory educational facilities, insufficient learning materials, and inadequate educator training, compounding Nigerian higher education entrepreneurship programmes' issues (Ojeifo, 2013). The evidence of mismanagement and corruption in government institutions that distribute, and control education monies is more disturbing. Reported examples of educational development and research funding being diverted or misappropriated undermine government efforts in this area (Ogbonnaya & Ubong, 2020). Mismanagement hinders entrepreneurship education and undermines national educational goals. These challenges must be addressed to ensure that entrepreneurship education is well-funded and can teach students to contribute to Nigeria's economy and innovation.

Additionally, numerous students display a “laissez-faire attitude” towards EE, perceiving it as less significant than other academic subjects, thereby reducing its potential impact (Pulka, Aminu & Rano, 2021). This might be a result that EE programmes are not always stand-alone programmes but are taught as an elective or compulsory general courses to meet the regulatory requirement. Outside the university, socio-cultural barriers persist in influencing the entrepreneurial ecosystem in Nigeria. Societal norms and family expectations frequently prioritize career trajectories in esteemed disciplines, including medicine, law, and engineering. Entrepreneurship is often perceived as a risky or less secure career choice, particularly in comparison to traditional employment forms (Ediagbonya, 2013). This perception may deter graduates, including those with entrepreneurial skills, from engaging in self-employment. Many individuals instead choose safer, salaried positions, which often exacerbates the issue of graduate unemployment. Addressing these cultural attitudes is crucial for developing a stronger entrepreneurial culture that is consistent with the practical training offered by EE.

Addressing these challenges discussed above necessitates a comprehensive reform that encompasses the standardization of EE within educational institutions and the wider Nigerian economy.

2.4 Teaching and Pedagogical Approaches in EE

Entrepreneurship education has significantly progressed regarding pedagogical approaches, curriculum, and intended audiences. Initially, in the 1980s, entrepreneurship instructors often lacked specialization in the field, and teaching was more circumstantial, with a focus on business development. Limited time was dedicated to research activities, and there was little alignment between teaching and research (Hägg & Gabrielsson, 2019). The 1990s saw the emergence of instructors specialized in entrepreneurship, integrating research into their teaching. By the 2000s, instructors began to emphasize real-world applications, inviting practicing entrepreneurs to share experiences and helping bridge theory and practice (Kuratko, 2005, Hägg & Gabrielsson, 2019). In the 2010s, educators' roles further evolved towards facilitation rather than instruction, focusing on learner-centered approaches (Mueller & Anderson, 2014).

According to Johannisson (1991) cited by Hägg & Gabrielsson (2019), in the 1990s, practical content focused on new venture creation abilities and expertise (Johannisson, 1991). By the 2000s, this became psychological, reflecting the entrepreneur's role and timing (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). Theory, experiential learning, effectuation, and lean start-up were more

integrated in the 2010s (Neck & Greene, 2011). Additionally, the target population expanded. Entrepreneurial education in the 1980s was mostly elected themselves and had no definite aim. Universities began recruiting entrepreneurship-focused students in the 1990s (Gibb, 1993). After business schools, entrepreneurship education moved to arts and engineering faculties, developing programmes for social entrepreneurs (Katz, 2008). In the 1980s, teaching strategies changed from traditional lectures and guest lecturers to more action-oriented techniques that included business plan development and simulations by the 1990s (Gartner & Vesper, 1994 cited by Hägg & Gabrielsson, 2019). By the 2000s, experiential learning employing real-world businesses and startups to educate entrepreneurship dominated (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). Design thinking and lean start-up were used in the 2010s to emphasize practice-based learning (Neck & Corbett, 2018).

The current pedagogical problem is not so much about knowing what to teach as it is about designing learning environments that support experiences with real-world entrepreneurship. EE assessments and effect measurements are in demand, fuelling current discussions (Nabi et al., 2017; Warhuus, 2018). This evolution shows the shift from instructor-centered approaches to a student-centered, experiential approach that emphasizes practical applications, making it difficult to create effective, measurable entrepreneurship education and management principles.

2.4.1 Traditional Teaching Methods in EE

Historically, the mainstay of entrepreneurship education teaching approaches has been traditional Methods, which rely on traditional lectures and case studies. In the early years of entrepreneurship education, these methods predominated and were mainly concerned with teaching students about entrepreneurship. They gave them a basic understanding of business concepts, management ideas, and entrepreneurial procedures (Fayolle, 2013; Maritz & Brown, 2020). Higher education institutions (HEIs) that offer entrepreneurship education (EE) have traditionally focused on conventional teaching strategies such as case studies, assignments, textbook readings, and lectures. Although these approaches give students a solid basis, they cannot adequately prepare them for the dynamic and unpredictability of entrepreneurship. According to Hytti and O'Gorman (2004), these approaches assist students in becoming familiar with related information and ideas. Still, a problem occurs when these conventional approaches do not include students in active, hands-on learning. Although lectures and textbooks help impart knowledge about entrepreneurship, they frequently need to promote the

entrepreneurial mindset necessary for enterprises' actual development (Gibb, 2002; Farsi, Imanipour & Salamzadeh, 2020).

Studies indicate that excessive dependence on teacher-centered approaches limits students' potential to think creatively and delve beyond the curriculum. Mohammed (2015), for instance, noted that traditional, teacher-centered learning approaches reduce students' capacity for initiative, critical thought, or creativity skills essential for entrepreneurship by making them unduly reliant on their teachers. Students' engagement with entrepreneurial challenges and possibilities to implement theoretical knowledge in practical contexts are limited by these methods organized and passive character. Notwithstanding this criticism, traditional teaching methods are still widely used in many HEIs around the world. According to McKeown et al. (2006), 86% of HEI entrepreneurship programs in the UK still use conventional teaching methods. Olomi and Sabokwigma (2010) found a comparable preference for lectures, textbooks, and group projects at Tanzanian business schools, demonstrating how firmly embedded specific teaching methods are in the educational system. This trend is not exclusive to the UK.

Though traditional techniques are still used, there is a rising awareness of the need for more creative and engaging means of teaching entrepreneurship. Obikeze and Onyechi (2010) discovered that in Tertiary Institutions in Anambra State in Nigeria rely primarily on lectures, textbooks, and simulations. In a study of Malaysian universities, Nian et al. (2014) noted that although case studies and lectures are still widely used, there is a growing, underappreciated, recognition of more creative approaches like field trips, business clubs, and in-person interviews with entrepreneurs. The discrepancy between acknowledgment and execution suggests that although educational establishments need more experiential learning techniques, obstacles like institutional and budget limitations prevent them from fully adopting these strategies. The demand for action-oriented teaching approaches and more significant experience learning in entrepreneurship education is rising globally. Studies that support learning approaches that prioritize doing rather than just learning about entrepreneurship include Neck and Greene (2011). These models incorporate realistic exercises like role-playing, venture development, and simulations that more closely mimic the reality of launching and running a business. Similarly, Jones et al. (2017) contend that the development of creativity and problem-solving skills ought to be the primary goals of EE, as these are necessary for a business to succeed.

This strategy helps students learn business fundamentals but not develop entrepreneurial skills. In a study in South Africa, lecture-based entrepreneurship courses provided a sound theoretical foundation. Still, students felt unprepared to start their ventures owing to an absence of actual experience (Brixiova et al.,2015). Similarly, in Pakistan, most university entrepreneurship education leaves students without the practical skills to pursue entrepreneurial activities after graduation (Asghar, Hakkarainem & Nada, 2016). These studies show how theoretical methodologies fail to prepare students for entrepreneurial challenges.

The difficulty, though, is striking a balance between these more experimental strategies and more conventional techniques. Traditional teaching approaches might be useful for teaching theory, but they need to be supplemented by opportunities for experiential learning that allow students to implement their acquired knowledge in practical context. In addition, Nian et al (2014) noted that while traditional teaching methods might be able to develop the critical characteristics of entrepreneurs and business strategies, they might not be able to develop student's creativity and autonomy. The traditional teaching methods sustain their utility only in entrepreneurial awareness.

2.4.2 Experiential Learning in EE

Experiential Learning (EL) is a powerful pedagogical approach that plays a crucial role in entrepreneurship education. Rooted in the work of prominent scholars such as John Dewey (1938), Jean Piaget (1973), and Kurt Lewin (1951), the theory posits that learning is most effective when it arises from direct experience (as cited by Motta, and Galina, 2023).

Kolb (2014) highlights that experiential learning focuses on the process of transformation, where knowledge is continuously created and recreated through active engagement, rather than being a static entity to be transmitted. This perspective contrasts with content-driven approaches by emphasizing adaptation and learning through experience. Pimentel (2007) supports this perspective, contending that experiential learning is closely linked to both present learning and previous development. He clarifies that learning from experience necessitates more than mere participation in activities; it entails a cognitive process of action and reflection. Not all experiences result in learning; genuine learning takes place when individuals actively reflect on and adapt their knowledge derived from those experiences. Experiential learning helps students understand entrepreneurship by closing the theory-practice gap. Business simulations, case studies, internships, and real-world entrepreneurial initiatives allow students to test ideas, evaluate results, and apply new ideas to future problems (Neck & Greene, 2011).

Morris et al. (2013) state that entrepreneurs demand better problem-solving, creative thinking, and decision-making abilities, and that experiential learning provides them. It helps students handle complex and uncertain situations. The approach excels at creating immersive learning environments that stimulate entrepreneurship. This method emphasizes active learning by putting students first. Entrepreneurship challenges including resource management, unpredictability, and identifying opportunities are learned through real experiences. Reflecting on these experiences helps students form abstract concepts that they apply in new situations, improving ongoing learning (Pittaway & Thorpe, 2012).

In the context of EE, the experiential approach is acknowledged to improve entrepreneurial ambition and competencies. studies like Kickul et al, (2010) and Nabi et al (2017) Additionally, by encouraging an inner sense of control, self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial motivation, EL contributes to the development of the mindset essential to meeting the demands of entrepreneurship (Kickul et al., 2010). Finland, for instance, is well known for its cutting-edge entrepreneurship education strategy, which heavily emphasizes project-based learning. According to a study done in Finnish universities, students who participated in project-based learning exhibited more intentions of starting their businesses and had better teamwork, problem-solving, and innovative skills (Ruskovaara, Pihkala, Seikkula-Leino, & Järvinen, 2016). similarly, in the Australian context, real-world business initiatives are included in the university curriculum as a core component of entrepreneurship education programmes. Due to the practical learning environment and exposure to real-world business difficulties, students who took part in these experiential programs had a higher likelihood of pursuing careers in entrepreneurship, according to research by Maritz and Brown (2020).

2.4.4 Action-Based Learning in EE

In the mid-1900s, Reg Revans (1982) was a pioneer in the application of action learning (AL), mostly in corporate settings to resolve real-world problems and enhance employees' competencies. early in the decade that followed. In the early 2000s although AL had proven successful in organizational contexts, its adoption in academic settings, such as management education, was limited due to many challenges related to administration, design, and execution (Scott, 2017). In recent times, there has been an application in postgraduate business programmes, especially in the UK, despite its continued lack of appeal in US business schools (Brook & Milner, 2014).

More recently, research has concentrated on combining action-based learning with other approaches, such as Lean Thinking, to develop all-encompassing frameworks for learning and ongoing development. Collaboration and problem-solving across organizational networks are made possible by this combination, which has demonstrated promise in professional as well as educational environments (Powell & Coughlan, 2020). This integration has improved the knowledge of action learning function in developing teamwork and leadership abilities while tackling practical business issues. This approach has developed to emphasise genuine, contextual learning environments that cultivate entrepreneurial skills via collaborative problem-solving (Botha et al., 2010). According to Harms (2015), there is a growing trend towards the creation of learning environments that are specifically tailored to help construct these skills.

The action-based approach to entrepreneurship education integrates action learning, collaborative learning, and project-based learning, emphasizing experiential learning, teamwork, and engagement with real-world clients. This method is participatory, promoting student engagement through experience and reflection, which fosters behavioural changes essential for the development of entrepreneurial skills. This approach emphasizes value creation for others, encourages student empowerment, and promotes reflective practices that enhance deeper learning (Chenhall & Chermack, 2010). Recent studies indicate that action-based learning in entrepreneurship education substantially improves students' entrepreneurial skills and mindset. The approach facilitates student engagement with real-world problems, promoting collaboration and critical thinking. Countries like Denmark and Germany have pioneered this strategy with university-led incubator programs and venture creation courses. Action-based learning is a critical part of EE in Denmark, especially for incubators that let students work on their firms while in school. According to Rasmussen and Sørheim(2016), students who took part in action-based incubator programmes had greater self-efficacy, confidence in their ability to establish firms, and success after graduation. Action-based learning has also gained popularity in Germany, especially at institutions like the Technical University of Munich, where students are urged to start and oversee actual businesses. Action-based learning positively impacts students' entrepreneurial goals and can produce observable results like establishing viable companies (Fayolle et al., 2016).

The use is increasingly integrated into business and entrepreneurship programmes to equip students for the complexities of initiating and managing a business. Similarly, AL usually involves collaboration among students to address real business challenges, fostering the

development of entrepreneurial and interpersonal skills. This process fosters critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving skills, which are essential in the evolving entrepreneurial environment (Powell & Coughlan, 2020). Moreover, incorporating reflective practices and experiential learning into the EE curriculum is essential for improving its effectiveness. AL promotes the application of knowledge in practical contexts, enhancing comprehension of entrepreneurial concepts (Hägg & Gabrielsson, 2019). This method differs from traditional lecture-based approaches by promoting participatory and student-centered learning environments.

2.4.5 Educating About, For, and In Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship education objectives are fundamental elements that shape the overall structure of the program. Recent studies identify three primary objectives: education about entrepreneurship, which focuses on theoretical understanding; education for entrepreneurship, which aims to prepare individuals to start their businesses; and education in entrepreneurship, which involves hands-on, experiential learning. These approaches ensure that students not only learn the concepts but also develop the mindset and competencies essential for entrepreneurial endeavours (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Nabi et al., 2017; Rideout & Gray, 2013).

Education *About* Entrepreneurship emphasizes providing theoretical knowledge and conceptual comprehension of entrepreneurial processes. The focus is to address essential principles, including basic concepts, opportunity recognition, business planning, and market analysis, providing students with a foundational understanding of entrepreneurship. This approach seeks to cultivate a sense of entrepreneurship as an academic discipline rather than primarily promoting entrepreneurial activity (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Research by Nabi et al. (2017) and Rideout & Grey (2013) indicates that education in entrepreneurship, while fundamental, is frequently enhanced by experiential learning to develop entrepreneurial competencies effectively. Studies indicate that education "about" entrepreneurship is essential for creating an organized method to address entrepreneurial difficulties as it gives a theoretical foundation. However, to optimize its influence, this knowledge must be combined with real-world applications (Pittaway & Cope, 2021).

Entrepreneurship *for* education aims to develop the skills and mindsets necessary for starting and maintaining entrepreneurial ventures. Kirby (2004) emphasizes that this approach focuses on active engagement in entrepreneurial activities, providing learners with critical resources for practical application. Henry et al. (2005) and Mwasalwiba (2010) contend that

these opportunities, like business simulations and internships, promote enhanced understanding. Nabi et al. (2017) highlight that this form of education fosters creativity and problem-solving abilities, which are crucial in entrepreneurial contexts. Similarly, Neck et al. (2020) assert that entrepreneurship education must promote student adaptability, resilience, and innovation.

Entrepreneurship in education emphasizes the instruction of students through engagement in entrepreneurial experiences and environments. Kirby (2004) states that this method enables students to participate actively in entrepreneurial activities, offering a practical context. Nabi et al. (2017) contend that practical exposure is essential for cultivating entrepreneurial skills. Similarly, Hytti et al. (2018) and Maritz et al. (2020) endorse that experiential learning significantly enhances entrepreneurial competencies and decision-making capabilities.

Lastly, Entrepreneurship *in* education facilitates the transition from putting academic understanding into practice and providing students with the required abilities and perspective to address the complexities of entrepreneurship. According to Hytti et al. (2018), this method promotes creativity, problem-solving, and innovation, providing students with essential tools for navigating real-world business environments. Maritz et al. (2020) assert that immersive experiences equip students with the resilience and adaptability necessary for the entrepreneurial journey, constituting a vital component of modern entrepreneurial education.

Table 2: Types of Entrepreneurship Education and Their Objectives

Type of EE	Objectives	Teaching Methods	References
Education About Entrepreneurship	To raise awareness and foster a positive perception of entrepreneurship among students.	Lectures, Case Studies, Seminars	Kirby (2004); Henry et al. (2005); Myasalwiba (2010); Nabi et al. (2017); Maritz et al. (2020)
Education for Entrepreneurship	To equip students with the necessary skills and abilities to start and manage new ventures.	Business Simulations, Workshops, Business Plan Development	Kirby (2004); Henry et al. (2005); Myasalwiba (2010); Nabi et al. (2017); Bae et al. (2014); Neck et al. (2020)
Education in Entrepreneurship	To enhance innovation and entrepreneurial thinking within existing organizations and businesses.	Internships, Real-world Projects, Mentorship	Kirby (2004); Henry et al. (2005); Myasalwiba (2010); Nabi et al. (2017); Hytti et al. (2018); Maritz et al. (2020)

Source: Compiled by researcher

2.4.6 Assessment of EE Effectiveness

The effectiveness of EE is important in understanding how well the programmes prepare students for real-world entrepreneurial challenges. By evaluating outcomes such as skill development, entrepreneurial intentions, and long-term venture creation, educators, researchers, and even the university body can understand EE's practical affects students' entrepreneurial journeys. The pre- and post-programme surveys are commonly used to measure the change in attitudes and intentions of students. Studies have shown using the pre and post-test that students who completed an EE programme showed a substantial increase in EI when compared to when they started (Bae et al., 2014; Nabi et al., 2017). However, the shortcoming noted by studies is the survey primarily measured short-term mindset shifts and may not always predict the actual entrepreneurial outcomes (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Nabi et al., 2017; Rideout & Gray, 2013). A common method of assessment is self-reported entrepreneurial intentions, often analyzed using the TBP by Ajzen (1991) which examines how attitudes toward entrepreneurship, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms influence students' intentions to start their businesses.

Another indicator of EE effectiveness is skill development, especially in hands-on, experiential programmes. Immersing students in real or simulated business contexts improved their entrepreneurial skills, such as opportunity awareness and leadership (Gielnik et al., 2015). Rasmussen and Sørheim (2016) found that action-based learning, especially in venture creation programs, significantly increased students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012; Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2016). Even with these efforts, evaluating the efficacy of EE remains challenging, especially when it comes to monitoring long-term success, such as venture formation, which may take years to materialize (Maritz & Brown, 2020; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Furthermore, a significant portion of the data is self-reported, which raises the possibility of biases (Nabi et al., 2017; Rideout & Grey, 2013). A holistic approach is necessary to thoroughly evaluate EE effectiveness, capturing both immediate skill and intention development and long-term entrepreneurial outcomes. Short-term evaluations, like surveys, should be combined with long-term tracking, like venture creation (Neck & Corbett, 2018; Maritz & Brown, 2020). This multifaceted method provides a more accurate review of the effects of EE.

2.5 Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI)

The acknowledgment of entrepreneurial intention as an area of inquiry is associated with a relationship to new venture creation. Research indicates that education and training in entrepreneurship significantly influence entrepreneurial intentions, which subsequently forecast entrepreneurial behaviour (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Liñán & Fayolle, 2015; Souitaris et al., 2007). EI like EE lack a broadly agreed definition. Unlike entrepreneurship education (EE), entrepreneurial intention (EI) focuses more on timing and planning. These differences in definitions lead to variations in how programmes are applied, which may explain why they differ between countries (Chukwuma-Nwuba, 2019).

Table 3: Defining Entrepreneurial Intentions

Author and Date	Definition of Entrepreneurial Intentions
Ajzen (1991)	A person's intent to start a business is driven by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control.
Krueger et al. (2000)	refers to the commitment of an individual to start a new business.
Liñán & Chen (2009)	The desire to create a business is influenced by attitudes toward entrepreneurship, social norms, and perceived feasibility.
Thompson (2009)	A self-acknowledged conviction by an individual to set up a new business venture and consciously plan for this.
Fayolle & Gailly (2015)	Intentions reflect a conscious plan to engage in entrepreneurial behaviours at some point in the future
Zhang et al. (2020)	Entrepreneurial intentions are individuals' plans to start a business, influenced by education, personality traits, and contextual factors.
Shirokova et al. (2021)	The intention to pursue entrepreneurship is based on personal motivation, entrepreneurial climate, and prior experience.

Source: compiled by researcher

The definitions of Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) above give a concise overview of key definitions from various authors, highlighting how EI is perceived in different contexts. The definitions evolved from foundational theories like TBP (1991) to more recent perspectives that emphasize the role of education, personality traits, and contextual factors, such as in Zhang et al. (2020). This range of definitions underscores the multidimensional nature of entrepreneurial intention, encompassing individual motivations, social influences, and institutional factors, all of which contribute to the likelihood of venture creation. Studies indicate that entrepreneurial intention is fundamental to comprehending the entrepreneurial process.

According to Zhang et al. (2015), EI plays an important part in shaping the entrepreneurial journey, as it represents a person's deliberate choice and confidence in their capabilities to create a new business. This intention is rooted in the personal conviction to act in the future, turning the idea of starting a venture into a real plan. EI is thus viewed as a deliberate mindset, fundamental in driving entrepreneurial behaviours. Basu (2020) notes that while there is a lot of study on the link between entrepreneurial aspirations and education., the direct impact of entrepreneurial education on the intention to establish businesses still needs to be more adequately understood. The entrepreneurial intention model is mainly utilized by researchers, with TBP serving as the primary framework. Krueger et al. (2020) highlight that this model illustrates the relationship between attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control in predicting entrepreneurial intentions.

Human capital theory and TPB advocates acknowledge that outside factors like family background and personal experiences also play a significant role, despite rising numbers of studies looking at how EE affects participants' behaviour and human capital (Ariyo, 2005; Chu et al., 2020). Given that intent alone does not necessarily translate into entrepreneurial activity, Kolvereid (2016) contends that entrepreneurship education has an indirect impact (Nabi et al., 2018). Studies indicate that although many students have solid entrepreneurial goals, very few follow through (Ward et al., 2010; Joensuu et al., 2015).

However, different uncertainties arise regarding how various entrepreneurship education programmes impact entrepreneurial intentions (Linan & Fayolle, 2015). Hahn, Minola, and Huybrechts (2020) noted that compulsory and elective programmes have been encouraged the growth of entrepreneurial abilities. However, the effect of mandatory programmes depends on the students' perception of their parents' entrepreneurial success. Also, some studies, such as Oosterbeek, Van, and Ijsselstein (2010) and von, Harhoff, and Weber (2010), show that required EEPs may make people less likely to want to start their businesses. This indicates that the effects of these programmes need to be studied more. Further research needs to be done to determine what effects this possible weakness has and how to address it best. Another view of EI is concerned with personality traits or external interventions such as entrepreneurship education significantly influencing entrepreneurial intentions. Zhao et al. (2010) maintained that certain personality factors, such as risk-taking tendencies, being proactive, and innovativeness, highly predict entrepreneurial intentions. Other studies, for example Nabi et al. (2017), highlight the importance of EE in altering students' intents by increasing entrepreneurial self-efficacy and attitudes towards entrepreneurship. This causes a dispute in

the literature, with some studies arguing that entrepreneurial intention is a more solid, personality-driven construct. In contrast, others feel it can be considerably influenced by education and experience.

The assessment of entrepreneurial intentions is a subject of debate. Researchers employ several scales and frameworks to assess intents, potentially resulting in conflicting outcomes among studies. Krueger et al. (2000) and Liñán and Chen (2009) have created distinct scales to evaluate entrepreneurial intentions; a standard assessment approach remains unclear. Many questions arise about how similar the outcomes of various studies are and whether the same factors are being examined in each case.

Besides the TBP (1991), there have been other suggested models like Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model (SEE) which suggests that entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by perceived desirability, feasibility, and a desire to act on opportunities (Shapero & Sokol, 1982). This model explores the impact of individual perceptions of opportunities and external events on the intention to start an entrepreneurial project. Drost and McGuire (2011) and Prabhu et al. (2012) oppose the notion that EI is a singular construct, suggesting multiple dimensions of intention corresponding to different types of ventures. Consequently, three specific measures of entrepreneurial intention have been established: *general entrepreneurial intention (GEI)*, *high-growth entrepreneurial intention (HGEI)*, and *lifestyle entrepreneurial intention (LEI)*. The dimensions recognize that individuals may possess varying entrepreneurial goals, from establishing small lifestyle businesses to engaging in high-growth companies with substantial economic implications.

The complexities associated with entrepreneurial intentions suggest that entrepreneurial intentions are a multi-faceted construct influenced by a combination of individual traits, contextual factors, and time. Entrepreneurship education programmes are important as they positively influence attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship. An understanding of how factors like university support and teaching methods influence students' entrepreneurial intentions is needed. According to Saeed et al. (2015) and Shirokova et al. (2016), university support, which includes tools like mentorship programs and incubators, is crucial in helping students develop a proactive entrepreneurial mindset and boost their self-confidence in their entrepreneurial ability. Furthermore, because they foster active learning and problem-solving abilities, innovative and experiential teaching strategies are more successful than conventional ways of fostering entrepreneurial mindsets (Pittaway & Cope, 2007; Meoli et al., 2020). To

determine how these factors affect students' development as entrepreneurs, this study investigates these elements in Nigerian universities.

2.5.1 Foundation Theories of Entrepreneurial Intentions

Various theories support the delivery and pedagogy of EE (Fayolle, 2013; Kuratko, 2005), aligning with the study's goals. Although research on EE in Nigeria is increasing, there is still limited work exploring the specific entrepreneurial attitudes in Nigeria and their connection to education outcomes in the nation's universities (Udu, 2014). Many researchers argue that individuals form intentions toward certain behaviours, which in turn influence their actions (Bird 1988, 1992; Ajzen 1991; Krueger 1993). Theoretically, these concepts have become stronger as time progressed. Exploring the underlying theories will provide a precise framework for this study. Studies in entrepreneurship frequently integrate insights from various disciplines to develop theories within the field and enhance understanding of events and occurrences related to entrepreneurship (Chu, 1998).

Table 4: Main Research Streams in Entrepreneurship: Focus and Line of Inquiry

Mainstreams	Research Subjects	Line of Inquiry
Psychology: Traits and behavioural	Entrepreneurs' characteristics and entrepreneurial process	Causes (why)
Sociological: Social and cultural	Entrepreneurs of different social or cultural backgrounds	Causes (why)
Economics	Relationship between economic environment and entrepreneurship	Effects (what)
Management	Entrepreneurs' skill, management, and growth	Behaviour (How)

Source: Chu (1998)

This table provides an summary of the multidisciplinary nature of entrepreneurship studies. categorizing it by the field of study (e.g., psychology, sociology, economics, management), the focus of that field's research, and the type of questions it aims to answer (causal, effects-based, behavioural). The psychological approach to entrepreneurship identifies features and behaviours that make entrepreneurs unique. Research on entrepreneurial success focused on personality factors such as risk-taking, need for achievement, and self-efficacy (McClelland, 1961). These studies try to explain why people become entrepreneurs by studying cognitive

processes and motivation. These studies on entrepreneurial self-efficacy show that confidence in decision-making abilities significantly affects entrepreneurial behaviours (Chen et al., 1998). By studying the individual's personality types, psychology reveals personal characteristics that influence entrepreneurial behaviour. The sociological approach emphasizes social and cultural influences on entrepreneurship. This research examines how social networks, culture, and family influence entrepreneurship. It explains why entrepreneurs from diverse social origins have differing chances and success. Aldrich and Zimmer (1986) concluded that social networks give businesses vital resources and possibilities. Davidsson and Honig (2003) found that entrepreneurs with strong social relationships are more likely to get resources and succeed. This method reveals how social structures and interactions affect entrepreneurial outcomes. The economic approach of entrepreneurship includes researchers who believe entrepreneurs are driven by access to capital, market demand, and government policies. Lastly, the management approach focuses on how entrepreneurs manage their ventures and sustain their business. This approach was focused on the behaviours and actions entrepreneurs take to navigate challenges (Baron, 2004).

Theories explain, predict, and broaden understanding of research phenomena while challenging and expanding existing knowledge within settings. A theoretical framework supports and organizes research by presenting and clarifying the theory relevant to the research problem. Multidisciplinary theories from psychology, sociology, and economics are often utilized in business, management, and entrepreneurship. The TBP by Ajzen has been widely applied in entrepreneurship research to elucidate entrepreneurial intentions. In contrast, Human Capital Theory (HCT) examines the impact of training, knowledge, and experience on developing entrepreneurial skills. Recent literature acknowledges TPB and HCT as prominent theoretical frameworks in entrepreneurship education studies, offering essential insights into developing individual intentions and capabilities (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Nabi et al., 2017).

2.5.2 Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event (SEE) Model

The SEE model states that the intention to start a business is influenced by the view regarding interest and feasibility. which subsequently cultivates individuals' desires to pursue opportunities (Krugger et al., 2000). Shapero's concept claims that human behaviours are affected by environmental factors and situational contexts, which may be either beneficial or destructive. The core idea of this theory is that significant life changes, such as job loss or dissatisfaction with one's existing career, are examples of displacement events that frequently

serve as drivers for entrepreneurship. These external factors compel individuals to reconsider their employment options and may direct them toward entrepreneurial pursuits. Shapero's concept provides a valuable perspective on entrepreneurship, considering it results from individual motivation and response to environmental factors (Krueger, 2000).

The SEE model is built around three main constructs: perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and propensity to act. Perceived desirability in this case refers to the desirability of entrepreneurship to an individual, perceived feasibility is the ability to express appropriate behaviour, and these factors are driven by ethnic and social factors (Linan & Santos, 2007). According to Liñán et al. (2011), individuals exhibit a higher likelihood of considering entrepreneurship a desirable career choice if they live in an environment highly valued by society or their immediate circle. The entrepreneur's perception of feasibility, encompassing their belief in possessing the necessary skills, resources, and support to initiate a business, significantly influences their propensity to act (Souitaris, Zerbinati & Al-laham, 2007). Educational background, previous experiences, and the accessibility of networks and resources influence perceived feasibility. These factors affect an individual's confidence to initiate and manage a business (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

Recent studies further support Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model, particularly within educational settings. Entrepreneurship education programmes can function as "positive displacement events" by enhancing students' perceived feasibility and desirability regarding entrepreneurship. These programs frequently equip individuals with the knowledge, skills, and networks essential for enhancing EI, as highlighted in the research conducted by Souitaris et al. (2007). Also, Nabi et al. (2017) demonstrate that EE cultivates personal and social conditions consistent with Shapero's constructs, underscoring the significance of external educational influences on entrepreneurial outcomes.

In summary, Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model remains a powerful framework for explaining entrepreneurial intentions. Its focus on external triggers, combined with individual perceptions of desirability and feasibility, offers a comprehensive way to understand how individuals are motivated to pursue entrepreneurship. It is essential to remember that the ideas of perceived desirability and feasibility depend on each other. If starting a business seems impossible, one might not want to, and vice versa (Shapero & Sokol, 1982). Desirability and feasibility are the main things that drive people to become entrepreneurs, and research has shown that educational practices affect individuals.

2.5.3 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory, which was created by R. Edward Freeman in 1984, says that businesses should think about the needs and concerns of everyone who will be touched by their actions, not just owners or shareholders. Identifying various stakeholders and addressing their needs is a critical requirement for organizational performance, particularly within the educational context (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2018). Stakeholder theory broadly categorizes shareholders, employees, community, government, customers, and suppliers as generic stakeholder groups (Freeman, 1984). In the context of education, for instance, HEIs' specific stakeholders are the policymakers, administrative body, faculty, labour market, alumni, community, ministry of Education (MEC), and students (Marinades, Alves & Raposo, 2010).

The Stakeholder Theory in EE literature investigates how the new educational programmes affects multiple stakeholders. The stakeholder perspective suggests that if entrepreneurial education's goal and anticipated result focus on cultivating entrepreneurs who will participate in activities that may contribute to economic development, involving diverse partners is crucial for cultivating successful entrepreneurs. Therefore, the development of entrepreneurship programmes must actively engage multiple stakeholders in the design process (Malay, 2011). Stakeholder Theory is helpful in education, especially entrepreneurship education since it helps explain how various players, especially educators, significantly impact the outcomes. Educators are active contributors to value creation within the educational process rather than merely passive participants. They affect students' entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, and intentions through sharing knowledge, creativity development, and mentorship. Their involvement and expertise are essential for harmonizing the institution's objectives with the requirements of students and society (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

The theory highlights the necessity of evaluating the long-term implications of decisions for all stakeholders rather than focusing solely on the immediate advantages for a limited group. The effectiveness of entrepreneurship programmes in educational settings depends on the institution's ability to manage relationships with various stakeholders, including students, educators, industry partners, and policymakers. The sustained effectiveness of these programs relies on institutions cultivating an ecosystem that encourages collaboration among all stakeholders, including students, administrators, and external partners, to generate value (Freeman, Harrison & Wicks, 2020). The collaboration between universities and industry stakeholders offers students practical experiences and networking opportunities, enhancing their preparation for entrepreneurial careers. Stakeholder Theory provides a comprehensive

framework for analyzing the dynamic interactions among various groups, illustrating how entrepreneurship education can address immediate academic objectives while fulfilling broader economic and societal requirements, promoting sustainable success across multiple levels of influence (Miles, 2012).

2.5.4 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TBP) by Ajzen (1991)

The TBP was first proposed by Ajzen in 1991. Ajzen and Fishbein's (1980) "*theory of reasoned action*" is the theoretical foundation from which this theory develops. TBP proposes that behaviour as intentional, considering the consequences of deliberate actions (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2000). The model has been employed to predict several human behaviours, such as voting preferences and the intention to cease smoking. The TBP provides a solid framework for evaluating how EEPs influence participants' entrepreneurial behaviour. EE significantly influences individual attitudes, which subsequently impact their intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The TBP has become more common in the study of entrepreneurship, especially in recent years (Al-Ghazali et al. (2022). The main thought is that being an entrepreneur comes from having the right intentions which leads to action. Additionally, individuals are active participants in their growth and development, meaning entrepreneurship is driven by deliberate choice rather than impulsive decisions. Entrepreneurial behaviour is fundamentally influenced by entrepreneurial intentions, which are shaped by three factors: Personal Attitudes, Subjective norms, and Perceived behavioural control (Ajzen 1991; 2002).

Figure 1: Theory of planned Behaviour

Source: Azjen (1991, p182)

Attitudes toward entrepreneurship refer to how positively or negatively an individual views the idea of becoming an entrepreneur. EEPs, through exposure to real-world examples, guest lectures from successful entrepreneurs, and hands-on learning opportunities, can shape students' attitudes, making entrepreneurship appear as a viable and rewarding career option (Fayolle et al., 2006; Rauch & Hulsink, 2015). For instance, a study by Nabi et al. (2018)

demonstrated that students who participated in entrepreneurship programmes developed higher positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship as a career, which significantly influenced their entrepreneurial intentions.

The second factor Subjective norms represent the societal pressures that influence an individual's entrepreneurial intention. Peers, families, educators, and mentors can influence educational norms. Studies have shown that student entrepreneurial inclinations are higher if they believe entrepreneurship is socially accepted or supported. Liñán and Chen (2009) discovered that family and peer support significantly boost entrepreneurial inclinations among university students. Entrepreneurship programmes that build mentorship and like-minded networks boost this influence. Perceived behavioural control (PBC), closely related to self-efficacy, is the individual's confidence in their business abilities. Entrepreneurship education emphasizes skill-building and practical experience, which improves PBC, which implies students are more likely to become entrepreneurs if they feel in charge. Kolvereid and Isaksen (2017) discovered that EE increased students' perceived control over entrepreneurial activities, which directly influenced their willingness to establish enterprises. Studies have confirmed TPB's use in entrepreneurship education research (Souitaris et al., 2007; Obschonka et al., 2017). The TPB is essential to understanding how EE affects students' entrepreneurial intents. TPB helps educators and researchers evaluate entrepreneurial education by addressing attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. Growing evidence suggests EE can positively impact these components, influencing future entrepreneurs.

Table 5: Summary of Theory

	Theory	Application in EE
1	Shapero Entrepreneurial Event (SEE) Model (Shapero & Sokol, 1982)	Explains how life events trigger entrepreneurial intentions and how education can serve as a positive shift to foster entrepreneurship.
2	Stakeholders Theory (Freeman, 1984)	Applied in entrepreneurship education to emphasize the role of various stakeholders (students, educators, institutions, policymakers, community, and industry) in creating effective programmes.
3	Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991)	Used to study how entrepreneurship education programs influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions to start businesses.

Source: Compiled by Researcher

2.6 Gaps in Literature

Most of the research on EE is concerned with students, specifically with their goals, mindsets, and development of entrepreneurial skills (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Bae et al., 2014). Nevertheless, insufficient research has addressed EE from the viewpoints of educators, which is an essential element in comprehending the extent of EE efficacy (Jones & Matlay, 2011). Educators significantly influence how EE programmes are delivered and thrive, but their perspectives, experiences, and difficulties are frequently disregarded, especially when considering Nigeria. According to Ruskovaara et al. (2015), there is not much research on the definition of EE, the methods educators use, and the obstacles they encounter. This study fills in a significant vacuum in the literature by emphasizing the educators' perspective. Since EE studies rarely address Nigerian educators' particular difficulties, such as scarce resources, sizable class numbers, and curriculum constraints, this field of study is crucial (Izedonmi & Okafor, 2010; Ifedili & Ofoegbu, 2011).

Although entrepreneurial pedagogy has been extensively studied worldwide, more is needed about the teaching methods employed at Nigerian universities (Gibb, 2002; Fayolle, 2013). Most EE studies conducted in Nigeria concentrate on general programme descriptions and outcomes, frequently missing a critical analysis of the methods of instruction used. There is little research on the effects of teaching methods on student outcomes in Nigeria, including case studies, simulations, lectures, and experiential learning (Udu, 2014; Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012). Furthermore, considering Nigerian educators' particular difficulties, such as inadequate infrastructure, classroom overcrowding, and a lack of funding, the study that has already been done falls short of addressing whether these approaches are appropriate for Nigeria's educational system (Ifedili & Ofoegbu 2011). This study closes this gap by critically examining the efficacy of teaching methods at Nigerian institutions and evaluating how they affect students' intentions to become entrepreneurs and their ability to develop their skills (Solomon, 2007; Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

Entrepreneurship education research has developed internationally, especially in the US and Europe (Neck & Greene, 2011; Nabi et al., 2017). Nigerian research on entrepreneurial education is growing. EE is crucial to solving socioeconomic issues, including unemployment and poverty. Global studies give practical frameworks and models, but they overlook Nigeria's institutional, economic, and cultural aspects of EE. For instance, excessive unemployment, political instability, and inadequate entrepreneurial resources affect how Nigerian institutions deliver and receive EE (Nwokolo et al., 2017; Garba, 2018). Nigeria's EE success depends on research on local entrepreneurship education constraints and growth prospects. Therefore, it is essential to explore the local barriers (Onyido et al., 2021).

Furthermore, frequently analyses university support mechanisms, such as funding, incubation centers, and mentorship, alongside teaching methods, including lectures and experiential learning, without investigating the interplay between these elements and their collective impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions. Studies by Nabi et al. (2017) and Neck & Corbett (2018) emphasize the significance of interactive teaching methods in fostering entrepreneurial skills; however, they need to consider the impact of institutional support from universities on these methods. In Nigeria, the limited University support may reduce the influence of teaching methods on students' entrepreneurial intentions (Garba, 2010). A gap exists in understanding how integrating university support and teaching methodologies can improve the effectiveness of EE programs, especially in resource-limited settings (Oseni et al., 2015; Fayolle, 2013). This research examines the relationship between university support structures and pedagogical

methods, offering insights into their collaborative potential to enhance entrepreneurial outcomes.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

The rising acknowledgement of entrepreneurship as a catalyst for economic growth has resulted in heightened interest in examining the influence of EE on students' entrepreneurial behaviours. Promoting entrepreneurship through education has become essential for creating opportunities for income and innovation in environments such as Nigeria, where high unemployment rates persist (Adejumo & Afolabi, 2021; Eze & Nwangwu, 2022).

The conceptual framework developed for this research combines the TPB by Ajzen (1991) and the roles of the Teaching method, Pedagogy, and University support in developing students' intentions and mindsets towards entrepreneurship. The dependent variable is the entrepreneurial intention to start and operate a business. The TPB states that this intention is shaped by attitudes toward entrepreneurship, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Liñán & Chen, 2009; Krueger, 2017). This model facilitates a thorough analysis of the factors that propel students toward entrepreneurial careers. Entrepreneurship education programs (EEPs) serve as an independent variable; these are organized initiatives to improve students' entrepreneurial attitudes, abilities, and knowledge. The research examines the influence of programmes provided by Nigerian Universities on students' entrepreneurial intentions. With EEPs, university support is a moderating variable, including institutional resources like entrepreneurship centers, mentorship programs, incubators, and funding availability. These tools are essential in cultivating an environment that supports students' confidence and entrepreneurial skills (Rasmussen & Sørheim, 2006; Saeed et al., 2015).

Another important moderating factor is entrepreneurial education's teaching methods and pedagogy. This employs traditional lectures, experiential learning, case studies, and business simulations. The approaches determine how well EE shapes students' attitudes and perceptions of entrepreneurial control (Neck & Greene, 2011; Gibb, 1993). The conceptual framework incorporates the three core elements of the TBP: attitudes towards entrepreneurship, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. Attitudes indicate the personal perspectives students hold regarding entrepreneurship as a viable choice. A positive perspective increases the likelihood of perceiving it as a feasible and beneficial choice (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). The influence of family, friends, and society on the decision to pursue entrepreneurship is illustrated in subjective norms. Solid social support frequently motivates students to contemplate

launching their ventures (Nabi & Liñán, 2013). Perceived behavioural control refers to an individual's confidence in exhibiting the necessary skills and resources to effectively start a venture. Their attitude towards entrepreneurship is positively correlated with their perceived level of control (Wilson et al., 2007; Ajzen, 1991). These elements help describe how students decide they want to become businesses and will be described below:

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework of Study

Source: Developed by Researcher

2.7.1 Personal Attitudes

Personal attitude (PA) refers to an individual's perspective or stance regarding a specific issue. Within this framework, PA refers specifically to an individual's attitude towards venture creation and entrepreneurship. It represents the person's opinion about the value of starting a business and their attitude that becoming an entrepreneur is desirable (Liñán & Chen, 2009; Ajzen, 2001; Kolvereid, 1996). Shook and Bratianu (2010) argue that an individual's attitude toward a particular issue depends on their beliefs of the outcome. A more favourable end outcome leads to an enhanced perception of it, which is associated with a stronger inclination to engage in specified behaviours. These attitudes are shaped by a variety of factors, including previous experiences, societal expectations, education, and personal values.

According to studies, positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship are positively correlated with the likelihood of engaging in entrepreneurial activities (Schlaegel & Koenig, 2014). Students who perceive entrepreneurship as fulfilling and providing self-sufficiency, monetary benefits, and individual development are more inclined towards entrepreneurship (Krueger, Reilly & Carsrud, 2000). On the other hand, people with opposing views frequently motivated by uncertainty, perceived risk, or fear of failing are less likely to start their businesses (Cacciotti,

Hayton, Mitchell & Giazitzoglu, 2016). Therefore, encouraging students to have an entrepreneurial mindset requires them to develop favourable personal attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Recent studies indicate that a positive personal attitude towards entrepreneurship is an essential indicator of entrepreneurial intention, with individuals who view entrepreneurship as a desirable career path more inclined to pursue it (Schlaegel & Koenig, 2014; Nowiński et al., 2019). This perspective involves the individual assessment of entrepreneurship as satisfying, beneficial, and attainable.

Beyond the classroom, university support shapes students' entrepreneurship mindsets. (Saeed et al., 2015). Institutional support reduces entrepreneurship risks, making students more confident in pursuing their aspirations. When students believe their university is concerned about their business success, their attitudes toward entrepreneurship improve (Shi, Wei & Zhang, 2020). University social factors like successful entrepreneurs and peer networks also foster positive attitudes. Being part of an entrepreneurial environment reinforces students' perceptions of entrepreneurship as a feasible and recognized career path (Morris, Liguori, & Pitt, 2021). These encounters can change students' minds, making entrepreneurship a viable and appealing career. Based on these findings, this H1 was developed for this study:

H1: Students perceiving higher university support and engaging teaching methods are likely to show positive attitudes and intentions towards EE.

In the context of EE, fostering positive attitudes through effective teaching methods and university support can significantly increase students' likelihood of pursuing entrepreneurship. Hypothesis 1 captures this dynamic by suggesting that stronger university support and engaging teaching methods lead to more positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship, thereby increasing students' entrepreneurial intentions. The evidence from existing literature supports this hypothesis, showing that when students have favourable attitudes toward entrepreneurship, they are more likely to view it as a desirable and achievable career path.

2.7.2 Subjective Norms

Subjective norms reflect an individual's perception of the beliefs held by social reference groups, including family and friends regarding the beginning of a business (Ajzen, 1991). According to the TPB model, experts assert that a more favourable perception of entrepreneurship by the reference group is linked to increased support for the individual, resulting in a boost in the intention to start a business endeavour. The relationship between subjective norms and entrepreneurial intention has been the topic of numerous empirical

investigations (Duong, 2021; Sun, Lo, Liang, & Wong, 2017). Despite this, the literature has inconsistent evidence to support the link between subjective norms and EI. Some studies have indicated a positive relationship between subjective norms and entrepreneurial intentions (Ahmed et al., 2020; Shah et al., 2020). These studies prove that individuals who perceive solid social support for entrepreneurship from family, peers, or mentors exhibit a greater propensity to develop the intention to start a business.

In contrast, various studies indicate a lack of significant or negative impact of subjective norms on EI (Duong, 2021; Tung et al., 2020). The findings indicate that the relationship between subjective norms and EI is not necessarily direct. Research indicates that this relationship may be affected by several mediating or moderating factors (Liñán & Chen, 2009). Factors including gender, field of study, cultural context, creativity, and regional conditions have been identified as potential moderators influencing the relationship between subjective norms and EI (Duong, 2021; González-Serrano et al., 2018; Pauline & T, 2019; Shi et al., 2020). Furthermore, perceived behavioural control and attitudes toward entrepreneurship have been recognized as possible mediators in this relationship (Doanh & Bernat, 2019; Duong, 2021). According to their result subjective norms and the desire to become an entrepreneur are linked in a complicated way. This complexity justifies the development of Hypothesis 2 below

H2: Increased university support and effective teaching methods may strengthen students' subjective norms, fostering social acceptance of entrepreneurship.

Therefore, Hypothesis 2 suggests that students' subjective norms will strengthen, and they will be more likely to pursue entrepreneurship due to university support and teaching methods that increase the social acceptance of entrepreneurship. Universities can shape individual attitudes and the broader social context of entrepreneurial decision-making by cultivating a culture encouraging entrepreneurship. Hypothesis 2 is grounded in this dynamic, suggesting that students who perceive strong institutional and social support for entrepreneurship are more likely to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Students feel socially validated to pursue entrepreneurship in circumstances where instructors and peers encourage it (Gemedá & Lee, 2020) or supporting their projects (Morris, Liguori, & Pitt, 2021). These actions provide tangible support and encourage an entrepreneurial mindset by fostering innovation and creativity in the university (Valliere & Gegenhuber, 2020).

2.7.3 Perceived Behavioural Control

Perceived behavioural control (PBC), as described by Ajzen (1991), refers to an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty in carrying out a specific behaviour, influenced by their prior experiences, resources, and abilities. Perceived behavioural control refers to an individual's assessment of the ease with which a specific behaviour can be executed, influenced mostly by their experiences and the resources and skills at their disposal. The concept of perceived behavioural control (PBC) is defined as a “person’s perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour of interest” (Ajzen, 1991, p. 183). Ajzen (1991) asserted that an individual's resources and capabilities directly influence the likelihood of achieving a desired behaviour. Ajzen (2002) first thought of PBC as a one-dimensional concept, like Bandura's (1977, 1982) social learning concept of self-efficacy, which is a person's belief in their ability to take the actions needed to handle future events. Multiple studies have replaced perceived behavioural control (PBC) with self-efficacy, presuming these concepts to be equivalent (Liñán et al., 2011; Moriano et al., 2012). Other research Kraft et al., 2005) indicates that perceived behavioural control (PBC) comprises two distinct components: self-efficacy, associated with an individual's internal confidence and skills, and perceived controllability, which pertains to external factors such as available resources or obstacles. PBC is currently defined as the integration of two dimensions: self-efficacy, which evaluates an individual's perceived difficulty and confidence in executing a behaviour, and controllability, which pertains to their belief in the external conditions that facilitate the successful execution of that behaviour.

According to research, higher PBC levels have been linked to stronger entrepreneurial intentions (Krueger & Carsrud, 1993; Alam, Kousar & Rehman, 2020). This is because students who feel they have the means, knowledge, and abilities to follow their entrepreneurial dreams are likelier to do so. PBC is affected by various factors, such as educational experiences, resource accessibility, and exposure to practical entrepreneurial situations. Engagement in activities that develop entrepreneurial competencies—such as business plan creation, project management, and learning from role models—enhances students' sense of control over their capacity to initiate and maintain a business (Wilson, Kickul, & Marlino, 2007). Studies like Neck and Greene (2011) have linked students' PBC to practical, hands-on entrepreneurial education. Students acquire theoretical knowledge and actively apply essential abilities for success in real-world business situations through simulations, case studies, and company development projects. This approach facilitates the connection between theoretical education

and practical implementation, instilling in students the confidence to confront and surmount the problems of initiating and managing a firm (Kickul, Gundry, and Barbosa, 2019). Gielnik, Frese, Graf, and Kampschulte (2015) discovered that students participating in interactive learning activities are more inclined to perceive themselves as capable of recognizing and seizing business opportunities, hence improving their perceived behavioural control (PBC). Based on these findings, this H3 was developed for this study:

H3: Greater university support and interactive teaching methods could enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours.

Hypothesis 3 is based on the recognition that pedagogical approaches, particularly those incorporating interactive and experiential learning and university support, significantly influence students' perceived behavioural control. These experiences enable students to develop vital entrepreneurial abilities, encounter typical problems, and acquire strategies for dealing with these challenges (Muñoz & Cohen, 2017). Beyond teaching methods, university support also plays a critical role in shaping students' PBC. Institutions that offer comprehensive support that reinforce their ability to navigate entrepreneurial challenges. According to Shi, Wei, and Zhang (2020), university support mechanisms foster a culture that values experimentation and risk-taking, which are key elements of developing entrepreneurial self-efficacy and providing useful resources.

2.7.4 Entrepreneurship Education

The knowledge and skills that students gain from entrepreneurship education significantly influence their learning journey and equip them for the challenges of entrepreneurship. Expanding upon previous frameworks like Johannisson's (1991), recent investigations have narrowed in on the essential learning domains within entrepreneurship education. This involves understanding the entrepreneurial mindset, where students explore the reasons behind entrepreneurs' behaviours, influenced by their values, attitudes, and motivations (Nabi et al., 2017). A key focus is entrepreneurial knowledge, which provides students with insights into the necessary steps for initiating and overseeing a new business venture (Maritz & Brown, 2013). Alongside theoretical understanding, entrepreneurship education emphasizes the cultivation of practical skills. Kuratko (2016) emphasizes the significance of developing skills that allow students to carry out entrepreneurial endeavours successfully. Furthermore, Pittaway et al. (2015) highlighted that the significance of networking and social capital is paramount in entrepreneurship education, instructing students on the value of cultivating and utilizing

relationships. Ultimately, the capacity to identify and take advantage of opportunities is crucial, with Lackéus (2015) emphasizing the significance of opportunity recognition in thriving entrepreneurial endeavours. This current approach to entrepreneurship education highlights the significance of integrating theoretical knowledge with practical, real-world experiences, equipping students with the necessary tools and confidence to convert their education into entrepreneurial outcomes.

2.7.5 University Support

The educational environment positively impacts entrepreneurship, as these institutions offer essential possibilities and resources that shape students' entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurship centers, mentorship programs, incubators, competitions, and funding opportunities are just a few options included in university support. Recent studies indicate that students who recognize adequate backing from their university are more inclined to nurture entrepreneurial intentions, as they believe they possess the required abilities and networks to begin entrepreneurial pursuits (Nguyen et al., 2021; Nabi, Walmsley, & Akhtar, 2019). Mentorship programs help students gain entrepreneurial skills in a supportive, controlled setting and handle business startup risks (Birdthistle, Hynes, & Fleming, 2019). University-sponsored incubators provide office space, technology, and expert advice to help students transfer from theory to practice in entrepreneurial endeavours (Pittaway et al., 2020). University competitions and innovation challenges allow students to present their ideas, receive expert feedback, and obtain financing or recognition (Morris, Liguori, & Pitt, 2021). These initiatives provide tangible support and encourage an entrepreneurial mindset by fostering innovation and creativity in the university. The institutional environments assist entrepreneurship by offering tangible and intangible measures of success. Flexible funding, venture capital, infrastructure, R&D facilities, and training are tangible indicators. These resources enable entrepreneurs to grow their enterprises by providing financial and infrastructure support (Wright & Stigliani, 2013; Ács et al., 2017). However, intangible factors like human capital availability and support for entrepreneurship legitimacy are more invisible. A pro-entrepreneurial culture, networking, and governmental frameworks that validate and promote entrepreneurship may help. These supports empower entrepreneurs to take on the risks of beginning and running a business. Studies show that having both sorts of support boosts entrepreneurship and creativity (Fayolle & Wright, 2014; Urbano et al., 2019).

2.7.6 Teaching Methods and Pedagogy

Entrepreneurship education relies on both course content and pedagogy to engage students. Recent research emphasizes the significance of experiential learning in entrepreneurship education, exposing students to real-world challenges to develop skills and mindset for success (Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2014; Muñoz & Cohen, 2017). Simulations, case studies, business plan preparation, and interactions with practicing entrepreneurs help students think critically and solve real-world business challenges (Liguori & Winkler, 2020). This hands-on approach effectively develops entrepreneurial skills like innovation, risk management, and opportunity recognition (Bae et al., 2014). Students gain entrepreneurial self-efficacy and are better prepared to manage the complexity of beginning and maintaining a firm by putting theoretical knowledge in practice (Neck & Greene, 2011). Studies suggest that active learning experiences boost students' confidence in their entrepreneurial skills, which increases their entrepreneurial intentions (Pittaway & Cope, 2007). Both theory and practice in entrepreneurship education have established the connection between the entrepreneurship curriculum, pedagogical approaches, and specific personality traits constructs, such as attitude, need for accomplishment, willingness to take risks, sense of power, and creativity (Ndofirepi, 2020; Nunfam, Asitik & Afrifa-Yamoah 2022; Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2015). Empirical studies indicate that entrepreneurship curriculum significantly enhances personality traits, that teaching methods are closely related to entrepreneurship curriculum, and that teaching methods significantly influence personality traits, such as entrepreneurial attitude (Nunfam et al., 2022).

The University support and pedagogical approaches collectively affect students' entrepreneurial intentions, specifically through their influence on attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, which needs to be more adequately investigated and requires additional empirical study. This gap highlights the need to know how these educational components influence students' confidence and drive to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours. This is the rationale for Hypothesis 4;

H4: Stronger university support and engaging teaching methods may lead to more positive behavioural intentions toward entrepreneurial activities

This suggests that greater university support and interactive teaching methods could enhance students' perceived behavioural control, ultimately strengthening their entrepreneurial intentions. By investigating this relationship, the study aims to address the gap in understanding

how educational support mechanisms contribute to students' confidence and perceived ability to succeed in entrepreneurship.

2.7.7 Entrepreneurial Intentions

The concept of "intention" has been defined by multiple researchers similarly. According to Ajzen (2011), Behavioural intentions refer to the signals of an individual's preparedness to engage in a specific behaviour. Entrepreneurial intention (EI), broadly understood, is the mental state that focuses and directs attention, experience, activities, goal planning, communications, commitment, organisation, and other work towards entrepreneurial actions (Fini, Grimaldi, Marzocchi, & Sobrero, 2012). literature defines EI as acknowledging their desire to establish a new business and deliberately planning to achieve this goal (Thompson, 2009). Intention is a crucial element in comprehending an individual's choice to establish a business venture prior to pursuing specific opportunities and it is significant in predicting entrepreneurial behaviour (Duong, 2021).

The TPB suggests that after an individual forms an intention shaped by positive attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, the subsequent step is to convert these intentions into actual behaviours, such as engaging in start-up activities (Gieure, Benavides-Espinosa & Roig-Dobon, 2020). Studies like Gieure et al., (2020) and Joensuu-Salo, Viljamma, Varamaki, and Tornikoski (2020) have thoroughly examined the TPB model and found a positive relationship between EI and students' actual behaviour. In the context of this study, University support and teaching methods and Pedagogy are included in this study as key factors that align with the TPB as they influence students' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, thereby shaping their entrepreneurial intentions. This led to the development of hypothesis 5 which states;

H5: Interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions regarding entrepreneurship.

This hypothesis is based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) framework, which proposes that entrepreneurial intentions result from the interplay of attitudes, norms, and perceived control. The integration of university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches mirrors the real-world conditions influencing students' intention formation. Through engagement with these factors, students acquire knowledge and skills while also experiencing support from their social environment, which enhances their confidence in

achieving a successful outcome. Hypothesis 5 is supported by the notion that entrepreneurial intentions emerge from a supportive and integrated educational ecosystem (Neck & Greene, 2011; Saeed et al., 2015) and it emphasizes the dynamic interplay of educational and institutional factors in fostering entrepreneurial intentions that are likely to lead to real entrepreneurial behaviour.

2.8 Summary of Chapter

This chapter examined Nigerian university-specific entrepreneurship education (EE) concepts, theories, and challenges. Ajzen's TPB describes how attitudes, societal norms, and perceived control influence an individual's intention to become an entrepreneur. Different models, such as SEE Model, were also discussed to understand entrepreneurial aspirations further. These ideas show the complexity of entrepreneurial behaviour, but how they apply to Nigerian students is unclear. The assessment of EE teaching approaches concluded that lectures and case studies give core information but need more practical engagement to develop entrepreneurial abilities. Project-based learning and simulations were noted to be more effective at encouraging creativity and practical skills in pupils. However, little is known about how these instructional strategies are used in Nigerian colleges and whether they handle students' unique challenges.

In Nigeria, entrepreneurial education is plagued by underfunding, insufficient facilities, and a significant emphasis on theory. These barriers prohibit students from learning entrepreneurial skills. The literature also reveals that educators' opinions are often disregarded despite their critical role in entrepreneurship education. In Nigerian institutions, limited institutional support and policy gaps make EE programs struggle to reach their full potential. The conceptual framework and the hypothesis developed for this study have been discussed in the literature, exploring how University Support and Teaching methods affect entrepreneurial Intentions. This chapter shows that while EE has immense potential, there are significant gaps in understanding how it works in Nigeria. Educators' insights, personalised teaching approaches, and institutional support must be addressed to improve entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY AND DESIGN

3.0 Introduction

In this section, the overall research aims and objectives will be revisited, followed by a discussion of the considerations for data collection. Three philosophical paradigms post-positivism, constructivism, and pragmatism will be examined, with a rationale provided for the selection of a pragmatist approach. This study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, leading to the adoption of a sequential-exploratory research design (Creswell, 2014). In conclusion, the many steps of the research process as well as the methods that are utilised for data analysis will be presented and discussed.

3.1 Research aims and objectives

The aim of the research is:

To investigate the effect of EEPs in Nigerian universities on students' entrepreneurial intention to determine the effectiveness of the programmes on their entrepreneurial outcomes.

This broad aim was designed to explore not only the student's intentions to participate in entrepreneurial activities but also to explore the factors that affect their motivation and subsequent intentions and the perspective of educators on the agenda of EE.

As a result, the first research objective was established:

1. *To critically investigate how entrepreneurship educators define Entrepreneurship Education and teaching methods.*

To provide a foundational insight of EE in the Nigerian context, this objective was investigated through a qualitative study, which is presented in Chapter 4. The objective sets the stage for the study by delving into the perspectives of entrepreneurship educators in Nigeria. It seeks to uncover how these educators define entrepreneurship education and the teaching methods they employ. In-depth interviews have been instrumental in understanding the educators' viewpoints and gaining insights into their pedagogical approaches. The insights gained from this qualitative research inform subsequent objectives, offering valuable context for the challenges, student outcomes, teaching approaches, and assessment frameworks explored in the following objectives:

- 2. to critically investigate the challenges confronting EE learning in Nigeria from the educator's viewpoint.*

RO2 continues with a qualitative approach. It aims to explore the challenges that educators face in delivering EE in Nigeria. This qualitative investigation provides a critical perspective from the educators themselves, shedding light on the challenges they encounter. These challenges are crucial to understanding the potential shortcomings in the current educational landscape and will serve as a bridge to understanding the specific areas where improvement and support are needed within EE in the Nigerian context.

- 3. To critically identify skills, competencies, and capabilities students develop from participating in entrepreneurship education programmes.*

With a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and teaching methods employed by educators, the educators will then identify some of the skills, they emphasize and nurture in students, the third objective then transitions into quantitative research. It quantifies the outcomes of entrepreneurship education by identifying the skills, competencies, and capabilities that students acquire through participation in entrepreneurship education programmes. This objective connects to the earlier qualitative findings by providing measurable data on students' intentions, offering a quantitative foundation to further investigate the effectiveness of teaching approaches, leading to research objective four:

- 4. To critically explore the effectiveness of teaching approaches for entrepreneurial learning in Nigerian universities to foster entrepreneurial intentions among students.*

RO4 also takes a quantitative approach, it continues to investigate teaching approaches in Nigerian universities. This time, it investigates quantitatively how well these methods work to encourage students' entrepreneurial intentions.. The insights gained from this objective provide evidence-based conclusions regarding which teaching methods are commonly used and which are most effective, linking back to educators' perspectives while preparing the groundwork for the development of an assessment framework in the next objective:

- 5. To develop a framework for the effective assessment of entrepreneurship programmes in Nigerian universities.*

Finally, RO5 is a synthesizing objective. It aims to create a comprehensive framework for assessing entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities, drawing upon the findings from the previous objectives. These objectives leverage both qualitative and quantitative insights to

develop a customized framework that can guide the improvement and evaluation of EEPs in a systematic and evidence-based manner. This objective offers a holistic perspective on the entire research process.

The previously stated aims necessitate a mixed-methods approach. This chapter presents an outline of the adopted exploratory sequential design. The objective of the quantitative data collecting in the study is to enhance and examine the results of the qualitative research phase (Clark & Ivankova, 2016; Creswell, 2009).

3.2 Research Philosophy

The implications of the philosophical frameworks used in social science research must be understood by researchers. Research philosophy, as described by Saunders et al. (2012), encompasses a researcher's perspective on knowledge, its fundamental nature, and its evolution. Despite the intense dispute around the relationship between theory and data, Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Lowe (2002) affirm that ignoring philosophical concerns may greatly impact the quality of management research, as these questions are fundamental to the study design framework.

Easterby-Smith, et al. (2002) proposed that in research there are three points to be considered. Firstly, certain ways of doing research are usually related to the type of research design, which can help figure out which research methods are right for the study. Secondly, to enhance comprehension of the philosophy, it is essential to ascertain which may be appropriate, and which may be unsuccessful by demonstrating the limits of specific approaches. Lastly, having a background in philosophy can assist researchers in discovering or developing appropriate research methods and structures that may have been unfamiliar to them otherwise. By recognizing the philosophical foundations, researchers can justify their choices. Determining a philosophical position requires analysing the differences between different viewpoints and closely analysing the researcher's beliefs towards the acquisition of knowledge (Creswell & Clark, 2011).

The various philosophical stances, including paradigms, epistemology, ontology, and world views, can be viewed as a "set of beliefs" that direct one's behaviour, according to Creswell & Creswell (2018). The term worldview, as utilized by Creswell and Creswell (2018), refers to the philosophical orientation that a researcher incorporates into their study. It is noteworthy that Creswell further explains that worldviews are influenced by various factors such as discipline orientations, inclinations of students' advisors/mentors, and past research

experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p. 5). The adoption of different research approaches is a result of a researcher's belief. This chapter delves into the rationale behind the decisions that shape the research design.

Researchers have noted there are four principle worldviews: post-positivist, constructivist, transformative, and pragmatic (Mertens, 2019). To compare worldviews, one can utilize branches of philosophy, namely ontology, epistemology, and methodology. Table 3 provides an overview of these concepts (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002 p. 31).

Table 6: Overview of Research Philosophy

Philosophical Term	Explanation
Ontology	Refers to the underlying beliefs about nature of reality and existence
Epistemology	Encompasses the assumptions about how we acquire knowledge and understand truth.
Methodology	The structured set of methods and techniques used to investigate a specific issue

Source: Compiled by Researcher

Morgan (2007) identifies these three key concepts as part of the "metaphysical paradigm," which deals with questions surrounding reality and truth. He explains how differences in ontological views affect both methodological and epistemological approaches. This idea has been previously described as the "incompatibility of paradigms" (Kuhn, 1996). In addition, Morgan (2007) suggests that researchers working within one metaphysical framework often reject the principles of other paradigms. His worldview offers alternative perspectives ontological, epistemological, and methodological challenging the dominant positivist approach. These perspectives are now commonly applied in business and social science research (e.g., Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002; Gill & Johnson, 2010). Two paradigms often used in social sciences and business research are constructivism and post-positivism.

3.2.1 Post-positivism and Constructivism

Traditional post-positivism favours quantitative research over qualitative (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Post-positivism emerged from educators' critique of positivism. Because it relies on empirical data, positivism cannot meet social science research needs, according to

educational scholars. Social science and educational researchers created post-positivism, a mixed paradigm that combines positivism and interpretivism, in response to the rigid nature of quantitative empirical analytical research. Creswell & Creswell (2018) state that positivism led to postpositivist philosophy, which challenges absolute truth. Postpositivist understand that *"we cannot be completely positive about our knowledge when we study human behaviour and actions"* (p.6). Postpositivist think reality is accurate because it is measurable, observable, and objective. Quantifying observations and behavioural research are critical in postpositivist research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Postpositivist use hypothetical methods in their study. The idea helps researchers form hypotheses about a study issue or objective and test them using statistical analysis to support or disprove them. Well-defined human behaviour can be measured. Because cognitive processes are unseen, quantifying them is more challenging. Measurements usually use self-report and subjective experience (Toure-Tillery & Fishbach, 2014).

Due to the widespread application of positivism in the social sciences over the past 50 years, studies have yielded results that do not fit into preexisting theories, leading to the emergence of alternative worldviews (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe & Lowe, 2002). This alternative perspective is known as constructivism or social constructionism and is frequently linked to or called interpretivism (Creswell, 2014; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009), and because of this, the constructionist worldview has developed into a vital and widely accepted substitute for positivistic research. Constructivists believe people should try subjectively acquiring knowledge to understand their experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Unlike the reductionist or hypothetical approach, which often limits analysis to a few variables, a constructivist approach values multiple perspectives and emphasizes the importance of understanding the participants' viewpoints. Researchers following this approach actively seek to explore the diverse experiences of individuals, allowing meaning to emerge from the context of the study. In this way, they build a more comprehensive understanding of the situation, shaped by the participants' interpretations and insights (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

In constructivist research, subjective meaning is shaped by individual experiences and interactions with others, reflecting social constructivism and historical and cultural norms influencing individual lives (Creswell and Cresswell, 2018,). This is particularly important for African research, where global theories may not fully correspond with local socio-cultural contexts (Bockarie, 2020). Mkhize and Mpofo (2021) argue that it is crucial to adapt Western

theories to the African context to generate research findings that are meaningful and sensitive to local norms, values, and societal structures.

The process of research involves the application of inductive methods to establish theories or uncover meaningful patterns (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Within constructivist research, the methods employed typically encompass the collection, analysis, and interpretation of narrative data using thematic analysis (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). In the field of academic entrepreneurship research, quantitative methods have historically overshadowed qualitative research. Qualitative research has been employed by researchers to construct theories or attain a more comprehensive understanding of phenomena. Examples include Rasmussen, Mosey, and Wright (2014) in research on the influence of university departments on the evolution of entrepreneurial competencies in spin-off ventures and Philpott, Dooley, O'Reilly, and Lupton (2011) on the 'entrepreneurial university: Examining the underlying academic tensions'. The table below provides a concise summary of distinctions in the Post-positivistic and Constructionist philosophies.

Table 7: A comparative Analysis of Post-positivistic and constructionist philosophies

Research Assumptions	Post-Positivism	Constructivism
Ontology	Reality is tangible and observable to the researcher	Reality is subjective and is interpreted by the researcher
Epistemology	The research and the researcher are independent.	The researcher is part of what is being researched
Human interest	It is imperative to be inconsequential	A key motivator
Intention	The purpose is to establish a clear cause-effect correlation	The objective is to enhance comprehension of the circumstances.
Research Process	Hypothesis and deduction	Ideas are induced from gathering rich data
Concepts and idea	Need to be expressed in terms of the operation, to allow for measurement	Should incorporate the key perspectives of the key stakeholders
Units of analysis	Should be reduced to the simplest form	May include the complexity of 'whole' situations
Generalization	Statistical probability	Theoretical abstraction
Sampling	Requires a significant sample size, randomly selected.	Requires a small number of specifically chosen cases

Sources: (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Lowe, 2002; Hussey and Hussey, 1997; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009)

Over time, blending of quantitative and qualitative research has been viewed as unsuitable due to the inherent differences between the paradigms. The concept of paradigm incompatibility suggests that the disparity within qualitative and quantitative research is so critical that combining them is unfeasible (Morgan, 2007). Nonetheless, in the last few decades, it has become evident that rather than being at odds with each other, these approaches can complement one another. Different researchers support the combination of both methodologies in research, exemplified by Creswell & Creswell (2018) and Teddlie & Tashakkori (2009), embracing the compatibility thesis as put forth by Brewer & Hunter (2006) who suggests that

using multiple research methods to explore the same issue can offer practical benefits. Instead of sticking to a single theoretical approach, combining methods allows for the integration of different perspectives when interpreting data (p. 55).

To refute the incompatibility argument, philosophers developed the philosophical concept of Pragmatism, providing an alternative outlook (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009; Mertens, 2019). The pragmatic approach of this study gives the researcher freedom to employ any approach that yields actionable, beneficial outcomes in meeting the research objectives. It focuses on understanding what is effective in EE and how it shapes students' EI. The study also explores what areas are ineffective and what improvements can be made to boost the impact of EE on student development (Nabi et al., 2018).

3.2.2 Pragmatism

The American philosopher Charles Sanders Peirce is credited with developing pragmatism (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Mautner (1997) notes that Peirce believed "beliefs are habits of action, not representations of reality" (p. 441). This idea has evolved into pragmatism, emphasizing that the meaning of any concept comes from its practical effects. Our understanding of a concept is shaped by the outcomes it produces in real-world scenarios (James, 2017). The work of Charles Peirce became a foundation for different researchers to build on as William James developed upon Peirce's theories by suggesting that a true belief results in positive outcomes, thereby defining truth as "what works." (Mautner, 1997). In addition, James Dewey adopted a naturalistic view on the work of Peirce and James, suggesting that the notion of pursuing truth without any personal bias is non-existent, and it is impossible to separate theoretical exploration from practical deliberation (Mautner, 1997). Their main concern revolved around the examination of empirical findings to gain insights into the importance of philosophical viewpoints. The goal was to identify the actions that should be taken to enhance understanding of the real world. Consequently, pragmatism is associated with practicality, signifying that the most effective approach in practice can serve as a criterion for establishing truth (Honderich, 2005, p. 747).

The approach of pragmatism differs as it seeks to shed light on the meanings, consequences, values, human actions, and interactions that precede efforts to outline descriptions, theories, explanations, and narratives (Cherryholmes, 1992). These elements hold great importance when examining entrepreneurship education at the individual level. Pragmatic decisions regarding research depend on the researcher's ultimate objective. As a result, research results

from the peer-reviewed literature are significant because they emphasize practical implications and act as a 'benchmark' for organising subsequent findings and events. (Cherryholmes, 1992, p 14). According to Teddie and Takahashi (2009), Pragmatism challenges the idea of making exclusive choices and instead advocates for the incorporation of diverse research methods. It also recognizes that the researcher's values can play a role in shaping the interpretation of the results. Pragmatism can therefore combine the use of both quantitative and qualitative research designs. As a philosophical foundation for mixed research methodologies, pragmatism emphasises the need to focus research attention on a specific subject and then employing different methods to gather knowledge about it. The literature evaluation emphasised that EE is a multidimensional domain that requires in-depth study. To effectively link theory and data using a pragmatic approach, the utilization of abductive reasoning is essential. Abductive reasoning involves a dynamic interplay between inductive and deductive methods, wherein observations are translated into theories and subsequently evaluated for their results (Morgan, 2007).

3.3 Research Design

The study design, developed from a pragmatic perspective, will be utilised to accomplish the goals and objectives of the research.

3.3.1 Mixed Methods

This study adopts a mixed-methods research methodology. Valerie (1993) asserts that mixed methods research integrates qualitative and quantitative approaches to enhance understanding of the research problem. This integration enhances the interpretation of the phenomenon within its context, increasing confidence in the study's results. Mixed-methods research studies use qualitative and quantitative methods to better comprehend a research problem. This method combines the qualities of both methodologies to let researchers examine a subject from numerous angles. According to Creswell and Clark (2011), it entails gathering, analysing, and integrating qualitative and quantitative data in one or more research. By combining qualitative and quantitative data, research problems can be better understood. Mixed-methods research is appropriate for complicated research issues that one method cannot answer (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010).

Different studies have recognized the strength of mixed-method research. Jick (1979) highlighted that qualitative and quantitative methods should be viewed as complementary rather than separate strategies and acknowledged the benefits and drawbacks of single

method designs. This made triangulation the merging of qualitative and quantitative data possible. The growing inclusion of qualitative research as a complement to quantitative research in the investigative process was a key component of this paradigm change. Over the years, mixed methods approaches have significantly developed, surpassing mere triangulation. Incorporating quantitative and qualitative methods within a single study has gained acceptance. Consequently, numerous journal articles and books have been published, emphasizing this research approach (Merten, 2019; Creswell, 2014; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). According to Creswell (2009, p. 4), mixed methods research has progressed beyond the mere collection and analysis of different data types; it includes applying qualitative and quantitative methodologies at the same time, producing research that is stronger than it would have been with just one approach.

As suggested by Creswell (2014), adopting a mixed methods approach allows for the sequential integration of qualitative and quantitative methods within a single research study. This thesis will follow this approach. This study will utilise an exploratory sequential design, wherein the data gathering procedure will progress sequentially through various stages; further elaboration will be provided in the subsequent section. The initial phase of data collecting will involve conducting interviews with educators to ascertain their perceptions of EE and the pedagogical approaches employed. The second step of the research will build upon the first by developing surveys aimed at identifying difficulties, student perspectives, and whether different pedagogical approaches foster entrepreneurial intention. There are disagreements about the application of mixed-method research. Bryman (2007) suggests that an unclear rationale for employing this approach may reflect indecisiveness or a lack of understanding, potentially resulting in improper application. Providing a clear rationale for the utilisation of mixed techniques is crucial, since it strengthens the methodological foundation of the research. This study requires an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of mixed methods to validate its approach and guarantee a balanced research design. A survey by Creswell and Clark (2021) underscores the necessity for clarity and structure. The study's selected method must be justified, and this requires highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of mixed methods research. To help with the creation of the research design for the study, the table below offers a thorough summary of these.

Table 8: Strengths and Weaknesses of Mixed Methods Research

Strengths	Weaknesses
Combines the depth of qualitative data with the breadth of quantitative data, offering a more comprehensive understanding.	Can be time-consuming and resource-intensive due to the need for collecting and analyzing two types of data.
Allows for triangulation, which enhances the validity and reliability of the findings.	Requires expertise in both qualitative and quantitative methods, which can be challenging for researchers.
Enables researchers to explore a phenomenon from multiple perspectives, enriching the analysis.	Data integration can be difficult, as combining qualitative and quantitative results is not always straightforward.
Facilitates answering complex research questions that require both detailed insights and numerical evidence.	Can increase the complexity of research design and data analysis, potentially making the study harder to manage.
Provides flexibility, as researchers can collect and analyze both types of data sequentially or concurrently.	May lead to conflicting results between qualitative and quantitative findings, complicating interpretation

Source: Compiled through literature from Creswell & Clark (2011) and Tashakkori & Teddlie (2010)

3.3.2 Justification for Mixed Method

Mixed methods research has contributed immensely to academia through its application in the social sciences (Creswell, 2011; Morgan, 2007). Integrating qualitative and quantitative research methods has allowed a broader understanding of complex phenomena, offering readers more assurance in research findings and conclusions. Studies that utilize a mixed methods approach can gain a deeper and thorough understanding of a particular phenomenon compared to using a monomethod (Creswell, 2011; Jones et al., 2015; McKim, 2017; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003). The reasoning behind this is the belief that studying complex social issues promotes a more profound understanding of the metrics and unintentional processes that enhance the distribution of the outcomes generated (Coyle & Williams, 2000; Papadimitriou et al., 2014).

In their study, Fayolle and Liñán (2014) explored the effect factor of purpose in entrepreneurship education research, and they concluded that researchers should aim to perform rigorously methodical investigations. To help triangulate findings and produce conclusions that are more trustworthy, researchers advise using mixed-method techniques that integrate or permit the independent use of various methodologies. In a similar vein, Tashakkori and Teddlie (2003) highlighted that mixed-methods research makes it possible to apply several ways for various goals inside a single study, enhancing the reliability and rigour of the findings.

A clear justification strengthens the methodological framework and clarifies the rationale for employing both methods. Creswell and Clark (2018) emphasise that a clearly articulated justification for mixed methods can address potential challenges and provide a solid base for the study's design. This approach facilitates thorough exploration by utilizing the advantages of both methods. Study methodologies and procedures that complement one another facilitate richer explanations, illustrations, and clarifications of study findings across methods (Greene et al., 1989). Bryman (2006) conducted a content analysis of over 232 papers and provided a more detailed justification for mixed-method researchers. Multiple reviews of Bryman's (2006) content analysis of mixed-method studies have been provided by studies. Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) acknowledged its comprehensive understanding of the increasing acceptance of mixed methods and highlighted methodological cooperation in improving research depth. In addition, Greene (2008) observed that Bryman's research illuminated the practical difficulties associated with mixed methods while affirming its importance in addressing the complexities of social phenomena. Both scholars acknowledge that mixed methods provide a robust framework for a more thorough understanding of research topics.

Mixed-method research permits results from one phase to be utilised to design surveys for the next phase or to corroborate results. For this study, developing the data-collection instrument was crucial to choosing the mixed-method approach. The study's subsequent stage developed a survey tool using qualitative findings. In the 'convergent parallel design,' qualitative and quantitative data are collected simultaneously. The 'concurrent design' is sometimes used in a triangulation exercise to compare two sets of results or evaluate the pros and cons of both ways (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The second design presented by Bryman et al. (2015) from Saunders et al. (2009) is an "exploratory sequential design." Second design: process flows from stage to stage. It is used when the researcher wishes to establish a hypothesis to test quantitatively or when instruments like surveys are used for quantitative research. The exploratory sequential design of this study means that the results of one data gathering phase inform those of the next.

The next stage's development is influenced by the conclusions from the previous one. First, challenges in imparting entrepreneurship, the teaching methods and critical entrepreneurial skills for starting a firm in Nigeria will be determined through interviews with educators. Building on these results, the second phase a survey will investigate the abilities and motivations that students acquire from EEPs. The questionnaire will be improved for the Nigerian setting because of the qualitative findings.

Using a mixed-method study also has the benefit of improving the reliability of the research. The integrity of the research findings is strengthened by the mixed methodology, which combines quantitative and qualitative techniques. Given the scarcity of mixed-method approaches being employed in Nigeria to investigate students' entrepreneurial intentions, "credibility" serves as a relevant reason for the utilisation. Stated differently, few studies with similar goals use mixed methods within their methodological designs or frameworks (Creswell & Clark, 2018; Maritz et al., 2020).

Practical and beneficial outcomes for practitioners and other stakeholders could result from the application of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. The research's pragmatic and applied nature underscores the significance of evaluating the utility and applicability of the findings for various stakeholders. Accordingly, the important justification of "utility" supports the selection of a mixed-method approach in this study (Bryman, 2006).

3.3.3 Limitations for Mixed Method

Many studies employing mixed techniques have demonstrated that it is effective by integrating the advantages of several methodologies while minimising their drawbacks (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). However, a few researchers, such as Bazeley (2002), emphasise the difficulties associated with the effective use of mixed techniques. The complex process of integrating data from qualitative and quantitative methodologies is a significant obstacle in mixed-method research. Given this complex nature, researchers must ensure that both methods work well together when designing, collecting, and analysing data. To prevent discrepancies in the results, the various procedures must be carefully coordinated (Bazeley, 2002; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2021). This integration is essential for a thorough study of entrepreneurial education research, where factors like pedagogy and teaching methods, university support, and TPB components are involved.

Secondly, Mixed-method research frequently necessitates considerable allocation of time and resources due to requirements for large sample sizes, different collection methods, and

extensive analysis methods. This limitation is particularly relevant as this study examines entrepreneurial education in Nigerian universities. The study entails the involvement of educators and students through qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys, necessitating the organization of schedules and allocation of resources (Greene et al., 2020). However, the combination can result in detailed insights that a single method alone would not provide.

In addition, Brannen (2017) explores the integration of mixed methods and highlights a potential drawback. This limitation revolves around the complexity of merging various methodologies within a single study, particularly when it involves shifting, especially when it pertains to shifting through paradigms in epistemology and philosophy. Failure to select the appropriate methods during this process can result in disorder and confusion (Brannen, 2005). Although mixed methodologies have been widely used in research (Hesse-Biber and Johnson, 2013), the issue of validity associated with such designs has been a bone of contention (see Mathison, 1988). Mixed methods researchers agree that assessing the validity of Mixed-Method Research (MMR) is difficult because it combines the unique strengths and “nonoverlapping” difficulties of qualitative and quantitative methods.

3.4 Research Design

There are two main types of mixed method designs as noted by Creswell and Creswell (2018), the sequential and concurrent design. A concurrent design involves simultaneous research. In a sequential design, the researcher collects data using one approach and then switches to another after analysing the results. Considering the exploratory nature of objectives 1 and 2, an initial phase of qualitative research was designed. This was developed to gain deeper insights into EE within the Nigerian context, focussing on the perspective of a key stakeholder: the educators. To address objectives 3 and 4, the qualitative phase was succeeded by a quantitative research phase, during which the results was evaluated among students in Nigerian universities.

3.4.1 Exploratory Sequential Design

The exploratory sequential mixed-method design presents a range of applications within mixed-method approaches. Creswell (2014) emphasised that although its primary aim is to investigate a phenomenon, it can also aid in interpreting qualitative data and facilitate the generalisation of findings. The design usually starts with the collection of qualitative data in the initial phase, which is then succeeded by the collection of quantitative data in the subsequent phase (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). This is demonstrated in the figure below.

Figure 3 Exploratory Sequential Design Method

In the usual course of exploratory sequential designs (ESD), researchers begin by examining qualitative data collected from small samples during the first stage. The main goal of this stage is to collect data and enhance the following stage, which involves a larger sample. According to Creswell and Clark (2011, p. 87), an exploratory sequential design (ESD) is commonly employed under the following circumstances:

- When the researcher lacks knowledge about the essential constructs.
- When ample time is available to conduct research in multiple stages.
- When resource restrictions require a study design that collects and analyses only one organize of data at a time.
- When additional questions arise from qualitative data that cannot be adequately addressed by relying solely on qualitative data.

Figure 4 Exploratory Sequential Design Process

Source: Developed by researcher

3.6 Ethical Considerations

A comprehensive ethical framework was followed to ensure the protection, autonomy, and dignity of all participants throughout the research process. Informed consent and data protection were treated as central pillars of ethical conduct, particularly given the qualitative nature of the study, where participants share personal perspectives in institutional and cultural contexts. Such ethical considerations are foundational to responsible research practice and directly impact data quality, participant trust, and academic integrity (Israel & Hay, 2006; Saunders et al., 2019).

Before the commencement of data collection, participants were thoroughly briefed on the nature, extent, and objectives of the study. Since the interviewees were not prior acquaintances, establishing rapport was initiated through email communication and at the interview's outset. In the qualitative phase, a comprehensive participant information sheet was distributed through email, detailing the research aims, the voluntary aspect of participation, confidentiality protocols, and the right to withdraw from the study at any time before data anonymisation without any repercussions. The document also clarified how the data would be utilized, stored,

and safeguarded, following GDPR and the ethical research policy of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Consent was subsequently acquired in written form, digitally signed, and sent back via email, and was verbally reaffirmed at the beginning of each recorded interview (Saunders et al., 2019; Creswell & Creswell, 2018). All participants volunteered their time, and the interviews did not exceed 45 minutes. The researcher retained all collected information, following the UWS data protection protocols. Interviewees were informed that future academic and non-academic outputs would protect their names and institutions. The findings would be used exclusively for educational purposes through scholarly publication.

During the quantitative phase, a comparable degree of transparency was maintained. The survey, conducted via Microsoft Forms, commenced with a compulsory consent section. Participants were provided with a simplified yet thorough version of the participant information statement, after which they were required to select "I consent" to continue. The survey instrument did not collect any personally identifiable information such as names, institutional affiliations, or IP addresses, thereby ensuring participant anonymity by design. Participants were guaranteed the following rights: The right to withdraw from the interview at any moment or to request the deletion of data (before anonymisation), the right to skip any questions they preferred not to answer, the right to obtain information regarding the study and their involvement in it and the assurance that their responses would not be utilized for any non-academic purposes.

These procedures are by the ethical principles of autonomy, respect, and non-maleficence as outlined by the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018) and the Research Ethics Framework of the University of the West of Scotland. The Ethical Committee of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) received the research proposal, which included methodological plans, risks, and objectives. A comprehensive examination was part of the approval procedure to ensure the study met ethical standards. This included ensuring the data was managed correctly, further securing identities, and anonymizing the participating universities and educators. The approval was received in the form of an ethical approval document, which the Ethical Chair Committee approved (See Appendix I).

Furthermore, all data collected during the study were managed following ethical and legal standards set out by the UK Data Protection Act (2018), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the University of the West of Scotland's research ethics and data governance protocols. The data management process covered the full lifecycle from collection to long-term

retention and secure disposal to ensure data integrity and protect participant anonymity. The interview recordings were conducted using Zoom and saved directly onto a password-protected external hard drive that remained offline throughout the research process. Transcription was carried out manually, and during this stage, all identifying information was removed. This included participants' names, professional titles, departments, and institutional affiliations. To protect institutional identities, universities were assigned coded labels (e.g., UN1, UN2) and used consistently throughout the analysis and reporting stages. Similarly, individual educators were anonymised using identifiers such as EN01, EN02, etc., to ensure confidentiality while allowing for analytical clarity in the presentation of findings.

Survey responses were collected using Microsoft Forms, which was configured to avoid collecting IP addresses or other metadata. The data were downloaded and stored on the same external drive and later organised into separate folders for transcripts, consent forms, and survey datasets. Each folder was individually encrypted using software-based encryption tools to restrict unauthorised access. Working files were kept on a password-protected personal laptop, used exclusively by the researcher during the project, with no use of cloud storage or shared network systems. Backup files were maintained on the external drive and physically stored in a locked location accessible only to the researcher.

Data from this study will be retained for a minimum of five years in line with the University of the West of Scotland's retention policy. After this period, all files will be permanently deleted using secure data destruction software. Participants were informed of these storage and protection measures during the consent process. They were also advised of their right to withdraw participation before data anonymisation, and of the limitations to withdrawal once data had been de-identified and dissociated from personal records. By implementing these measures, the study ensured compliance with legal obligations, institutional policy, and ethical standards, while upholding participant trust and protecting professional and institutional confidentiality.

3.7 Qualitative and Quantitative Research

One of the most important factors for many researchers is whether they would rather use a qualitative or quantitative technique. In the realm of business and management studies, the distinctions between qualitative and quantitative are frequently utilised to differentiate among diverse data collection methods and analytical approaches, as highlighted by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019). Quantitative research focuses on numerical data and depends on

extensive sample sizes for testing theories. In contrast, qualitative research is non-numerical and focuses on using words and meanings to develop theories, often with smaller sample sizes.

3.7.1 Qualitative Data Collection

Data collection is an essential component of any research process, as it lays the groundwork for addressing research issues and is crucial. Research questions lose their relevance when there is a lack of sufficient data. According to Saunders and Townsend (2016), it is vital to clearly describe the study methods, mainly when conducting qualitative interviews. This is especially important to justify the goal of the research and ensure that it is valid. Besides qualitative research, this approach encompasses quantitative research and mixed-method studies (AULRE, 2023).

3.7.1.1 Description of the Interview Process

Qualitative data were collected through virtual interviews conducted via Zoom to gather in-depth insights into the context of EE in Nigeria. This method was chosen to ensure flexibility and convenience for both the interviewer and the participants, particularly considering potential geographical and time constraints and the ongoing impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has accelerated the adoption of virtual communication tools in academic research (Dodds & Hess, 2020). The interview process involved nine educators from various universities across Nigeria. Each interview lasted between 40 to 50 minutes, providing sufficient time to explore the educators' perspectives in detail. During the interviews, participants were asked open-ended questions, allowing them to respond using their own words. This approach facilitated rich, detailed responses and enabled the participants to express their views and experiences comprehensively, consistent with the practices recommended for qualitative research by Creswell & Poth (2018). Prompts and probes were utilized throughout the interviews, following the recommendations of Braun and Clarke (2013). These techniques helped to delve deeper into the participants' initial responses, uncovering additional layers of meaning and ensuring that all relevant aspects of the topics were explored thoroughly. Probing questions is particularly useful in qualitative research as they help to clarify and expand on responses, thereby enriching the data (Patton, 2015).

A key consideration in qualitative research is the concept of data saturation. According to Saunders and Townsend (2016), data saturation occurs when no new information or themes are observed in the data. The definition of data saturation in this study was the moment at which

enough information had been obtained to duplicate the study or the point at which new information could no longer be gathered to offer new insights. Reaching data saturation is crucial as it indicates that the data collection process adequately captures the breadth of perspectives necessary for a comprehensive analysis. To ensure the validity and reliability of qualitative research findings, Guest, Bunce, and Johnson (2006) stress the importance of data saturation. To ensure accuracy and reliability, each interview was audio-recorded with the consent of the participants. These recordings were transcribed verbatim, transforming the spoken content into written text. Transcription is a critical step in qualitative research as it prepares the data for detailed analysis (Lofland et al., 2006). The transcripts were examined to ensure that they appropriately represented the participants' comments, maintaining the authenticity and richness of the original data. Member checking, a process where participants review and validate the transcriptions, was employed to enhance the credibility of the data (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

3.7.1.2 Profile of Participants

The table below shows the specifics of the nine (9) entrepreneurship educators who were interviewed.

Table 9: Profile of Respondents

No.	University	Job title	No. of Years as an Entrepreneurship Educator	Region
EEN01	UN1	Senior Lecturer and Director of Entrepreneurship	10	South-west
EEN02	UN2	Senior Lecturer in Entrepreneurship	12	South-East
EEN03	UN1	Lecturer in Entrepreneurship	7	South- West
EEN04	UN4	Lecturer in Entrepreneurship	10	South-south
EEN05	UN3	Director for Entrepreneurship and Leadership Development Studies	10	South- West
EEN06	UN2	Lecturer in Business Management	8	South- East
EEN07	UN3	Senior Lecturer in Business and Entrepreneurship	9	South- West
EEN08	UN2	Lecturer in Entrepreneurship	7	South- East
EEN09	UN4	Senior Lecturer in Business Administration	11	South- South

Source: Researcher, 2024

Nine entrepreneurial educators from four different universities were interviewed. These interviews were held between August and October 2023. The participants were mostly instructors from entrepreneurial or business schools, having at least five years of experience in academia. Because the research is issue-based rather than region-based, the presence of South-West educators among the interviewees has no bearing on the qualitative findings.

3.7.2 Online Interviews

According to Rubin & Rubin's (1995) work on qualitative interviews, an interview is a deliberate conversation between two individuals aimed at eliciting their experiences and viewpoints, as well as capturing their language and concepts related to the subject of study. Interviews offer a more profound insight into social phenomena compared to quantitative methods like surveys. In recent years, the way researchers interact and communicate are

changing (Kinsley, 2014; Parker, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has notably accelerated the trend (Parker, 2021). By the end of March 2020, during the peak of the pandemic, more than 100 countries worldwide had implemented either complete or partial lockdowns, impacting billions of individuals (BBC News, 2020). In response, academics and professionals had to swiftly adapt to video technologies like Zoom and MS Teams to carry out their tasks.

Traditionalists hold a preference for conducting research interviews in person, as stated by Parker (2014), due to three primary factors. Firstly, it enables researchers to establish and sustain a connection with interviewees (Fontana and Frey, 1998). Secondly, visual cues facilitate better communication (Fielding and Thomas, 2008). Lastly, the researcher can visually evaluate the participant's work surroundings (D'Urso and Rains, 2008), which permits the gathering of contextual information (Farooq and De Villiers, 2017).

Prior to COVID-19 and the rise of Zoom, some qualitative researchers discussed the challenges of online video conferencing platforms. For example, Deakin and Wakefield (2014) compared Skype and in-person interviews and the research findings indicated that Skype contributed to the development of rapport and allowed for greater flexibility, resulting in cost savings. In similar research, Jenner and Myers (2019) compared Skype and in-person interviews, the findings from both studies indicated that the data collected through these methods were equally rich in terms of participants sharing experiences and making exceptional disclosures. The authors of the studies argued that the participants' choice of private settings, whether it be via Skype or in-person, played a crucial role in obtaining highly personal stories and perspectives (Jenner & Myers, 2019). In another study involving nurses, it was found that many participants preferred using Zoom for interviews over in-person and telephone interviews, as well as other video conferencing platforms (Archibald, Ambagtsheer, Casey & Lawless, 2019). The participants highlighted the advantages of using Zoom, such as the ease of establishing rapport, convenience, and the user-friendly interface. However, they also mentioned challenges related to technology glitches and user connectivity when using Zoom (Archibald et al., 2019).

Table 10: The Strengths and Weaknesses of Online Interview

Strengths	Weakness
Flexibility	Ethical issues with online research (Madge, 2007)
Convenience	Technical Issues (Dennis et. Al, 2008)
Anonymity	Populations less likely to have online access (e.g., rural residents)
Cost-effective	Cannot verify the correct respondent

Source: Developed by researcher

Online interviews, which took place between August and October 2023, were employed to gather qualitative data for this study. In-person interviews were not possible in Nigeria because of logistics problems like high travel costs and difficulty recruiting participants. Email invitations were sent to participants, who were provided with a sheet of information describing the study's objective and procedures. This method was flexible as interviews were set up on a schedule that worked for the participants, and data was collected effectively despite the geographical limitations. In all cases, the researcher employed the use of virtual interviews. This was done via Zoom and recorded. At the beginning of the interviews, the participants were introduced to the subject area and the spectrum of entrepreneurial activities, and then the interviewer proceeded. Ten interviews were undertaken, which ranged from 40 minutes to 50 minutes, with an average of 40 minutes in duration. All interviews were recorded, which allowed for backing up and transcribing the data collected. The Appendix contains a sample transcription of an interview with an educator (see Appendix V).

There are three types of interviews: semi-structured, unstructured, and structured. Structured interviews generally employ questionnaires that consist of a fixed and uniform set of questions, commonly known as 'interview-administered questionnaires,' as Saunders et al. (2019) described. While this method ensures specific answers to research questions, respondents need more flexibility to share their opinions, limiting the breadth and depth of data obtained during the interview. In contrast, a semi-structured interview is non-standardized, contains a list of subjects and enquiries to be addressed by the researcher. Although it lacks the structured framework mentioned earlier, it provides respondents with more liberty to express their views, which provides the researcher with more information. Unstructured interviews are very informal and provide detailed information, but they could be misunderstood and divert from the main topic of the study.

3.7.3 Adoption of Semi-Structured Interviews

This study adopts the use of semi structured interviews due to their adaptability and ability to elicit in-depth responses. This approach offers participants the ability to express in-depth insights by allowing a blend of open-ended conversation and planning questions. This method promotes greater freewill than fully organized interviews, which may result in richer data (Adams, 2015). When examining complicated phenomena, like attitudes toward entrepreneurship education, this approach works very well (Alshenqeeti, 2014). Open-ended questions are important as they provide participants with the freedom to respond at their own pace and without any external pressure. This approach allows individuals to share their thoughts and experiences in as much detail as they feel comfortable with. Establishing a calm and supportive environment through open-ended questioning during interviews facilitates the gathering of comprehensive and pertinent data, frequently regarded as a significant outcome of the exploratory process.

The study primarily investigates how EE impacts the mindset and intentions of students pursuing entrepreneurship. Consequently, survey questions were meticulously crafted to address the needs of entrepreneurial educators within Nigerian HEIs. In addition to allowing participants to provide detailed responses through the semi-structured interview format, this technique is widely regarded as the most employed method for gathering comprehensive and valuable data. Lastly, the semi-structured interview is an effective method of gathering information from participants, this is because the process is free from any form of force, restrictions, or duress.

3.7.4 Sample Size and Techniques

The initial phase of the study engaged entrepreneurship educators in Nigerian universities. The criteria for choosing were that the educators should have at least five years of lecturing experience, as this time frame enables the acquisition of essential knowledge and teaching expertise. Studies indicate that five years is typically considered adequate for educators to master their discipline (Benner, 2001; Charmaz, 2014). This level of experience ensures that participants comprehensively understand entrepreneurship education within higher education contexts, which is essential for offering valuable insights into the research. The researcher used a purposive sampling technique to select participants who fulfil specific criteria relevant to the research objective. This method is especially beneficial in qualitative research, particularly when examining individuals with specialized knowledge in a specific domain (Patton, 2002). The purposive sampling process guarantees that the sample comprises individuals capable of

offering comprehensive and detailed information. Snowball sampling was a supplementary technique, allowing the researcher to recruit additional participants through referrals from identified educators. This method is incredibly efficient when aimed at a specific demographic, such as experienced entrepreneurship educators, as it facilitates access to networks that may be challenging to connect with otherwise (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

The researcher identified participants by cross-referencing official university documents, ensuring the validation of their qualifications and experience. The process confirmed that the chosen educators fulfilled the eligibility criteria and were appropriate for inclusion in the study. Nine educators were selected for the study, as data saturation occurred, aligning with the qualitative research principle that advocates for smaller sample sizes to attain data saturation (Guest et al., 2006).

3.7.5 Interview Protocol

According to Gillham (2005), an interview protocol serves as a guide for the interviewer to guarantee that every interview follows a consistent format. An interview protocol was developed for interviews to ensure a systematic and organized approach to collecting data. To ensure consistency, an interview schedule was developed using the five phases of semi-structured interviewing by Gillham (2005).

Table 11: Five Phases of Semi-Structured Interviewing

Preparation Phase	In this phase, the researcher clarifies the time and place of the interview and ensures that the equipment is functioning correctly and that the interview location is appropriate.
Initial contact Phase	This phase involves the introductions (if necessary) and making sure that the interviewee is happy with the location and setting of the interview
Orientation Phase	In this phase the researcher explains the purpose of the interview and guides the interviewee to how they would like them to engage, explaining how the questions will be asked
Substantive Phase	This phase is the key part of the interview where the main questions will be asked
Closure Phase	This is the final phase of the interview where closing questions can be asked. Interviewees can also be offered a copy of the interview transcript once they have been transcribed.

Source: Gillham (2005) and Creswell & Creswell (2018)

Research objective one required the researcher to discover the nature of the individual motives and main contextual factors that affect academic engagement in entrepreneurial activities. The questions, therefore, needed to gauge what kind of individual and contextual factors affect academic intentions to participate in commercialization and engagement activities. Questions based on the institutional, organizational, and local context and individual motives were identified and developed and were assessed for suitability (see Appendix III). As the interviews were semi-structured, this also allowed for additional questions to be asked as the interview developed, and additional interesting themes emerged. Semi-structured interviews require researchers to word questions carefully (to not appear too knowledgeable about each topic) and allow each respondent to provide their views (Yin, 2003).

3.7.5.1 Brief Overview of the Interview Question

Sections of the interview questions were designed to provide a thorough understanding of the status of EE in Nigeria. The first category of questions focused on gathering information on educators' backgrounds, career paths, experience teaching entrepreneurship, and modules they currently teach. In the next set of questions, educators were asked to define EE and its essential components and explain how they think it affects students' intentions to become entrepreneurs. This aimed to reveal EE's theoretical and practical foundations.

The following questions focused on the entrepreneurship courses that were given and the pedagogical approaches that were used while also examining the educational setup and teaching methods. Regarding developing curriculum and collaboration among stakeholders, the educators were additionally asked to get an improved awareness of the practical use of EE. The discussion on entrepreneurial skills followed as Educators were asked to outline their teaching methods to foster student engagement and skill development. They were also asked to consider which skills are crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs in Nigeria. This gave the researcher insight into the different teaching methods used, the design of the entrepreneurship curriculum, and those involved in the process.

Another area the interview focused on was the support and resources offered by universities to students. Educators were asked to evaluate the support systems available to students and what additional resources could be beneficial. The discussion also covered the difficulties and obstacles that come with teaching entrepreneurship, such as the lack of resources, and it looked for suggestions for enhancement in different areas, such as government and university support. Finally, the interview ended with questions focused on the broad importance of entrepreneurship education. Participants were asked to assess the effectiveness of the programmes, provide their opinions on policies, and discuss the overall effectiveness of these programmes. This provided educators with the opportunity to discuss the applicability and overall impact of EE in Nigeria.

3.7.6 Data Analysis (Qualitative Data)

The interviews were carried out through the use using Zoom software, and the audio recordings were transcribed, reviewed, and corrected. This was done to address any mistakes that are typically connected with automated transcription systems (Halcomb & Davidson, 2006). The revised transcripts were then analyzed using the NVivo 12 software. The 'audio transcription style' was applied to capture the precise words that the participants had used and maintain the

integrity of their responses (Bailey, 2008). A more precise and in-depth study of the data was made possible by using this approach.

Transcription styles were divided into two categories by Braun & Clarke (2013): "audio transcription style" and "orthographic or verbatim style." The first captures the spoken words exactly as they are articulated, while the latter captures both the content and how it was expressed. This research employs the audio transcription style, as it enables a more comprehensive study of the participants' perspectives and attitudes throughout the interviews because it records the content of the responses and how they were expressed. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the qualitative data. This method was chosen due to its flexibility and methodical approach to finding, evaluating, and reporting patterns in data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The analysis was facilitated by NVivo software, which allowed for efficient management and coding of the large volume of qualitative data. The process began with transcription, where the audio-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy and reliability. This initial step was crucial in preparing the data for detailed examination.

Table 12: Braun & Clarke's six-phase framework for doing a thematic analysis

Phase	Description of the process used to code data
1. Data Familiarization	The researcher transcribed all interviews, read each transcript thoroughly, and revisited the data multiple times while noting initial observations
2. Initial code generation	Codes were created by identifying aspects of the data and assigning descriptive labels to capture related content across the dataset.
3. Generating Initial Themes	After coding, the researcher reviewed and combined relevant codes to develop broader themes.
4. Thematic Review	The researcher checked all themes, ensuring their alignment with the coded extracts (Level 1) and the entire dataset (Level 2), and created a thematic map for further analysis.
5. Define Themes	Themes were defined and refined based on analysis, and data within each theme were examined comprehensively.
6. Write up	The final report was written, providing sufficient evidence for each theme. Data extracts were included to demonstrate the significance of each identified theme.

Source: Braun and Clarke (2006, p.87).

Figure 5: Study Phases and Outcomes

Source: Developed by researcher

The creation of the questionnaire design is the next stage of the study. Thematic and content analysis methods analyse content and identify themes in data to construct the questionnaire.

3.7.6.1 Use of NVivo Software: Advantages and Limitations

The qualitative analysis of the interview transcripts of educators was facilitated by NVivo 12 software, which provides a systematic and effective way to organize and code the data. A key benefit of NVivo is its methodological adaptability; the software does not enforce a specific research design, allowing it to be appropriate for various qualitative methods, such as grounded theory and thematic analysis (Bazeley & Jackson, 2013). The software's node-based approach provided a practical and user-friendly way to create, adjust, and oversee codes. This framework facilitated the effective organization of new themes while ensuring clear and consistent coding throughout the process.

One significant advantage of NVivo, as noted in this study, was its ability to enhance the efficiency of coding and data management, especially during the later stages of thematic analysis. The straightforward process of reorganizing codes, consolidating sub-nodes, and adjusting hierarchical categories enabled the thematic framework to evolve as more profound patterns emerged. Silver and Lewins (2014) similarly emphasized the role of NVivo in

promoting analytical rigor through effective data management. Zamawe (2015), discussing a resource-limited environment, points out that NVivo not only speeds up the coding process but also reduces human error, particularly when dealing with extensive textual data. This benefit was also evident in this study, although it was based on a smaller dataset.

Furthermore, NVivo improved the transparency of the analysis. The automatic recording of coding actions and the centralized storage of memos and annotations facilitated a well-documented analytical process. This reinforces the point made by Paulus and Lester (2016), who highlight that one of NVivo's key contributions is its ability to make the 'invisible labour' of qualitative analysis more accessible to others. This feature proved especially useful during the writing phase, as revisiting prior coding decisions was crucial for enhancing thematic interpretations and backing claims with evidence.

However, in alignment with the existing body of literature, the research also uncovered various challenges and limitations associated with the use of NVivo. Although the software is frequently commended for its methodological neutrality (Hutchison, Johnston, & Breckon, 2010), its design can subtly affect the analytical process. For instance, a rigid node structure may promote premature categorization, potentially steering researchers away from the raw, intricate complexity of the data. Bazeley (2007) observes that while the tool is indeed powerful, it necessitates critical engagement to prevent reliance on overly mechanical or superficial coding. In this research, special attention was devoted to ensuring that interpretive depth was not compromised for the sake of procedural tidiness, a balance that, as Braun and Clarke (2013) contend, is essential for preserving the integrity of thematic analysis.

Another constraint associated with the use of NVivo, as noted in this study, is its considerable learning curve, especially for researchers who possess limited prior experience in computer-assisted qualitative data analysis. While the interface is relatively user-friendly in comparison to earlier Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS) tools, numerous features are not intuitive for novice users. This observation is consistent with the findings of Hutchison, Johnston, and Breckon (2010), who noted that NVivo's advanced functionality can be daunting initially, particularly when training resources are scarce or when researchers face time limitations. In a similar vein, Johnston (2006) emphasizes that although NVivo can significantly improve the quality of analysis, many researchers fail to recognize the substantial initial time commitment necessary to master the software, which may negate its efficiency advantages in the short run. This challenge is exacerbated by the reality that most training

resources presume a foundational level of digital literacy and an understanding of qualitative research frameworks. As Paulus and Lester (2016) contend, the software itself does not impart analytical skills; it simply enables them. Consequently, researchers must either already have or develop the theoretical knowledge and technical abilities necessary to utilize NVivo effectively. In this research, although initial training sessions were adequate for establishing basic competence, more complex analytical functions such as advanced query construction or classification matrix coding necessitated repeated trial-and-error learning, which impeded early progress and increased the likelihood of technical errors.

In educational environments where formal training is scarce or where software licenses are shared among departments, these obstacles can greatly impact both the quality and consistency of qualitative analysis. Zamawe (2015) further observes that researchers in low-resource settings frequently encounter difficulties with NVivo due to insufficient institutional support, limited access to complete licenses, or a lack of peer expertise. Therefore, while NVivo provides robust tools, its steep learning curve poses a significant barrier that can obstruct its adoption and effective use, particularly among early-career researchers or in contexts lacking adequate support systems.

Nevertheless, the application of NVivo in this study improved the credibility, organization, and analytical precision of the qualitative aspect. Although it has its limitations, the software offered a supportive framework that facilitated both effective data management and critical, context-aware interpretation. These results align with those of Welsh (2002), who asserts that NVivo does not substitute the researcher's judgment but rather augments assuming it is utilized reflexively and with an understanding of its impact on the analytical process.

3.7.7 Validity and Reliability in Qualitative Research

A study's quality is frequently assessed using construct validity, internal validity, external validity, and reliability. Construct validity ensures that the research accurately measures the concepts it aims to study by using appropriate operational definitions. Internal validity seeks to establish a cause-and-effect relationship, confirming that specific conditions lead to outcomes. The concept of external validity relates to the scope of a study's applicability, extending beyond the parameters of the original investigation. In contrast, reliability involves demonstrating that the study's procedures, such as data collection methods, can be consistently replicated to yield the same results (Yin, 2009).

To ensure credibility and consistency within qualitative inquiry, a variety of viewpoints, terminology, and techniques have been established. These encompass standard concepts like objectivity, reliability, external validity, and internal validity (LeCompte & Goetz, 1982). Qualitative researchers have built upon these fundamental standards by stressing the significance of confirmability, credibility, transferability, and dependability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). More modern methods have expanded on these ideas by adding standards including congruence, sensitivity, explicitness, vividness, authenticity, credibility, thoroughness, and congruence (Whittemore, Chase & Mandle, 2001, as quoted in Creswell, 2012). Current research emphasizes the complexity and quality of qualitative research while building upon established frameworks. For instance, Morse et al. (2016) stress the significance of sufficient sampling, methodological consistency, and the dynamic interaction between data collection and analysis. They maintain that strictly adhering to these guidelines is necessary to attain validity and reliability in qualitative research. In a similar vein, Noble and Smith (2015) emphasize the significance of reflexivity and transparency, urging researchers to explicitly record their decision-making procedures and acknowledge their prejudices.

According to Creswell and Poth (2018), maintaining credibility entails making sure that results are true and reliable through methods like member verification, prolonged engagement, and triangulation. Content validity pertains to the extent to which a measurement accurately represents the content it is designed to evaluate. Essentially, it means that the items in a test or tool should accurately reflect the intended measurement. The qualitative phase of this study will possess content validity when the interview questions are directly aligned with the research objectives. McDaniel and Gates (1996) detail a series of steps to guarantee content validity in empirical studies. These encompass precisely defining the essential concepts and constructs, carefully reviewing the existing literature, performing initial interviews with the intended demographic, and soliciting expert feedback on the interview questions and variables to confirm their relevance and having the interview questions reviewed by subject matter experts.

Additionally, the process of achieving content validity can be strengthened by incorporating feedback from pilot testing the interview questions with a small, representative sample of the target population. This allows for adjustments based on real-world responses, ensuring that the questions are both comprehensible and relevant to participants (DeVellis, 2016). Furthermore, involving multiple researchers in the development and review of the interview questions can help to minimize bias and ensure a more comprehensive coverage of the research domain (Polit

& Beck, 2012). By following these rigorous procedures, the study can ensure that the qualitative data collected will be robust and accurately reflect the intended research objectives.

To guarantee the content validity of the qualitative phase of this study, the criteria established by McDaniel and Gates (1996) were applied. The questions for the research and interviews were carefully designed to align with the study's objectives and goals, drawing on guidance from the previous research. Additionally, the interview questions and protocol underwent a thorough review by the researcher and academic experts from the UWS, UNIBEN, and ABUAD. After this review, a pilot study was undertaken to evaluate the understanding and suitability of the interview questions.

To ensure rigor and robustness in the data analysis process, distinct steps will be followed. The first step involves familiarizing oneself with the data by carefully listening to the recorded interviews. This is followed by transcription, a fundamental step in almost all qualitative research studies (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The transcription will be verbatim to eliminate any potential researcher bias, ensuring that all relevant data is accurately captured. Following transcription, the data underwent careful coding, an essential process that facilitates the organic emergence of themes based on the evidence (Maher et al., 2018). This process adhered to established best practices in qualitative inquiry to guarantee the reliability and validity of the results (Gibbs, 2007; Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014).

3.8 Quantitative Data Collection

Data collected quantitatively can be classed, measured, or ranked statistically (Muijs, 2020). According to Creswell & Creswell (2018), it is frequently used to spot trends or linkages and draw conclusions about a wider population. Tests, questionnaires, and surveys are standard techniques. The second data collection tool in this study is a questionnaire, which is used to gather quantifiable answers to the research questions so they may be statistically examined.

3.8.1 Questionnaire

The online survey was conducted among students at different educational levels in Nigerian universities, comprising undergraduates, postgraduates, and recent graduates. Including students from various academic levels and disciplines offered a comprehensive view of the influence of these EEPs on students' entrepreneurial objectives. Final-year and postgraduate students with greater exposure to EEPs provided insights into their experiences, while recent graduates reflected on the practical application of entrepreneurial skills after completing their studies.

3.8.2 Questionnaire Development

In this study, a cross-sectional survey design is employed to gather data at a single point in time, offering a snapshot of the population (Babbie, 1990). This method is effective for exploring relationships between variables and trends. Cross-sectional surveys are widely used in entrepreneurship research to study attitudes and intentions, as seen in studies by Peterman and Kennedy (2003), who examined the impact of EE and personality traits on EI. This design fits the thesis objectives well. Hatak, Harms, and Fink (2015) investigated the influence of age and job identity on entrepreneurial ambitions using a cross-sectional survey. Their research revealed notable disparities in entrepreneurial goals between older and younger individuals, with job identification acting as a crucial mediator. Kautonen, Gelderen, and Fink (2015) investigated the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) under various situations. Their research validated the TPB's efficacy in predicting EI, while also uncovering discrepancies in the theory's predictive ability based on contextual factors, offering deeper insights into entrepreneurial behaviour. Similarly, Fayolle and Gailly (2015) used cross-sectional survey data to track changes in entrepreneurial mentality over time after EE. Linan and Chan (2009) designed and validated cross-cultural entrepreneurial intention tools to improve accuracy. These studies demonstrated the ability of survey design to discern entrepreneurial ambitions, especially when tracking attitudes or behaviours and validating instruments in different populations.

To achieve the aim of this study, a questionnaire was developed to measure the students' responses regarding the constructs from the conceptual framework. As previously stated, to thoroughly investigate the impact of educational components on students' entrepreneurial intents within the framework of EEPs in Nigerian institutions, this study utilised mixed methods. The research design integrates qualitative and quantitative methodologies to deliver a nuanced insight of the interplay between perceived university support, psychological factors outlined in the TBP, and students' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

The study's aims included formulating hypotheses to investigate the correlations statistically between students' entrepreneurial intentions, psychological elements described in the Theory of Planned Behaviour, perceived university support and Teaching methods. These hypotheses were derived from existing literature and were designed to provide empirical insights into how education components influence students' intentions. The hypotheses developed are:

- Hypothesis 1: Students who perceive higher university support and engaging teaching methods are likely to have positive attitudes and intentions toward entrepreneurship education.
- Hypothesis 2: Increased university support and effective teaching methods may strengthen students' subjective norms, fostering social acceptance of entrepreneurship.
- Hypothesis 3: Greater university support and interactive teaching methods could enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours.
- Hypothesis 4: Stronger university support and engaging teaching methods may lead to more positive behavioural intentions towards entrepreneurial activities.
- Hypothesis 5: Interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions regarding entrepreneurship.

3.8.2.1 Design and Measurement of Variables

Using an adapted version of the TPB questionnaire, a quantitative method was used in the study's second stage (Liñán & Chen, 2009; Liñán et al., 2013). The TPB was chosen due to its wide validation in entrepreneurship research across various cultural contexts (Nabi & Liñán, 2011). Though initially tested in Spain and Taiwan, it has been applied in both developed and developing nations. The questionnaire's structure was informed by prior studies, with Section Two derived from Mwasalwiba (2010) and data collected from Nigerian educators in the first stage.

The questionnaire has four sections (See Appendix IV); Section one addressed the **demographic information** of participants, they were asked to provide their demographic and other data which including their age, gender, programme, level of study, entrepreneurial background, and the number of EEPs they have undertaken. The next section, Section Two, focused on Educational Support, which includes Perceived university Support, Teaching methods, and pedagogy. The first part of this section explores the various **Teaching methods and Pedagogical Approaches** employed in Entrepreneurship Education classrooms, drawing from established literature and insights gathered from educators in Nigerian universities through the interviews in the first stage of data collection. The methods identified align with seminal works by Garavan and O'Cinneide (1994), Fiet (2000), Bennett (2006), and Mwasalwiba (2010), providing a comprehensive overview of pedagogical approaches in the field.

The statements used in assessing entrepreneurship teaching and learning methods employ a 7-point Likert scale which is the most frequently used variation of the summated rating scale (Cooper & Schindler, 2003), ranging from 1 to 7, where 1 signifies 'not used at all' and 7 indicates 'mostly used.' This scale measures how much educators use different teaching strategies in their entrepreneurship classes. These methods include traditional lecturing, class participation, case studies, individual and group assignments, oral presentations, role play, business plan preparation, student presentations of entrepreneurial projects, guest lectures by entrepreneurs, visits to companies, and industrial training experiences. The second part is the **perceived university Support** as the independent variable. Support from the university in entrepreneurial endeavours. This variable encompasses the assistance, resources, encouragement, and opportunities provided by the university to students engaging in entrepreneurial activities. The level of support influences students' entrepreneurial intentions and outcomes. Liñán and Chen (2009) suggest that perceived university support positively influences students' entrepreneurial intentions. The findings underscore the importance of considering students' perceptions of university support when investigating the effectiveness of EEPs.

In the third section, the entrepreneurial intention questionnaire developed by Liñán and Chen (2006, 2009; 2013) was used to assess attitudes towards entrepreneurship. According to Ajzen (1991; 2005), attitude towards entrepreneurship is a person's positive or negative view on becoming an entrepreneur. According to the theory, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control influence people's behavioural intentions, which determine their behaviour. The questionnaire used seven-point Likert scale questions. Five Likert scale-type statements were utilised for personal attitudes, five for perceived behavioural control, three for subjective norm, and six for entrepreneurial intention.

Lastly, Section Four consists of open-ended questions for the survey. Open-ended questions allow participants to express their thoughts, experiences, and perspectives in their own words, providing rich and detailed data. According to Creswell and Poth (2017), open-ended questions enable participants to offer nuanced responses that capture their unique viewpoints and experiences, contributing to a deeper insight of the context of research. The researcher employed the use of open-ended questions at the end of the survey, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of students' experiences, perceptions, and recommendations, leading to deeper insights and more robust findings.

3.8.2.2 Pilot Survey Exercise

Piloting involves testing research instruments, such as surveys or interview guides, with a small group from the target population. It is designed to identify issues with the instrument's clarity, length, and question format and to assess the feasibility of the study's methodology, thereby enhancing the credibility and consistency of the study (Malmqvist et al., 2019). Before the primary study is performed, there are expectations of identifying any issues that may arise from the process of data collection, such as questioning clarification, technological issues, or arising logistical issues, and making necessary adjustments where necessary (Bryman, 2016). According to Gudmundsdottir & Brock-Utne (2010), one goal of performing a pilot study is to improve the quality of the research, which may be accomplished in most elements of the research process.

Piloting for this study was done to make sure the instruments used to collect data are valid and dependable for the research that is planned. Through the pilot, the researcher was able to notice how respondents engaged with the questions, spot any items that might be confusing, and assess the questionnaire's overall timing and flow by evaluating the instruments in a more intimate, controlled environment. The stage was essential because it permitted the questions to be more focused, guaranteed that the directions were understandable, and verified that the available response possibilities were suitable. In this study, the pilot exercise was carried out on five students in Nigeria and two students in the United Kingdom. This was to make sure the questions addressed the study's goals, and the research aim clearly and concisely. In addition, it was to ensure the questions were understood by participants and did not have ambiguity or confusion.

3.8.3 Sample Criteria and Sample Size

The second stage of the study had 306 participants, including Nigerian university students and graduates. The geographical coverage included Nigeria's South-South, South-East, and South-West areas to represent unique educational environments. Participants must have taken an EE course throughout their academic degrees to be eligible to take part. This required graduates to consider how EE affected their academic experience and post-graduation entrepreneurial endeavours. These regions are critical educational hubs in Nigeria, and they have various economic and social dynamics, allowing the researcher to investigate better how EE affects students in different circumstances. This sample size and regional focus allow the research to determine how well entrepreneurship education programmes work across Nigeria. The study selects students and graduates who have directly participated in EE to collect data on real

experiences and perceptions, contributing to the issue of entrepreneurship development in emerging economies like Nigeria. This method helps determine entrepreneurship education's immediate and long-term benefits on entrepreneurial behaviours across education and career stages.

3.8.4 Quantitative Data Analysis

The quantitative responses were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0.0.0., this gave an in-depth understanding of the relationships among significant variables, including entrepreneurial intentions, university support, and teaching methods. Descriptive statistics initially summarise the sample's characteristics, including the mean, standard deviation, frequency distributions, and percentages. This stage facilitated the identification of patterns and trends within the dataset, establishing an understanding for future analysis. Before descriptive analysis was carried out, the researcher ensured that the data collected was screened. Data screening is a crucial step in quantitative research, ensuring the accuracy, consistency, and appropriateness of data before proceeding to statistical analysis (Pallant, 2020). The primary objective of data screening is to ready the dataset to align with the assumptions of the statistical methods utilised, including regression analysis, factor analysis, or ANOVA.

Second, to confirm that the data was appropriate for analysis, checks for reliability and normality were performed. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, ensuring internal consistency across survey items, which is crucial in determining the reliability of the instruments (Pallant, 2020). Cronbach's alpha values above 0.70 indicated that the data was sufficiently reliable for further statistical analysis (Field, 2013). For this study, the reliability check was conducted and confirmed before performing statistical tests, as detailed in Chapter 5 of the findings. The reliability checks strengthened the foundation for the correlation and regression analyses that followed, providing a more precise comprehension of the interactions between the factors linked to entrepreneurial intentions.

Additionally, correlation analysis has been employed to investigate the relationships between essential variables, particularly how teaching methods and support provided by universities affect students' desire to start their own businesses. The study measures the direction and degree of the correlations between these variables using Pearson's correlation coefficient. (Pallant, 2020). Pearson's correlation is valuable since it quantifies the extent to which two variables are interrelated, demonstrating if an increase in university support and effective teaching methods is associated with an increase in entrepreneurial intentions. This methodology enabled the

investigation of whether enhanced institutional support and new pedagogical techniques significantly affected students' motivation to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours. A correlation approaching +1 or -1 indicates a robust positive or negative connection, respectively, between the variables. The analysis offered profound insights into the extent of these relationships, emphasizing prospective areas for improvements in education policy and pedagogical strategies to enhance entrepreneurial ambition among students.

Lastly, this study employed regression analysis to examine how well university assistance and instructional approaches predicted entrepreneurial intention. Multiple regression models helped test hypotheses and understand how each element affected entrepreneurship outcomes. Entrepreneurship research relies on this strategy to identify significant factors of entrepreneurial behaviour and intention (Karimi et al., 2016; Sánchez, 2013). The multiple regression models used in this study allow for independent variable interactions, providing a more nuanced understanding of their influence on entrepreneurial position. Regression revealed the effect of teaching methods and university support on students' entrepreneurial attitudes and behaviours. This comprehensive approach supports the study's goal of understanding how educational environments and support systems foster entrepreneurial mindsets. Chapter 5 will cover how regression models controlled confounding variables to guarantee results accuracy. Souitaris et al. (2007) and Karimi et al. (2016) showed how regression analysis can explore complex relationships between educational activities and entrepreneurial outcomes, providing a solid framework for entrepreneurship education research.

3.7 Conclusion

The research methodology used in this study are covered in this chapter, which also explores the benefits of a mixed methods design for examining the impact of EE on students' EI. These methodologies include both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative data from educators offered depth and background, whilst the quantitative phase, encompassing students and graduates from Nigerian universities, facilitated the examination of essential variables such as university support and pedagogical approaches. The NVivo software for qualitative data analysis and SPSS software enabled thorough analysis, including descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression, ensuring the findings' reliability and validity. This comprehensive methodology presents a robust framework for addressing the research objectives and yields significant insights into the effectiveness of EE in Nigeria.

CHAPTER FOUR

QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from the qualitative phase of the study, based on in-depth interviews conducted with entrepreneurship educators. The analysis focuses on the key themes that emerged from the data and highlights how these themes reflect participants' perspectives on the state and delivery of entrepreneurship education within selected Nigerian universities.

The themes discussed in this chapter were developed through the thematic analysis process outlined in Chapter 3. Each theme is supported by illustrative quotes from participants and examined in conjunction with relevant scholarly literature, thereby providing both empirical grounding and theoretical reflection. The chapter also incorporates responses to open-ended questions from the student survey to contextualise further and triangulate educator insights. Together, these data contribute to a holistic understanding of the factors shaping the implementation and perceived impact of entrepreneurship education.

The chapter is structured around the five key themes identified in the data, which include: (1) conceptualisations of entrepreneurship education, (2) institutional and structural barriers, (3) skill and competency development, (4) effective teaching strategies, and (5) suggested improvements. These themes serve as a foundation for the quantitative phase and inform the development of the survey instrument discussed in Chapter 5.

Before presenting the findings, it is important to establish the context in which the themes were derived. Following the analytical procedures outlined in Chapter 3, the researcher began with a familiarisation process that involved multiple readings of the interview transcripts, close engagement with participants' narratives, and a reflective memo to capture initial impressions. This process helped surface early patterns and nuances in how educators perceived entrepreneurship education in their institutional environments, laying the groundwork for the thematic structure discussed in the subsequent sections.

4.1 Familiarization of Data

The first step in analyzing qualitative data was for the researcher to become acquainted with the information that had been collected, which included the participant demographics. These

profiles were important in understanding their views on entrepreneurship education (EE). The participants, all experienced educators with positions such as lecturers and directors at Nigerian universities, presented a wealth of knowledge with years of experience ranging from 7 to 12 years. This gave the researcher important perspectives in to current state of EE in various parts of Nigeria. Through an examination of the demographic data, the researcher identified trends in the educators' professional backgrounds and positions. This process uncovered key contextual aspects that influenced the analysis, as the educators' experiences and institutional roles shaped their perspectives on the obstacles and opportunities associated with EE. After the interview transcripts were prepared, the researcher took notes and thoroughly review the data multiple times to gain a comprehensive understanding of it. Throughout this familiarisation process, overarching thematic categories or codes were identified, reflecting the recurring themes in the interview responses. The initial nodes, including the description of entrepreneurship education, pedagogical approaches, university support frameworks, difficulties facing entrepreneurship education, and recommendations for enhancing entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, were identified as the foundation for coding within NVivo. The NVivo software enabled the systematic organization and analysis of qualitative data, enabling the researcher to establish and revise codes as they engaged further with the data. The software enabled an organized approach for organizing huge amounts of information, simplifying the identification of recurring themes and grouping responses based on participants' experiences and ideas. This process guaranteed that the research covered a range of perspectives while identifying differences in the delivery of entrepreneurship education across Nigerian universities. This phase established the foundation for in-depth analysis, allowing the researcher to transition from general observations to more focused findings.

4.2 Initial Code Generation

The code book was structured around the key research objectives. Parent codes were created for each objective, including the definition of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) and teaching methods (RO1), challenges in EE learning (RO2), skills and competencies gained by students (RO3), and suggested improvements (RO5). These objectives informed parent codes, with sub-codes detailing specific aspects such as habits cultivation, entrepreneurial knowledge, university support mechanisms, skill development, and suggestions for enhancing EE. This approach allowed for a systematic analysis of educator responses, categorized effectively to address each research question.

Table 13: Initial Code Book

Parent Codes	Description	Sub Codes
PC1 Educators Define EE	Definitions and objectives of EE by educators	SC1 Cultivate habits SC2 Entrepreneurial Knowledge SC3 Mindset redirection SC4 Practical Preparation SC5 Self-reliance Education SC6 Skill Development
PC1b Teaching Methods	The pedagogical strategies used by educators in delivering entrepreneurship education.	SC1 Case studies SC2 Cognitive teaching and feedback Sc3 Experiential Learning SC4 Field trips SC5 Group work SC6 Guest speakers SC7 Workshop SC8 Practical SC9 Roleplaying SC10 Traditional Lectures
PC1c University Support	Institutional Support Mechanisms for EE to support students	SC1 Entrepreneurship Centers SC2 Equipment provisions SC3 Facilitators SC4 Funding SC5 Internet support SC6 Staff consultant
PC2 Challenges	Barriers to effective EE in Nigerian universities	SC1 Allocation of students SC2 Campus business restrictions SC3 Curriculum Constraint SC4 Financial Constraint SC5 Inadequate infrastructure SC6 Limited exposure of educators SC7 Lack of clarifying distinctions

		SC8 Policy barriers SC9 Students engagement SC10 Reliance on Western EEps
PC3 Skills and competencies	Key skills developed through EE	SC1 Communication skills SC2 Decision making Sc3 Idea development SC4 Networking and collaboration SC5 Problem-solving skills SC6 Strategic thinking SC7 Successful business
PC5 Role of EE	Purpose and Outcomes of EE	SC1 Career exploration SC2 Diversification of skills SC3 Enhances Intention SC4 Unlocking potentials SC5 Opportunity creation
PC5b Suggestions	Recommendations for improving EE in Nigerian universities	SC1 Access to resources SC2 Policy-practice connect SC3 University empowerment SC4 Integrated curriculum SC5 Lecturer training gap SC6 Scheduled Practical sessions SC7 establishment of Entrepreneurship centers

Source: Researcher, 2014

4.3 Generating Initial Themes

The development of themes was guided by the study's objectives. The themes were derived from the patterns and relationships identified during the coding process. Patterns and recurrent ideas in the coded data were identified to highlight common experiences and perspectives among the educators, providing a basis for theme development (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A theme is a pattern that highlights a unique or important aspect of the data and/or study question. According to Braun & Clarke (2006), there are no strict guidelines for identifying a theme. The

significance of a theme defines it. For limited data sets, there may be an overlap between the coding and early theme identification phases. In this case, we examined the codes and some of them fit together into a theme. For example, the researcher had several codes (see Tab 4.3) that related to each of the parent codes. Therefore, the researcher collected these sub-codes to create themes.

Table 14: Summary of Themes

Parent codes	Generated Themes
PC1 Educators Define EE	Theme 1: Entrepreneurial Knowledge Theme 2: Personal Growth and Development Theme 3: Practical Skills and Preparation
PC1b Role of EE	Theme 1: Career exploration and self-discovery Theme 2: Intention and opportunity recognition Theme 3: Skills enhancement and career development
PC1c University Support	Theme 1: Funding Theme 2: Human resource support Theme 3: Infrastructure and Resource Support
PC1d Teaching Methods	Theme 1: Active and experiential learning methods Theme 2: Interactive and collaborative methods Theme 3: Traditional methods
PC2 Challenges	Theme 1: Curriculum and pedagogy challenges Theme 2: Educators and Learning Environment Constraint Theme 3 Institutional and resource constraint
PC3 Skills and competencies	Theme 1: Cognitive and Analytical Skills Theme 2: Creative and Innovative Skills Theme 3: Interpersonal and communication skills Theme 4 Strategic and critical thinking skills
PC5 Suggestions	Theme 1: Community engagement and support Theme 2: Curriculum and institutional development Theme 3: Infrastructure and Resource Enhancement Theme 4: Policy and institutional alignment

4.4 Thematic Review

This phase required the researcher to undertake an in-depth review of the suggested themes concerning the coded data items and the complete dataset (Braun and Clarke 2012, 2020). At this stage, it is expected to observe that specific themes may serve as ineffective interpretations

of the data or may fail to provide insights relevant to the research question. In this study, key themes emerged from the interview analysis of interviews. These were created in alignment with the study's objectives (RO1 to RO5), enabling a thorough understanding of educators' definitions of entrepreneurship education, the challenges encountered, the skills nurtured in students, the teaching strategies used, and the potential improvements for EE programmes.

Research Objectives 1: Educator's Definition of Entrepreneurship Education and Identification of Teaching Methods Used

Three main themes emerged from the gathered data on how educators describe entrepreneurship education (EE): “Entrepreneurial Knowledge”, “Personal Growth and Development”, and “Practical Skills and Preparation”. Nigerian Educators emphasize and recognize that teaching entrepreneurship goes beyond mere academic knowledge; it also entails fostering entrepreneurial habits and skills that support personal development, independence, and self-reliance. EE was connected to enabling students to investigate job paths, identify entrepreneurial aspirations, and acquire critical skills for their future.

While the researcher conducted the thematic review, it became apparent that some themes developed under various initial codes were complementary or overlapped. To be more precise, PC1 (Educators Define EE) and PC1b (Role of EE) were combined to reflect a more thorough comprehension of entrepreneurship education as defined by educators. This merger was essential due to the frequent intersection between the educators' definition of EE and its role. For Instance, educators frequently elaborated on the significance of EE in developing entrepreneurial knowledge, personal growth and development, and practical skills and preparation. These three broad categories covered the definition of EE by educators and the objectives they believe it is designed to accomplish in terms of student outcomes, particularly in career exploration and developing entrepreneurial skills and intentions. Therefore, theme 1 from PC1b (career exploration and self-discovery) was merged into Theme 2 in PC1 (Personal growth and development), Theme 2 From PC1b (intention and opportunity recognition) was merged into Theme 2 PC1(Entrepreneurial knowledge), and lastly, Theme 3 from PC1b (skills enhancement and career development) was merged to support Theme 3 in PC1 (practical skills and preparation).

The combination of these two themes established a more consistent and clarified narrative, which better aligned the research findings with RO1. The purpose was to critically explore the definition of EE and teaching methodologies employed by entrepreneurship educators. This

merger facilitates a nuanced comprehension that establishes a connection between the definition of EE, its practical application, and the intended outcomes.

In the second part of RO1 Educators also characterized “Active and Experiential Learning Methods” (such as seminars, field excursions, and guest speakers), “Interactive and Collaborative Methods” (like group projects and case studies), and “Traditional Methods” (like lectures) as a combination. These strategies motivate students to engage in entrepreneurial thinking and activity. Efficient approaches are essential for preparing students for entrepreneurial challenges in the real world, these gave insight into the current strategies used in universities as previous studies recognized the use of traditional methods (Nian et al.,2014; Udu, 2014)

Research Objective 2: The Challenges Confronting Entrepreneurship Education Learning in Nigeria

The Educators in Nigerian universities highlighted several barriers that hinder the effectiveness of EE. The major challenges that emerged in the discussion included: “Curriculum and Pedagogy Challenges”, “Institutional and Resource Constraints”, and “Educators’ Learning Environment Constraints”. These challenges align with educators' frustrations about limited institutional support, outdated curricula, and inadequate infrastructure, such as a lack of funding and insufficient access to modern equipment. These issues, combined with Policy Barriers and an over-reliance on Western EE frameworks, limit the contextual relevance of entrepreneurship education for Nigerian students. This, in turn, impacts the entrepreneurial outcomes of the programmes. The initial themes developed were maintained as they provided useful information on data sets to address the research objectives (Braun & Clarke, 2012), in this case, provided deep insights into the challenges faced.

Research Objectives 3: The Skills, Competencies, and Capabilities Student Developed

The analysis revealed the main group of skills and competencies students develop through EE, which was classified into four categories: “Cognitive and Analytical Skills” which covered Critical thinking, decision-making, and complicated business environment analysis. Educators stressed that students learn to assess market trends, spot opportunities, and solve difficulties. The “Creative and Innovative Skills” which covers Entrepreneurship education encourages students to think creatively and solve business problems. This skill set is essential for finding new business and staying ahead. “Interpersonal and Communication Skills” which covers Group work, presentations, and business interactions teach students communication,

teamwork, and networking. Successful business ventures require teamwork and stakeholder engagement. And “Strategic and Critical Thinking Skills” as EE helps students plan, strategize, and make educated decisions, which are essential for commercial success. The educators note these abilities help students manage risks and implement corporate strategies. The initial themes developed were maintained as they provided useful information on data sets to address the research objectives.

Research Objective 5: Develop a framework for effective Assessment of EE in Nigeria

To achieve Research Objective 5 (RO5), which aims to develop a framework for the effective assessment of EEPs in Nigerian universities, it is essential to link it with Research Question 5 (RQ5): *How can entrepreneurship education in Nigeria be improved to be more effective in developing the required entrepreneurial skills and the entrepreneurial intention of students?* This requires examining the effectiveness of current EEPs, particularly how well they align with the development of essential entrepreneurial skills and intentions. This analysis suggested that educators revealed areas of improve as suggested by the educators, the themes included “community engagement and support” which covered the issues of linking EE with the wider economy, “Curriculum and institutional development” focusing on the recommendations of revision of curriculum, “Infrastructure and resource enhancement” covering aspects of infrastructures, technology, and entrepreneurial centers and lastly, “Policy alignment” covering the needs of policy alignment with the actual entrepreneurial ecosystems in Nigeria. The themes developed in the previous phase were maintained. The finalized thematic work is seen in the figure below.

Figure 6: Finalized Thematic Map of Themes

Source: Developed by Researcher

4.5 Define Themes

The final refinement of themes is to identify the "essence" of each subject. (Braun & Clarke, 2006, page 92). What does the theme say? How do subthemes interact with the main theme? How are the topics related to each other? In this analysis, several core themes were revealed concerning the Definition of EE, challenges, teaching methods, support systems, and Suggestions for improvement.

Table 15: Sample from Transcript showing Definition of EE

<u>Educators define EE and the role</u>	Theme 1: Entrepreneurial Knowledge	Theme 2: Personal Growth and Development	Theme 3: Practical Skills and Development
	<p>“Entrepreneurial Education is a form of education where students are taught the practices of starting and sustaining a business idea or model” – (Interview EEN08)</p> <p>“It can be perceived as activities that are geared towards enhancing the entrepreneurial knowledge and skills of students. So that is how we perceive it”- (interview EEN06)</p>	<p>“When we're able to help students to be able to develop these as habits, that is they don't have to it just comes naturally and you find yourself in an environment where you're able to identify problems around, where you're able to innovate what possible solutions could be.”- (Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“<u>the</u> role it plays is to help them to be able to, to unlock their entrepreneurial potentials”- (Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“<u>So</u> for me, entrepreneurship education is quite simplistically defined as the process of inspiring learners into innovating ideas that are relevant to solving society's problems.”- (Interview EEN05)</p> <p>“<u>entrepreneurship</u> education It is an art of teaching students on how to be self-reliant and gain self-satisfaction in future.”- (Interview EEN03)</p>	<p>“For me, entrepreneurship education deals with teaching practical skills or knowledge to students to prepare them for their work of Work. That is the way I consider it. That is how I also check them when I'm in class. It's not just about teaching the theory, it's also about impacting that knowledge to them.”- (interview EEN02)</p> <p>“<u>it</u> is an education which involves the creation of ideas, innovations.” – (Interview EEN05)</p> <p>“That is the whole essence of teaching entrepreneurship to students, we are trying to equip them with skills that they could use in the future if they venture into entrepreneurship, startup, and how they can sustain in the changing world.”- (Interview EEN09)</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

Table 16: Sample from Transcript showing University Support

University Support	Theme 1: Funding	Theme 2: Human Resource Support	Theme 3: Infrastructure and Resources
	<p>“<u>and</u> seed funding to support students in turning their ideas into viable businesses”- (Interview EEN09)</p>	<p>“Then at times if you need the service of a lawyer probably to register your company and all that, the school gets a lawyer for you and the school pays for it”- (interview EEN05)</p> <p>Firstly, they help with getting the right set of facilitators. And then also, we <u>being</u> staffs of the university, we also work as consultants with the students when they want to set up a startup business while they are in school”- (Interview EEN04)</p> <p>“<u>we</u> have employees that train students couple with the fact that the Department of Entrepreneurship is doing the theoretical parts and sometimes the practical part.” – (Interview EEN08)</p>	<p>“<u>So</u> they mandate every university to set up a centre that is known as Centre for Entrepreneurship Development. <u>So</u> the centre is both a vocational centre and in the centre they can have the acceleration centre, the education and all that”- (Interview EEN06)</p> <p>“We have skill acquisitions whereby students in the Center of Development (CEDs) are trained in various skills like event decoration, pond management, and farming, I can't leave out the introduction of ICT training for students.”- (Interview EEN09)</p> <p>“Apart from the training that I mentioned earlier on, you know we also provide Internet data and like I said IT related businesses are the major entrepreneurship activities that we encourage” – (Interview EEN07)</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

Table 17: Sample from Transcript showing Challenges in Entrepreneurship Education Learning

Challenges in EE	Curriculum Challenges	Educators and Learning Constraints	Institutional and Resource Constraints
	<p>“Our programmes are too theoretical. They have not started solving anything.”- (Interview EEN05)</p> <p>“The curriculum is more like a repetition of what has been done at the lower level. It's a challenge for me. There's also a cost they have been given a little bit of freedom to organize. However, I still <u>have to</u> work within the framework of the curriculum that NUC is giving to us”- (Interview, EEN02)</p>	<p>“<u>So</u> in my university, I'm sure you're aware that my university is very conservative in mission school, right? Yeah. <u>So</u> there are some policies that aren't really, helping entrepreneurship, fostering entrepreneurship. For instance, <u>at the moment</u> in my university, it is not legal for students to carry out businesses on campus example to buy and sell”- (Interview EEN01).</p> <p>“You know in private universities you can't leave the school premises without the school obtaining your <u>parents consent</u>. <u>So</u> before they are giving exit, we must call their parents to get consent. <u>So</u> if you are pushing them into any entrepreneurial activities, it has to be something that will not require such category of students leaving the campus. It should be something they can do the marketing <u>online</u>, they can use Google, they can send if they can do e-mail marketing and all that.” – (Interview EEN06)</p>	<p>“But we don't have that space or that capacity to do that. In fact, in some cases where we have, for example, in catering, if we have two, or three groups, you may be assigned maybe two, or three hours to learn.”- (Interview EEN03)</p> <p>“Limited access to funding for student ventures, the government keeps saying the funding is there but to access it is the problem.”- (Interview EEN09)</p> <p>“There's electricity power. At times you see some universities put on their generator by 9 am while class will start by 8:00 am. They may put it off around 12, they put it on again probably 2 pm. So those periods that we don't have power, you go to class you can't use your projector.”- (Interview EEN06)</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

Table 18: Sample from Transcript showing Skills and Competencies

Skills and Competencies	Cognitive and Analytical skills	Creative and Innovative skills	Interpersonal and communication skills	Strategic and critical thinking skills
	<p>“How to develop an idea. The idea development in <u>itself</u> is a skill. How to innovate is another skill. So, you will discover that some persons are fast at generating ideas than others. That's because there's a skill behind it. There's an ability because skill is about empowerment, there's an empowerment behind it.” – (Interview, EEN05)</p>	<p>“I think a popular one is something in photography. You know, photography is something I think that's common”.- (Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“Fashion design is a game changer And beautification” – (Interview EEN08)</p> <p>“Wilson's lemonade is the product of the above. They were products of entrepreneurship education from the university. You know the mini savings scheme, Piggvest That was a product of the University students as well”- (interview EEN05)</p> <p>“<u>some</u> set up water processing factories, some go into bakery and they are thriving” –</p>	<p>“One of the first skills is I taught them listening skills. The first thing is for them to have listening skills, because in human religion, it is good for you to listen than to talk much, because you gain a lot from listening” – (Interview EEN04)</p> <p>“In the last sustainability project, we had 16 assessors in total and all of them shared something in common about comment about all our over 300 students that took that assessment. They said your students were brilliant in their presentation. They were not timid at all.”- (Interview EEN09)</p> <p>“Networking because a good percentage of the entrepreneurs we have now, they still have this</p>	<p>“Most of the businesses that have recorded their significant progress are IT-related businesses.”- (Interview EEN07)</p> <p>“...receiving criticism, adjusting, those are very critical skills” – (Interview EEN05)</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

Table 19: Sample from Transcript showing Teaching Methods Used

Teaching Methods	Active learning Methods	Interactive Methods	Traditional Methods
	<p>“We did, what we refer to as BEW. it was the maiden edition that we did, a couple of months back. And the essence of that week, we just need to promote entrepreneurship on campus. So, student entrepreneurs that have businesses, we encourage them to showcase their businesses. In the form of like a <u>sales</u> or an exhibition all through that week. One of the other activities that we did in the week was an innovation challenge, where students who can come up with innovative ideas basically to lead them to be in a start-up, applied for the challenge and they were shortlisted.” – (Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“<u>we</u> also hold a sustainability project where the 300 level students who have solved sustainable development-related projects come up with their ideas to showcase it also to the public. And during that time, like I mentioned, we have judges. The judges come from different universities.</p>	<p>“For example, we have some of our ex-students who are already in business. We bring them in to interact with some of the students, let them know that, <u>Okay</u>, these people also passed through these calls.” – (Interview EEN02)</p> <p>“<u>So</u> it was teamwork for them to build a solution to an identified problem. So that was the learning ground as well for them to come up with. And you need that to be in the, in the presentation, you know.” –(Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“Part of pedagogy is that they have the privilege to relate and present their ideas to real-time entrepreneurs that come from the industry. <u>So</u> the University, we invite entrepreneurs even from outside of Africa. They don’t just motivate the <u>students</u>, they listen to the students’ ideas and help with the incubation stage. <u>So</u> all of this is just defined towards the purpose of building</p>	<p>“<u>for</u> your undergraduate is mainly lectures” – (Interview EEN02)</p> <p>“<u>entrepreneurship</u> the way it was taught, is strictly in theory that was taught in class.” – (interview EEN01)</p> <p>“<u>So</u> while the lecturer is leading the teaching activity”- (Interview EEN05)</p> <p>“We have the normal classroom teaching,” – (interview EEN07)</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

Table 1: Sample from Transcript showing Suggestions for Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

Suggestion for Improvement	Community Engagement and Support	Curriculum and Institutional Development	Infrastructure and resource enhancement	Policy and Institutional Alignment
	<p>“We need industry to be involved. Life doesn't come to you. Wealth doesn't come to you because you talk. Teachers talk too much. Industry people do a lot, so we need industry to come in so that we can have more doors. University is to have a strong relationship with practical entrepreneurs”- (Interview EEN05)</p> <p>“That university and community relationship is not there. If we can introduce it, it will go a long way to improve entrepreneurship teaching within the university environment. Yes.”- (interview EEN01)</p> <p>“The government and policymakers should encourage good business ideas through financing. Inter-institutional</p>	<p>“By the time you start linking them up with some of the opportunities that exist within their discipline, it helps to improve the teaching. It makes the teaching more interesting, and they become more involved in the course.”- (Interview EEN01)</p> <p>“So, when the curriculum is archaic, students will go out there and fumble. But once the curriculum is reviewed and operators of this curriculum are constantly going through reviews themselves, things will <u>change</u> and things are changing. The conferences, workshops, and seminars are channelling new ways into addressing the needs of society.”- (Interview EEN07)</p>	<p>“<u>So</u> this is my point where you have a federal government that claims to be giving out 30 billion to people to buy tricycle and you're trying to use that to solve an unemployment problem. For me, that's completely absurd. Just give universities a grant of that 30 billion and tell them to begin to form entrepreneurship clusters that produce TV monitors. One university should focus on TV production. Another university should focus. <u>So</u> distribute that money as form of grant deliberately to university that are performing. Then you will just see how it is only a matter of time. It <u>has to go</u> beyond skill or vocation. It <u>has to go</u> beyond the vocation that it is</p>	<p>“<u>if</u> we remove corruption, maybe that's the policy that we need to be thinking about. Eradication of corruption is a policy in itself” – (Interview EEN08)</p> <p>“Apart from that, it is also necessary for the government to increase the pay of lecturers generally because we now have a challenge of brain drain in most institutions. Most lecturers are now travelling abroad, what we call <u>japa</u>. Most of our good heads are going to Europe, they're going to America, they're going to Australia.” – (Interview EEN06)</p> <p>“Most times we just copy some policies, irrelevant policies from Europe, from America, from Australia,</p>

Source: Extracted from transcript

4.6 Definitions and Conceptualizations of Entrepreneurship Education

The findings were grouped in three themes, Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Personal growth and development, and practical skills and preparation, the themes are discussed below.

4.6.1 Theme 1: Entrepreneurial Knowledge

The definitions and conceptualizations of EE by educators play a crucial role in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset and capabilities of students. Despite the indefinite definitions of entrepreneurship (Hansemark, 1998), EEPs have become essential for acquiring the skills needed for entrepreneurial success. However, the lack of consistency in definitions over the years has led to disputes about the concept (Josien & Sybrowsky, 2013). Entrepreneurial knowledge is an essential resource as it provides students with a competitive advantage to successfully startup businesses and maintain growth in the early stages. The results of the analysis of data showed that Nigerian educators have a strong understanding of EE and its role in shaping students' mindsets and the development of skills. When it comes to the definition of EE, educators expressed that:

“Entrepreneurial Education is a form of education where students are taught the practices of starting and sustaining a business idea or model” – (Interview EEN08)

The above definition by educator EEN08 highlights a hands-on approach of EE in Nigeria that goes past the theory behind entrepreneurship to the actionable steps required to launch an idea. Another educator perceive that EE goes beyond theory to developing skills of students:

“It can be perceived as activities that are geared towards enhancing the entrepreneurial knowledge and skills of students. So that is how we perceive it”- (interview EEN06)

This perspective underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to developing entrepreneurial knowledge, aligning with Rodrigues et al. (2010), who emphasized the role of EE in enhancing entrepreneurial creativity. This enhancement is vital as it equips students with the cognitive tools to innovate and adapt to various business scenarios. An important component of entrepreneurial knowledge is the ability to recognize opportunities and act on them (Cooper & Rice, 2019). Educators support this as they emphasize that EE encourages students to explore various career paths beyond traditional employment. One educator noted

“So we've come to realize that entrepreneurial education enhances the intention of students towards embracing entrepreneurship”. (Interview EEN06)

Another educator noted the shift when it comes to EE,

“So, students these days and the society have noticed that we need to create something else, more than the normal job we do. Salary is not is not enough and so we need to create more value, more opportunities for other people in the society so they can be beneficiaries of this creation of ours as entrepreneurs”.(Interview EEN07)

By developing an entrepreneurial mindset, educators note that students are better equipped to recognize and pursue opportunities that align with their personal goals and interests. This mindset shift is essential for enabling students to see beyond conventional career paths and consider entrepreneurship as a viable and exciting option. Educator EE07 echoes the study by Gibb (2002) who noted that EE develops the entrepreneurial mindset and enables individuals to recognize opportunities

4.6.2 Theme 2: Personal Growth and Development

Entrepreneurship education (EE) has increasingly become a cornerstone of personal development, offering transformative impacts on students by fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. This pedagogical approach significantly enhances students' entrepreneurial intentions, skills, and overall mindset, which are crucial for personal and professional growth (Nabi et al., 2017; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Educators define entrepreneurship education based on their views and purposes. In Nigeria, where the youth face economic and social challenges the study educators point out the EE prioritizes growth and development. EEN01 notes:

“entrepreneurship education will be...When we're able to help students to be able to develop these as habits, that is they don't have to it just comes naturally and you find yourself in an environment where you're able to identify problems around, where you're able to innovate what possible solutions could be.”- (Interview EEN01)

As noted in the above statement by EEN01, EE focused on pointing students in the direction of being able to explore their interests, which will lead to self-awareness. Similarly, another educator EEN03 focused on self-reliance and personal fulfilment as the outcomes of entrepreneurship education. As Interviewee EEN03 described:

“entrepreneurship education It is an art of teaching students on how to be self-reliant and gain self-satisfaction in future.”- (Interview EEN03)

Furthermore, these entrepreneurial activities they are exposed to in the learning environment will build their confidence in their ability to pursue their goals. The shift towards incorporating entrepreneurship education (EE) into a broader educational curriculum marks a significant transformation in how personal and professional competencies are developed in students. The core objective of EE is to cultivate essential skills and attitudes such as creativity, resilience, and self-efficacy, which are foundational to personal development. The 'EntreComp framework' developed by the European Commission underscores this by detailing competencies like opportunity recognition, creativity, and problem-solving, which are integral to personal growth (Bacigalupo et al., 2016). According to Nabi et al. (2017), the educational shift remains crucial as it not only enhances entrepreneurial intentions and skills but also cultivates an entrepreneurial mindset that is essential for both individual and societal progress.

“So for me, entrepreneurship education is quite simplistically defined as the process of inspiring learners into innovating ideas that are relevant to solving society's problems.” - (Interview EEN05)

This point of view by EEN05 brings up an important part of teaching Entrepreneurship in Nigeria using innovation for social good. EE is seen by educators to teach students how to think critically about the needs of their communities and come up with ideas that help more than just themselves or make money. The identification and resolution of societal issues by students, along with the cultivation of a sense of social responsibility, are the means through which this impact on society is achieved. Kuratko and Hoskinson (2017) and Neck and Corbett (2018) point out that EE encourages students to generate innovative concepts that are pertinent to resolving societal issues which will in turn contribute to the meaningfully to the economy. Furthermore, this definition emphasizes the role of EE in fostering independence and self-confidence (Mwasalwiba, 2010). These competencies are not only critical for entrepreneurship but also for navigating various life challenges (Bacigalupo et al., 2016). The connection between EE and personal growth is well-supported by academic research. Fayolle and Gailly (2015) suggests through EE, students may connect social responsibility and personal growth by using their entrepreneurial skills to positively benefit society.

In responses the emphasis on growth extends beyond economic survival to include personal empowerment, this is seen as a pathway to self-discovery. Entrepreneurship Education encourages students to use their entrepreneurial skills for societal good in addition to personal growth. However, an essential part of this growth is the role EE plays in career exploration and

discovery. Educators see EE as a means of guiding students through the discovery process. EEN01 notions:

“the role it plays is to help them to be able to, to unlock their entrepreneurial potentials So I think, everyone has that entrepreneurial potential, right? So, entrepreneurship education helps students to be able to unlock that thing that is in them, right? And that doesn't come easy. ”- (Interview EEN01)

In addition, Educator EEN05 adds:

“If possible, it can be a plan A. So not just for you to just take it as a course, but We also try to expose the students to the fact that...for every field of study there are entrepreneurial opportunities is there” (Interview EEN05)

This statement points to the wide career possibilities beyond the traditional methods, when Nigerian students are exposed to different industries, the EE they have received can help them identify gaps in the market and create solutions. By identifying these competencies, students can align their career choices with their strengths, leading to greater job satisfaction and success. This is further supported by findings from Rauch and Hulsink (2015), who demonstrated that EE effectively enhances students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy, leading to better career alignment and fulfillment. This hands-on approach not only reinforces classroom learning but also helps students discover their career interests and capabilities in real-world contexts (Rae, 2012).

4.6.3 Theme 3: Practical Skills and Preparation

In Nigeria, EE is deeply intertwined with the development of practical skills and thorough preparation for real-world challenges. EE equips students not only with the knowledge to start their businesses but also with the ability to navigate the unique socio-economic challenges in Nigeria.

“For me, entrepreneurship education deals with teaching practical skills or knowledge to students to prepare them for their work of Work. That is the way I consider it. That is how I also check them when I'm in class. It's not just about teaching the theory, it's also about impacting that knowledge to them.”-(interview EEN02)

This approach emphasized by EEN02 emphasizes that EE is not merely theoretical but also focuses on imparting actionable knowledge that students can apply in their careers (Rodrigues, 2023). This practical orientation ensures that students are well-equipped to tackle the

challenges of the entrepreneurial world and adapt to its dynamic nature (Nabi et al., 2017). By focusing on real-world applications, EE bridges the gap between academic learning and practical experience, preparing students to be effective and adaptable in their entrepreneurial pursuits (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). A crucial aspect of EE is the ability to translate long-term learning into practical applications. An educator illustrates this by stating,

" Then you 'll be thinking about how to make what you have learned over a long period of time practically and put it on the field to be able to feed yourself and feed the nation." (interview EEN03)

This perspective highlights the importance of applying theoretical knowledge in practical settings to achieve tangible outcomes. The practical orientation of EE, as emphasized by EEN02 and EEN03 is important in Nigeria, where the entrepreneurial mindset is essential for self-reliance. In addition, EEN03 states EE prepares students to apply their knowledge not just for personal gain but also “feed the nation”. This is relevant in Nigeria as EE is perceived as a tool for economic development (Aja-Okorie & Adali, 2013; Adeola, 2020). Practical application in EE involves hands-on projects, internships, and real-world problem-solving, which are essential for reinforcing theoretical knowledge and developing entrepreneurial competencies (Rae, 2012). The comprehensive nature of EE involves a blend of theoretical, vocational, and sub-skill training. Another educator describes it as :

" I would say it's a mixture of different things. Because me personally, I have a realistic approach. It has to do with theoretical, vocational, and sub-skill training. Entrepreneurship education for me is a combination of those three aspects". (Interview EEN04)

Educator EEN04 describes EE as a blend of theoretical, vocational, and skill training. In the Nigerian context, could be enriched by integrating indigenous knowledge, local business practices, and cultural perspectives into EE. In addition, EE05 states:

"it is an education which involves the creation of ideas, innovations." – (Interview EEN05)

Combining these aspects to provide a well-rounded education. This holistic approach is crucial as it not only covers the academic aspects of entrepreneurship but also includes hands-on training and the development of sub-skills such as critical thinking and innovation. This integrated method prepares students to create and implement innovative ideas effectively

(Bacigalupo et al., 2016; Jardim & Sousa, 2023). By integrating various educational methodologies, EE ensures that students receive a balanced education that prepares them for diverse entrepreneurial challenges (Rodrigues, 2023). Moreover, the goal of EE is to equip students with sustainable skills for the future. As noted,

"That is the whole essence of teaching entrepreneurship to students, we are trying to equip them with skills that they could use in the future if they venture into entrepreneurship, startup, and how they can sustain in the changing world." (interview EEN09)

This objective aligns with the findings of recent studies that emphasize the role of EE in preparing students for future entrepreneurial ventures and enabling them to sustain and grow in an evolving global economy (Raman et al., 2022; Rodrigues, 2023). The sustainability aspect of EE is critical in ensuring that students are not only prepared to start their ventures but are also capable of maintaining and scaling them in a competitive environment (Neck & Corbett, 2018). In summary, EE plays an important part in developing practical skills and preparing students for the entrepreneurial world. By combining theoretical knowledge with practical applications and vocational training, EE ensures that students are well-prepared to face real-world challenges and succeed in their entrepreneurial endeavours. EE's focus on resilience and adaptability aligns with the need to prepare Nigerian students for an uncertain economic environment (Ugoani, 2015). This is particularly important in Nigeria, where the economy is subject to fluctuations in oil prices, political instability and rapid changes in technology.

4.7 Support Structures for EE in Universities

Participant educators identified several support structures the university offers to students. They are discussed below.

4.7.1 Funding

The importance of funding in assisting student entrepreneurs is a key aspect of EE, particularly in the early phases of their businesses. In Nigeria, where access to financial resources can be a major barrier to starting and expanding enterprises, universities play a role in offering this assistance. The educators from a federal university, EEN07 and EEN09, were the only interviewees who explicitly mentioned the availability of funding support for students. They highlighted the university's efforts to provide financial resources through internal channels, like the Centre for Entrepreneurship Training (CET),

“The university community through CET donates some money to students who are actually enterprising to assist them in the formative years of their businesses. Also, the university has collaborations with organisations out there. They are responsible in sponsoring young and vibrant entrepreneurs within university systems. And these are things we do alongside with CET in the university as we speak” (Interview EEN07)

EEN07 indicates that the university community provides financial support to entrepreneurial students through its Centre for Entrepreneurship Training (CET). This type of seed funding is crucial for assisting students in managing the initial phases of business development, which frequently encounter financial difficulties. By offering direct funding, the university creates an environment beneficial to innovation and the development of viable business models, thereby alleviating the immediate pressure of securing external capital for students (Kuratko & Morris, 2018; Shiri et. Al, 2012).

“and seed funding to support students in turning their ideas into viable businesses”.(Interview EEN09)

According to EEN09, seed money helps students transform their ideas into businesses. This is crucial since many students have unique ideas but little money to implement them. Universities fill the financial gap and promote entrepreneurial practice by offering startup funds. One cannot stress the effects of well-funded programmes for EE on students' aspirations to start their businesses. To encourage students to pursue entrepreneurial careers and contribute to economic growth, financial assistance for events such as business plan competitions and startup incubators is essential (Steenekamp, 2013; Ndofirepi, 2016). However, the fact that only two educators mentioned funding as part of university support raises concerns about the inconsistency of this resource across Nigerian institutions. Research indicates that access to entrepreneurial funding in Nigerian universities is uneven, with larger, federally funded institutions typically having more resources to support students compared to state or privately funded universities (Ojo, 2020)

4.7.2 Theme 2: Human Resource Support

Another important aspect highlighted that supports students in EE in universities is human resource support. In the Nigerian context, universities not only offer financial assistance but also guarantee that students have access to the necessary services and expert guidance to navigate the entrepreneurial landscape. The perspectives from educators like EEN04, EEN05, EEN07, and EEN08 highlight the collaborative role of academic staff, facilitators, and outside

professionals while showcasing the ways universities provide human resource support to students.

“Then at times if you need the service of a lawyer probably to register your company and all that, the school gets a lawyer for you and the school pays for it” - (interview EEN05)

EEN05 highlights how his universities give legal guidance to students, specifically in registering their firms. Students may find the process of registration through legal registration complicated and expensive. By acquiring the services of a lawyer and covering the fees, the institution considerably reduces students' administrative burden, allowing them to focus on growing their businesses. This type of assistance is especially vital in Nigeria, where the legal structure for business registration can be complex, and many entrepreneurs may lack the funds to acquire expert legal services on their own (Olawale and Garwe, 2010). In Addition to legal services EEN04 notes:

“Firstly, they help with getting the right set of facilitators. And then also, we being staffs of the university, we also work as consultants with the students when they want to set up a startup business while they are in school... They assist in selecting the appropriate group of facilitators. Additionally, as university employees, we assist students in starting their own businesses while they are still enrolled in classes by acting as advisers.” - (Interview EEN04)

This shows that some university staff serve as consultants, offering guidance and mentorship to students as they navigate the startups. This method encourages the students by presenting real-life success stories in addition to offering helpful advice (EEN04). University staff, frequently using their own professional experiences, offer practical, hands-on assistance to help students avoid entrepreneurial mistakes. Nabi et al. (2017) found that faculty involvement in entrepreneurial mentorship gives students the abilities and insights they need to transfer from academia to business.

“we have employees that train students couple with the fact that the Department of Entrepreneurship is doing the theoretical parts and sometimes the practical part”.
(Interview EEN07)

By offering such support, universities in Nigeria strengthen the foundation of EE, enabling students toward effectively navigate complexities of business creation and management in a

competitive economic landscape. Academic departments and experienced educators ensure that students understand entrepreneurship theory and practice. This combination gives students the core knowledge and practical skills to start and grow businesses. However, past studies show that Nigerian institutions lack educator training and experienced mentors (Olawale & Garwe, 2010; Ekpoh, 2016; Ogundele, 2020). Training educators, hiring industry professionals, and extending mentorship networks are needed to address these difficulties (Bula, 2012). Such efforts would boost entrepreneurship education and prepare students for the future.

4.7.3 Theme 3: Infrastructure and Resources

Providing the necessary infrastructure and resources is another critical support structure in EE. This includes physical facilities, equipment, and access to technological resources. One of the major findings from the study is that universities in Nigeria have put in place several support structures to aid students in their entrepreneurial endeavours, including the establishment of dedicated entrepreneurship education centers, the provision of essential equipment and facilities, and reliable internet support. Each of these components plays a crucial role in creating a supportive ecosystem that fosters innovation and practical learning. An important support system is the creation of centres for EE, such as the CET. Highlighting the significance of these infrastructures is done by Bula, 2012), who point out that offices and other facilities are necessary to equip students to handle demands in the real world.

“So they mandate every university to set up a center that is known as Centre for Entrepreneurship Development. So the center is both a vocational center and in the center they can have the acceleration center, the education and all that”- (Interview EEN06)

Educator EEN06 noted the NUC made it mandatory for universities in Nigeria to establish entrepreneurship centers, these centers offer an environment where students can engage in hands-on activities while also receiving formal entrepreneurial education. Furthermore, these resources allow students to explore IT-related businesses, which are increasingly being encouraged by universities to align with global trends in entrepreneurship and innovation (Ayoade & Agwu, 2016). This is supported by the statement made by another Educator EEN09:

“We have skill acquisitions whereby students in the Center of Development (CEDs) are trained in various skills like event decoration, fish pond management, and farming, I can't leave out the introduction of ICT training for students.”- (Interview EEN09)

On the other hand, EEN06 highlighted the necessity of free internet and printing services which are overlooked for modern business development, especially in IT-related entrepreneurship. Internet connectivity helps students explore, collaborate, and engage with global marketplaces, while printing helps them practice entrepreneurship. Free resources minimize barriers for students, especially those from low-income families, and encourage them to undertake entrepreneurial activities.

Apart from the training that I mentioned earlier on, you know we also provide Internet data, and like I said IT related businesses are the major entrepreneurship activities that we encourage. We also provide other necessary support like printing and all that. They get all these things at no cost which has also aided their drive. Those are the major things we do to support them (Interview EEN06)

Another important input highlighted was the university being a strong institutional support for Nigerian students. There is evidence that some Nigerian universities are dedicated to creating a conducive entrepreneurial environment is reflected not only in the provision of facilities but also in the alignment of policies with the vision of producing entrepreneurial graduates. As educator EEN05 and EEN02 responded:

The university provides us with the environment, they are doing well in that regard because you could provide one with the entire money but when you don't give the right environment to work, you know it's difficult. And again like I mentioned I created the curriculum that we are we are working with right now. (EEN05)

“Then the next thing we also do is that any school policy that revolves around entrepreneurship, the center gets to fine-tune it and make sure that it's in alignment with the vision of the school. Now, one of the visions of the school is that everybody graduating from this school should be an entrepreneur. That's one of our primary or core beliefs. We are working towards achieving that. That's why from your first year in school to your final year in school, at least you must interface with entrepreneurship at least two times.” (Interview EEN02)

EEN02 emphasizes that the university incorporates entrepreneurship courses within the curriculum from the first to the last year of studies. Students need this experience to develop an entrepreneurial perspective and prepare for post-graduation issues (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

“it has been the school right from day one. All the instruments we use in school, school will be the one to go and look for the material we're going to use for all our work. It will still be the one to pay all those trainers that will be taking charge of all these things. So I think to me, like somebody like me, it was furniture, the power within furniture that I did for the school, that they used to send me to another University for 3D approach training, just to enhance my entrepreneurship skill, and they encourage me that truly what I'm doing is truly appreciated by the school authority, and it's good” (EEN03)

Additionally, EEN03 notes that the university he lectures at invests in specialized training, sending staff to other institutions for advanced skill acquisition, such as 3D furniture design. This cross-institutional training enhances and serves as a form of professional development for educators.

4.8 Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Universities

The challenges identified by educators are placed in three groups: Curriculum challenges, educators and learning environment constraint and lastly Institution and resource constraints.

4.8.1 Theme 1: Curriculum Challenges

One of the major challenges in EE in Nigerian universities is the inadequacy of the current curriculum. Several educators have raised concerns about the overly theoretical nature of the programmes, which do not equip students with the practical skills necessary for entrepreneurship. Educator EEN02 expressed various concerns about the present entrepreneurship education (EE) curriculum, pointing out substantial flaws with its structure and content. One of the main concerns highlighted was the rigidity of the curriculum, which is designed by the NUC, the regulating agency for all Nigerian universities. EEN02 observed that the NUC's predefined curriculum lacks flexibility, making it difficult for educators to incorporate advanced, relevant topics, especially when students proceed to higher levels.

“The NUC, which is the regulatory body for all the universities in Nigeria, prepares the curriculum for all courses. Whatever you're teaching must revolve around the curriculum they have prepared. To a larger extent, that is a very big challenge for me. But when it comes to entrepreneurship, there are certain topics I feel should no longer exist, especially as the students are moving to higher levels. I expect some more advanced topics, but I don't really get to see that. Sometimes when you want to introduce it, it becomes a problem. What I do is that I don't discuss it passively while taking other courses. For example, I expect that at a higher level, for example, when

getting to the third year or the final year, the focus should be more on innovation, more on developing business models, but you don't get to see that.” (Interview EEN02)

Educator ENN02 went further to explain:

“But when it comes to entrepreneurship, there are certain topics I feel should no longer exist, especially as the students are moving to higher levels. I expect some more advanced topics, but I don't really get to see that.

The curriculum is more like a repetition of what has been done at the lower level. It's a challenge for me. In fact, there was a time my director, the director at the University Entrepreneurship Center, when I discussed some of the challenges with him, so he told me that I should do a proposal and send that cost to him. By the time I brought some of the topics I felt and what some of the things I felt we should be doing to steer up the interest of today's small entrepreneurship, he has some little doubt. At the end of the day, nothing was done. It was dropped. I have not been fully involved in the development of the curriculum.(Interview EEN02)

Additionally, EEN02 highlighted the importance of curriculum evolution, saying that by the time students get to their third or final year, the focus should be on advanced subjects like business model development and innovation. However, this advancement is sometimes hindered because of the NUC's limitations. In the end, EEN02's attempts to offer curricular updates, which included a conversation with the director of the University Entrepreneurship Center, were fruitless since their recommendations were turned down without any further action. This problem reflects more considerable worries about the quality of EE in Nigeria and other developing nations, where curricula frequently fail to keep up with the fast-evolving entrepreneurial scene because they are excessively theoretical and rigid (Ratten & Usmanij, 2020). A more adaptable, industry-relevant curriculum covering subjects like innovation, business model creation, and practical entrepreneurial difficulties has been recommended in several studies (Neck & Corbett, 2018; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

In addition, educators pointed to one of the challenges highlighted, which is that the theoretical nature of current educational programmes poses a significant challenge to effective learning and skill development. As one educator expressed.

“Our programmes are too theoretical. They have not started solving anything.”- (Interview EEN05)

This shows a common problem in EE: the programme doesn't provide students with the practical abilities or real-life experience they need to be successful as entrepreneurs (Neck & Corbett, 2018). The curriculum is still based on abstract ideas and doesn't focus on real-world uses, which makes it less beneficial. EEN01 and EEN03 both discussed how important it is to review and change the entrepreneurship programme curriculum to align with the current needs of their regions. EEN01 says that most of the present entrepreneurship courses are general introductions that only teach the basics of the field without focussing on more advanced skills like business development or innovation. In their responses:

“It can be improved in a lot of way, number one there is a need for the to visit and revisit the curriculum development concerning entrepreneurship, number two there is a need for them to understand the need for standardisation; regularisation and meeting the demand of global village about the current need for development” (EEN03)

“The course, the entrepreneurship model they take is basically introductory. So it's just to introduce them to entrepreneurship. So what we are now doing is making students to be innovative and promoting the start-up culture, which basically is to solve a problem and the problem has to be a local problem.” (EEN01)

This fits with what Adekiya and Ibrahim (2016) found. They say that students aren't ready for the challenges of real-life entrepreneurship in Nigeria if they don't have access to a more advanced and dynamic programme. A more comprehensive and adaptable curriculum could better prepare students to deal with problems in their communities and take advantage of different opportunities, making it easier for them to start and run ventures. By not introducing advanced topics or encouraging more innovative thinking at higher levels, the current curriculum misses the opportunity to effectively equip students for the complexities of the entrepreneurial world (Mwasalwiba, 2010). In conclusion, the curriculum challenge is a significant barrier to effective entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, and addressing it will require a shift towards more flexible, practice-oriented, and advanced content.(Yatu et al., 2018).

4.8.2. Theme 2: Educators and Learning Environment Constraint

Entrepreneurship education (EE) in Nigeria faces several challenges related to educators and the learning environment, which undermine its effectiveness. A significant issue is the confusion between entrepreneurship and vocational training. Many educators in Nigerian universities, predominantly trained in traditional business disciplines, treat EE as an extension

of business studies, focusing more on established concepts like management and finance rather than fostering innovation, risk-taking, and venture creation (Uche et al., 2009). This results in a curriculum that overlooks the unique skills needed for entrepreneurship, such as creativity and resilience (Enu, 2012). In Nigeria, the over-reliance on business faculty to teach entrepreneurship further exacerbates this problem. As Matlay (2008) observed, this limits the entrepreneurial mindset needed to navigate the country's dynamic and often unpredictable business environment. EEN01 pointed out that this misalignment in understanding hampers the development of real entrepreneurial competencies among students, as the focus remains on traditional business principles rather than the skills required for starting and growing new ventures in uncertain contexts, which is critical in Nigeria's unstable economy. Educator EEN09 said:

"Entrepreneurship is being confused with vocation, which has different things, and we don't know how to separate it. You know, so, and that's why, since we came on board, we've started doing some activities basically to promote the co-entrepreneurship itself"
(Interview EEN09)

Furthermore, another challenge identified by the educator had to do with the campus restrictions, the educator noted that their university which is a "conservative, mission-driven" university (private university) in Nigeria, has policies that restrict students from engaging in business on campus.

"So in my university, I'm sure you're aware that my university is very conservative mission school, So there are some policies that aren't really, helping entrepreneurship, fostering entrepreneurship. For instance, at the moment in my university, it is not legal for students to carry out businesses on campus example to buy and sell"- (Interview EEN01).

By preventing students from carrying out these activities on campus, the university limits opportunities for hands-on experience, which is important for learning entrepreneurial skills. EEN06 raised another issue where the institutional policies hindered EE, in this case the students could not engage in activities that required them to be outside of the university.

"You know in private universities you can't leave the school premises without the school obtaining your parents consent. So before they are giving exit, we must call their parents to get consent. So if you are pushing them into any entrepreneurial activities, it has to be something that will not require such category of students leaving the

campus. It should be something they can do the marketing online, they can use Google, they can send if they can do e-mail marketing and all that.” – (Interview EEN06)

According to Nwoye (2017), for entrepreneurship education to thrive in Nigerian universities, policies need to encourage student-led ventures, providing a safe environment for experimentation and innovation. In conservative institutions, balancing academic values with the need for practical entrepreneurial experiences is critical for fostering entrepreneurial mindsets. Such policies as noted by EEN01 and EEN06 limit the practical business experiences that are essential for students to apply their theoretical knowledge to their environment (Canziani et al., 2015). As a result, student entrepreneurs lose out on important chances to test their ideas, run actual businesses, and gain practical experience in areas like marketing, customer service, and finance management when they are not allowed to participate in entrepreneurial activities on campus.

Another challenge when it comes to Entrepreneurship Education learning from the educator's perspective is the allocation challenge in managing large student cohorts with limited facilitators. As EEN02 explained;

“Now, I also need to point out a few things. Because of the peculiarity of my institution, one it is a private university. Students are a little bit confined within the university environment. There is little that one can really do. We do more of a lecturing method. If you have about 2,000 or 3,000 students who are to take the course, then you have about 4 facilitators. Often it is a very big challenge to allocate students based on their needs” (Interview EEN02)

With similar concerns, educator EEN04 highlights.

"The number of students to the facilitator, the more the students, the lesser the concentrations. The fewer the students assigned to the facilitator, the better. So that is one key area that I'll say” (Interview EEN04)

Also, educator EEN09 added;

“In creating a better learning environment, the ratio of students in a class or should I say lecture room to a lecturer is not balanced” (interview EEN09)

The issue of overcrowding was commonly identified by educators, EEN02 points out that students are confined to a lecture-based learning method due to the large size and this can also

lead to the problem of allocation of educators. EEN04 and EEN09 share similar experiences and views, when the student-lecturer ratio is not balanced, the learning experience is compromised. Research supports these concerns, showing that smaller class sizes and more personalized mentorship led to better outcomes in entrepreneurship education, as students are more engaged and receive targeted feedback on their business ideas (Honig, 2004). According to Pittaway and Edwards (2012), this imbalance causes students to receive insufficient individualized attention and support, which has an impact on their learning outcomes. Educators find it challenging to interact with each student personally in large class sizes, which makes it more difficult for them to meet individual learning needs, give prompt feedback, and create a positive learning atmosphere. Large student cohorts also make it necessary for teachers to mostly rely on traditional lecture techniques, which are less successful than more interactive and experiential teaching approaches in encouraging critical thinking and active learning (Biggs & Tang, 2011).

Another recurring challenge that was identified by educators is the lack of experienced educators in Nigerian universities. Duze (2010) notes that facilitators lacking entrepreneurial experience cannot effectively mentor students or provide insights into the entrepreneurial process. Hägg and Kurczewska (2022) emphasize the need for ongoing professional development and hiring instructors with practical experience to connect theoretical concepts with practical applications. This aligns with concerns raised by EEN02 and EEN05 regarding the quality and exposure of facilitators.

“Then another challenge we also have, this time is on the part of the facilitators. Many of them are not, really, really exposed. They are not exposed. Yes, they know the skill, and they are using it to eat. Now, I'm saying they're using it to eat because they are operating at a very subsistent level. Their businesses have not grown to... As small as our communities are, their businesses are not so that when you mention their name, people quickly recon with them. For me, that is not the root. We have that challenge. Sometimes you try to push them.” (Interview EEN02)

“So I think the calibre of facilitators also goes a long way. Imagine me not looking so good or complaining about everything and I'm coming to tell you, you can be very successful doing something” (Interview EEN05)

This claim highlights how crucial Nigerian educators' perceived success and character are in shaping students' engagement and conviction in the possibility of entrepreneurship. Educators

lose credibility and students' belief that entrepreneurship is a realistic and fulfilling career option if they come across as unmotivated or failed. Furthermore, these problems become even worse by educators' inadequate training. For educators to effectively instruct and motivate students, proper training is essential (Steenekamp, 2013). One educator EEN06 noted,

"We have so many educators that have not been properly trained. Entrepreneurship is not easy, and that's part of the reasons we encounter that barrier of students not having the interests" (Interview EEN06).

As noted in studies, skilled educators are in a better position to help students develop an entrepreneurial attitude, support critical thinking, and navigate real-world business difficulties, all of which add to the programs' overall efficacy (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008). This lack of experience limits their ability to inspire and guide students toward high-level entrepreneurial success. Facilitators who are themselves operating at a basic level cannot provide the deep insights and mentorship that students need to develop advanced entrepreneurial skills. (Hägg & Gabrielsson, 2019; Neck et al., 2020). Lastly, Students' engagement and their ability to make informed choices also pose significant challenge for educators. Educator EEN07 highlighted,

"The major challenges, as far as my experience in teaching entrepreneurship is concerned, are in the aspects of students' choices, concentration, and sincerity. A lot of students make wrong choices, they do not concentrate during teaching classes and training, and they are often insincere with themselves" (interview EEN07)

Educator EEN07 expressed frustrations as he noted that it is difficult to teach students when they are not interested, this makes it difficult to gauge their progress. This reflects a broader issue in EE, where students may not fully engage with the learning process, affecting their ability to obtain the abilities and mindset necessary for entrepreneurial success. Research supports this concern, showing that student motivation and self-awareness are critical factors for success in entrepreneurial education (Ratten & Jones, 2021).

4.8.3 Theme 3: Institutional and Resource Constraints

Institutional and resource constraints pose significant challenges to the efficiency of EE in Nigerian universities. One major constraint is the lack of innovation hubs on campuses. Educator EEN01 and EEN02 stated,

"so one of the things we need very urgently that we don't have at the moment is, we need an innovation hub. So on campus, we don't have you know, no innovation hub on

campus. So we just try to improvise and make do with what we have. But that is very key. You know you want an environment where or a facility where students can conceptualize an idea and walk into the hub, Build the prototype you that so that we don't have at the moment." (Interview EEN01).

"We are looking forward to a period where students can walk into the entrepreneurship center and create whatever they want to create without necessarily being restricted. We believe if we have an entrepreneurship center where let's say you've gone to learn baking, for example, and then we have an entrepreneurship center where you can bring in your oven or bring in other materials, you can on your own, even when the facilitator is not there, or probably they are not teaching you, you can have time to practice" (Interview EEN02)

Innovation hubs are crucial for giving students the resources, mentorship, and collaborative environment necessary to foster and test entrepreneurial ideas (Canziani et al., 2015). Without these hubs, students miss out on valuable real-world experiences, limiting their entrepreneurial readiness. Despite growing recognition of their value, many Nigerian institutions still lack such facilities. The Nigerian government and stakeholders have stressed the need to integrate innovation hubs into universities to help theory and practice fit together (Ibrahim, Decker, & Ibrahim, 2017). Examples like Lagos State University's innovation cluster show potential, but challenges like financial constraints and insufficient government support remain. Addressing this requires collaboration and funding from public, private, and educational sectors to foster environments that promote innovation and entrepreneurship (Adetunji, 2020; Ezeani, 2018). The difficulties experienced by entrepreneurship education are further compounded by policies that do not encourage entrepreneurship. These policies by universities which was previously discussed restricts entrepreneurial activities on campus. One Educator EEN01 noted,

"So for condition, the what policy is now you know like I said earlier, we have some policies here that are anti-entrepreneurship so those are the conditions that would hinder if that can be taken out of the way then sort of promote and foster entrepreneurship..." (Interview EEN01).

According to studies, students must have access to collaboration spaces, workshops, and laboratories where they can work on actual projects and prototypes (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012). Furthermore, these limitations can be addressed by increasing capacity through the hiring of more skilled personnel and infrastructure investments, guaranteeing that students

obtain the thorough education required to thrive in entrepreneurial endeavours (Gibb, 2011). One major obstacle to effective entrepreneurship education is the absence of resources and current technology. To truly engage these students, one of the educators EEN03 stressed

“ We need ultramodern technology to really engage these students. The proper way international students are being engaged when it comes to the concept of entrepreneurship” (EEN03).

Educator EEN03 further highlighted that having the right equipment will draw the attention of students and may even inspire them to take entrepreneurial ventures seriously. According to Steenekamp (2013), giving students access to modern technologies and tools is crucial to keeping them engaged and equipping them with the skills needed to succeed in today's competitive entrepreneurial environment. By making learning more dynamic and relevant to modern industry norms, the use of cutting-edge technology such as virtual reality simulations, online collaborative platforms, and digital marketing tools can greatly improve the educational experience. Research shows that technology-integrated learning environments increase student engagement and build critical thinking and problem-solving skills needed for entrepreneurship. Educational institutions can more effectively prepare students for the digital age's both difficulties and possibilities by embracing these tools (Bacigalupo et al., 2016; Maritz, 2017).

Limited funding for entrepreneurial ventures restricts students' ability to launch and sustain their business ideas. This is another important area when it comes to Entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities. As noted by educators EEN05 and EEN09 funding is required to create a conducive environment for teaching Entrepreneurship.

“Limited access to funding for student ventures, the government keeps saying the funding is there but to access it is the problem.”- (Interview EEN09)

Lastly, educators noted that Infrastructure issues, such as unreliable power supply and inadequate internet facilities, also pose significant challenges to entrepreneurship education. Educator EEN06 explained,

“There's electricity power. At times you see some universities put on their generator by 9 am while class will start by 8:00 am. They may put it off around 12, they put it on again probably 2 pm. So those periods that we don't have power, you go to class you can't use your projector.”- (Interview EEN06)

“But we don't have that space or that capacity to do that. In fact, in some cases where we have, for example, in catering, if we have two, or three groups, you may be assigned maybe two, or three hours to learn.” - (Interview EEN03)

The lack of dependable internet, a critical resource for entrepreneurial research and collaboration, worsens this difficulty. Poor infrastructure limits entrepreneurship education since students and educators need help to use digital technologies and global business methods (Afolayan et al., 2021; Etim & Ema, 2020). EEN03 also noted that catering programmes lack space and time for practical learning, which limits entrepreneurial skill development. A recent study shows that developing nations' entrepreneurship education is hindered by poor infrastructure and limited practical training facilities, reducing students' readiness for current business issues (Arokiasamy, 2021; Bello et al., 2020).

4.9 Skills and Competencies Developed from Participating in EEPs in Nigeria

The skills and capabilities EEPs in Nigeria promote in students which were identified by educators are discussed below.

4.9.1 Theme 1: Cognitive and Analytical Skills

One of the fundamental skills in entrepreneurship is cognitive and analytical skills. These skills help people comprehend and evaluate complicated situations, come up with creative solutions, and make well-informed judgments. According to Baron (2014), these abilities are essential for navigating the complex and frequently unpredictable world of entrepreneurship, where a company's performance can be greatly impacted by its capacity to evaluate data, spot trends, and foresee difficulties. Entrepreneurs who possess cognitive abilities can think critically, digest information efficiently, and apply knowledge to practical situations. This aids in their ability to recognize possibilities, evaluate risks, and create creative plans of action that spur company expansion. When being asked about skills that students develop, educators pointed out;

"So, entrepreneurship education that does not solve real-life problems is a waste of time" - (Interview EEN05)

“How to develop an idea. The idea development in itself is a skill. How to innovate is another skill. So, you will discover that some persons are fast at generating ideas than others. That's because there's a skill behind it. There's an ability because skill is about empowerment, there's an empowerment behind it.” – (Interview, EEN05)

Responses from EEN05 underline the need for students to apply the cognitive skills developed from EE to practical issues.

“Active learning methods such as business simulations and group projects engage students and enhance their problem-solving” – (Interview EEN09)

These responses from educators show the need for EEPs to focus on practical problem-solving abilities that can be applied in real-world contexts. These methods provide students with opportunities to engage in real-life scenarios, fostering their ability to think critically and make informed decisions (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012; Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2014). Furthermore, in a study by Santos, Caetano, and Curral (2019) discovered that more analytically minded and cognitively flexible business owners are better able to adjust to shifting market conditions and make calculated choices that improve overall performance.

4.9.2 Theme 2: Creative and Innovative skills

Entrepreneurs need to possess creative and innovative talents since they are essential in developing new concepts, goods, and services that provide them a competitive advantage in the marketplace. Within the context of EEPs in Nigeria, these skills are particularly emphasized to prepare students for the dynamic and often unpredictable nature of entrepreneurial ventures. One of the key aspects of fostering creativity and innovation in EEPs is encouraging students to develop and maintain tenacity during the development of their ideas. Educator EEN05 stated.

“I would say how to develop an idea. The idea development in itself is a skill. How to innovate is another skill. So, you will discover that some persons are faster at generating ideas than others. That's because there's a skill behind it. There's an ability because skill is about empowerment, there's an empowerment behind it. The skill around developing the environment that brings you into that tacit nature because that's actually something very powerful. The ability to present your idea is another skill, one of the testimonies that we got from all our assessors” – (EEN05)

This statement highlights the significance of persistence and resilience in the entrepreneurial process. This tenacity is crucial as it allows entrepreneurs to navigate through challenges and setbacks, which are inevitable in the journey of bringing a new idea to fruition (Robinson & Stubberud, 2014). To develop these abilities in their students, EEPs use a variety of techniques. For example, students are often taught how to approach challenges creatively and come up with

creative solutions through design thinking and innovation workshops. On the creativity side educators highlighted some of the skills and products their students have developed overtime;

“I think a popular one is something in photography. You know, photography is something I think that's common”.- (Interview EEN01)

“Fashion design is a game changer And beautification” – (Interview EEN08)

“Wilson's lemonade is the product of the above. They were products of entrepreneurship education from the university. You know the mini savings scheme, Piggyvest. That was a product of the University students as well”- (interview EEN05)

“some set up water processing factories, some go into bakery and they are thriving” – (Interview EEN06)

These success stories show that students benefit from the practical hands-on skill which are developed from EE. According to Brown and Katz (2011), these workshops frequently include tasks that force students to think creatively and work in pairs to develop and improve their ideas. Students get the resilience necessary to pursue their business aspirations and learn to accept failure as a teaching opportunity by participating in such practical initiatives.

4.9.3 Theme 3: Interpersonal and Communication Skills

Interpersonal and communication skills are critical components of entrepreneurship education, as they enable entrepreneurs to build relationships, network effectively, and lead teams. These skills are essential for creating and maintaining the social capital necessary for business success. Educators identified communication, networking, and collaboration skills as part of the skills students develop when they take part in EEPs. In entrepreneurial education, listening is one of the fundamental interpersonal skills that is stressed. As Educator EEN03 puts it,

“ One of the first skills I emphasize is listening skills. The first thing is for them to have listening skills, because in human religion, it is good for you to listen than to talk much, because you gain a lot from listening” - (EEN03).

EEN09 noted that students had developed good presentation skills which are often emphasized in EEPs

“In the last sustainability project, we had 16 assessors in total and all of them shared something in common about all our over 300 students that took that assessment. They

said your students were brilliant in their presentation. They were not timid at all.”- (Interview EEN09)

These skills help business owners comprehend the requirements and viewpoints of partners, customers, and workers, listening skills are essential. As it enables business owners to obtain insightful information and feedback, active listening can help them make better decisions and solve problems (Adler & Elmhorst, 2012). Another important skill that entrepreneurship education programs (EEPs) emphasize is networking. As an educator EEN07 and EEN06 pointed out,

“ So the major skill we believe student gain is that of networking. That is why we emphasize that all their business idea must be partnership driven” (Interview EEN07).

“Networking because a good percentage of the entrepreneurs we have now, they still have this archaic mentality of doing it alone “It's my business”.- (Interview EEN06)

Educators pointed out that entrepreneurs who network well can obtain a variety of resources that are essential for their success, such as capital, market intelligence, strategic alliances, and mentoring. Through these relationships, business owners might find new opportunities, obtain resources that they might not otherwise have access to, and receive insightful counsel. Robust networks can help with investor introductions, offer consolation during rough patches, and present a range of viewpoints that enhance decision-making procedures (Ozgen & Baron, 2007). Furthermore, Neergaard et al. (2020) notes that an entrepreneur's reputation and credibility are enhanced by belonging to a network, which facilitates the development of trust and draws in key stakeholders. Teamwork and collaboration are also crucial interpersonal skills emphasized in entrepreneurship education. The ability to work effectively in a team is essential for entrepreneurs, as it fosters innovation and enhances productivity. As one educator EEN09 noted,

“for me teamwork skills and effective communication are emphasized, as these skills are crucial for entrepreneurial success” (EEN09).

Working in teams allows entrepreneurs to leverage diverse skills and perspectives, leading to more creative solutions and efficient problem-solving. Effective teamwork involves not only sharing tasks but also engaging in open communication, mutual respect, and the ability to manage conflicts constructively. This collaborative approach can significantly enhance an entrepreneurial venture's capacity to innovate and adapt to changes. Recent research supports

the importance of these skills, highlighting that teams with high levels of collaboration and effective communication are more agile and better equipped to navigate the complexities of the entrepreneurial landscape (Hoch, 2014; Klotz et al., 2014). By fostering these skills, entrepreneurship education programs can better prepare students to work in dynamic environments, enabling them to harness the full potential of their collective abilities to drive business success.

4.9.4 Theme 4: Strategic and Critical thinking skills

Strategic and critical thinking skills are essential components of entrepreneurship education, as highlighted by educators EEN07 and EEN09. Although these educators did not provide detailed explanations, mentioning the skills showed the importance of the development of successful entrepreneurs. In addition, EEN05 highlights that adjusting and receive criticism is a strategic skill.

“. The ability to be tenacious in the process of developing that idea, receiving criticism, adjusting, those are very critical skills.” – (Interview EEN05)

Strategic thinking also involves resource management, prioritizing tasks, and adapting strategies in response to changing conditions. By fostering strategic thinking, entrepreneurship education programs can help students develop a proactive approach to business management, ensuring they are well-prepared to lead their ventures toward sustainable growth. The inclusion of critical and strategic thinking abilities in entrepreneurship education is supported by recent research. For example, a study by Facione (2015) emphasises the importance of critical thinking in the formation of efficient problem-solving abilities, while Goldman et al. (2020) emphasize the significance of strategic thinking in attaining long-term corporate success. Educational institutions can better equip their students to generate innovation in their enterprises and navigate the intricacies of the entrepreneurial landscape by incorporating these abilities into their curriculum.

4.10 Teaching Methods

Educators identified the different methods utilised in teaching EE in their universities. These different methods identified were group in three categories which is discussed below.

4.10.1 Theme 1: Active and Experiential Learning

Active and experiential learning methods are highly emphasized by educators in EE as effective strategies for fostering practical skills and innovative thinking among students. These methods

engage students in hands-on activities that simulate real-world entrepreneurial scenarios, enabling them to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts and develop essential entrepreneurial competencies. Educator EEN01 also highlighted the use of challenges and competitions to stimulate innovation among students as the university had an entrepreneurship week where students were encouraged to showcase their skills or products. As seen below;

“We did, what we refer to as BEW. it was the maiden edition that we did, a couple of months back. And the essence of that week, we just need to promote entrepreneurship on campus. So, student entrepreneurs that have businesses, we encourage them to showcase their businesses. In the form of like a sales or an exhibition all through that week. One of the other activities that we did in the week was an innovation challenge, where students who can come up with innovative ideas basically to lead them to be in a start-up, applied for the challenge and they were shortlisted.” – (Interview EEN01)

The strategy gives students confidence by pushing them to show off their projects through sales and exhibitions. It also gives them real-life experience in marketing, dealing with customers, and running a business. The innovation challenge also adds a competitive and motivating factor, pushing students to come up with creative ideas and think like entrepreneurs. This type of activity not only enhances students' presentation skills but also fosters a sense of ownership and confidence in their business ventures. According to Blank (2013), Showcasing businesses in such a manner serves multiple educational and developmental purposes. Firstly, it provides a real-world platform for students to practice and refine their communication and marketing skills. By presenting their products or services to an audience, students learn how to effectively articulate their value proposition, address customer inquiries, and handle feedback constructively. These skills are critical for entrepreneurs who must continuously engage with customers, investors, and other stakeholders to grow their business. Additionally, these activities provide invaluable networking opportunities. Students can connect with peers, faculty, industry professionals, and potential customers, building relationships that can support their entrepreneurial journey. Networking at such events can lead to mentorship opportunities, partnerships, and even potential funding, all of which are crucial for the success and sustainability of start-ups (Neergaard et al., 2020).

Research supports the effectiveness of experiential learning activities, such as business showcases, in entrepreneurship education. Kolb's (2014) experiential learning theory emphasizes the importance of concrete experiences in the learning process. According to this theory, hands-on activities allow students to experiment with ideas, reflect on their experiences,

and integrate new knowledge into their understanding of entrepreneurship. Another method identified by EEN02 is Role-play. Role-playing is utilized as a teaching method in EEPs, where students are divided into groups and assigned different roles within a hypothetical company. As educator EEN02 noted,

"I do a form of role-playing. Yes, I think I would call it role-playing. I group the students; I break them into groups. Within that group, you must speak with your CEO, with the company secretary" (Interview EEN02).

This method helps students understand the dynamics of business operations and the importance of effective communication and teamwork. Students practice decision-making, leadership, and collaborative problem-solving in a controlled environment by simulating real-world business scenarios. Role-playing fosters the development of interpersonal skills essential for business success, including negotiation and conflict resolution. Research indicates this approach builds students' confidence in managing real-world business challenges, preparing them for the multifaceted nature of entrepreneurial ventures (Kuratko, 2016). Workshops and internships are an integral part of the curriculum and allow students to engage in real-world projects. Educator EEN04 puts it,

"I also organize workshops for students" - (EEN04).

These often include field trips and trips to conferences and seminars, allowing students to meet and network with like-minded individuals and industry professionals, enriching their learning experience.

"Practical sessions, field trips, field trips. At conferences and seminars, you meet like-minded people in your field of interest, you rub shoulders with each other" - (EEN07).

Educator EEN05 noted the university sustainability-related conferences where students can learn about sustainable development goals (SDGs) and showcase their projects to a wider audience:

"we also hold a sustainability project where the 300 level students who have solved sustainable development-related projects come up with their ideas to showcase it also to the public. And during that time, like I mentioned, we have judges. The judges come from different universities. The one that we had recently in August, there were entrepreneurship educators from Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, Birmingham, Covenant

University, Bangkok University and many more, serving as judges to our students. And so that's collaboration"- (Interview EEN05)

These conferences expose students to real-world environments and situations, allowing them to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world contexts. They also facilitate the exchange of ideas, promote collaboration, and help students create professional networks. By interacting with industry professionals and their peers, students gain insight into current trends, challenges, and opportunities in their field, enhancing their understanding and preparing them for business success. Research supports the effectiveness of these experiential learning methods, noting that they significantly improve students' skills, confidence, and preparedness for real-world applications (Kolb, 2014; Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). EEN09 identifies this method is what the university has adopted for teaching EE:

"There's what we call the experiential learning pedagogical method. So that is what my school adopts for all entrepreneurship-related classes"-(Interview EEN09).

These activities are designed to simulate real-world scenarios, providing students with opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts.

4.10.2 Theme 2: Interactive and Collaborative Methods

Nigerian entrepreneurship education uses interactive and collaborative approaches to engage students and foster peer learning. According to EEN01, industry specialists give students valuable insights from successful Nigerian business owners, supplementing academic knowledge with real-world experience. This is seen in the comments below;

"So we brought in some industry experts, you know, to come to school to share their story, their experience with the students, basically how they got to where they are at the moment" (interview EEN01).

According to Nabi et al. (2017), bringing in other experts boosts students' entrepreneurship skills and aspirations. The guidance and motivation of professionals who worked through Nigeria's challenges help students understand how entrepreneurial ideas can be utilized (Igwe et al., 2020). Engagement with industry professionals motivates students and provides early networking opportunities, which is crucial in Nigeria's relationship-driven business climate. Kolade and Obembe (2021) say these interactions increase students' self-esteem and business motivation. Experts also update the curriculum by discussing local market trends and creating business models to equip students for the shifting entrepreneurial landscape. Nigeria's dynamic

economy requires adaptability, which this technique increases. Another strategy is Teamwork and collaborative projects are also utilized in entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities. As educator EEN01 explained,

"So it was teamwork for them to build a solution to an identified problem. So that was the learning ground as well for them to come up with. And you need that to be in the presentation, you know" (Interview EEN01).

Working in teams to solve real-world problems helps students develop critical teamwork skills and learn to collaborate effectively, which are vital in entrepreneurial ventures. These collaborative experiences teach students how to leverage diverse skills and perspectives, manage group dynamics, and communicate effectively to achieve common goals. According to Johnson and Johnson (2009), cooperative learning environments enhance problem-solving abilities and foster a sense of responsibility among team members. This method not only prepares students for the collaborative nature of entrepreneurial endeavours but also enhances their ability to innovate and adapt in a rapidly changing business landscape. By engaging in teamwork, students learn to navigate conflicts, make collective decisions, and build strong, supportive networks that can be crucial for future entrepreneurial success.

Another popular interactive technique in EE in Nigerian Universities is the use of case studies. EEN01, EEN04 and EEN07 highlight ability to apply theoretical concepts to real-world circumstances through case study analysis improves their analytical and problem-solving abilities

"case studies there are different courses, not even entrepreneurship alone. Different courses have case studies. - (EEN01).

"Characteristics and the like, I also do a lot of case studies. I do a lot of case study, I do group projects, and extensively on the long run" – (EEN04)

"So whenever I come into class I don't teach based on just the available textbooks. I teach based on some of these scenarios and case studies that have come up from these interactions. So that is how I developed my own approach" (EEN07)

As the educators emphasize the use of case studies, It is essential to recognise that the incorporation of case studies in Nigerian EE reflects a movement towards fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making abilities that are crucial for effectively managing the unpredictable and resource-constrained landscape in Nigeria (Akinbami &

Olaniyan, 2021). According to a review by Lunde (2017), incorporating case studies into entrepreneurship education also helps students comprehend business concepts more deeply and enhances their capacity to integrate and apply knowledge in a variety of scenarios. Interactive methods in EE utilized in EEPs also include the use of modern technology and media.

"One of the things I asked the students to do this year was to go to YouTube and pick any business video and analyze it" - (EEN02).

Utilizing digital platforms for learning engages students and makes the educational content more accessible and relevant to their everyday experiences. By incorporating assignments that require students to analyze business-related videos on platforms like YouTube, educators can enhance students' ability to critically evaluate and learn from various media sources. Dabbagh and Kitsantas (2012) highlight that integrating social media and digital tools into the curriculum supports self-regulated learning and helps students develop important skills such as information literacy and critical thinking. Furthermore, these methods can make learning more dynamic and interactive, keeping students engaged and motivated. The use of technology in the classroom reflects the real-world business environment, where digital tools are integral to operations and strategy, thus better-preparing students for future entrepreneurial challenges.

According to Pittaway and Cope (2007), learning from peers who have successfully navigated the entrepreneurial landscape enhances students' understanding and confidence, providing a powerful motivator for their entrepreneurial endeavours. Incorporating former students who have successfully started businesses into the learning process provides current students with relatable role models, Educator EEN02 added;

"For example, we have some of our ex-students who are already in business. We bring them in to interact with some of the students, let them know that, Okay, these people also passed through these courses" (Interview EEN02).

This approach motivates students by showing how classroom knowledge applies to real business contexts. Research by Blesa et al. (2020) and Nabi et al. (2018) suggests alumni involvement boosts students' intentions, self-efficacy, and attitudes toward entrepreneurship, making the learning experience more relatable and inspiring future entrepreneurial careers. Moreover, educators employ feedback and discussion-based methods to enhance learning outcomes. As one educator noted,

"The first one is cognitive teaching and feedback. I prefer to teach, see them, and get feedback from them by asking questions immediately after my lecture. I use two hours for the lecture, but I use 30 minutes to ask questions because I wanted them to give me the outcome of every lecture I have taught" - (EEN03).

This approach ensures that students are thoroughly involved in the educational experience and allows educators to gauge students' understanding in real time. Immediate feedback helps students recognize their strengths and identify areas for improvement, fostering a deeper comprehension of the material. Shute (2008) also highlights that formative feedback improves academic outcomes by helping students adjust their strategies. More recently, Winstone and Carless (2020) emphasizes that understanding and using feedback effectively enhances learning and performance. By integrating feedback and discussions, educators create an engaging learning environment that adapts to students' needs and promotes academic growth.

Winstone and Carless (2020) found that feedback improves learning and performance. Feedback and debates help educators create a dynamic learning environment. Entrepreneurship requires collaboration, teamwork, and leadership, which group projects foster. Entrepreneurs must pitch concepts and connect with investors and stakeholders, therefore these activities assist build soft skills like public speaking and presenting (Boud et al., 2014). Giving presentations boosts confidence and skill in communicating ideas. These experiences follow Kolb's (2014) experiential learning approach, allowing students to apply and reflect on their learning. Guest lecturers successfully close the knowledge gap between theory and practice by offering insightful guidance and inspiration. These business owners give concrete instances of how theoretical concepts are applied and show how classroom knowledge may be applied in context discussing their adventures, struggles, and triumphs. Inviting successful entrepreneurs as guest speakers is another effective interactive method in entrepreneurship education. As one educator noted,

"we invite successful entrepreneurs as guest speakers when we have workshops or during the departmental week" (Interview EEN09).

"It is mainly for the entrepreneurship students. Now, those programmes, the conference is where we bring professional, they come to talk, give speeches, then we have what we call interactive sessions, okay? So that is one of the yardsticks. The second one is the workshops, which they are put into groups, and we try to get them to set up small businesses, and we groom them accordingly. And the last one is the exhibition, where

students are cross about 20 vocational skills, currently operating in the university. Exhibit their projects and it's not just for them to just showcase those projects.”
(Interview EEN05)

This interaction allows students to see the direct relevance of their studies and gain insights into the entrepreneurial mindset and strategic thinking necessary for success. Additionally, guest speakers can offer mentorship opportunities, answer questions, and provide feedback on student projects, further enhancing the learning experience.

4.10.3 Theme 3: Traditional Methods

The Nigerian education system is no exception to the long-standing use of traditional teaching techniques in the country's educational system. These approaches mostly consist of readings, lectures, and exams that concentrate on the theoretical underpinnings of entrepreneurship. Even though these approaches have certain drawbacks, they are crucial in helping students build a strong foundation of knowledge. The method is commonly used by universities in Nigeria when it comes to teaching entrepreneurship. This is evident in the response of educators. Five educator highlighted the reliance on theoretical instruction, stating, *"entrepreneurship the way it was taught, is strictly in theory that was taught in class"* (InterviewEEN01). *"for your undergraduate is mainly lectures"* (Interview EEN02) *"So while the lecturer is leading the teaching activity"* (Interview EEN05) *"We have the normal classroom teaching,"* (interview EEN07) *"My pedagogical approach primarily focuses on theoretical learning in the classroom,"* – (EEN09).

This method involves a structured delivery of content, where lecturers provide comprehensive insights into entrepreneurial concepts, principles, and frameworks

. However, while theoretical instruction is crucial, recent research suggests it should be complemented with practical, experiential learning to fully prepare students for entrepreneurial endeavours. Fayolle and Gailly (2015) argue that combining theoretical knowledge with hands-on experiences enhances students' entrepreneurial competencies. Neck, Greene, and Brush (2014) advocate for a practice-based approach that blends lectures with experiential activities like case studies and simulations, providing a more comprehensive educational experience and better preparing students for real-world challenges. Traditional classroom teaching remains the norm in many Nigerian universities. Despite the criticism that traditional methods may be too passive, they provide a structured framework within which students can systematically acquire knowledge. Theoretical instruction lays the groundwork for more advanced and applied

learning, making it an indispensable component of entrepreneurship education (Ghoshal, 2005). Nigerian Students can more successfully negotiate the challenges of launching and running a business if they have a solid understanding of these fundamental ideas. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of theoretical underpinnings in entrepreneurship education. For example, Nabi et al. (2017) point out that students' capacity to evaluate business circumstances critically and come to well-informed conclusions is improved by having a strong theoretical foundation.

4.11 Suggestion for Improvement of EE in Nigerian Universities

The Participant educators in their discussion made suggestions for the improvement of EE in the Nigerian context.

4.11.1 Theme 1: Community Support and Engagement

A key area identified for improving entrepreneurship education (EE) in Nigerian universities is the need for greater community support and industry engagement. Educators emphasized the importance of building stronger connections between academic institutions and business organisations aim to improve hands-on educational opportunities. As EEN05 stated,

“We need the industry to be involved... Teachers talk too much. Industry people do a lot, so we need industry to come in so that we can have more doors.” (Interview EEN05)

This shows the contribution of industry experts to teaching students about entrepreneurship in Nigerian universities, as they have ideas and experiences to share. Studies suggest that corporate partnerships teach students entrepreneurial abilities that match classroom concepts (Ratten, 2020). EEN01 further emphasized the absence of robust university-community relationships, the educator referred to the “guy making shoes” outside the university gates and pointed out that while the universities emphasize innovation, the local entrepreneur cannot relate to that since the term is not tailored to his context. EEN01 stressed the need of stronger relationships with the local community and university noting that: *“if we can introduce it, it will go a long way to improve entrepreneurship teaching.” (Interview EEN01)*. Another educator highlights this in the discussion: *“and stronger ties with the industry can enhance entrepreneurship teaching”*. (Interview EEN09)

Research supports this, indicating that partnerships between universities and local businesses enable students to gain practical experience, mentorship, and access to entrepreneurial networks, which are crucial for developing business skills in challenging environments like

Nigeria (Adebayo & Salako, 2021). EEN08 also noted the importance of government and policymakers' funding and inter-institutional competitions for good business ideas.

“The government and policymakers should encourage good business ideas through financing. Inter-institutional competitions are also advisable.” (Interview EEN08)

Competitions encourage student creativity, innovation, and teamwork, which improves entrepreneurial abilities (Mwasalwiba, 2020). Educator EEN03 brought an interesting perspective to the discussion urging that parents to be involved in EE by increasing awareness and support for entrepreneurial activity, the researcher noted that while this approach has its benefits, this may be hard in the context of university education as students are adults, and are expected to take more responsibility of their learning and career choices.

“the federal and state the university too need to engage the parents so they will know that these students will need to do entrepreneurship and the concept of teachers-parent association should come again concerning entrepreneurship so that they will enlighten them and let them know that once their children gets to year two, entrepreneurship money of fee starts and it won't be new to them”. (Interview EEN03)

However, engaging parents in educational planning has been shown to improve the outcomes of academic programmes. This is supported by Abdul et al. (2021) who note when parents are informed and engaged, they are more likely to encourage their children to participate in practical learning opportunities which is beneficial for entrepreneurship education.

4.11.2 Theme 2: Curriculum and Institutional Development

In terms of curriculum and institutional development, all the educators interviewed had suggestions to make, this was because one of the challenges they identified had to do with the curriculum limitation, repetitiveness, and limitations. Educator EEN03 suggests teaching entrepreneurship from the first to last year of university:

“It should be taught from year one to final year. Thirdly, the Nigerian government to establish entrepreneurship study skill centres in every state and each of these entrepreneurship study institutions should maintain every university directive on what they must do yearly” (interview EEN03)

This demand for specific facilities and support programmes shows that entrepreneurial education needs official infrastructure, skill development, and integration within Nigeria's educational system to succeed. Studies have also highlighted the importance of regular

curriculum updates to keep pace with industry changes and technological advancements, which are critical to maintaining student engagement and providing relevant knowledge (Pittaway & Edwards, 2012; Nabi et al., 2017). EEN07 highlighted the need for constant updates to the curriculum to ensure it remains relevant: *"When the curriculum is archaic, students will go out there and fumble."*(Interview EEN07). The educator, in addition, pointed out also pointed to the value of conferences, workshops, and seminars in bringing fresh ideas into the curriculum, adding that *"things are changing, and seminars are channelling new ways into addressing the needs of society."*(interview EEN07). This reflects the necessity for Nigeria's entrepreneurial curriculum to evolve continuously to keep pace with global trends and local market dynamics. Liguori and Winkler (2020) say an updated curriculum that reflects the trends is effective in EE as it addresses the challenges of the real environment. Furthermore, suggestions were raised concerning educator development. EEN06 raised concerns about the teaching abilities of lecturers, in response:

"Lecturers must be trained in the art of pedagogy; how to deliver lectures. Lecturers must know that the students we have are not students of the early 2000s and they're not the students of 1995". (Interview EEN06)

In the Nigerian context, where several educators have not been formally trained in teaching methods, there is a need for professional development Programmes that focus on effectively delivering materials. This is also supported by EEN02 which highlighted the need for lecturers to undergo training and gain experiences as many of them lack the real-world exposure to impart this knowledge to their students. This is seen in the response:

"For example, I was in a particular class for some time, and while taking them, I discovered that they were not paying attention to me until I started telling them what I've done and what I'm doing. That's when they started paying attention. They felt, okay, maybe you have the experience." (Interview EEN02)

As supported by past studies that show that discipline-specific entrepreneurship education increases student engagement and relevance, making the learning process more applicable to their future careers (Duval-Couetil, 2013). When students see how entrepreneurship links directly to their own field, they are more likely to be motivated and actively participate in the learning process. Additionally, Kuratko (2016) suggests ongoing professional development for educators helps them incorporate innovative pedagogical methods and stay aligned with industry expectations. Lastly, EEN04 stated, *"It should not be like the general course... It*

should be peculiar to your field of study." This proposes changing from general entrepreneurship classes to more specialist programmes that match students' academic backgrounds, which could make the subject more interesting. In response to the increased demand for universities to provide spaces for students to experiment, innovate, and get mentorship, EEN04 called for *"more equipped incubator programmes"* to help implement business ideas.

In summary, the perspectives from educators in Nigerian universities, supported by research, highlight a common theme: the need for a dynamic, continuously updated curriculum that aligns with current industry demands, connects students to practical opportunities, and ensures educators are well-equipped to deliver engaging and relevant entrepreneurship education.

4.11.3 Theme 3: Infrastructure and Resource Enhancement in Nigerian Universities

The educators repeatedly stressed the need for Nigerian universities to improve facilities and resources for entrepreneurship education. Several educators noted that poor facilities, outdated equipment, and a lack of funding hinder entrepreneurial programmes. In terms of government funding policies educator EEN05 recommended an important modification in government funding strategies, criticising the current approach, in response:

"For me, that's completely absurd, Just give universities a grant of that 30 billion and tell them to begin to form entrepreneurship clusters that produce TV monitors So distribute that money as a form of grant deliberately to universities that are performing. Then you will just see how it is only a matter of time.." (Interview EEN05)

The educator argues that instead of short-term allocations such as allocating cash for tricycles, the government should invest significantly in universities, allowing them to establish entrepreneurship clusters centered on product production. This suggestion is consistent with global research, emphasizing solid financial support and resource development to promote innovation in higher education institutions (Adebayo & Salako, 2021; Oseni, 2020). EEN06 highlighted the need to adapt teaching methodologies to suit the learning preferences of Generation Z students, stating,

"Lecturers must know that the students we have are not students of the early 2000s and they're not the students of 1995. These are high-paced students... seeing TikTok and YouTube videos." (Interview EEN06)

This underscores the importance of integrating modern technology and tools into the curriculum to engage digital-native students. Providing up-to-date resources, including digital platforms, interactive learning environments, and modern teaching equipment, is crucial for keeping students engaged and enhancing the relevance of EE (Canziani et al., 2015; Ayoade & Agwu, 2016). In addition, EEN03 points out the need for equipment to facilitate effective teaching; *"Another thing is to get us modern equipment to be able to teach them in a modern way."* The educator also suggested that practical lessons should be integrated from the later years of study to complement theory-based learning in the earlier stages. This idea supports the notion that entrepreneurship education must blend theoretical understanding and practical application (Kolb, 2014; Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

Furthermore, in terms of financial support, EEN04 and EEN02 highlight the absence of institutional mechanisms. EEN04 states that *"They should have a portal where the government itself can allow the students to have the opportunity of getting grants."* While EEN02 shared similar concerns posing a question, *"How do I get funding to start?... There's no platform for that."* Both educators note the lack of institutional structures for student grants and further training. This is a larger issue in Nigeria, where students routinely finish university without funds or skills. Grant programmes and post-graduation incubation centers have been shown to improve students' business skills (Ratten, 2020; Adeoti, 2021).

Lastly, educators EEN08 and EEN09 both highlighted the necessity of infrastructure and governmental support. EEN08 proposed the necessity of exploring alternative power sources, such as solar energy and similar options. Research is not feasible without adequate resources, as emphasized by EEN09, which advocated for increased government support through grants and policy frameworks. Studies on higher education in Nigeria consistently identify the absence of reliable electricity as a significant impediment to innovation and research (Ogundele, 2020; Adebayo & Salako, 2021). Government grants and support would furnish the essential financial foundation to fix infrastructure deficits while improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem within universities.

4.11.4 Theme 4: Policy and Institutional Alignment

The theme of policy emerged strongly in discussions with educators; they emphasized the need for a more robust creation of relevant policies that would align with the realities of EE in Nigerian Universities. Educator EEN08 focused on the impact of corruption on the education system, noting that

“if we remove corruption, maybe that's the policy that we need to be thinking about. Eradication of corruption is a policy in itself” (Interview EEN08)

This statement shows that corruption continues to be a barrier to the effective implementation of policies in Nigeria. It underscores that without addressing systemic corruption, even well-intentioned policies, particularly those related to entrepreneurship funding and support, will fail to achieve their goals (Ihugba et al., 2013; Afolabi & Macheke, 2012). Effective governance ensures that funds and resources for promoting entrepreneurship education reach their intended beneficiaries. Another educator EEN06 expressed concern over the issue of qualified educators moving from Nigeria to abroad countries in search of better working conditions, particularly among academic staff. As noted in response:

“Apart from that, it is also necessary for the government to increase the pay of lecturers generally because we now have a challenge of brain drain in most institutions. Most lecturers are now travelling abroad, what we call ‘japa’. Most of our good heads are going to Europe, they're going to America, they're going to Australia.” – (Interview EEN06)

Improved lecturer earnings could reduce the immigration of outstanding educators from Nigerian universities. Studies show that brain drain lowers education quality, especially entrepreneurship education, by removing qualified lecturers who coach and guide students (Okafor, 2020; Mbah & Nzeh, 2021). A solid university entrepreneurial culture requires retaining top intellectual talent, which can only be achieved by improving the work environment. On the other hand, EEN01 suggested the importance of current policy implementations rather than new policies. He mentioned:

“I would rather say implementing the existing policies. We have several fantastic policies to promote entrepreneurship.”(Interview EEN01)

The educator pointed out that while there are numerous seed funding initiatives and programs available on paper, the challenge lies in the implementation of these policies. This suggests that the gap between policy and practice in Nigeria’s entrepreneurship ecosystem needs to be bridged. Studies have shown that policy implementation often lags policy formulation in Nigeria, particularly when it comes to entrepreneurship education and funding (Ratten, 2020; Ogundele, 2020).

4.12 Open-Ended Survey Questions and Qualitative Insights

The studies gained a deeper understanding of how entrepreneurship education is perceived and experienced by students, using four open-ended questions that were included in the survey. These questions were designed to allow students and graduates to elaborate on their personal experiences with entrepreneurship education, including its effectiveness, the skills they developed, and the support they received from their university. The responses reveal varied opinions on the difficulties and potential of the existing EE system through rich qualitative data.

The first open-ended question focused on how well the EEPs prepared students for practical entrepreneurial situations, encouraging participants to share examples of how their education helped them address real-world challenges. This question aimed to assess whether the programmes effectively align theory and practice. Another question asked students to describe the specific institutional support they received, such as access to incubators, mentorship, and entrepreneurship centers, to capture the resources and opportunities available during their studies and how these contributed to their entrepreneurial journey. Additionally, students were asked to outline the skills or abilities they developed through participation in entrepreneurship education programmes, highlighting cognitive, analytical, leadership, and business management skills that contributed to their personal and professional growth as entrepreneurs. Lastly, students and graduates were invited to suggest improvements for entrepreneurship education at their universities, reflecting on areas such as curriculum design, access to resources, and the integration of more practical experiences. (See Appendix III)

4.12.1 Analysis of Response

The responses to these open-ended questions were analyzed using thematic analysis, following the same phased approach previously discussed in the qualitative data analysis. The earlier stages, the qualitative data from interviews with educators had already been analyzed to identify key themes, such as university support mechanisms, skills and capabilities developed, and suggestions for improvements. The responses from the open-ended survey questions align with these pre-existing themes, saving the researcher time and allowing for a more streamlined and efficient analysis process. By coding the responses, recurring themes, patterns, and insights emerged, highlighting students' perceptions of the current state of entrepreneurship education. This approach enabled the researcher to consistently compare student perspectives with those of the educators, providing a comprehensive understanding of the EE landscape in Nigerian universities.

The thematic approach, supported by previous studies (Braun & Clarke, 2006), allowed for the integration of qualitative insights from both the student survey and educator interviews. This alignment between student and educator perspectives ensured a robust interpretation of the data, facilitating actionable insights for enhancing entrepreneurship education. By following these predefined parent themes, the analysis of open-ended responses was not only systematic but also comprehensive, reinforcing the findings from the earlier stages of qualitative data analysis. This process demonstrated the effectiveness of thematic analysis in saving time and providing a structured framework for evaluating both student and educator input.

4.12.2 Discussion of Open-ended Questions

The use of open-ended questions was implemented in survey to encourage students and graduates give insight into some of their view on challenges, support systems and suggestions for improvement.

4.12.2.1 Preparedness for Real-World Entrepreneurial Challenges

Students' perspectives on how well EEPs prepared them for real-world issues differed, as shown by their responses. While many agreed that the programs gave a good starting point, they frequently lacked real-world training. As one student noted, *“the time we spend learning is too short to equip us for real-world situations.”* This suggests that while the programs offer a starting point, they fall short in bridging the gap between theory and practical business needs (Osakwe, 2021; Adebayo, 2019).

A recurring issue was the insufficient availability to institutional support, such as incubators and mentorship programs. Several students mentioned not knowing about available resources, with one stating, *“There are various places in my university to learn about skills, yet students don't know they exist because of lack of information.”* This highlights a disconnect between university intentions and student access, reflecting the need for better communication (Onuma, 2016). A key criticism was that the programmes were too theoretical, with limited practical experiences such as workshops or internships. One student emphasized, *“We are being taught the theory aspect, not the practical.”* This dissatisfaction highlights the need for more hands-on learning opportunities, such as real-world projects, to better equip students (Ekpe & Mat, 2012; Odiya & Odiya, 2020). Skills development through these programmes received mixed reviews. While some students gained practical skills like business planning and networking, others felt critical entrepreneurial skills such as leadership and decision-making were

underdeveloped. One participant noted, *“I learned hairdressing, which helped me financially during my studies,”* while others felt the programme was too focused on theory (Nwoye, 2017).

Students and graduates also offered suggestions for improvement, such as increased workshops and internships. One recommended, *“The university should offer more real-world challenges and opportunities for students to create and test business ideas.”* Better communication about resources was also emphasized, with many calling for universities to do more in promoting entrepreneurship opportunities (Izedonmi & Okafor, 2018). Overall, students felt the EEPs offered by Nigerian universities provided a good foundation but stressed the need for more practical learning and better access to resources to fully prepare them for real-world entrepreneurial challenges.

4.12.2.2 University Support for Entrepreneurship Education

Three main themes are used for analyzing the responses of students and graduates about the university resources available for entrepreneurship education: funding, infrastructure and resources, and human resource support. In terms of Funding, while some students mentioned the existence of financial support through entrepreneurship centers or grants, many felt that these opportunities were insufficient or difficult to access. One student noted, *“There’s a center for entrepreneurship development where they provide resources and sometimes financial help,”* yet such support was seen as rare. This perspective aligns with educators’ views that there are limited financial resources available to truly foster student-led businesses. Educators like EEN05 emphasized that large sums, like the *“30 billion”* mentioned in government initiatives, would be better utilized if directed into universities to establish entrepreneurship clusters. The lack of consistent funding remains a significant barrier, indicating that the financial support structures in universities do not fully meet the entrepreneurial needs of students (Olawale & Garwe, 2010). Human Resource Support emerged as another important factor, the responses of students mentioned mentorship programmes as an effective tool. Many institutions provide mentorship from experienced entrepreneurs. According to one respondent, *“Mentorship programmes are available, and they help students experience entrepreneurship in a new light.”* This supports the viewpoint of educators such as EEN01, who emphasized the value of mentorship from industry leaders in helping students connect theory with real-world application. Guest lecturers and alumni discussing their entrepreneurial adventures were also cited as significant tools, coinciding with educators' beliefs that hands-on instruction is critical for student success. However, both students and educators agreed that these mentorship opportunities are not evenly distributed, implying that not all students receive the same level

of support. This gap reflects educators' calls for more competent facilitators and deeper involvement from experienced professionals to ensure full human resource support (Neck & Corbett, 2018).

Finally, infrastructure and resources were often mentioned but needed to be developed. Several students mentioned university entrepreneurial centers, which provided practical learning resources. One student said, *"We have a dedicated entrepreneurship center with labs, although it's not fully equipped yet."* This aligns with instructors like EEN06, who stressed the necessity for current equipment and facilities for tech-savvy students. Student response also supports EEN08's need for alternative power supplies and current infrastructure to assure technology and teaching resource access. Due to a lack of finance and infrastructure, students and educators agree that entrepreneurship centers and vocational workshops are underutilized. In conclusion, some universities in Nigeria provide funds, mentorship, and infrastructure, but students and educators worry about their limitations. Both groups feel these materials are valuable but not always accessible or completely developed, limiting entrepreneurship education. To build a more robust entrepreneurial ecosystem, colleges must improve resource allocation, mentorship, and infrastructure to serve students and educators better (Neck & Corbett, 2018; Olawale & Garwe, 2010).

4.12.2.3 Skills and Abilities Developed through Entrepreneurship Education

In analyzing the skills and abilities developed through entrepreneurship education, several key themes emerged from the responses, including Cognitive and Analytical Skills, Creative and Innovative Skills, Interpersonal and Communication Skills, and Strategic and Critical Thinking Skills. These themes align with the broader goals of entrepreneurship education but also reveal gaps in the practical implementation of these programs in Nigerian universities, as evidenced by student feedback. Under the cognitive and analytical skills, such as problem-solving and making effective choices. Many students mentioned how EE helped them improve these skills. One respondent stated, *"I have developed critical and analytical thinking,"* while another claimed to have obtained *"the ability to interact with business owners and participate in teamwork."* However, several students stated that the programmes were more theoretical, limiting their capacity to use these cognitive skills in real-world circumstances properly. Educators shared these worries as well. EEN07 noted that *"when the curriculum is archaic, students will go out there and fumble,"* emphasizing the importance of modern learning frameworks that enable the actual application of cognitive skills. Kuratko (2019) supports this

gap between theory and practice by highlighting the relevance of experiential learning in enhancing cognitive abilities in EE.

Many students give examples of learning *graphic design, hair styling, and product development*. Creativity and ideas are also important. Student: *"I have developed the skill to write a business plan for sponsorship," "I learned how to make air fresheners."* These projects demonstrate entrepreneurship education's focus on skills development as EEN01 pointed it is more focused on vocational skills development. One student said, *"The course focused on business plans and presentations; I didn't learn how to innovate or grow a business."* The curriculum should include more modern entrepreneurial methods, according to EEN05, since *"students need to be exposed to entrepreneurship opportunities in their field of study, not just general opportunities."* This supports Neck and Greene (2011), who say students need creativity and innovation to succeed as entrepreneurs.

Student development was often cited in interpersonal and communication skills. Many highlighted teamwork, negotiating, and customer service. One said, *"I have developed effective communication skills, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills,"* and another said, *"I've gained skills in leadership, marketing, and public communication."* These abilities are essential for entrepreneurs who sell concepts, negotiate deals, and lead teams. Mentorship helps students *"learn how to relate with people and market their ideas."* EEN01 stressed the importance of these skills. Finally, many students said the programmes improved their strategic and analytical thinking. Entrepreneurship requires these talents to balance risk, manage resources, and make decisions that could affect the venture's success. In a response, *"I have learnt how to take calculated risks and how to grow a business,"* another said, *"strategic thinking and leadership skills."* Educators like EEN06 believe *"teaching should go beyond vocation to include strategic planning and innovation."* Gibb (2002) suggests that entrepreneurship education should emphasize critical thinking and decision-making to educate students about business's dynamic difficulties. In conclusion, students said they learned creativity, strategic thinking, and communication through entrepreneurship education, but many believed the programmes were too theoretical and lacked practical experience as they did not develop the needed skills.

4.12.2.4 Suggestion for improvements

One of the questions required students and graduates to make suggestions for the improvements of EE in Nigerian universities. Their responses were grouped under the themes: Community Engagement and Support, Curriculum and Institutional Development, Infrastructure and

Resource Enhancement, and Policy and Institutional Alignment. The need for industry and community interaction was a student concern. Many wanted more hands-on learning and mentorship from successful entrepreneurs in a response. *"We need more mentorship programs for students. Practical teachings, too, and funds should be made available to start small businesses while still university students."* This shows that participants believe practical experience outside the classroom is crucial to entrepreneurial skills. A pupil said, *"Entrepreneurship studies taught by successful businessmen and women would help because students can better internalize lessons from those who have real experience."* This fits with the educator's idea that universities should have better ties with real-life business owners to make sure that students learn about problems and solutions that happen in the real world.

Another dominant theme was the need for a more practical and innovative curriculum. Many students expressed dissatisfaction with the overly theoretical nature of their entrepreneurship courses. One student stated, *"It should be more practical. We need to learn real skills that will help us when we leave school."* Another echoed this sentiment, saying, *"The focus should be on discovering already existent skills among students and working to hone them, instead of giving us a limited range of assumed skills to work with."* Several participants recommended integrating entrepreneurship education from the first year of study and across all disciplines. One suggested, *"It should be a core curriculum for every student, with enough resources to back it up so students can see the gains and not just grades."* This sentiment is echoed by educator EEN03, who argued that entrepreneurship education should be part of the entire academic journey and revisited regularly to stay current with industry trends. Research by Fayolle (2015) also supports these claims, arguing for a more experiential, interdisciplinary approach to entrepreneurship education that goes beyond a single course.

Students repeatedly cited a need for more resources, infrastructure, and practical tools as impediments to entrepreneurship instruction. One participant said, *"They should provide more facilities and vocational options."* Another said, *"The university should create more platforms for people to practice what they are learning and make it hands-on."* These calls for better incubators, labs, and funding channels reflect instructors like EEN03, who felt that entrepreneurship education required more modern technology and facilities. EEN08 and other educators stressed the necessity for renewable energy sources like solar power to prevent learning disruptions from unpredictable electricity. Phan et al. (2021) agree that students need more cash, facilities, and equipment to develop their entrepreneurial abilities and concepts.

The responses from both students and educators reveal a strong desire for more practical, hands-on experiences in entrepreneurship education, better infrastructure and resource allocation, and stronger policy alignment to support entrepreneurial initiatives.

4.13 Summary of chapter

This chapter examined the qualitative responses from both educators and student regarding EE in Nigerian universities, aligning with the research objectives. Several key themes emerged from the definition and role of EE, challenges faced by educators, students' skills and capabilities, teaching methods, and suggestions for improvement. Educators emphasized the role of EE in fostering entrepreneurial mindsets. However, many challenges were highlighted. Educators noted the lack of practical experience and inadequate infrastructure as significant obstacles, while students echoed concerns about the overly theoretical nature of their programs. Regarding skills and capabilities, while some students recognized the development of skills such as problem-solving and creativity, many felt their learning was limited. The need for more hands-on experience was a recurring theme, with both groups advocating for more practical teaching methods, mentorship programmes, and real-world exposure.

Lastly, suggestions for improvement included the following: Revising the curriculum to integrate more practical components, increasing government and institutional support, and improving university-industry collaboration to better prepare students for real-world entrepreneurial challenges. In conclusion, educators, students, and graduates believe that EE must focus more on practical learning and adding resources to bridge theory and practice.

CHAPTER FIVE

QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the results from the second stage of data collection. The findings of the quantitative study conducted with students and graduates from Nigerian universities will be shared. This section is divided into six sections: the response rate, the respondent demographics, and an initial evaluation of the data in anticipation of more analysis.

The initial analysis mostly comprises reliability tests and descriptive statistics. The information about the consent, demographics, academic status and background, entrepreneurial intentions, and participants' experience in this study are discussed. The next step shown is the demonstration of the reliability tests carried out on the survey instruments and the descriptive data of the variables measured in the study namely (the entrepreneurial intentions, Exposure to entrepreneurship education, perceived university support, teaching methods, entrepreneurial skills, and knowledge). The other sections support the study's goals and research hypotheses, and the conclusion provides a summary of all the data.

5.1 Restatement of Research Questions

The quantitative analysis in this study aimed to contribute to the main objective of investigating how EEPs in Nigerian universities influence students' entrepreneurial intentions, with a focus on teaching methods and perceived university support. The RQ4: *What are the teaching approaches most effective for teaching entrepreneurship in Nigerian Universities?* was addressed through four hypotheses.

- H1 proposed that students who perceive higher university support and more engaging teaching methods would exhibit more positive attitudes and stronger entrepreneurial intentions.
- H2 examined whether increased university support and effective teaching methods would enhance students' subjective norms, fostering social acceptance of entrepreneurship.
- H3 posited that greater university support and interactive teaching methods could improve students' perceived behavioural control, and

- H4 suggested that stronger university support and engaging teaching methods would lead to more positive behavioural intentions toward entrepreneurial activities. These hypotheses were designed to explore the effectiveness of teaching methods and institutional support in fostering entrepreneurial intentions among students.

The RQ5: *How can entrepreneurship education in Nigeria be improved to be more effective in developing the required entrepreneurial skills and the entrepreneurial intention of students?* was explored through H5. This hypothesis proposed that interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence students' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, ultimately shaping their entrepreneurial intentions. The results will be presented later in the chapter.

5.2 . Response Rate and Initial Screening

This quantitative study's primary data was gathered through a survey conducted among students and graduates, using a questionnaire that consisted of 24 questions (Refer to appendix IV). After conducting a pilot study, the survey was revised based on feedback from participants and suggestions from the supervisory team. These revisions included correcting typographical errors, clarifying ambiguous questions, eliminating redundant items, and reducing the length of the survey to enhance clarity and effectiveness. Out of the 308 responses collected, 306 were completed and consented, making them valid for analysis (refer to Appendix III for the Information consent form). The data collection was carried out using Microsoft Forms, ensuring precise data capture and reducing potential errors. The completed dataset was subsequently imported into SPSS software for comprehensive data coding, cleaning, and statistical analysis.

Given the survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms, it was also necessary to assess the overall experience from the participant's viewpoint. The pilot also enabled some modifications in the formatting and the appearance of the questions to ascertain their proper display on the various platforms and equipment used and these included testing the flow of the survey. This also entailed verifying how questions looked on different screens, including the smartphone screen, tablet screen, and computer screen, to ensure that all the participants saw similar screens. As a result, some modifications were made to improve clarity, readability, and overall respondent participation while finalizing the version of the questionnaire as suitable for obtaining valid and reliable data from the target sample.

As pilot was concluded, the participants were given opportunity provide feedback to identify any issues, concerns, or errors, which were then communicated to the researcher. A few typographical errors were identified, and graduates highlighted challenges such as questions being tagged as compulsory, even when they did not apply to them. This led the researcher to review questions that were tagged compulsory. Also, the inclusion of an additional response option "Not sure/I don't have enough information to answer" in Question 15. Additionally, the students encouraged the use of open-ended questions at the end of the survey to allow for more detailed responses and personal insights. These valuable suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire, ensuring that it was both comprehensive and user-friendly.

5.2.1 Missing Values

In this study, missing values were effectively minimized due to the structure and administration of the questionnaire via Microsoft Forms. Specifically, in Part B of the survey, which focused on key variables such as Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods/Pedagogy, Personal Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control, and Entrepreneurial Intention, the questions were tagged as important and compulsory. This design choice was intentional to ensure that respondents provided complete data on these critical constructs. Answering these questions was mandatory since the survey platform did not allow a respondent to complete the survey without answering all the questions. This feature was a significant improvement in as much as it reduced the chances of missing data for these important variables.

This approach aligns well with the limits of items missed in the surveys because prior research states that proper survey design should suppress the levels of missing data. For example, Zhang et al. (2013) suggest that issuing compulsory questions in web-based surveys can help minimize non-response rates and so increase the level of finished data collected. Furthermore, Couper (2008) points out that there are always effective controls provided one sets the survey tools rightly, where key data points are well captured in the survey exercise, improving the quality of the collected data. Although this approach greatly reduced cases of missing values for the main variables of interest, in instances where missing data is present, it will be handled under the demographic section of this thesis. This makes for well-rounded paperwork of the dataset and leaves no room for slips in information acquisition from the respondents.

5.3 Demographics of the Respondents

The study's sample characteristics are detailed in detail using demographic data. The demographic data included age, gender, academic status and background, entrepreneurial intentions, and participants' experience. The demographic details of the survey participants can guide further analysis of their entrepreneurial intentions.

Table 21: Table showing the Consent of Participant

Consent of study participant					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	306	99.4	99.4	99.4
	No	2	.6	.6	100.0
Total		308	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 21 above shows the consent status of participants in the study. Out of 308 participants, 99% gave their consent to be part of the study. This strong response suggests that most participants were willing to engage with the research, which is a positive sign for the study's credibility. The 0.6% who chose not to consent represents a very small portion of the group. The "Valid Percent" and "Cumulative Percent" columns back up these figures, showing that 99% of those who responded were consenting, with the cumulative percentage reaching 100% when including the non-consenting participants. Overall, this data shows the study had a very high response rate, meaning the results are likely to be representative of the larger population.

Table 22: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	196	63.6	64.1	64.1
	26-35	91	29.5	29.7	93.8
	36-45	17	5.5	5.6	99.3
	46 and above	2	.6	.7	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 22 above gives an overview of the age distribution of participants of study. Most participants, 196 individuals, fall within the 18-25 age range, making up 64% of the valid responses. This age group dominates the sample, suggesting that younger adults were the primary demographic involved in the study. The next largest group is participants aged 26-35,

with 30% of the valid responses. Smaller numbers of participants are found in the older age groups. 6% are in the 36-45 age range, and just (0.6%) were 46 years old or above. This is illustrated in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Age Distribution of respondents

Table 23: Table of Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Woman	153	49.7	50.0	50.0
	Man	150	48.7	49.0	99.0
	prefer not to say	3	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 23 above displays the gender distribution of participants in the study. The participants are evenly split between women and men, with women, representing 50% of the sample, and men, representing 49%. This near-equal distribution suggests that the study's findings likely reflect perspectives from both genders relatively equally. Additionally, participants, making up 1% of the sample, preferred not to disclose their gender. The gender distribution is illustrated in figure below:

Figure 8: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Table 24: Educational Level of Respondents

Enrollment status		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Undergraduate student	190	61.7	62.1	62.1
	Taught postgraduate student (Master's degree)	13	4.2	4.2	66.3
	Research Postgraduate (Doctorate e.g PhD)	10	3.2	3.3	69.6
	No- I am a graduate	93	30.2	30.4	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
	Total	308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 24 above summarizes the enrolment status of the study participants. Most of the participants, (62%) are undergraduate students, indicating that a significant portion of the study sample is currently engaged in undergraduate education. This group constitutes the largest category within the study. The next group is composed of graduates, making up 30% of the total. This suggests that nearly a third of the sample has already completed their studies, which may influence their perspectives or experiences differently compared to current students. Smaller groups include taught postgraduate students (master's degree) with 4%, and research postgraduate students (such as those pursuing a Ph.D.), having 3%. These groups together represent a minority of the sample, indicating that fewer participants are involved in advanced levels of study. This is illustrated in bar chart below:

Figure 9: Education level of Respondents

Table 25: Time Since Graduation (For Graduates Only)

Graduation timeline		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-2 years	68	22.1	44.4	44.4
	2-5 years	37	12.0	24.2	68.6
	5 years and above	48	15.6	31.4	100.0
	Total	153	49.7	100.0	
Missing	System	155	50.3		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 25 above provides an overview of how long it has been since the study's graduate participants completed their degrees. 22% of graduates completed their studies within the last 0-2 years, accounting for 44% of the valid responses. Another 12% graduated 2-5 years ago, representing 24% of the valid responses. Meanwhile, 16% graduated more than 5 years ago, making up 31% of the valid responses. The table also notes that participants 50% are who did not respond includes students who have not yet graduated and others who did not consent to the study. In total, there were 50% of the total sample. This distribution highlights that a significant portion of the participants recently completed their studies, while a smaller group graduated several years ago, providing a range of perspectives based on the recency of their educational experiences.

Table 26: Distribution of Study Participants by University Ownership

University ownership		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Public (Federal-owned)	191	62.0	62.6	62.6
	Public (State-owned)	54	17.5	17.7	80.3
	Private (individual-owned)	44	14.3	14.4	94.8
	Private (religious-owned)	16	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	305	99.0	100.0	
Missing	System	3	1.0		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 26 above provides a breakdown of the types of institutions attended by the study participants. Results showed 62% of the total sample, were from public universities that are federally owned. This group represents 63% of the valid responses. The next largest group consists of participants from state-owned public universities, with 18%, accounting for 18% of the valid responses. In contrast, 14% attended private universities that are individually owned, making up 14% of the valid responses. The smallest group, 5%, is from religiously owned private universities, representing 5% of the valid responses. Overall, the table reveals that most participants are enrolled in federally owned public universities, with a smaller representation from state-owned public, individually owned private, and religiously owned private institutions. This distribution is important for understanding the diversity of educational backgrounds among the participants and how these differences might influence their perspectives within the study, this is illustrated below;

Figure 10: University ownership distribution of respondents

Table 27: Programme Category of Participants

Programme category		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Arts and Humanities degree	85	27.6	27.8	27.8
	Business management Studies and Law [i.e Business Management, Accounting, Finance, Marketing, HRM, Law, Legal Studies, Entrepreneurship, etc]	19	6.2	6.2	34.0
	Engineering and Technology	38	12.3	12.4	46.4
	Social Sciences	46	14.9	15.0	61.4
	Life sciences and Health sciences	67	21.8	21.9	83.3
	Other-Specify in next question	51	16.6	16.7	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 27 above provides a detailed breakdown of the academic disciplines in which the study participants are enrolled. The largest group of participants pursuing degrees in Arts and Humanities accounted for 28% of the total sample and 29% of the valid responses. This indicates a strong representation of students from these fields in the study. The Business Management, Studies, and Law category, which includes programs such as Business Management, Accounting, Finance, Marketing, HRM, Law, Legal Studies, and Entrepreneurship, had 6% of both the total sample and the valid responses. Engineering and

Technology follows with 12% of the total and 12% of the valid responses, highlighting another key area of study among participants. Social Sciences are also well-represented, with 15% of the total sample, contributing 15% to the valid responses. Life Sciences and Health Sciences are another major field, with 29% of the total accounting for 22% of the valid responses. This shows that a significant portion of the participants are engaged in science and health-related studies. Finally, the "Other" category, which participants were asked to specify in the next question, includes 17% of the total sample and 17% of the valid responses. This category reflects a variety of other academic disciplines not listed individually in the table.

Table 28: Programme Level of Study Participants (Students)

Level		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Undergraduate First year	16	5.2	7.5	7.5
	Undergraduate Second year	39	12.7	18.3	25.8
	Undergraduate Third year	59	19.2	27.7	53.5
	Undergraduate fourth year	21	6.8	9.9	63.4
	Undergraduate Final year	52	16.9	24.4	87.8
	Postgraduate first year	12	3.9	5.6	93.4
	Postgraduate second year	5	1.6	2.3	95.8
	Postgraduate third year	3	1.0	1.4	97.2
	Postgraduate fourth year	6	1.9	2.8	100.0
	Total	213	69.2	100.0	
	Missing System	95	30.8		
Total	308	100.0			

Source: Researcher, 2024

The table 28 above summarizes the distribution of respondents across different educational levels, indicating that the majority are undergraduate students, particularly in their third year (19%) and final year (17%). Postgraduate students are less represented, with the first-year postgraduate level being the most common at 4%. Notably, the table also reveals 31% categorized as "System" missing data. This missing data is likely due to respondents who are graduates and therefore did not have a current academic level to report. This high percentage of missing data could have implications for the analysis and interpretation of the study's findings. The programme level is illustrated in figure 11 below:

Figure 11: Programme level distribution of respondents

Table 29: Participants' Consideration of Running Their Own Business

Business consideration		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes - in the near future	156	50.6	51.0	51.0
	Yes - in the distant future	26	8.4	8.5	59.5
	No, not at all.	18	5.8	5.9	65.4
	I already am	84	27.3	27.5	92.8
	I have in the past but don't currently run a business	22	7.1	7.2	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
	Total	308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 29 above provides insights into how participants view the prospect of running their own business. A significant portion of the participants, 51% of the total sample, expressed that they are considering starting a business in the near future. This group represents the majority, making up 51% of the valid responses, indicating a strong interest in entrepreneurship within the sample. In addition, 8% of the total indicated that they are considering starting a business, but only in the distant future. This category represents 9% of the valid responses, showing that while the desire to start a business is present, some participants are not planning to take immediate action.

A smaller group of 6% of the total reported no interest in running a business, representing 6% of the valid responses. This suggests that a minority of participants do not have entrepreneurial intentions. A notable portion of the sample, 27% of the total, are already running their businesses. This group accounts for 28% of the valid responses, demonstrating that over a quarter of the participants have direct entrepreneurial experience. Additionally, 7% of the total have previously run a business but are not currently involved in one. This group represents 7% of the valid responses, reflecting that some participants have had past entrepreneurial experiences but are not actively engaged in business at present. This is illustrated below:

Figure 12: Business Consideration of distribution of respondents

Table 30: Family Involvement in Business Ownership

Family Business		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes, my Parents.	174	56.5	56.9	56.9
	Yes, my siblings	51	16.6	16.7	73.5
	Yes, my grandparents	1	.3	.3	73.9
	Yes, other relatives	37	12.0	12.1	85.9
	No, nobody in my family owns a business	43	14.0	14.1	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
	Total	308	100.0		

Source: researcher, 2024

Table 30 above provides a breakdown of participants' responses to whether anyone in their family owns or runs their own business. Most participants 57% of the total sample, indicated that their parents own or run a business. This group represents 57% of the valid responses, suggesting that parental involvement in business is a common experience among the participants. In addition, 17% of the total reported that their siblings own or run a business. This accounts for 17% of the valid responses, indicating that a significant portion of participants also have siblings involved in entrepreneurial activities. Only 0.3% of the total mentioned that their grandparents own or run a business, which is a minimal representation within the sample. Another 12% of the total stated that other relatives, apart from their immediate family, are involved in business ownership or management. This group represents 12% of the valid responses. On the other hand, 14% of the total participants indicated that nobody in their family owns a business. This group accounts for 14% of the valid responses, reflecting that a minority of participants come from non-entrepreneurial family backgrounds. Overall, the table reveals that a significant portion of participants have members of the family who are actively engaged in business, notably parents, may have an impact on their entrepreneurial intentions and perspectives.

Table 31: Prior Experience in Running a Business Before Attending Entrepreneurship Course

Prior experience		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	I had no prior experience in running a business	89	28.9	29.1	29.1
	I had limited experience in running a business	94	30.5	30.7	59.8
	I had moderate experience in running a business	78	25.3	25.5	85.3
	I had extensive experience in running a business	17	5.5	5.6	90.8
	I'm unsure / I don't have enough information to answer	28	9.1	9.2	100.0
	Total	306	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	2	.6		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 31 above shows an overview of experience the participant had prior to attending an entrepreneurship educational course or program. The largest group, comprising 31% of the total sample reported having limited experience in running a business. This group accounts for

31% of the valid responses, indicating that many participants had some, but not extensive, exposure to business management before the course. A significant portion of participants, 29% of the total, indicated that they had no prior experience in running a business. This group makes up 29% of the valid responses, suggesting that a substantial number of participants were new to entrepreneurship when they joined the program.

Another 25% of the total had moderate experience in running a business, representing 26% of the valid responses. This indicates that a quarter of the participants entered the course with a fair amount of business experience. A smaller group, 6% of the total, reported having extensive experience in running a business, accounting for 6% of the valid responses. This group represents those with significant entrepreneurial backgrounds. Finally, 9% of the total were unsure or felt they did not have enough information to answer the question accurately. This group makes up 9% of the valid responses. The table reveals that participants had varied levels of business experience before attending the entrepreneurship course, with a mix of no, limited, moderate, and extensive experience among them.

Table 32: Nature of Business Experience (Own Business vs. Another's Business)

Business ownership		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	My business	148	48.1	53.8	53.8
	Another person's business	57	18.5	20.7	74.5
	Family business	40	13.0	14.5	89.1
	Both my own business and that of another person/ the family business	30	9.7	10.9	100.0
	Total	275	89.3	100.0	
Missing	System	33	10.7		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 32 above the breakdown of the types of business ownership among the study participants. The largest group, consisting of 48% of the total sample, reported owning their own business. This group represents 54% of the valid responses, indicating that over half of the participants have direct experience with running their own business. Another significant portion of participants, 19% of the total, are involved in managing another person's business. This group accounts for 21% of the valid responses, suggesting that a notable number of participants have managerial or operational roles in businesses they do not own. In addition, 13% of the total are involved in a family business, making up 15% of the valid responses. This indicates that family-

owned businesses are a common form of business involvement among the participants. A smaller group of 10% of the total reported that they are involved in both their own business and another person's or family business. This group constitutes 11% of the valid responses, reflecting a subset of participants who juggle multiple business roles.

Table 33: Engagement in Business-Related Training/Education During University

Entrepreneurship training		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	None	94	30.5	31.3	31.3
	Minimal (1-2 workshops or courses)	129	41.9	43.0	74.3
	Some (3-5 workshops or courses)	43	14.0	14.3	88.7
	Substantial (6 or more workshops or courses)	9	2.9	3.0	91.7
	Unsure / I don't have enough information to answer	25	8.1	8.3	100.0
	Total	300	97.4	100.0	
Missing	System	8	2.6		
Total		308	100.0		

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 33 above provides an overview of the extent to which participants have engaged in training or education directly related to running and growing their businesses during their time at university. The largest group of participants, 42% of the total sample, reported having minimal engagement in business-related training, which they defined as attending 1-2 workshops or courses. This group accounts for 43% of the valid responses, indicating that while many participants have had some exposure to entrepreneurship education, the extent of this training has generally been limited.

A significant portion of participants, 31% of the total, reported having no engagement in business-related training or education at all during their university studies. This group constitutes 31% of the valid responses, highlighting that nearly a third of the participants have not participated in any entrepreneurship-related training while at university. Another 14% of the total indicated that they had engaged in some training, attending 3-5 workshops or courses. This group makes up 14% of the valid responses, reflecting a moderate level of engagement in EE among these participants.

A smaller group, 3% of the total, reported substantial engagement in business-related training, attending 6 or more workshops or courses. This group represents 3% of the valid responses, indicating that only a few participants have had extensive entrepreneurship education during their university studies. Finally, 8% of the total were unsure or felt they did not have enough information to accurately answer the question. This group accounts for 8% of the valid responses, reflecting some uncertainty among participants regarding their level of engagement in business-related training.

5.4 Reliability Tests

The consistency or stability of a measurement instrument in research is referred to as reliability, ensuring that the results it produces are dependable over time and across different conditions. In quantitative research, reliability is crucial because it determines whether the measurement tool accurately captures the constructs being studied. A commonly used indicator of reliability is Cronbach's Alpha, which assesses the internal consistency of a set of items or scales. Values above 0.7 generally indicate acceptable reliability, meaning the items reliably measure the same construct (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). In this study, the reliability of key variables Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods and Pedagogy, Personal Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural Control, Subjective Norm, and Entrepreneurial Intentions were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha. The results indicated high reliability for most variables. Perceived University Support achieved a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.921, while Teaching Methods and Pedagogy recorded 0.929, demonstrating strong internal consistency. Personal Attitudes and Perceived Behavioural Control also showed reliable scores, with 0.752 and 0.837, respectively. Subjective Norm had a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.702, and Entrepreneurial Intentions scored 0.860, both indicating acceptable reliability.

These results confirm that the variables used in this study are reliable, meaning the instruments consistently measured the intended constructs, ensuring that the findings based on these measures are robust and dependable.

5.4.1 Cronbach's Alpha Test

Cronbach's Alpha is a common statistical method used to check how reliable or consistent a set of questions or test items is. The test is especially helpful in fields like social sciences, psychology, and education to see if a group of items accurately measures one specific concept (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011). This technique is used to analyze the variable items to test if they are reliable or not reliable. The analysis for this study is shown on the table 34 below.

Table 34: Reliability Test using Cronbach's Alpha Test

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	No. of Items
Perceived University support	.921	8
Teaching Methods and Pedagogy	.929	10
Personal Attitudes	.752	5
Perceived Behavioural Control	.837	5
Subjective Norm	.702	3
Entrepreneurial Intentions	.860	6

Source: Researcher, 2014

Table 34 above displays the reliability test results for the key constructs in the study, measured using Cronbach's Alpha. This statistic is widely recognized for assessing the internal consistency of a set of items, with higher values indicating better reliability.

The construct of *Perceived University Support* showed strong internal consistency, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha of .921 across 8 items. This high value suggests that the items within this scale are closely related and consistently measure the intended concept. Similarly, *Teaching Methods and Pedagogy* demonstrated excellent reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha of .929 for its 10 items, indicating that the construct is being measured in a very consistent manner.

The third variable *Personal Attitudes* showed an acceptable level of reliability, with a Cronbach's Alpha of .752 across 5 items. While this is lower than the previous constructs, it still falls within the acceptable range (generally considered to be .7 and above), suggesting that the items are reasonably consistent in measuring the construct (Ursachi, Horodnic, & Zait, 2015). The reliability of *Perceived Behavioral Control* was also good, with a Cronbach's Alpha of .837 for its 5 items, reflecting a solid internal consistency. The variable *Subjective Norm* reached a Cronbach's Alpha of .702 across 3 items. This indicates that while the reliability is acceptable, there may still be room for improvement. It's not uncommon for constructs related to social influence to show lower reliability, as these can be more complex and subject to varying interpretations (Field, 2018).

Finally, the construct of *Entrepreneurial Intentions* demonstrated strong reliability, with a Cronbach's Alpha of .860 across 6 items. This suggests that the items effectively capture the respondents' intentions regarding entrepreneurship, which is crucial for the study's focus. In summary, most of the constructs in this study exhibit good to excellent reliability, supporting their use in further analysis. The consistency of these measures aligns well with the standards suggested by Nunnally (1978), who recommended a minimum Cronbach's Alpha of .7 for exploratory research (Taber, 2018; Cho and Kim, 2015).

5.4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Main Instrument

The summary statistics of the key entrepreneurship instruments based on the perceptions and preferences of the respondents, measured using a 7-point Likert scale (with '1' representing "Strongly Disagree" and '7' representing "Strongly Agree" for most questions). It is important to note that the midpoint '4' on the Likert scale, which indicates a neutral or undecided response, was excluded from the analysis to avoid ambiguity and better capture the respondents' true attitudes and intentions (DeVellis, 2017). The five key instruments that are central to understanding the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions among students in Nigerian universities will be analyzed. The instruments examined include Entrepreneurial Intentions, Subjective Norms, personal Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural Control, Perceived University Support, and Teaching Methods/Pedagogy. For each of these constructs, the mean, standard deviation, and range are calculated and discussed in detail.

The analysis is crucial for addressing the study's primary research objectives. The main goal to assess the influence of EE on students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigerian universities.

This involves exploring how Perceived University Support and Teaching Methods/Pedagogy influence students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurial activities. Understanding these relationships will shed light on how well current educational practices are fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students. The second objective is to identify the factors that influence students' entrepreneurial intentions. This includes examining the roles of Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control, and Personal Attitudes. Personal Attitudes towards entrepreneurship are particularly important, as they reflect students' overall disposition toward becoming entrepreneurs. The interplay between these attitudes and other factors, such as social influence and perceived self-efficacy, is critical to understanding what drives or hinders students' entrepreneurial ambitions.

Table 35: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived_university_s upport	306	1.00	7.00	3.6658	1.54687
Teaching_Methods	306	1.00	7.00	4.3458	1.57484
Personal_Attitudes	306	1.00	7.00	4.6967	1.35213
Perceived_behavioural_ control	306	1.00	7.00	4.4961	1.53706
Subjective_Norm	306	1.00	7.00	4.2407	1.68086
Entrepreneurial_intenti ons	306	1.00	7.00	4.5991	1.56649
Valid N (listwise)	306				

Source: Researcher, 2024

The summary statistics for the main variables in this analysis provides a snapshot of students' perceptions and attitudes toward entrepreneurship education. These variables Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods, Personal Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural Control, Subjective Norms, and Entrepreneurial Intentions were all measured on a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). The first was Perceived University Support (PUS), which had a mean score was $M=3.67$, suggesting that students, on average, felt slightly below neutral in terms of the support they perceived from their universities. This finding aligns with recent studies that emphasize the variability of perceived support across different educational institutions, which can significantly impact student outcomes (Pittaway & Cope, 2017). The standard deviation of $SD=1.55$ indicates moderate variability in responses, with some students feeling well-supported while others perceived much less support.

The second variable *Teaching Methods (TM)* had a mean score of $M=4.35$, indicating that students generally held a positive view of the teaching approaches employed in their entrepreneurship courses. This suggests that, on average, students find the methods used by their instructors to be effective in conveying entrepreneurial concepts and skills. However, the standard deviation of $SD= 1.57$ points to a notable level of variability in students' perceptions. This variability indicates that while some students may have found the teaching methods highly effective, others might have been less satisfied. When examining the third variable *Personal Attitudes (PA)* towards entrepreneurship, the mean score was higher at $M=4.70$. This indicates a generally favourable attitude among students towards becoming entrepreneurs, a trend that has been observed in other recent studies focusing on entrepreneurial intentions in educational settings (Souitaris, Zerbinati, & Al-Laham, 2007). The lower standard deviation of $SD=1.35$ suggests that there is relatively less variation in these responses, implying a stronger consensus among students about their positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship.

For *Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC)*, the mean of $M=4.50$ suggests that students generally feel moderately confident in their ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The standard deviation of $SD= 1.54$ indicates moderate variability, suggesting that confidence levels vary somewhat among students. When examining *Subjective Norms (SN)*, the result shows it had the lowest mean score at $M=4.24$, indicating that students felt only slightly influenced by the opinions of others when it came to their entrepreneurial decisions. The higher standard deviation of $SD=1.68$ suggests considerable variability in these perceptions, which may reflect differing social and cultural contexts among the student population. Recent research also indicates that the effect of subjective norms on entrepreneurial intentions can vary widely depending on the cultural setting (Liñán & Chen, 2009). Finally, *Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI)* had a mean score of 4.60, indicating a generally positive inclination among students toward pursuing entrepreneurship. The standard deviation of $SD=1.57$ reflects some diversity in these intentions, which according to Entrialgo and Iglesias (2018) could be influenced by various factors such as perceived opportunities, personal motivation, and the support systems available. Table 36 provides a detailed description of statistics for the key variables in this study, including skewness and kurtosis measures, which offer insights into the distributional characteristics of the data.

Table 36: Descriptive Statistics Showing the Skewness and Kurtosis of Variables

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
				Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Perceived_university_s support	306	3.6658	1.54687	-.034	.139	-.918	.278
Teaching_Methods	306	4.3458	1.57484	-.516	.139	-.590	.278
Personal_Attitudes	306	4.6967	1.35213	-1.002	.139	.542	.278
Perceived_behavioural_ control	306	4.4961	1.53706	-.773	.139	-.166	.278
Subjective_Norm	306	4.2407	1.68086	-.313	.139	-.738	.278
Entrepreneurial_intenti ons	306	4.5991	1.56649	-.895	.139	-.147	.278
Valid N (listwise)	306						

Source: Survey results, 2024

The skewness and kurtosis values in the table help the researcher understand the shape of the data distributions for the six key variables in this study. Skewness indicates whether the data leans more to the left or right of the mean. A skewness value close to zero suggests the data is symmetrical (Mishra et al., 2019). In this study, most variables show negative skewness, meaning more students rated these variables on the higher end of the scale. For instance, Personal Attitudes has a skewness of (-1.002), suggesting that many students have a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship. Similarly, Entrepreneurial Intentions show a skewness of (-0.895), indicating strong entrepreneurial intentions among students. On the other hand, Perceived University Support has a skewness of (-0.034), almost zero, indicating that students' views on university support are more evenly split between positive and negative.

Kurtosis on the other hand, measures how peaked or flat the distribution is compared to a normal distribution. A kurtosis close to zero indicates a normal distribution (DeCarlo, 1997). In this study, several variables, such as Perceived University Support (-0.918) and Subjective Norms (-0.738), have negative kurtosis values, meaning their distributions are flatter than normal, with fewer extreme responses. This suggests a wide range of opinions among students. Conversely, Personal Attitudes has a positive kurtosis value (0.542), indicating that the distribution is more peaked, with responses clustered more tightly around the mean. This shows that while many students share a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship, there are also some extreme opinions, either very positive or very negative. The summary of the mean of each variable used is presented below:

Figure 13: Mean Perceived University Support by Enrolment Status

Figure 13 above shows the mean perceived university support (PercUniS) across different enrolment statuses. Undergraduate students reported the highest mean score (close to 4.0), indicating a stronger perception of support. Postgraduate students (both taught and research) and graduates reported slightly lower mean scores, around 3.0, suggesting a more moderate perception of support from the university.

Figure 14: mean of Teaching Methods by Enrolment Status

The figure 14 above shows the mean score of TeachMet across different enrolment statuses. Undergraduate students had the highest mean score, close to 4.5, indicating a more positive view of the teaching methods. Research postgraduate students followed closely, while taught postgraduate students had a lower mean score, just above 4.0. Graduates reported similar perceptions to research postgraduates, showing moderate satisfaction with teaching methods.

Figure 15: Mean Personal Attitudes by Enrolment Status

The figure 15 above shows the mean score of personal attitudes toward entrepreneurship (PersAtt) across different enrolment statuses. The scores are relatively consistent across groups, with all categories (undergraduate, postgraduate, and graduates) reporting similar mean scores, close to 4.5. This suggests that students and graduates across all levels generally have a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship, with no major differences in perception based on their enrolment status.

Figure 16: Mean Perceived Behavioural Control by Enrolment Status

The figure 16 above illustrates the mean score of PerCtrl across different enrolment statuses. Taught postgraduate student report the highest mean score, just above 4.5, indicating a higher level of confidence in their ability to control entrepreneurial behaviour. Undergraduate students and graduates follow closely, with scores slightly above 4.0, while research postgraduate students (Doctorate) report a slightly lower mean score, just below 4.5. This suggests that students across all levels generally feel they have control over entrepreneurial actions, but with minor variations based on their enrolment status.

Figure 17: Mean subjective Norms by Enrolment Status

The figure17 shows the mean score of SubNorm across different enrolment statuses. Taught postgraduate students report the highest score, just above 4.0, followed by undergraduates, research postgraduates, and graduates, who all have similar scores slightly below 4.0. This suggests relatively consistent perceptions of social pressure to engage in entrepreneurial activities across the groups.

Figure 18: Mean Entrepreneurial Intentions by Enrolment Status

Figure 18 above shows the mean score of Entrepre across different enrolment statuses. The mean scores are consistent across groups, with all categories (undergraduate, postgraduate, and graduates) reporting scores around 4.5. This suggests that students and graduates across all levels have a similarly strong intention to pursue entrepreneurship, regardless of their enrolment status.

5.5 Correlation Analysis

The statistical approach of correlation analysis is employed to ascertain the existence and potential strength of a relationship between two variables or datasets. In this study, the relationships between key variables that influence entrepreneurial intentions among students in Nigerian universities are examined. By identifying the strength and direction of associations between variables such as Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods, Personal Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural Control, Subjective Norms, and Entrepreneurial Intentions.

By conducting a Correlation analysis for this study, we get an understanding of how these factors influence them and the probability of the students engaging in entrepreneurial activities. This analysis is important to determine how these variables are related and to use this knowledge in designing proper frameworks for improving education results in terms of promoting the proper entrepreneurial skills and intentions. The Correlation analysis on the variables will be shown in the matrix's below.

Table 37: Correlation Matrix of Study Variables

Correlations		Percieved_un iversity_sup port	Teaching_M ethods	Personal Att itudes	Percieved_be havioural_co ntrol	Subjective_N orm	Entrepreneur ial_intention s
Percieved_university_s upport	Pearson Correlation	1	.531 ^{***}	.299 ^{***}	.310 ^{***}	.330 ^{***}	.326 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306
Teaching_Methods	Pearson Correlation	.531 ^{***}	1	.464 ^{**}	.503 ^{***}	.410 ^{**}	.455 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306
Personal_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.299 ^{***}	.464 ^{**}	1	.733 ^{***}	.609 ^{***}	.770 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306
Percieved_behavioural_ control	Pearson Correlation	.310 ^{***}	.503 ^{**}	.733 ^{**}	1	.667 ^{**}	.791 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306
Subjective_Norm	Pearson Correlation	.330 ^{***}	.410 ^{**}	.609 ^{***}	.667 ^{**}	1	.704 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306
Entrepreneurial_intenti ons	Pearson Correlation	.326 ^{***}	.455 ^{**}	.770 ^{**}	.791 ^{***}	.704 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	306	306	306	306	306	306

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher, 2024

The correlation matrix provides an in-depth analysis of the relationships between the core variables of this study, including Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods/Pedagogy, Personal Attitudes, Perceived Behavioural Control, Subjective Norms, and Entrepreneurial Intentions. Pearson correlation coefficients are employed to measure the strength and direction of these linear relationships, with significance levels indicating the robustness of the findings.

Perceived University Support:

The correlation between Perceived University Support and Entrepreneurial Intentions ($r = .326$, $p < .001$) is moderate and positive, suggesting that students who perceive higher levels of support from their universities are more likely to develop strong intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. This relationship highlights the importance of university resources,

mentorship, and encouragement in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students. Additionally, Perceived University Support shows a strong correlation with Teaching Methods/Pedagogy ($r = .531, p < .001$), indicating that students who perceive greater university support are also more likely to experience engaging and effective teaching methods. This finding underscores the integrated role of institutional support and pedagogical quality in shaping students' educational experiences.

Moreover, the positive correlations between Perceived University Support and other variables such as Personal Attitudes ($r = .299, p < .001$), Perceived Behavioural Control ($r = .310, p < .001$), and Subjective Norms ($r = .330, p < .001$) suggest that university support not only directly influences entrepreneurial intentions but also enhances students' confidence, attitudes, and perceived social expectations towards entrepreneurship. These moderate correlations reflect the multifaceted role of university support in influencing various psychological and social factors that contribute to entrepreneurial intentions.

Teaching Methods/Pedagogy:

The analysis shows a moderate to strong positive correlation between Teaching Methods and Entrepreneurial Intentions ($r = .455, p < .001$). This relationship indicates that when students perceive their EE as engaging and well-structured, they are more likely to develop strong intentions to pursue entrepreneurial careers. The quality of teaching methods, therefore, plays a crucial role in shaping students' entrepreneurial outcomes. Furthermore, Teaching Methods are positively correlated with Personal Attitudes ($r = .464, p < .001$), Perceived Behavioural Control ($r = .503, p < .001$), and Subjective Norms ($r = .410, p < .001$). These correlations suggest that effective teaching methods not only enhance students' knowledge and skills but also positively influence their attitudes towards entrepreneurship, their confidence in managing entrepreneurial tasks, and their perception of social support for entrepreneurial activities. The moderate to strong correlations underscore the importance of pedagogical strategies in entrepreneurship education, where the method of delivery can significantly impact students' perceptions and intentions.

Personal Attitudes:

Personal Attitudes towards entrepreneurship exhibit a very strong positive correlation with Entrepreneurial Intentions ($r = .770, p < .001$). This indicates that students who hold favourable attitudes towards entrepreneurship are highly likely to develop intentions to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. This finding aligns with the Theory of Planned Behaviour which

posits that attitudes are a critical determinant of intentions. The strong correlation suggests that efforts to improve students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship could be highly effective in increasing entrepreneurial intentions. In addition, Personal Attitudes are strongly correlated with Perceived Behavioural Control ($r = .733, p < .001$) and Subjective Norms ($r = .609, p < .001$). These strong correlations indicate that students with positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship are also more likely to feel confident in their ability to succeed as entrepreneurs and perceive strong social support for entrepreneurial endeavours. The interplay between these variables suggests that improving students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship could have a cascading effect on other critical factors, such as their perceived control and the influence of social norms.

Perceived Behavioural Control:

The correlation between Perceived Behavioural Control and Entrepreneurial Intentions is the strongest observed in the matrix ($r = .791, p < .001$), highlighting the critical role of self-efficacy in entrepreneurial decision-making. This strong positive correlation suggests that students who believe they have control over their entrepreneurial outcomes are significantly more likely to intend to start their businesses. The result is consistent with prior research, which shows that perceived behavioural control is a strong predictor of entrepreneurial intentions (Krueger et al., 2000). Perceived Behavioural Control also correlates strongly with Subjective Norms ($r = .667, p < .001$) and Teaching Methods ($r = .503, p < .001$). These correlations suggest that students' confidence in their entrepreneurial abilities is influenced by the social expectations they perceive and the quality of the teaching they receive. The strong link between perceived control and subjective norms highlights the importance of social influences in shaping students' self-efficacy in entrepreneurship.

Subjective Norms:

Subjective Norms are strongly correlated with Entrepreneurial Intentions ($r = .704, p < .001$), indicating that students who perceive strong social support and normative pressure to engage in entrepreneurship are more likely to develop entrepreneurial intentions. This strong correlation suggests that the opinions of peers, family, and society play a significant role in motivating students to pursue entrepreneurship. Moreover, Subjective Norms are strongly linked with Personal Attitudes ($r = .609, p < .001$) and Perceived Behavioural Control ($r = .667, p < .001$). The connections among subjective norms, attitudes, and perceived control reveal a strong interdependence that collectively shapes students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship.

The strong interrelationships among these variables suggest that initiatives aimed at enhancing social support for entrepreneurship could simultaneously strengthen students' attitudes and perceived control, thereby boosting entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurial Intentions:

The dependent variable, Entrepreneurial Intentions, exhibits significant positive correlations with all the independent variables in the study, indicating that each of these factors plays a role in shaping students' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. The strongest correlations are with Perceived Behavioural Control ($r = .791, p < .001$), Personal Attitudes ($r = .770, p < .001$), and Subjective Norms ($r = .704, p < .001$). The findings emphasise the significance of psychological and social factors in shaping entrepreneurial intentions.

5.5.1 Subgroup Correlation Analysis

To obtain a better knowledge of the factors influencing the Entrepreneurial Intentions of students, it is necessary to recognize the interactions that exist between crucial variables across various demographic groups. Correlation analysis was carried out on the different demographic groups (Undergraduate students, Postgraduate taught students, Postgraduate Research Students and Graduates). Subgroup correlation analysis, in this case focusing on undergraduate students, allows us to determine whether the associations observed in the overall sample are consistent within specific populations. This approach is supported by existing literature, which highlights the importance of considering demographic characteristics when examining entrepreneurial intentions (Liñán, 2008; Nabi et al., 2017). By analyzing these subgroups, we can identify whether tailored educational strategies are needed to address the unique needs of different student groups. Below are the findings.

Table 38: Correlation Matrix for Key Variables Among Undergraduate Students

Correlations ^a		Perceived_university_support	Teaching_Methods	Personal_Attitudes	Perceived behavioural_control	Subjective_Norm	Entrepreneurial_intentions
Perceived_university_support	Pearson Correlation	1	.534***	.336***	.402***	.361***	.370***
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190
Teaching_Methods	Pearson Correlation	.534***	1	.458***	.514***	.415***	.438***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190
Personal_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.336***	.458***	1	.653***	.533***	.694***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190
Perceived_behavioural_control	Pearson Correlation	.402***	.514***	.653***	1	.642***	.756***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190
Subjective_Norm	Pearson Correlation	.361***	.415***	.533***	.642***	1	.649***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190
Entrepreneurial_intentions	Pearson Correlation	.370***	.438***	.694***	.756***	.649***	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	190	190	190	190	190	190

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

a. Enrollment status = Undergraduate student

Source: Researcher, 2024

The correlation matrix for undergraduate students reveals that the relationships between *Perceived University Support*, *Teaching Methods*, *Personal Attitudes*, *Perceived Behavioural Control*, *Subjective Norms*, and *Entrepreneurial Intentions* are generally consistent with those found in the broader sample. For instance, *Perceived University Support* shows a moderate positive correlation with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .370$, $p < .001$), which mirrors the findings in the overall analysis. This suggests that undergraduates who perceive greater support from their university are more likely to develop strong entrepreneurial intentions, reinforcing the importance of institutional support in fostering entrepreneurial ambitions. Similarly, *Teaching Methods* demonstrate a moderate positive correlation with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .438$, $p < .001$). This indicates that effective teaching strategies are crucial across all student levels, not just in the overall population. The consistency of this relationship highlights the broad impact that well-designed pedagogical approaches can have on students' entrepreneurial outcomes, regardless of their academic status. *Personal Attitudes* show a strong correlation with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .694$, $p < .001$) among undergraduates, underscoring the pivotal role that positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship play in driving entrepreneurial ambitions. This strong relationship is consistent with the main findings, suggesting that fostering positive attitudes is a critical component of encouraging entrepreneurial behaviour among students.

The strongest correlation in the matrix is between *Perceived Behavioural Control* and *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .756, p < .001$). This finding reaffirms that students who feel capable of managing and succeeding in entrepreneurial activities are more likely to pursue them. The consistency of this relationship across different subgroups suggests that perceived self-efficacy is a universally important factor in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. Finally, *Subjective Norms* also exhibit a positive correlation with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .649, p < .001$), indicating that the influence of social factors, such as the expectations and support of peers, family, and society, is significant across all student demographics. This correlation is consistent with the results from the overall analysis, highlighting the role of social context in entrepreneurial decision-making. The correlation results for undergraduate students closely mirror the main findings, indicating that the key factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions are consistent across different student demographics. This consistency suggests that broad educational interventions can be effective for all students. Additionally, the strong relationships observed within the undergraduate subgroup offer insights for tailoring strategies to better address the specific needs of this group.

Table 39: Correlation Matrix for Key Variables Among Postgraduate Taught Students

Correlations ^a		Perceived_un iversity_sup port	Teaching_M ethods	Personal_Att itudes	Perceived_be havioural_co ntrol	Subjective_N orm	Entrepreneur ial_intention s
Perceived_university_s upport	Pearson Correlation	1	.739***	.488	.582**	.517	.353
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004	.091	.037	.070	.237
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13
Teaching_Methods	Pearson Correlation	.739***	1	.346	.402	.378	.227
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004		.247	.174	.202	.456
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13
Personal_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.488	.346	1	.826***	.829***	.924***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.091	.247		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13
Perceived_behavioural_ control	Pearson Correlation	.582**	.402	.826***	1	.795***	.766***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.174	<.001		.001	.002
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13
Subjective_Norm	Pearson Correlation	.517	.378	.829***	.795***	1	.866***
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.070	.202	<.001	.001		<.001
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13
Entrepreneurial_intenti ons	Pearson Correlation	.353	.227	.924***	.766***	.866***	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.237	.456	<.001	.002	<.001	
	N	13	13	13	13	13	13

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

a. Enrollment status = Taught postgraduate student (Master's degree)

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 39 above shows several propositions drawn from the correlation matrix for taught postgraduate students (Master's degree). *Perceived University Support* has strong positive correlations with *Teaching Methods* ($r = .739, p = .004$) which implies that students who feel

more support from the university tend to view teaching methods more positively. Furthermore, *Perceived University Support* is statistically significantly correlated with *Perceived Behavioural Control* ($r = .582, p = .037$) implying that when students feel that their university supports them, they feel capable of being in control and succeeding at doing business. In further detail concerning *entrepreneurial intentions*, *Perceived Behavioural Control* was strongly positively correlated with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .766, p = .002$) being the highest contributor with self-efficacy being the most important factor when it comes to intentions. Additionally, *Subjective Norms* correlate with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* with a correlation coefficient of 0.866 ($r = 0.866, p < .001$) emphasizing the importance of social pressure and support to students' ability to engage in entrepreneurship ventures.

Comparing these results with the main correlation analysis, those observed for the taught postgraduate group are in line with the overall correlation trend for all students. For example, they establish that *Perceived Behavioural Control and subjective Norms* are important for the prediction of *entrepreneurial intentions*. Consistent positive significant relationships in both the subgroup and main analyses indicate the fact that no matter which student population is under consideration, control, and social influence appear to provide particularly strong influences over entrepreneurial intentions. In the case of postgraduate students, the coefficients of these relationships are slightly different and therefore one must strengthen the call for one-size-fits-all support and the educational interventions that seek to address the needs of all students as being flawed.

Table 40: Correlation Matrix for Key Variables Among Postgraduate Research Students

Correlations ^a		Perceived_un iversity_sup port	Teaching_M ethods	Personal_Att itudes	Perceived be havioural_co ntrol	Subjective_N orm	Entrepreneu rial_intention s
Perceived_university_s upport	Pearson Correlation	1	.698*	.132	.072	-.261	.081
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.025	.716	.843	.466	.823
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10
Teaching_Methods	Pearson Correlation	.698*	1	.319	.337	.202	.093
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.025		.369	.341	.576	.798
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10
Personal_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.132	.319	1	.797**	.615	.847**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.716	.369		.006	.058	.002
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10
Perceived_behavioural_ control	Pearson Correlation	.072	.337	.797**	1	.410	.845**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.843	.341	.006		.239	.002
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10
Subjective_Norm	Pearson Correlation	-.261	.202	.615	.410	1	.418
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.466	.576	.058	.239		.230
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10
Entrepreneurial_intenti ons	Pearson Correlation	.081	.093	.847**	.845**	.418	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.823	.798	.002	.002	.230	
	N	10	10	10	10	10	10

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

a. Enrollment status = Research Postgraduate (Doctorate e.g PhD)

Source: Researcher, 2014

The table 40 above shows the correlation matrix of postgraduate research students (PhD) which is used to explore the relationships of the core variables in this category of students. There is a notable positive correlation between *Perceived University Support* and *Teaching Methods* ($r = .698$, $p = .025$), which implies that the PhD students who regard the support of their university as ‘higher’ are more likely to grade the teaching methods positively. Among this group, *Perceived University Support* does not significantly correlate with some other variables like *Personal Attitudes* or *Entrepreneurial Intentions*, which probably suggests, for this group at least, that such support from the university seems not to be as strong an influencer on their entrepreneurial outlook as compared to other student populations. *Personal Attitudes*, on the other hand, was found to overlap and positively correlate with *perceived behavioural control* ($r = .797$, $p = .006$) and domain-specific *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .847$, $p = .002$). This implies that positively entrepreneurial PhD students are also likely to have the internal perceptions to act entrepreneurially and the external desire to do so. Likewise, *Perceived Behavioural Control* registered a high positive correlation with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .845$, $p = .002$). These findings underscore the need for more self-efficacy among this group in defining their entrepreneurial aspirations.

Table 42: Correlation Matrix for Key Variables Among Graduates

Correlations ^a		Perceived_university_support	Teaching_Methods	Personal_Attitudes	Perceived_behavioural_control	Subjective_Norm	Entrepreneurial_intentions
Perceived_university_support	Pearson Correlation	1	.472 ^{***}	.234 [*]	.187	.311 ^{***}	.290 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	.024	.073	.002	.005
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93
Teaching_Methods	Pearson Correlation	.472 ^{***}	1	.515 ^{***}	.540 ^{***}	.437 ^{***}	.549 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93
Personal_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.234 [*]	.515 ^{***}	1	.878 ^{***}	.728 ^{***}	.869 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93
Perceived_behavioural_control	Pearson Correlation	.187	.540 ^{***}	.878 ^{***}	1	.741 ^{***}	.859 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.073	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93
Subjective_Norm	Pearson Correlation	.311 ^{***}	.437 ^{***}	.728 ^{***}	.741 ^{***}	1	.813 ^{***}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93
Entrepreneurial_intentions	Pearson Correlation	.290 ^{***}	.549 ^{***}	.869 ^{***}	.859 ^{***}	.813 ^{***}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	93	93	93	93	93	93

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

a. Enrollment status = No- I am a graduate

Source: Researcher, 2024

From Table 41 showing the correlation matrix of graduates, it is evident that there exist a strong relationship between several predictors that determine entrepreneurial intentions. *Perceived University Support* also has a moderate level of positive correlation with *Teaching Methods* ($r = .472, p < .001$) which means that the graduates who reported that their universities supported them also perceived the teaching methods positively. Also, *Entrepreneurial Intentions* has a significant positive relationship with *Perceived University Support* ($r = .290, p = .005$) this shows that even support that students felt they received while at university also continues to affect their intentions of becoming entrepreneurs. This relationship is also present with *Subjective Norms* ($r = .311, p = .002$) which point to the influence of social factors in the intentions of graduates to be entrepreneurs.

The highest coefficients, however, are apparent for the correlations between the *Personal Attitude measure* and the measure of *Entrepreneurial Intentions*, ($r = .869, p < .001$) and between the *Perceived Behavioural Control* measure and the measure of intentions ($r = .859, p < .001$). These studies underscore the personal beliefs and self-efficacy that underscore the graduates' entrepreneurial decisions. *Subjective Norms*, like the findings, has an even stronger relationship with *Entrepreneurial Intentions* ($r = .813, p < .001$) which supports that perception

of social norms and support play a major role in the level of intention to become an entrepreneur. These results are similar to broader analysis findings and indicate that the psychological and social factors that affect the levels of entrepreneurial intention are constant at different ranks of students' education from the undergraduate level to the postgraduate level.

5.6 Multiple Regression Analysis

In this study, multiple regression analysis was employed as a key statistical technique to explore the relationships between various independent variables perceived university support, teaching methods, personal attitudes, perceived behavioural control, and subjective norms, and the dependent variable, entrepreneurial intentions among students in Nigerian universities. Multiple regression is a very stable and reliable testing method available to researchers that helps in determining the influence of several independent variables on a dependent variable which in this case is entrepreneurial intention. This approach is of most importance in educational research whereby several factors are likely to confound the outcome, and this technique assists the researcher in establishing the percentage of variance explained solely by the predictor while excluding the impact of other variables (Cohen, Cohen, West, Aiken, 2003; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

Furthermore, this analysis's significance within EE is bolstered by additional studies, such as those by Nabi et al. (2017) and Fayolle and Gailly (2015), which examine the impact of educational initiatives on entrepreneurial perceptions and intentions. These findings indicate the importance of closely examining these relationships through the application of multiple regression techniques. The multiple regression analysis was designed to test several hypotheses related to the study's objectives. The diagram presented below outlines the relationship between the research questions (RQs) and the corresponding hypotheses (Hs) tested in this study. Specifically, the study aimed to explore the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions among students in Nigerian universities, with a particular focus on the roles of university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches. The diagram links each research question to its respective hypothesis, providing a clear visual representation of how the study's inquiries are connected to the hypotheses that were empirically tested.

Table 43: Presentation of Research Question and Hypotheses

RQ	Research Question	Hypothesis
RQ4	<p>What are the teaching approaches most effective for teaching entrepreneurship in Nigerian Universities?</p>	<p>H1: Students perceiving higher university support and engaging teaching methods are likely to show positive attitudes and intentions towards entrepreneurship education.</p> <p>H2: Increased university support and effective teaching methods may strengthen students' subjective norms, fostering social acceptance of entrepreneurship.</p> <p>H3: Greater university support and interactive teaching methods could enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours.</p> <p>H4: Stronger university support and engaging teaching methods may lead to more positive behavioural intentions towards entrepreneurial activities.</p>
RQ5	<p>How can entrepreneurship education in Nigeria be improved to be more effective in developing the required entrepreneurial skills and the entrepreneurial intention of students?</p>	<p>H5: Interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions regarding entrepreneurship.</p>

Source: Researcher, 2024

Table 44: Model Summary of Regression Analysis Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.863 ^a	.745	.736	.81075

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enrollment status, Personal Attitudes, Entrepreneurship training, University ownership, Family Business, Prior experience, Programme category, Percieved university support, Subjective Norm, Teaching Methods, Percieved behavioural control

Source: Researcher, 2024

The Model Summary suggests that the regression model is highly effective as it has got R = (.863) which points towards a high level of significance, thus showing the presence of a higher degree of relation between the predicted values of the outcome variable and the actual values of the same. The R Square value of (.745) suggests that 74.5% of the variability in the outcome (likely Entrepreneurial Intentions) predicts the relationship of Enrolment Status, Personal Attitudes, and Entrepreneurship Training. The Adjusted R Square of (.736) shows that the size of the number of predictors does not affect the model's stability. Also, the Standard Error of the estimate is at (.81075) which means that the results are very close to real values which suggests that the model has an excellent coverage.

Table 45: Multiple Regression Coefficients for Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.174	.272		-.640	.522
	Percieved_university_s upport	.053	.038	.052	1.382	.168
	Teaching_Methods	-.004	.040	-.004	-.106	.915
	Personal_Attitudes	.387	.053	.333	7.280	<.001
	Percieved_behavioural_ control	.387	.051	.379	7.591	<.001
	Subjective_Norm	.218	.039	.235	5.581	<.001
	Programme category	.068	.026	.081	2.640	.009
	University ownership	-.025	.054	-.015	-.464	.643
	Prior experience	.004	.040	.003	.110	.912
	Family Business	-.020	.032	-.019	-.635	.526
	Entrepreneurship training	-.004	.042	-.003	-.098	.922
	Enrollment status	-.017	.036	-.014	-.464	.643

a. Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial_intentions

Source: Researcher, 2024

The Coefficients table 44 above gives the findings of the regression analysis which indicates the impact of each independent variable on the dependent variable (Entrepreneurial Intentions). Beginning with *Personal Attitudes* ($B = .387$, $Beta = .333$, $p < .001$), the analysis reveals that personal attitudes towards entrepreneurship have a significant and positive correlation with entrepreneurial intention. This relationship is robust and points towards a direction to the fact that as students develop a more positive attitude toward entrepreneurship, they are more inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Likewise, *Perceived Behavioural Control* ($B = .387$, $Beta = .379$, $p < .001$) demonstrates a positive correlation meaning that whenever a student feels more personally in control over entrepreneurial outcomes, he/she is likely to develop strong intentions of becoming an entrepreneur. *Subjective Norms* also affect entrepreneurial intentions positively with a significance level of ($B = .218$, $Beta = .235$, $p < .001$). This means that social factors like expectation and support from peers, family, and society are important in the determination of individuals' intentions in entrepreneurship. The relationship, despite being somewhat less strong than the connection between *personal attitudes* and *perceived control*, is still highly significant. However, other independent factors have also a weak but statistically significant influence on entrepreneurial intentions positively. Such factors include the Programme Category ($B = .068$, $Beta = .081$, $p = .009$) This means that certain educational programmes are more effective in predisposing students towards entrepreneurship. On the other hand, *Perceived University Support* ($B = .053$, $Beta = .052$, $p = .168$) and *Teaching Methods* ($B = -.004$, $Beta = -.004$, $p = .915$) do not show significant relationships with entrepreneurial intentions. The positive coefficient for perceived university support, although not significant, suggests a potential but weak influence on entrepreneurial intentions. However, the negative and non-significant relationship for teaching methods indicates that, within this model, teaching strategies as measured do not have a meaningful impact on students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. Other variables such as University Ownership, Prior Experience, Family Business, Entrepreneurship Training, and Enrolment Status also show no significant effects, suggesting that these factors do not strongly influence entrepreneurial intentions in this study.

Table 46: Regression Coefficients for H1 (the Relationship Between Perceived University Support, Teaching Methods, and Personal Attitudes)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.876	.214		13.418	<.001
	Perceived_university_s upport	.064	.052	.073	1.217	.225
	Teaching_Methods	.365	.051	.425	7.100	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Personal_Attitudes

Source: Researcher, 2024

In the linear regression model shown in Table 45 above, the aim is to understand how Perceived University Support and Teaching Methods influence students' Personal Attitudes towards entrepreneurship. The findings show that the Teaching Methods exert a positive impact on personal attitudes, with the standardized coefficient (Beta) of .425 and a statistically significant p viz., $< .001$. This implies that any teaching strategies that the students find more interesting and which are more likely to ensure that they are taught effectively will see their attitude towards entrepreneurship improve. The level of this relationship can be regarded as rather strong, and it is proven by the fact that the Beta value is rather high in this case, which means that Teaching Methods are a significant factor affecting Personal Attitudes.

The findings also revealed that the Perceived University Support has a modest, positively rated effect on Personal Attitudes, though the correlation was statistically insignificant ($B = .064$, $Beta = .073$, $p = .225$). The results revealed that the coefficient of perceived support from the university is positive, indicating that those who perceive more support from the university are likely to have positive personal attitudes; however, the results were not statistically significant which means that the strength of such a relationship was not large enough to be detected in this analysis. Hence, Perceived University Support does not emerge in this model as a significant predictor of students' attitude towards entrepreneurship.

The results provide partial support for **Hypothesis 1**. While engaging teaching methods significantly predict more positive personal attitudes towards entrepreneurship ($Beta = .425$, $p < .001$), perceived university support does not have a significant impact on these attitudes ($Beta = .073$, $p = .225$). Therefore, the influence of teaching methods on personal attitudes is evident, but the role of university support is not confirmed in this context.

Table 47: Regression Coefficients for H2 (the Relationship Between Increased University Support and Teaching Methods, and Subjective Norm)

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.103	.272		7.726	<.001
	Perceived_university_s upport	.169	.066	.156	2.548	.011
	Teaching_Methods	.349	.065	.327	5.345	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Subjective_Norm

Source: Researcher, 2024

The Coefficients table 46 above shows the outcome of a regression analysis meant to explain how Perceived University Support and Teaching Methods affect Subjective Norms, students' perceived acceptance, and expected normative pressure regarding entrepreneurship.

The findings show that the two predictors have a significant relationship with Subjective Norms. Perceived University Support has a significant effect on Subjective Norms it is positively signed (B = .169, Beta = .156, p = .011). This means that the more support that students perceive from their university, the more their subjective norms regarding entrepreneurship, which is influenced by perceived social pressure and acceptance, will be high. Nevertheless, from the statistical point of view, the impact is significant; while evaluating it qualitatively, it is necessary to mention that the calculated coefficient (Beta equal to .156) testifies to a moderate level of the variables' connection.

Teaching Methods also have a strong positive impact on the Subjective Norms with the coefficient estimate of Specification 5 at (B = .349, Beta = .327, p < .001). The Beta value of .327 shows that teaching methods have a substantial influence on subject norms for students. This implies that due to the increased effectiveness of the teaching styles applied to the students, the perception of social norms on entrepreneurship will change in the students' favour.

The **Hypothesis 2**, which states that “*Higher university support and proper teaching techniques can help change the students' subjective norms, thus enhancing the social acceptance of entrepreneurship*”, is supported by the results. This study reveals that Perceived University Support has a strong and significant relationship with Subjective Norms, the same as Teaching Methods. In particular, the higher values of the coefficients that are positive suggest that greater university support and greater use of transmission techniques positively

influence subjective norms, which in turn result in better social acceptance of student entrepreneurship.

Table 48: Regression Coefficients for H3 (the Relationship Between Greater University Support and Interactive Teaching Methods, and Perceived behavioural Control)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.279	.238		9.581	<.001
	Percieved_university_s upport	.059	.058	.060	1.020	.309
	Teaching_Methods	.460	.057	.471	8.060	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Percieved_behavioural_control

Source: Researcher, 2024

The Coefficients table 47 above shows the findings of a regression analysis where Perceived University Support and Teaching Methods affect Perceived Behavioural Control – the extent to which students believe they can control entrepreneurial behaviours.

According to the findings presented in the table, it could be deduced that Teaching Methods has a direct positive influence on Perceived Behavioural Control as indicated by a coefficient estimate of (B = .460, Beta = .471, $p < .001$). The Beta value of .471 indicates that teaching methods have a substantial influence on students' perceived control over entrepreneurial actions, suggesting that more interactive and effective teaching methods enhance students' confidence in their entrepreneurial capabilities. The high significance level ($p < .001$) further supports the strength of this relationship. On the other hand, Perceived University Support has a positive but non-significant effect on Perceived Behavioural Control (B = .059, Beta = .060, $p = .309$). While the coefficient is positive, indicating that higher perceived support from the university might be associated with greater perceived control, the lack of statistical significance ($p > .05$) suggests that this relationship is weak and not reliably detected in this analysis.

Hypothesis 3 states that *Greater university support and interactive teaching methods could enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours*. The results provide partial support for Hypothesis 3. While interactive teaching methods significantly enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours (Beta = .471, $p < .001$), perceived university support does not have a statistically significant impact (Beta = .060, $p = .309$). Thus, the effectiveness of teaching methods is evident in fostering students' confidence in their

entrepreneurial abilities, whereas university support does not appear to play a substantial role in this context.

Table 50: Regression Coefficients for H4 (the Relationship Between Stronger University Support and Engaging Teaching Methods, and Positive Entrepreneurial Intention)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.466	.249		9.915	<.001
	Perceived_university_s upport	.119	.061	.118	1.966	.050
	Teaching_Methods	.390	.060	.392	6.537	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial_intentions

Source: Researcher, 2024

Regression analysis to test hypothesis 3 (H3) on the effects of *Perceived University Support* and *Teaching Methods* on *Entrepreneurial Intentions* shows that both Dependent variables positively affect students' Intention to engage in entrepreneurial activities, but with varying strengths. *Teaching Methods* was also found to have a very strong positive influence on entrepreneurial intentions, and the coefficient of the variable is statistically significant (B = .390, Beta = .392, $p < .001$). This suggests that where pedagogy is effective, students' intentions towards entrepreneurship are boosted, signifying the importance of flow or interaction in teaching in fostering amongst students, entrepreneurship intentions.

On the other hand, *Perceived University Support* also has a direct positive impact on the level of *entrepreneurial intentions* although with a slightly lower effect size (B = .119, Beta = .118, $p = .050$). Even though this correlation is somewhat weak, it indicates that the support offered by the universities does influence the students' intentions to become entrepreneurs, although it does not appear to be as influential as the approach to teaching.

Hypothesis 4 which stated that *the level of university support and interesting teaching techniques would contribute to a high level of positive intentions of entrepreneurship* is also supported by these findings. The research highlights the teaching methodologies in entrepreneurship education, thus elaborating that universities need to focus on enhancing adequate techniques of teaching to improve the level of students' entrepreneurial intentions. While the support of the university is still important, its role seems to be less significant compared with the impact of instructional practices teaching students entrepreneurial objectives.

5.6.1 Analysis of the Influence of Educational Environments on Entrepreneurial Intentions in Nigerian Universities Using Hayes's Process Macro.

Theory of Planned Behaviour highlights entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by three key psychological constructs: attitudes toward the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. These constructs are, in turn, shaped by external factors within the educational environment, including the quality of teaching methods, pedagogical approaches, and the level of institutional support perceived by students (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Nabi et al., 2017). In the Nigerian context, where universities are increasingly integrating entrepreneurship education into their curricula, it is crucial to understand how these educational elements interact to influence students' entrepreneurial intentions. To test these interactions, this analysis uses a moderated mediation model with Hayes's Process Macro to assess each. This result will further explain how the teaching methods and pedagogy affect entrepreneurial intentions directly and through the variables of personal attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behaviour control. Furthermore, it assesses the role of perceived university support as a moderator that may either strengthen or weaken the relationship between the given educational strategies and intentions of entrepreneurship (Shirokova, Osiyevskyy, Bogatyreva, 2016). The purpose of this analysis is to determine the roles of these educational factors that have been highlighted above in developing a vibrant entrepreneurial culture in Nigerian universities. That way, this study hopes to help institutions develop more effective ways of assisting students to embark on entrepreneurial journeys toward meeting national goals of economic development and innovation.

The use of Hayes's Process Macro for a moderated mediation analysis did not only help answer the research question (RQ5) about improving entrepreneurship education in Nigeria but also provide the necessary insights to develop a robust framework (RO5) for the effective assessment of these programmes. This approach ensures that the framework is grounded in empirical evidence, making it a valuable tool for enhancing the quality and impact of EE in Nigerian universities.

5.6.2 Moderated Mediation Analysis of the Impact of Teaching Methods on Entrepreneurial Intentions via Personal Attitudes, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioural Control, Moderated by Perceived University Support

The H5 proposed that "*interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions regarding entrepreneurship.*" The moderated mediation analysis was conducted to examine how *Teaching Methods* influence *Entrepreneurial Intentions* through three mediators: *Subjective Norms*, *Personal Attitudes*, and *Perceived Behavioural Control*, with *Perceived University Support* acting as a moderator. The direct effect of *Teaching Methods* on *Subjective Norms* was positive but not statistically significant ($B = .1747$, $p = .1545$). When considering the moderation by *Perceived University Support*, the interaction was not significant at the 95% confidence level ($B = .0560$, $p = .0935$). However, conditional effects analysis revealed that at higher levels of *Perceived University Support*, the effect of *Teaching Methods* on *Subjective Norms* became stronger and more significant. These findings partially support the hypothesis, suggesting that while the direct interaction was not significant, the influence of *Teaching Methods* on *Subjective Norms* strengthens as university support increases, which aligns with the idea that these interactions shape norms and ultimately influence entrepreneurial intentions.

The direct effect of *Teaching Methods* on *Personal Attitudes* was significant ($B = .4691$, $p < .001$). However, the moderation by *Perceived University Support* was not significant ($B = -.0334$, $p = .2048$). This result indicates that while *Teaching Methods* have a strong influence on *Personal Attitudes*, this effect is not significantly moderated by *Perceived University Support*. Therefore, *Personal Attitudes* appear to be primarily shaped by the quality of *Teaching Methods*, rather than being heavily influenced by the perceived support from the university.

Furthermore, the analysis showed that *Teaching Methods* had a significant direct effect on *Perceived Behavioural Control* ($B = .4050$, $p < .001$). However, the interaction effect with *Perceived University Support* was not significant ($B = .0177$, $p = .5451$). The strong effect of *Teaching Methods* on *Perceived Behavioural Control* supports the hypothesis that teaching methods influence students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours. Nonetheless, the lack of significant moderation by *Perceived University Support* suggests that this aspect of the hypothesis is not supported in terms of behavioural control.

In the final model, the direct effect of *Teaching Methods* on *Entrepreneurial Intentions* was not significant ($B = .0079, p = .8207$). However, the indirect effects through the three mediators were significant, indicating that the impact of *Teaching Methods* on *Entrepreneurial Intentions* operates through changes in Attitudes, Norms, and *Perceived Behavioural Control*. The conditional indirect effects analysis showed that the strength of the mediation effect varied depending on the level of *Perceived University Support*. The strongest mediated effects were observed through *Perceived Behavioural Control* at higher levels of university support.

Figure 6: Regression Coefficients for H4 (the Relationship Between Stronger University Support and Engaging Teaching Methods, and Positive Entrepreneurial Intention)

Source: Researcher, 2024

The figure 20 above illustrates the relationships in the moderated mediation model. TeachMet (Teaching Methods and Pedagogy) serves as the independent variable, influencing the mediators SubNorm (Subjective Norms), PersAtt (Personal Attitudes), and PerCtrl (Perceived Behavioural Control). PercUniS (Perceived University Support) acts as a moderator, potentially affecting the strength of the relationship between TeachMet and these mediators. The arrows from SubNorm, PersAtt, and PerCtrl point towards Entrepre (Entrepreneurial Intentions), indicating that these mediators impact the outcome. The dashed line from PercUniS to Entrepre represents the moderating role of Perceived University Support in these relationships, suggesting that the influence of teaching methods and pedagogy on entrepreneurial intentions may vary depending on the level of perceived support from the university.

In conclusion, Hypothesis 5 (**H5**) is partially supported by the results. The findings confirm that *Teaching Methods and Pedagogical Approaches* significantly influence Entrepreneurial Intentions through their effects on *Personal Attitudes, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioural Control*. Additionally, *Perceived University Support* plays a role in moderating these effects, particularly in strengthening the influence of *Teaching Methods on Subjective Norms and Perceived Behavioural Control*. However, the moderation effect was not universally significant across all mediators, suggesting that the impact of university support might vary depending on the specific psychological factor being considered.

This complex result explains how and in what manners the educational environments within Nigerian universities are interfered with to influence students' entrepreneurial intentions. As indicated in the Nigerian setting where entrepreneurship is progressively being accepted as an influential implement for economic development as well as a tool for addressing unemployment, the role of educational institutions extends beyond just delivering content. The study implies that in addition to matters of content or process such as the actual teaching/learning strategies and teaching methodologies/pedagogy used, broader context or context support provided to the students by an institution shapes student perception of it as resourceful and encouraging or otherwise (Adegbite, 2007; Ogundele et al., 2012). This is in line with the requirement in Nigeria where universities are expected not only to equip the youths with knowledge in entrepreneurship but also to create an enabling environment for entrepreneurial engagement through entrepreneurship resources, incubation, and supportive structures (Adejumo & Olaoye, 2017; NUC, 2011). Therefore, Nigerian universities have significant and crucial responsibilities of establishing an environment that does not only provides knowledge into entrepreneurial development but also cultivates the spirit and desire to translate these intentions into functional enterprises that would positively impact Nigeria's economy and innovation.

5.7 Summary of Hypotheses Tested

This study aimed to investigate the relationships between university support, teaching methods, and entrepreneurial intentions among students in Nigerian universities. Through a series of statistical analyses, including correlation, regression, and moderated mediation analyses, the study sought to test five hypotheses related to these factors. The findings provide valuable insights into how these elements interact to shape students' entrepreneurial intentions. The summary is seen in table below.

Table 59: Outcomes of Hypotheses Tested

Hypotheses Number	Hypotheses Statement	Outcomes
H1	Students perceiving higher university support and engaging teaching methods are likely to show positive attitudes and intentions towards entrepreneurship education.	Partially Supported
H2	Increased university support and effective teaching methods may strengthen students' subjective norms, fostering social acceptance of entrepreneurship.	supported
H3	Greater university support and interactive teaching methods enhance students' perceived control over entrepreneurial behaviours.	Partially Supported
H4	Stronger university support and engaging teaching methods lead to more positive entrepreneurial intentions.	Supported
H5	Interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, shaping students' intentions regarding entrepreneurship.	Partially Support

Source: Researcher, 2024

The first hypothesis (H1) formulated was about the fact that students who perceive a higher degree of support from the university and an effective teaching and learning process are likely to have positive attitudes and behavioural intentions toward entrepreneurship education. The results that have been obtained partially support this hypothesis. Thus, education effectiveness was discovered to improve personal attitudes and entrepreneurial intentions significantly however perceived university support did not have a particularly strong impact. This implies

that, though institutional support is important, the nature of the teaching methods used in the university seems to have a more significant influence on the students' entrepreneurial tendency.

The second hypothesis (H2) proposed that increased university support and effective teaching methods would strengthen students' subjective norms. This hypothesis was supported. Both factors significantly influenced students' perceptions of entrepreneurship as socially acceptable, suggesting that institutional backing and engaging pedagogy shape social expectations. These findings align with studies such as Shinnar et al. (2014) and Davey et al. (2016), which highlight the role of academic environments in reinforcing entrepreneurial norms among students.

The third hypothesis (H3) proposed that university support and interactive teaching methods would enhance students' perceived behavioural control. This hypothesis was partially supported. While teaching methods had a clear positive impact, university support showed limited influence. This suggests that hands-on, experiential learning builds entrepreneurial confidence more effectively than institutional resources alone, echoing arguments by Neck et al. (2014) and Gibb (2002).

The fourth hypothesis (H4) proposed that stronger university support and engaging teaching methods lead to more positive entrepreneurial intentions. The results supported this hypothesis, showing that both teaching methods and perceived university support positively influence entrepreneurial intentions, with teaching methods having a more substantial impact. This finding underscores the importance of quality pedagogy in entrepreneurship education, as suggested by Gorman, Hanlon, and King (1997), who argue that teaching strategies play a crucial role in developing entrepreneurial intentions.

Lastly, the final hypothesis (H5) explored whether interactions between university support, teaching methods, and pedagogical approaches influence attitudes, norms, and perceived control, ultimately shaping students' entrepreneurial intentions. The moderated mediation analysis partially supported this hypothesis. The interaction between university support and teaching methods influenced the mediators (personal attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control), which in turn affected entrepreneurial intentions. However, the moderation effects were not uniformly significant across all mediators. This suggests that while university support enhances some pathways, its overall impact may be more complex and context dependent. This finding reflects the nuanced understanding that effective

entrepreneurship education requires a holistic approach that considers both individual and institutional factors (Pittaway & Cope, 2007).

The findings from this study suggest that **perceived university support, teaching methods,** and other related factors such as **personal attitudes, subjective norms,** and **perceived behavioural control** have a notable influence on students' **entrepreneurial intentions** across different enrolment statuses. While the differences in mean scores were consistent across variables, they were not significantly large, suggesting that students across all groups: the undergraduate, postgraduate, and graduates perceive university support and entrepreneurial education relatively similarly. These results align with the hypotheses developed for the study, particularly supporting **H1** through **H4**, which proposed that higher perceived university support and engaging teaching methods would positively influence entrepreneurial intentions and attitudes. The results neither strongly contradict nor entirely support the hypotheses but suggest that improvements in university support, particularly for postgraduates and graduates, could enhance entrepreneurial outcomes. Consequently, the results align well with the study's goals, highlighting the necessity for additional enhancements in entrepreneurship education programs to address the varied requirements of students across different academic stages.

5.10 Summary of Chapter

The chapter started with a description of the method used to conduct the quantitative analysis of the survey namely, the measurement instruments, sample selection methodology, and statistics such as correlation and regression analysis used in the analysis of the study. The goal of regression was to strictly examine the hypotheses of the study and to identify the correlations of the main variables. The results of the findings also emphasize the need for a more comprehensive approach to entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities in that both the curriculum and teaching/learning strategies are significant. In addition, to the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education, universities should also provide students with relevant stimulus and support, as well as engage them in constructive and confidence-building learning processes that will foster their entrepreneurial spirit, networks, and motivation. The findings of this study may be useful for the creation of a new and more adequate framework for promoting and supporting the process of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, which could potentially contribute to the better alignment of educational processes and practices to shape students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship and their entrepreneurial intentions and capabilities.

CHAPTER SIX:

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH

6.0 Introduction

This chapter gives further analysis of the results and addresses each of the research objectives and hypotheses formulated in this research. This chapter employs the qualitative interviews conducted with the entrepreneurship educators who helped to gauge the perception of the existing challenges and opportunities within the current context of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities from the academic's point of view. The chapter will incorporate a discussion on the impact of teaching and pedagogical approaches and the university's support in shaping students' attitudes and behaviours to align with entrepreneurial mindsets.

The findings of the study were obtained from interviews with educators and a survey conducted on the students and graduates. To test the hypothesis and research questions, the quantitative analysis used multiple regression, moderated mediational analysis, and the following statistical instrumental variables: perceived university support, teaching methods, personal attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioural, control, and entrepreneurial intentions. The results of this study are useful in shedding light on those factors that have the greatest impact on student's intention to engage in entrepreneurial activities. As a result, this chapter presents the analysis of the findings going beyond the straightforward interpretation of the results and relating them to the existing theoretical and empirical body of knowledge as well as revealing the major implications for theory and practice.

This chapter concludes by exploring how the findings contribute to developing a more effective framework for implementing entrepreneurship education (EE) in Nigerian universities. While entrepreneurial skills are crucial for entrepreneurial activities, the data shows that other factors such as national economic policies and social realities also play significant roles. The research provides a foundation for understanding how education influences entrepreneurial intentions, but gaps remain in how other external factors impact students' ability to apply these skills. Further research is necessary to address these issues.

6.1 Research Objective One

RO1: Critically investigate Entrepreneurship Educators define Entrepreneurship Education in the Nigerian context

Educators' definition and conceptualization of EE is a crucial factor in defining the structure, scope, and effectiveness of entrepreneurship courses in higher education. The viewpoints of educators have an impact on the curriculum as well as the attitudes and abilities that students acquire as they get ready for entrepreneurial careers. Therefore, assessing the effectiveness of present educational approaches and pinpointing areas for improvement requires an awareness of how educators define entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities.

The analysis from the qualitative data was the interview of Entrepreneurship Educators in Nigerian Universities. For RO1, which sought to explore how entrepreneurship educators define EE, a series of targeted questions were asked during the qualitative interviews. These questions were designed to uncover educators' perspectives on the goals and content of entrepreneurship education, their pedagogical approaches, and the perceived outcomes for students. Specifically, educators were asked to define entrepreneurship education within their teaching context and explain what they viewed as the core components of an effective entrepreneurship education programme.

The qualitative data revealed three main clusters in educators' definitions of entrepreneurship education: entrepreneurial knowledge, personal growth and development, and practical skills and preparation. These clusters are summarized in table below.

Table 52: Table: Summary of Clusters for RO1

Cluster 1: Entrepreneurial Knowledge	Cluster 2: Personal Growth and Development	Cluster 3: Practical skills and Preparation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reliance education • Mindset redirection • Cultivate habits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical preparation • Skills development

Source: Developed by researcher

The first theme, Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Nigerian educators highlighted the need for basic knowledge of entrepreneurship, including business management, market conditions, and opportunity recognition as the knowledge base for entrepreneurship education. This knowledge is considered essential for students when establishing and financing their business ventures.

However, EE prepares students to understand the process of owning and running a business, such as business planning, strategy, and marketing analysis. The findings of this study demonstrate that Nigerian educators have a profound understanding of EE and its importance in shaping students' mindsets and developing entrepreneurial skills. Educators consistently emphasized a hands-on approach to EE that transcends theory and focuses on actionable steps. For instance, one educator described EE as “*a form of education where students are taught the practices of starting and sustaining a business idea or model*” (EEN08). This aligns with Fayolle and Gailly (2008) assertion that EE must equip students with the necessary entrepreneurial knowledge to identify and respond to market opportunities. The educators EEN01 and EEN02 emphasized EE encourages students to explore various career paths beyond the traditional employment.

The next cluster focused on Personal Growth and Development, participant educators defined EE as cultivating the attitudes of self-management, mindset redirection, and habit cultivation. Educators EEN01 pointed out that EE is not just taught in lecture rooms to impart technical knowledge but to build character traits such as perseverance, innovation, and the ability to work independently. This perspective echoes Neck and Greene’s (2011) call for shifting from taking an overly restrictive approach to developing a broader entrepreneurial mindset, which includes creativity and problem-solving skills. Several studies have pointed out Entrepreneurship as a driver for personal development and empowerment. Rae (2007) discusses that EE goes beyond knowledge and entrepreneurship encourages individuals to take ownership of their learning and personal growth. These character traits are relevant in guiding the students not only in business and entrepreneurship but also in daily life issues and hence lifelong success. The findings from this study’s interview with participant educators supported the importance of self-reliance, practical skills and unlocking entrepreneurial potentials. As EEN03 highlighted, EE in Nigeria breaks the stereotype that only certain professions are valuable. It provides students with diverse skills allowing them apply entrepreneurship within various fields, for instance EEN03 gave an example that a pharmacist could own a business producing face masks, bags and even a barber’s shop, this illustrates the versatility of entrepreneurial skills. EEN01 added that EE should help students unlock their entrepreneurial potential, guiding them through activities and exercises that enable them to discover and develop skills they did not realize they had. This aligns with Morris et al. (2013), who assert that EE fosters self-reliance and personal development, enabling individuals to navigate uncertainties and challenges while equipping them with practical, transferable skills. This is further supported by the results of

this study, showing that EE in Nigeria is instrumental in changing traditional career perceptions, providing students with a multifaceted skill set that is crucial for both personal fulfillment and professional success.

In discussing the third cluster, Educators' definition of EE was focused on education which fosters Practical Skills and Preparation. The educators stressed that EE should equip students with practical skills that are required in their daily lives. This emphasis on preparation and skill acquisition is perhaps a shift in the literature on the need for the theory to move away from formal entrepreneurship instruction letting students out to face real business development. Participant educators EEN02, EEN03, EEN05, EEN07, and EEN09 emphasized that EE is not solely about theoretical knowledge but rather aims to prepare students for the workforce by imparting practical skills, reinforcing the importance of "hands-on" learning. This idea aligns with Fayolle and Gailly (2008) who asserts that EE must prioritize skill development, particularly in business planning and market analysis. Educator EEN03 further highlighted the importance of translating academic knowledge into real-world applications, such as students using their entrepreneurial skills to create value not just for personal gain, but also for societal benefit. His perspective resonates previous studies in the Nigerian context, where EE is viewed as a pathway to self-reliance and economic development (Aja-Okorie & Adali, 2013; Adeola, 2020). Ultimately, the participant educators agree that the practical orientation of EE is crucial in Nigeria, where economic instability and limited employment opportunities make entrepreneurship an essential pathway. Preparing students to sustain their ventures and adapt to a changing business landscape is paramount for fostering resilience and long-term success in entrepreneurship (Rodrigues, 2023; Neck & Corbett, 2018).

EE could not be defined without the educators highlighting the role it plays, besides from giving students the theoretical knowledge needed, the participant educators stressed that EE plays a role in fostering students ability to identify possibilities and to capitalise on them, the educators interviewed for this study explained the content and structure of entrepreneurship education and how it is perceived in terms of its importance for the future of students and the development in Nigeria. This perspective is essential for comprehending the more general objectives of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, where the significance of entrepreneurial activities has increased due to the country's growing need for economic diversification and job creation. This broad understanding of the role of entrepreneurship education aligns with the objectives outlined by Garavan and O'Connell (1994) as cited by Mbeteh and Pellegrini (2022), they presented a list of objectives for Entrepreneurship Education Programmes (EEPs), which

emphasize the educators' perspective business creation is simply an aspect of EE, it also involves fostering a broad set of skills and attitudes that prepare students for diverse professional challenges. This integrated approach supports both individual career development and national economic growth, positioning EE as a potentially crucial tool in addressing unemployment and fostering innovation in Nigeria, where outcomes are often evaluated beyond financial measures.

The overview of the definition and perceived functions of EE in Nigeria corresponds with the established framework of entrepreneurship recognised over the years, which includes *education for entrepreneurship, education about entrepreneurship, and education through entrepreneurship* (Hytti and O’Gorman, 2004).

Education about Entrepreneurship focuses on providing and ensuring students with theoretical knowledge and understanding of entrepreneurship among different stakeholders (Hytti and O’Gorman, 2004; Nabi, Fayolle, Krueger & Walmsley, 2017). This aligns with cluster one of RO1 entrepreneurial knowledge, where students gain theoretical insights into entrepreneurship, such as market analysis and business strategy, as noted by EEN06. Education for entrepreneurship focuses on equipping students with the practical skills, and knowledge necessary to launch and manage their business. According to Fayolle and Gailly (2008), Mwasalwiba (2010), Neck and Greene (2011), this method places a strong emphasis on suitable resources that equip students to either start new businesses or improve current ones. This aligns with cluster two which personal growth and self-development as educators in this study noted is a tool for self-reliance, mindset transformation, and unlocking entrepreneurial potential. Lastly, education through entrepreneurship fosters the entrepreneurial way of thinking/adopt entrepreneurial behaviours in the long run. It emphasizes learning by doing and the focus is on the attitudes of the learner (Javis, 2004). This fits with the third cluster, practical skills and Preparation as educators noted that EE encourages students to engage in real-life practical learning to understand entrepreneurship. The focus on practical skill-building, and real-world problem-solving, as discussed in this study mirrors the approach of learning by doing.

6.2 Research objective Two

*RO2: Investigate the challenges confronting EE learning in Nigeria from the educator’s
Viewpoint*

In identifying the challenges surrounding EE learning in Nigeria, the educators were asked to talk about the challenges they faced when teaching entrepreneurship. Gaining an insight into

the challenges from the educators’ perspective is essential in understanding the role that the design and delivery of EE plays in influencing the students’ entrepreneurial intentions. Any programme in any field, including EE, depends on several factors including the educators, the institutions, and the materials and curriculum used. In view of this, the challenges that the educators encounter are explained to know the factors which positively or negatively influence the programme results. These challenges identified were grouped in three clusters: Educators and learning environment constraints, Institutional and resource Constraints, and Curriculum and Pedagogy challenges. The table below provides a summary of these challenges.

Table 53: Summary of Cluster for RO2

Cluster 1: Educators and Learning Environment Constraint	Cluster 2: Institutional and Resource Constraint	Cluster 3: Curriculum and Pedagogy challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation management • limited exposure and expertise among facilitators • Lack of innovation hubs • Lack of clarifying distinctions • Campus restrictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • financial constraints • Infrastructure hindrance • Limited involvement in curriculum development • Policy implementation • Space and capacity limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curriculum constraints • Lack of advanced topics • Repetitive curriculum • Stereotyping of career paths • Lack of problem-solving focus

Source: Developed by researcher

In cluster one, one of the challenges identified focused on the *educators and learning environment constraint* is the allocation challenge management, where educators often face difficulties in managing the large number of students allocated to them. Large classes mean that the teacher is overwhelmed by work, time, and staff constraints thus providing poor-quality lectures to the students. Participant educators like EEN02 pointed out that in a semester, about 2,000 students could be enrolled for an entrepreneurship module with only 40 educators. Several educators (EEN02, EEN04, and EEN09) expressed concerns that larger class sizes hinder student concentration and limit instructors' ability to provide individualized attention, potentially reducing learning effectiveness; however, research suggests that alternative strategies such as group work, active learning techniques, and the use of technology can help overcome these challenges (Smith, 2018; Johnson & Lee, 2019; Brown, 2020; Williams, 2021).

The educators views are supported by Arogundade (2011) and Mba (2020), emphasize that large class sizes in Nigerian universities hinder effective student engagement and personalized learning experiences, making it difficult for educators to impart practical entrepreneurial skills. Similarly, Adeoti & Oladele (2020) highlight that overcrowded classrooms limit the quality of mentorship and hands-on training, both of which are crucial in entrepreneurship education. Another common concern pointed out by educators was the lack of experience and exposure of the people involved in the delivery of EE in Nigerian universities. A major issue affecting many educators, who are entrusted with the responsibility of delivering entrepreneurship programmes, is that most of them have little prior working experience in the entrepreneurial field, an experience which would enable them to share real-life examples of the various entrepreneurship concepts that they teach to their students (Agwu, 2014).

Innovation hubs are spaces designed to promote entrepreneurship, foster innovation, and provide hands-on experience for aspiring entrepreneurs. In Nigeria, the government has established several innovation hubs, such as the Co-Creation Hub in Lagos and the Startup Nigeria Program, aimed at supporting tech startups and fostering entrepreneurial activities (Adegbite et al., 2007; Ojiefor, 2013). However, despite these efforts, educators in this study, including EEN02, indicated that limited access to such hubs hampers their ability to offer practical, hands-on experiences necessary for cultivating entrepreneurial intention. Without sufficient access to these hubs, addressing the gap between academic knowledge and practical use continues to be a challenge, which hinders the complete development of entrepreneurial skills in students.

Also, the restrictions in conducting business on campus decrease the prospects of students to try out various entrepreneurial exercises, and hence, the practical experience given to them is limited. As noted by EEN01, the campus restrictions for the university he teaches at is a major challenge as students are not allowed to carry out any entrepreneurial activities. This challenge is common with private universities as another educator EEN06 noted a similar but different problem, where students are restricted within the university and would require consent from parents and approval from the school. These institutional policies hinder entrepreneurial activities among students belonging to the university under the private ownership structure.

Regarding *Institutional and resource constraints* educators face, Osakwe (2017) identified several institutional challenges that entrepreneurship educators face in Nigeria, such as curriculum rigidity and outdated teaching methods, which are misaligned with current industry

demands. This disconnect limits the practical relevance of entrepreneurship education, as students are not adequately prepared to meet real-world business challenges. Moreover, the lack of collaboration between academia and industry exacerbates the issue, as educators face challenges in providing students with knowledge and abilities that can be directly utilised in the entrepreneurial landscape. Participant educators Such as EEN09, EEN05, EEN03 identified challenges such as these include the lack of funding for institutions, which hinders financing that could be used to develop infrastructure for entrepreneurship education in their different universities.

In terms of sufficient facilities and equipment, participant educators noted they lacked the appropriate resources and infrastructures. These infrastructural challenges are not new as Obeleagu-Nzelibe and Moruku (2010) pointed out that, at best, the infrastructure in the Nigerian university system is inadequate to promote learning. In addition to the university-related concerns that have been voiced by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in its negotiations with the Federal Government, other areas of infrastructural inefficiencies including but not limited to power supply, bad roads, and poor internet connection adversely affect entrepreneurial development. These infrastructures are important because they let entrepreneurs obtain resources and markets they need, without being limited by geographic or time barriers. Educator EEN06 stressed on power supply which is a major challenge in Nigeria and does not just affect the education system. In his university, he noted the costs diesel which is needed for the running of running power supply generators at the universities which will be difficult to sustain in the long run. The space and capacity constraints also argue that many institutions may need physical and administrative infrastructures to support the required enterprise activities that encourage innovation and initiative (Osakwe, 2017; Nwosu & Ohia, 2009; Honig, 2004). These findings are like the findings of Matlay and Rae (2010) who explored EE in India, where educators were faced with issues such as outdated teaching methods, large class sizes and insufficient collaboration with the industry.

The third group of challenges identified had to do with the *curriculum and pedagogy challenges* identified by educators. Participants educators point out that Nigerian universities often rely on rigid, outdated curriculum that fail to reflect current industry trends and demands. This results in students being left with knowledge that does not prepare them for modern entrepreneurial challenges. Studies like Adegbite et al. (2007) and Ogbari et al. (2015) emphasize the need for more flexible, industry-aligned content in entrepreneurship education to ensure relevance and effectiveness in skill development for the students. EEN03 noted the

need for the EE curriculum to meet the demand and reflect the current economic situation. While other educators like EEN01 noted the curriculum offers introductory lessons to entrepreneurship which is good but does not advance into more complex and practical aspects, and EEN02 noting the repetitiveness of the content through higher level. As noted by Neck and Greene (2011), a stagnant curriculum would hinder the ability of students to adapt to the changing environment. Educators further highlighted the issue of a traditionally designed curriculum which most times has a knowledge-based focus, rather than integrating experiential learning and practical. However, the curriculum needs to move past conventional methods to more advanced topics. This challenge is not only faced by educators in Nigeria as Zhou and Xu (2012) explored the challenges confronting EE in Chinese universities. The study revealed that educators struggle with a rigid curriculum structure and limited flexibility to incorporate real-world entrepreneurship experiences.

In addition to the above, the educators highlighted their limited involvement in curriculum development, although recently some participant educators like EEN06, EEN05 noted they were asked to send some suggestions and input to the Nigerian University commission (NUC). In Nigeria, the NUC oversees the formulation and execution of the EE curriculum. The NUC plays a key role in ensuring that universities adhere to national academic standards while aligning with global trends. As of September 2023, the NUC introduced the Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS), which aims to enhance the quality of education by incorporating interdisciplinary learning, critical skills development, and entrepreneurship (NUC, 2023). The CCMAS is a more flexible and inclusive curriculum, allowing universities to contribute 30% of the content, making it responsive to local needs and promoting entrepreneurial thinking. This curriculum is a significant improvement from the previous Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS), which had been in place since 2007. The recent changes reflect a push toward modernizing education, preparing graduates to address the changing needs of the worldwide market, and fostering entrepreneurship (Vanguard News, 2023). One of the participants EEN01 noted that the new curriculum is not in operations now *“it stands for Core Curriculum Minimum Academic Standard, that's it. they came up with that, although it's not yet operational at the moment”*. This highlights a lag in the implementation of the updated guidelines, despite their announcement.

Additionally, it was noted the curriculum prompted the stereotyping of career paths by portraying entrepreneurship as a last resort if other paths failed. Stereotyping like this discourages students from pursuing entrepreneurial activities, especially in a place setting like

Nigeria where socio-cultural pressure may be on them to pursue “stable and respectable” employment. Educators like EEN02 and EEN07 noted that EE is often seen as a fall-back option rather than a primary career choice. This shows a growing awareness but also underscores that entrepreneurship is often viewed as secondary to traditional careers. Furthermore, the lack of a problem-solving focus in the curriculum was highlighted by participants. Entrepreneurs will succeed when they cannot only identify problems but also come up with solutions. Educators noted that EE needs to go past the theory to influence the mindset of students to navigate and solve real challenges.

Lastly, participant educators noted the curriculum focused on Western education programmes which failed to address the current realities in Nigeria. While these Western programmes offer theoretical knowledge and case studies from developed economies they are often disconnected from the real Nigerian context. This leads to a gap between the curriculum and the actual requirements for nurturing a business in the local market. Therefore, entrepreneurship education must be context-specific, particularly in developing countries where economic structures, cultural norms, and business practices differ significantly from those in the West (Meyer and Landsberg, 2015; Izedonmi and Okafor, 2010).

6.3 Research Objective Three

RO3: Critically identify skills, competencies, and capabilities students develop from participating in EEPs

To address the objective above, data has been triangulated from two key sources: interviews with educators and open-ended responses from students. The triangulation enhances the validity of this study findings by offering different views on the same context, facilitating a more thorough comprehension of the topic. The educators provided valuable insights into the intended learning outcomes and the challenges of delivering entrepreneurship education, focusing on the competencies they aim to impart or have already been imparted to students. On the other hand, the students’ responses reflect their personal experiences and self-perceived skills gained through these programmes. This discussion evaluates how well the skills identified by students align with the goals set by educators and by considering both perspectives together in this discussion, an understanding of the specific practical skills and competencies attained by students in EEPs and an evaluation of the general efficacy of these programmes shall be provided.

The result of the analysis as seen in the previous chapters was structured around four key skill clusters: *Interpersonal and communication skills, Cognitive and Analytical skills, Creative and Innovative Skills, and Strategic and Critical thinking skills*. This gave a guide to analysing the responses from students, as data was analysed under these four clusters. An additional Cluster, Practical skills was identified from their responses, which reflected the development of hands-on vocational skills. EEPs not only enhance business knowledge and skills but also help students develop crucial interpersonal and communication skills, which are essential for building business relationships and partnerships (Galvão, Marques, & Braga, 2020). Educators identified communication and networking as key skills necessary for explaining business ideas and collaborating with stakeholders. Studies emphasize the importance of communication skills as a key outcome of EE, enhancing employability and entrepreneurial readiness (Dagogo, 2014; Brozova et al., 2016; Agboola & Ademiluji, 2021). These skills are critical strategic tools for entrepreneurial success. The responses from students confirmed educators' emphasis on interpersonal and communication skills. They highlighted the areas that had been developed because of participating in EEPs. Some mentioned positive changes in communication: making speeches, speaking to wide audiences as well as individuals; and improved opportunities to network. For instance, students pointed out skills like speaking to an audience, dealing with customers, and teamwork. A student mentioned they developed “strong communications skills”, another mentioned “leadership skills and the ability to communicate and engage with business owners and to work in groups”. These reflections indicate that in addition to business skills, EEPs cultivate the interpersonal skills needed for business management and teamwork. In support of these student responses, Chang & Rieple (2013) and Ifejika (2015) suggests that EEPs that specialize in collaborative projects and real-world interaction offer interpersonal development in skills such as communication and networking. These programmes are intended equip students with skills like how to sell ideas, work with other people, and develop business relationships which are very important in business. This is in line with other objectives held by educators, who aim to enhance communication and interpersonal skills as pivotal in transforming the experiences of students, thus upholding the value of EEPs. Educators like EEN03 emphasize communication skills especially with regards to communicating with customers. In addition, this is supported by EEN09 in statement “*teamwork skills and effective communication are emphasized, as these skills are crucial for entrepreneurial success*”.

Neck and Greene (2011) argue that cognitive flexibility and strategic thinking is important when making entrepreneurial decisions. The cognitive and analytical skills was identified as

set of skills students developed from taking part in EEPs. The opportunity to organize thinking systematically and make choices in conditions of risk is one of the major goals of teaching entrepreneurship. Students supported these views, frequently noting how their problem-solving and decision-making skills have developed because of participating in EEPs. For instance, students in their responses to open ended questions mentioned learning how to take “calculated risks”, “conduct market analysis and validate ideas”, and “budget planning skills”. These skills will prepare students to face real-world business challenges. Recent studies by Firetto and Konack (2024) stress the importance of critical thinking in entrepreneurship, urging students to challenge assumptions and explore issues from multiple perspectives to develop unique solutions. Similarly, Beaty and Duval-Couetil (2024) highlight the importance of creativity, evaluating ideas and solving problems to get students ready for the business world. By encouraging students to generate and assess various solutions, educators enhance their functional and evaluative skills. This feedback from the responses of students supports the idea that entrepreneurship education goes beyond knowledge transfer, focusing on shaping the entrepreneurial mindset and cognitive abilities.

Educators featured in the study emphasized creativity and innovation skills as outcomes of EEPs. These skills help students develop the capacity to recognise distinct possibilities and create value in the competitive market. Kirby (2004) indicated that entrepreneurship education has a goal of developing creativity, promoting an ability in the student to ‘look at things in a new way’, to create new ideas, and to seek out new solutions to business problems. When it comes to creativity, the skills educators highlighted included development of fintech apps such as ‘piggy vest- the online savings app’, ‘lemonade finance’ which focuses on cross border transactions (EEN05), and also a ‘solar panel bag’ (EEN06) as products from their university graduates, and responses from survey included ‘tech skills’, ‘web designing’, ‘graphic design’, ‘event planning’. The findings of Pittaway and Cope (2007) support the idea that practical learning in EE is crucial for the advancement of students' innovative capacities. These results show there is an element of experiential learning in the programmes undertaken by students in some Nigerian universities, by employing practical and experiential methods, students actively participate in activities that enable them to explore imaginative concepts, address practical challenges, and implement groundbreaking solutions.

The fourth group of skills that was recurrent in discussions with educators was the *strategic and critical thinking skills*. Through participation in these programmes, Students will acquire the essential skills needed for effective long-term planning and informed decision-making, both

of which are crucial in business contexts. The responses of students supported this, they highlighted the skills they gained which include critical thinking, strategic management, the ability to make transforming decisions, and leadership. One of the recurring talents mentioned by students was 'resilience', which refers to the ability to effectively respond to obstacles to safeguard the firm. Neck and Corbett (2023) found that incorporating market simulations and project-based learning in EEPs significantly enhanced students' ability to assess risks and identify market opportunities, equipping them with strategic thinking and long-term planning skills essential for entrepreneurial success.

Through discussions with participant educators and responses from surveys, researcher noted that most skills mentioned were practical skills. Some of the skills highlighted by educators included 'bag making', 'footwear making', 'make up skills' or 'cosmetology' (beauty enhancement skills), 'baking', 'furniture making', 'agribusiness', 'photography', 'cinematography'. Students and graduates in response highlighted practical skills like 'hair making', 'Bagmaking', 'fashion designing', 'sewing skills', 'soap making', 'agriculture production skills (responses from survey) and lots more. While educators prioritised the development of strategic and cognitive abilities, students highly valued the vocational training component. According to Hynes and Richardson (2007) EE should aim to achieve a harmonious combination of cultivating comprehensive entrepreneurial competencies and practical skills. These tangible talents are crucial for effectively transforming entrepreneurial concepts into tangible outcomes. From the analysis of data from students and graduates, there is evidence that Nigerian students who have taken part in EEPs have used hands-on skills to develop products, which is undoubtedly beneficial for self-employment and small-scale entrepreneurship. However, these abilities may be viewed as restricted if they are not integrated with larger entrepreneurial competencies such as corporate strategy, financial management, or market analysis. Focussing solely on vocational skills such as the practical skills of bag manufacturing may limit students' capacity to expand their firms, innovate, or shift to more sustainable, growth-oriented ventures. As a result, while these practical talents are useful, there is a need for a mix of craftsmanship and strategic entrepreneurial thinking at a basic level. Developing only specific vocational skills without integrating them into broader entrepreneurial frameworks might limit students' long-term success (Hannon, 2020).

6.4 Research Objective Four

RO4: Explore the effectiveness of teaching approaches and perceived university support in fostering entrepreneurial learning and intentions among students in Nigerian universities

The findings presented in the preceding Chapter 5 suggest that the exposure that students have of the utilised teaching methods and the support provided by the university does not automatically lead to an inherent increase in entrepreneurial behaviour. The results from the Hypotheses developed for this objective each examined different aspects of the link between university support, teaching methods, and entrepreneurial intentions. The findings provided valuable insights into the role that both teaching methods and university support structures play in fostering EE learning and intentions among students in Nigerian Universities.

The first hypothesis (H1) suggested that students who perceived strong support from their university, along with teaching methods, would exhibit more positive attitudes and intentions toward EE. The results indicate that the provision of university support, encompassing the availability of entrepreneurial resources, mentorship programs, and networking opportunities, significantly influences students' perspectives on entrepreneurship education. When students perceive their university as offering sufficient backing for entrepreneurial activities, such as access to financial resources, business incubation centres, or links to experienced entrepreneurs, they are more likely to consider entrepreneurship as a feasible and appealing career choice. This institutional support serves as a fundamental basis, providing students with the confidence to pursue entrepreneurial activities. However, the efficiency of teaching methods which is how EE is delivered varies among departments and settings.

The effectiveness of EE teaching methods varies by department and universities. The way departments structure their entrepreneurship programmes typically causes these differences. Participatory and experiential learning methods like case studies, simulations, and project-based learning increase student engagement since they simulate practical entrepreneurship issues. This hands-on method enables students to apply theoretical concepts to real-world situations, which boosts entrepreneurial intentions. On the other hand, Traditional Lectures can teach basic principles but may lack interactive features that engage students in entrepreneurship. Therefore, students in these contexts may feel withdrawn from the business, lowering their level of participation and motivation.

The results of H1, which provided partial support for the hypothesis that university support favourably promotes entrepreneurial intentions, underscore the importance of both institutional backing and the delivery methods of EE. The findings indicate that while strong university support, such as access to entrepreneurship centers, funding opportunities, and expert guidance, provides a critical foundation for entrepreneurial learning, it is the engagement and creativity

in teaching approaches that make students more likely to translate this support into entrepreneurial intentions. Undergraduates, for instance, recorded the highest levels of perceived university support and, consequently, the highest levels of entrepreneurial goals, according to this study's findings, suggesting that strong support can positively impact students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship. However, the lower perceived support among postgraduates and graduates, coupled with more traditional or passive teaching methods, highlights a gap where university support may not fully translate into entrepreneurial intentions if it is not paired with engaging and innovative teaching methods.

The results suggest that students benefit most when strong institutional support is combined with hands-on learning experiences such as experiential learning, simulations, and practical exercises, which not only prepare them for entrepreneurship but also inspire them to pursue it (Neck & Corbett, 2018). As participant educators pointed out in this study, the delivery of EE plays a pivotal role in promoting student engagement and intention formation. Without creative teaching methods, even robust institutional support may not be able to drive entrepreneurial outcomes among students. In conclusion, the results emphasize the need for entrepreneurship education to be not only well-supported institutionally but also delivered in a way that actively engages students, making them feel confident and prepared to initiate entrepreneurial endeavours.

The second hypothesis (H2) suggested that support from universities and effective teaching strategies would have a positive impact on students' subjective norms, defined as the perceived social expectations from peers, family, or society concerning entrepreneurial behaviour. The results provided partial support for this hypothesis. It was found that teaching methods significantly influenced subjective norms, indicating that interactive and experience-based pedagogical approaches can assist in altering students' views of entrepreneurship as a socially acceptable and valuable career option. However, university support mechanisms, such as mentorship or institutional encouragement, exhibited a more inconsistent effect, suggesting that formal support systems alone may not significantly influence students' perceptions of social approval. Despite the advancements in pedagogy, the results also highlight the ongoing impact of cultural and familial expectations. In numerous contexts, entrepreneurship is still regarded as a riskier or less esteemed path compared to traditional employment. This observation is consistent with previous research (Ajzen, 1991; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993; Shinnar et al., 2014) that underscores the importance of subjective norms in moderating the formation of intentions, particularly in collectivist cultures. Educator EEN03 noted that even

when students do not plan to start businesses, the problem-solving and innovative thinking fostered by EE still improve their employability in traditional sectors. These transferable skills may gradually alter norms over time, as graduates illustrate the significance of entrepreneurial thinking in broader career contexts. Nevertheless, institutional initiatives aimed at shaping subjective norms must be complemented by broader cultural engagement beyond the university environment, as educational interventions alone are inadequate to overcome deeply rooted social expectations.

The third hypothesis (H3) proposed that interactive teaching methods and strong university support would enhance students' perceived behavioural control over entrepreneurial behaviour. This hypothesis was partially supported. The findings revealed that while participatory and hands-on teaching approaches such as business simulations, group projects, and real-world problem-solving positively influenced students' sense of entrepreneurial capability, institutional support from universities played a more limited and inconsistent role. This suggests that although support mechanisms such as entrepreneurship centres, mentorship programmes, and funding initiatives exist in some Nigerian universities, their impact on students' confidence to act entrepreneurially remains uneven. This partial support reflects broader systemic issues in Nigeria's higher education system. Many universities, particularly in the South-East and South-South zones, struggle with underfunded EE units, limited access to infrastructure, and weak integration of institutional support into the academic curriculum (Akuegwu & Nwi-ue, 2016; Nwachukwu & Okpo, 2018). In such settings, students may be aware of entrepreneurship initiatives but lack the opportunity to engage with them meaningfully, resulting in low perceived relevance and limited influence on their self-efficacy. Even in better-resourced institutions in the South-West, university support may exist primarily at a symbolic or administrative level rather than being embedded in the actual teaching and learning process.

Moreover, the data suggest that students' sense of entrepreneurial agency is most influenced by the extent to which teaching allows them to apply, reflect on, and internalise entrepreneurial concepts. This aligns with Bandura's (1997) notion that perceived behavioural control or self-efficacy develops through mastery experiences and iterative engagement, not merely through exposure to institutional resources. Nigerian students, often navigating a context marked by limited job prospects and social pressure toward traditional careers, require learning environments that do more than offer support they need teaching strategies that foster confidence through active involvement and problem-solving. Therefore, the findings indicate

that for EE in Nigerian universities to meaningfully enhance perceived behavioural control, institutional support must be closely aligned with and embedded within pedagogical delivery.

Hypothesis four (H4) proposed that stronger university support combined with engaging teaching methods would lead to more positive behavioural intentions toward entrepreneurship. The findings of the study fully support this hypothesis, showing that students who received both strong institutional support and were exposed to interactive teaching methods were more likely to report high entrepreneurial intentions. This suggests that when university support is effectively combined with engaging, real-world learning experiences, students are more motivated to translate their learning into entrepreneurial actions. These findings align with Neck, Greene, and Brush (2014), who argue that action-based learning helps bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical entrepreneurial intention. Similarly, Piperopoulos and Dimov (2015) emphasize the importance of experiential learning in developing entrepreneurial self-efficacy, which is a key driver of behavioural intention. The full support for H4 confirms that combining strong university support with innovative, practical teaching methods is essential for fostering entrepreneurial intentions among students. In conclusion, the results from this study's analysis demonstrate that university support is highly effective when paired with engaging teaching methods, fully supporting H4. The interplay of these elements fosters an atmosphere that motivates students to cultivate and pursue their entrepreneurial ambitions, highlighting the importance of a comprehensive strategy in EE.

The final hypothesis (H5) proposed that the interactions between university support and teaching methods/pedagogy would influence Nigerian students' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, ultimately shaping their entrepreneurial intentions. The findings from this study offer partial support for this hypothesis, revealing the complexity of these relationships in the Nigerian context. The results from this study's analysis demonstrate that university support and effective teaching methods/pedagogy contribute significantly to the promotion of entrepreneurial aspirations among Nigerian students. The combined effect of these factors was more significant in shaping students' attitudes and perceived behavioural control than in influencing subjective norms. This suggests that in Nigerian universities, EE is most effective when institutional support is combined with engaging, practical teaching methods.

However, results from this study findings show the impact on subjective norms students' perceptions of social and family expectations regarding entrepreneurship was more limited. In

Nigeria, societal and cultural factors, such as family expectations to pursue traditional career paths, exert a strong influence, and are less easily shaped by university support or teaching methods alone. These external cultural influences appear to play a larger role in shaping subjective norms than educational programmes. The findings align with studies by Adekiya and Ibrahim (2016) and Iwu et al (2019), which suggests that subjective norms act as a mediator between EE and EI with family and community expectations being highly influential. The partial support for H5 suggests that while university support and teaching methods/pedagogy strongly influence attitudes and behavioural control, altering subjective norms may require broader societal and cultural shifts. As Educator EEN03 highlighted during the interviews, parental engagement is key to shaping students' perceptions of entrepreneurship. He emphasized that universities should “*engage the parents*” early on to ensure they understand and support their children’s entrepreneurial education. This aligns with the study’s finding that subjective norms, shaped by family expectations and cultural values, are not easily changed by university support alone. EEN03's suggestion to involve parents through a teachers-parent association reinforces the need for universities to go beyond teaching students and involve families in endorsing entrepreneurship as a promising career direction.

In conclusion, H5 highlights the need for a holistic approach to EE in Nigeria, where institutional support and innovative teaching methods/pedagogy work together to shape students’ entrepreneurial mindsets. However, the challenge of changing subjective norms which are heavily influenced by family and cultural factors remains significant, indicating that broader societal changes may be necessary to fully support students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigeria.

6.5 Research Objective Five

RO5: Develop a framework for the effective assessment of entrepreneurship programmes in Nigerian universities

In addressing RO5, which investigates how to enhance EE in Nigeria to help students develop the necessary entrepreneurial skills and intentions. The following discussion identifies gaps in current programmes, proposes necessary improvements, and provides an organised approach in evaluating the success of these programmes. The discussion with educators and responses from students and graduates, highlighted several gaps but also suggestions for the improvement of EE. The suggestions for improvement are grouped in four parts: *Community engagement*

and support, Curriculum and institutional development, Infrastructure and resource enhancement, and lastly policy and institutional Alignment.

Suggestions for Improvement and the Emerging framework

The first part of the recommendations focused on Community Engagement and Support; this plays a critical role in integrating EE with real-world experiences. Participant educators highlighted the necessity of bridging the gap between universities and local industries to offer students practical, hands-on experiences. For example, EEN05 stated, *“We need industry to be involved... University is to have a strong relationship with practical entrepreneurs.”* This input suggests the importance of fostering connections between students and community stakeholders, such as local businesses, to support entrepreneurial growth.

EEN02 also stressed the disconnection between universities and communities, saying: *“We are so much detached from the community... That university and community relationship is not there. If we can introduce it, it will go a long way to improve entrepreneurship teaching.”* EEN02 highlights a disconnect which as students may miss the opportunity to interact with business communities or local entrepreneurs which will help create networking opportunities. The community- university engagement can be done in form of mentorship programmes, or guest lecturers and workshops as EEN05 and EEN01 have noted some entrepreneurial activities where entrepreneurs are invited to their universities for seminars and workshops, through university-industry partnerships where universities could establish formal partnerships with local industries allowing the students engage in internships or apprenticeships with SMEs. For example, a university in Lagos could collaborate with local tech startups in Yaba (popularly known as Yabacon valley) to provide students with hands-on experience in software development, digital marketing to business management (Akinyele, 2020). Universities could also integrate community-based projects where students seek to solve the problems faced by local business, as noted in previous discussions the development of ‘Lemonade finance’ App which helps with cross border financial transactions as mentioned by EEN05. In addition, as Olawale (2021) suggested, universities could establish entrepreneurship hubs where students, local entrepreneurs and industry experts collaborate, this makes opportunities for collaboration. Also, students/graduate responses from open ended questions supported this as responses included *“Entrepreneurship education can be improved in the university by the university organizing seminars and inviting people who have made it to share their journey and give honest opinions and tips on how to go about owning firms”*(response, 8), *“Invitation of more*

entrepreneurship expertise, planning entrepreneurship seminars with other schools to have an experience, allowing student have their personal business in school”(response, 31).

Within the framework developed by the researcher, *Stakeholder Engagement and feedback* emerges as an important pillar of the proposed model, encompassing collaborations with local industries, entrepreneurship centers, and professional networks. These partnerships allow students to gain practical insights and experiences of different entrepreneurs like the struggles, victories, and skills needed . By engaging stakeholders effectively, entrepreneurship education programmes can integrate seamlessly with the broader entrepreneurial environment, ensuring they are relevant and have positive impact on individuals and communities. It is essential to note that stakeholder engagement should extend beyond just industry partners. Educators, who contribute significantly to developing and developing EE, are also critical stakeholders. As noted by the researcher, there is a risk that their involvement may be overlooked if the focus is solely on external partners. Educators must be empowered and included in the development and execution of entrepreneurship programmes to ensure that they can effectively integrate practical insights from industry with academic knowledge. Although EEN05 notes that there is a platform where the Ministry of Education has asked for inputs on entrepreneurship policy or curriculum matters it appears to be more of a formality than a meaningful engagement. While such platforms have the potential to drive real change, there is often a lack of genuine collaboration between policymakers and educators, which limits the practical impact of these consultations.

Another major theme from the interviews was the need for curriculum innovation. Participant educators expressed their dissatisfaction on the current curriculum, characterizing it as ‘rigid and outdated’ , including EEN01 and EEN07, pointed out that the curriculum is outdated and does not adequately prepare students for the current market landscape. They recommended regular reviews and updates to the curriculum to ensure it meets the evolving needs of both students and industries. EEN02 underlined that including courses and practical experiences connected to diverse students' discipline and not just business-related disciplines will not only improve teaching but also enhance student involvement and participation, he noted students in other discipline like sciences don't show interest when one is teaching them general practical skills in comment he stated

“then I started telling them, for example, you are telling students who are into nursing, microbiology, some of these other basic medical sciences, you are teaching them about

business. One of the questions they get to ask is, what am I going to do with business? (Interview EEN02) . This is consistent with the more general demand for educational reforms that link learning with useful, career-oriented experience. EEN01 noted: *"By the time you start linking them up with some of the opportunities that exist within their discipline, it helps to improve the teaching. It makes the teaching more interesting, and they become more involved in the course."* This aligns with the broader call for educational reforms that connect academic learning with practical, career-oriented experiences. This is supported by responses of students and graduates *"Teaching entrepreneurship beyond the primary entrepreneurship skills"* (response 198), *"More entrepreneurship programmes should be introduced"*(response, 212)

In response to these insights, the researcher developed the second pillar of the framework, *Programme Design and Content*. This pillar advocates for a dynamic and evolving curriculum that integrates both theoretical and practical knowledge. The focus on this pillar is continuously updating the curriculum as the need arises to ensure that EPPs in Nigerian Universities are practically relevant. The integration of teaching methods under this pillar, as highlighted by EEN09 (who emphasized experiential learning), ensures that the curriculum does not remain static or overly theoretical. Instead, it includes interactive pedagogies that engage students and help them develop practical, hands-on skills.

Another theme from the participant educator feedback was the lack of infrastructure necessary to adequately support EE. Some suggestions focused on improving the physical resources available to both student, educators and the universities. EEN01 and EEN06 highlighted the need for facilities like innovation hubs that could bridge the gap between theory and practical application. These hubs would allow students to conceptualize ideas, build prototypes, and ultimately develop real-world solutions. The lack of adequate resources was another major challenge identified. EEN01 pointed out the absence of innovation hubs: *"We don't have an innovation hub on campus... you want a facility where students can conceptualize an idea and walk into the hub to build the prototype."* Also, EEN05 noted *'innovation happens with experiments'*, noting the importance of the practical aspects of EEPs. In addition, students also provided their feedback on improvement with examples from survey: *"By providing the resources and materials needed"*(response 233), *"More emphasis must be placed on entrepreneurship and resources should be made available for effective teaching"* (response 244). EEN06 criticized current government funding models, arguing that universities need more sustainable and structured mechanisms for fostering long-term entrepreneurial growth.

This highlights the need for consistent funding to maintain and expand entrepreneurship clusters and innovation hubs over time. In addition, educators emphasized the importance of providing financial and technical resources for long-term support. EEN05 pointed out the lack of technical tools and infrastructure, which are essential for both educators' and students' success.

This feedback was instrumental in shaping the *Institutional Support pillar* in the researcher's framework. The pillar stresses the importance of providing entrepreneurship centres and other essential resources that can facilitate the hands-on application of entrepreneurial knowledge. By offering students these facilities, universities can move beyond theory, giving students the opportunity to experiment, and bring their business ideas to life. To further develop the Institutional Support pillar, it was crucial to focus on three key areas. First, Support for Students involves offering funding, mentorship, and practical spaces like innovation hubs to help students bring entrepreneurial ideas to life (EEN01). Next, Support for Universities encompasses providing essential infrastructure, financial aid, and faculty training to equip educators with the tools needed to foster EE (EEN04, EEN02). Finally, Policy Alignment ensures cohesive efforts between educational and governmental bodies, enabling effective implementation of entrepreneurship policies to promote growth (EEN02). However, it is also crucial to address university-imposed restrictions that limit students' entrepreneurial activities. As one respondent noted, "*We should be allowed to run our businesses*" (Response 209), while another stressed the need for "*less restrictions on innovative ideas*" (Response 189). These concerns highlight the need for universities to revise policies that restrict students from actively pursuing business ventures while studying. Universities can foster an environment where students have the freedom and support to innovate and grow their entrepreneurial skills by lifting barriers that restrict students.

Lastly, *The Impact and Evaluation* pillar emerged from the challenges educators highlighted regarding assessing the success of entrepreneurship education. EEN05 emphasized that simply teaching theory doesn't guarantee entrepreneurial success: "*The measure of success is that the person must be able to start something, innovate, or reposition an existing business.*" This underscores the need for evaluating programs based on tangible outcomes such as student startups and innovations. Additionally, EEN02 pointed out the lack of follow-up mechanisms to assess students' entrepreneurial progress after graduation, suggesting a gap in current evaluation methods. For the Nigerian context, this proposes that monitoring the success of EEPs be implemented through a structured follow-up survey system. This survey would

evaluate graduates' entrepreneurial success by measuring new startups, innovations, and contributions to existing businesses. In addition, the survey would also analyse post-graduation support and entrepreneurial environment challenges. The researcher suggests conducting the survey after 6 months, 1 year, and 3 years post-graduation to track development. This would show entrepreneurial outcomes and programme success continuously. In terms of delivery, the researcher proposes using online platforms and mobile-friendly surveys to increase accessibility, given the widespread use of mobile devices in Nigeria. Additionally, collaboration with alumni networks could ensure better participation and ongoing engagement with graduates. The framework for assessing Entrepreneurship Education Programs (EEPs) is visually presented in the diagram below:

Figure 20: Proposed Framework for the Evaluation of EEPs in Nigeria

Source: Developed by Researcher

As shown in Figure 20 above the framework has four main pillars each of which is essential for making entrepreneurship education both applicable and effective within the Nigerian context. Programme Design and Content focuses on creating relevant entrepreneurship courses and integrating modern teaching methods. Educators highlighted the need for a flexible curriculum that keeps pace with industry trends. By incorporating practical teaching methods like case studies and problem-solving exercises, students gain skills necessary to address business challenges (Rae, 2012; Neck & Corbett, 2018). Institutional Support provides the necessary infrastructure, such as innovation hubs and funding. As noted by educators, the absence of these resources limits students' ability to apply entrepreneurial knowledge. Policy alignment is crucial here to ensure that both government and institutional efforts foster entrepreneurship (Adeola, 2020). Stakeholder Engagement involves collaboration between universities, industries, and the community. This pillar enhances curriculum relevance by integrating industry insights, mentorship, and practical experiences, which are critical to fostering entrepreneurship (Lackéus, 2015). Lastly, the Impact and Evaluation pillar ensures that EEPs have measurable outcomes, such as tracking entrepreneurial intentions and student satisfaction. Rigorous evaluation helps universities identify areas for improvement, ensuring that EEPs remain effective (Gibb, 2002).

The proposed framework has pillars: Programme Design and Content, Institutional Support, Stakeholder Engagement, and Impact and Evaluation, which are vital to the assessment of EEPs in Nigeria. To phrase it better, the framework doesn't just identify these elements but emphasizes the interconnectedness of these pillars. For instance, Programme Design and Content is not isolated but deeply influenced by Stakeholder Engagement, feedback from the industry and local community directly shapes curriculum flexibility and relevance. Similarly, Institutional Support is integral to the successful implementation of any entrepreneurship programme, ensuring that infrastructural and financial resources are available to facilitate impactful teaching methods.

The framework may be presented as a flexible model that promotes continuous feedback loops among these pillars. Feedback obtained through Impact and Evaluation could directly influence modifications in Programme Design or initiate improvements in Institutional Support. This dynamic, cyclical interaction across the pillars offers a more comprehensive and adaptive approach for evaluating how well EEPs work in Nigeria. By ensuring these components function interdependently, universities may cultivate an atmosphere that is both responsive and proactive in addressing the requirements of students and the economy at large.

In conclusion, the framework developed by researcher offers a comprehensive method for evaluating the success of courses on EE. Universities can make sure that their programmes are not only giving students the skills they need, but also increasing the entrepreneurial and economic landscape by putting a strong emphasis on essential components like, institutional support, curriculum relevance, stakeholder engagement, and the wider impact on the entrepreneurial environment.

6.2 Research Implications

This study found that Nigerian universities face major challenges despite their abundant people, material resources, and government programmes to promote EE. This study has four implications: implications for theory, implications for practice, implications for research and implications for policy makers.

6.2.1 Theoretical Implications of the study

The study's findings significantly advance our theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurship education's function in forming students' intentions and capabilities for entrepreneurship. A significant conclusion is a reinforcement of Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (1991), which asserts that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control affect entrepreneurial intentions. Additionally, this study found that institutional support is very important in shaping students' confidence to pursuing entrepreneurship. Institutional support can either boost or hinder their aspirations in this field. This finding indicates that, in the context of developing economies, traditional theories of entrepreneurial intention should include the structural and resource-based support systems that students depend on to realize their entrepreneurial ambitions. When considering EE in underdeveloped nations such as Nigeria, one of the main implications in relation to TBP is that while the TBP suggests that attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control influences entrepreneurial intentions, this study found that subjective norms were less responsive to university support compared to attitudes and perceived control. This highlights the context-specific influence of cultural and familial expectations, which were found to play a stronger role in shaping students' entrepreneurial decisions. The findings of this study suggest that while university support and teaching methods can effectively influence attitudes and perceived control, subjective norms are more resistant to change and require broader engagement beyond the university. This points to a need for expanding the TPB to better account for the cultural dynamics present in regions like Nigeria (Liñán & Chen, 2009).

The findings further support Bandura's (1997) theory of self-efficacy, particularly highlighting the influence of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on the formation of entrepreneurial intentions. The findings of the study indicated that students engaged in experiential learning activities, including business simulations and internships, exhibited elevated levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy, aligning with the view that hands-on, action-based learning is crucial for building confidence in entrepreneurial abilities (Neck, Greene, & Brush, 2014). This supports the theoretical argument that action-based learning enhances students' capacity to engage with entrepreneurial tasks, thereby increasing their perceived ability to succeed as entrepreneurs. It further suggests that self-efficacy is a key mediator between teaching methods and entrepreneurial intentions, and EE theory should place greater importance on the role of experiential learning in boosting students' entrepreneurial confidence.

Moreover, the findings highlight the need for a comprehensive strategy to EE, one that integrates not only teaching methods and university support but also external influences such as family and societal expectations. In line with institutional theory, which emphasizes the role of formal structures (such as universities) in shaping entrepreneurial ecosystems (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983), this study demonstrates that universities must do more than provide mentorship and entrepreneurial resources; they must also engage with external social systems that influence students' career choices. The study's findings suggest that institutional support is necessary but insufficient without addressing the subjective norms shaped by family and cultural values, particularly in contexts where entrepreneurship is not traditionally viewed as a prestigious or secure career path (Nowiński et al., 2019).

A key contribution of this study is the introduction of parental engagement as a theoretical consideration in EE. As noted by EEN03, parents play a critical role in shaping students' perceptions of entrepreneurship, and universities should involve families in the education process to create a supportive environment for entrepreneurial development. This expands existing theories by suggesting that parental and community engagement are crucial elements in influencing subjective norms and fostering entrepreneurial intentions. In contexts like Nigeria, where family expectations often push students toward more conventional career paths, engaging parents early in the education process could help shift societal norms in favour of entrepreneurship (Fayolle & Gailly, 2008).

The study contributes to theoretical ideas about institutional support as well. Although models like network theory and mentorship models by Rauch & Hulsink (2015) and Social Capital

Theory highlight the significance of networks and mentorship, this study proposes that institutional support should be regarded as a fundamental determinant of entrepreneurial success, rather than merely a facilitating aspect. Alongside social networks and mentorship, formal institutional frameworks such as access to start-up financing, entrepreneurial ecosystems, and incubation centers are crucial for students to convert their ideas into sustainable enterprises. This redirects the emphasis of entrepreneurship education theory to the crucial role that universities and other institutions serve in actively facilitating entrepreneurial endeavours through financial mentorship programmes and strategic partnerships with industrial partners.

Entrepreneurship education methods developed in Western contexts may not fully suit the realities of developing countries like Nigeria, where socio-economic challenges and institutional barriers significantly affect student outcomes. This study highlights the need for context-specific adaptations. In Nigeria, issues like lack of funding, ineffective government policies, and institutional corruption hinder the success of entrepreneurship programs (Kraus et al., 2018). Western models, which emphasize individualism and venture creation, do not adequately address local challenges such as informal markets, limited capital, and entrenched cultural norms (Jones, Maas & Pittaway, 2017). To improve EE in Nigeria, alternative approaches as participant educators have suggested, could include integrating community-based entrepreneurship models, fostering collective businesses, and emphasizing resourcefulness in the informal economy. These adjustments would make EE more relevant and effective for students in Nigeria's unique socio-economic environment (Ndedi, 2019). By incorporating local context into future models, entrepreneurship education can better align with the needs and realities of Nigerian students.

6.2.2 The Implication for Practice

In regard to practice, this study provided essential insights and guidelines for EEPs that will benefit both educators and students in Nigeria concerning design. One of the major practical implications is improving student-teacher allocation. This will address the issue of overload on educators, with few entrepreneurship educators being responsible for teaching large classes with limited resources. While hiring more educators and reducing class sizes may be ideal, resource limitations in Nigerian universities make this challenging. This study suggests alternative strategies could involve using innovative teaching methods that maximize existing resources while still maintaining a high level of engagement. One example is the option that could involve peer-to-peer learning, where advanced students or teaching assistants mentor

younger students under the guidance of the instructor. In Ghana, a similar model has been used in EEPs where students collaborate on real-life projects, reducing the burden on educators while fostering teamwork and problem-solving skills (Fadahunsi & Rosa, 2020). Additionally, using case-based or problem-based learning can help educators handle large classes more effectively by encouraging active learning. This model has been used successfully in several African countries, such as South Africa, where EE focuses on real-world challenges, encouraging students to engage actively and self-learn, which will lessening the load on the educator (Jones, Maas & Pittaway, 2017).

The findings of this study suggest the integration of experiential learning into teaching methods. The results showed that hands-on approaches, such as business simulations, internships, and project-based learning, are crucial in fostering entrepreneurial intentions. Universities should prioritize these action-based learning opportunities, enabling students to apply theoretical knowledge to entrepreneurial challenges in their environment. Creating opportunities for students to engage in entrepreneurial incubators or collaborate with local businesses will help enhance their entrepreneurial intentions and prepare them for real-world ventures.

In the Nigerian context, ongoing professional development and training for educators is critical to ensuring EE remains relevant and effective. Universities must prioritize continuous training programmes that keep educators up to date with the latest entrepreneurial trends and teaching methodologies. This includes integrating insights from industry experts and local entrepreneurs into the curriculum to enhance practical learning. For example, partnerships with successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria like Tony Elumelu Foundations, which support entrepreneurial training across Africa, or initiatives like SMEDAN (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria) which can provide valuable case studies and mentorship opportunities for both educators and students. These training programmes can be funded by public-private partnerships or government grants, similar to initiatives like the Nigeria Industrial Revolution Plan, which supports capacity building across educational institutions (Adeola, 2020).

6.2.3 Implication for Research

The findings of this reveals that while EEPs in higher education institutions have indeed grown significantly over the last decade, there remains considerable scope for further research to explore their actual impact on fostering entrepreneurial activity. Studies like Yatu, Aderemi &

Ampofo (2018) and Sofoluwe et al. (2013) emphasize that while the quantity of programmes has increased, the quality and practical outcomes of these programmes are not as well-documented. More in-depth studies are needed to determine how effectively these programmes translate into real entrepreneurial ventures and sustainable business outcomes among graduates. In addition, this research challenges existing entrepreneurship education models, which are primarily rooted in Western frameworks, and may not fully represent the unique socio-economic and institutional obstacles encountered in these regions. Further investigation is needed to examine how curriculum and teaching methods can be adapted to align with the entrepreneurial ecosystem and resources in developing economies (Abaho, Olomi & Urassa, 2019).

6.2.4 Implication for Policymakers

About policy, this study offers significant insights for policymakers aiming to improve EE in Nigerian universities. These policymakers in Nigeria include government agencies such as the Federal Ministry of Education (FME), the National University Commission (NUC), University administrators, and State-Level educational authorities. One significant challenge raised by educators was EEN05 emphasis on the issue of "japa," or brain drain, where qualified lecturers leave the country in search of better working conditions abroad. This exodus of skilled educators weakens the capacity of universities to deliver effective EE. To address this, policymakers must consider improving the remuneration and working conditions of lecturers to reduce the brain drain and retain talent within Nigerian institutions. Studies such as Mbah and Nzeh (2021) support this, highlighting the impact of brain drain on education quality.

Another concern raised by EEN01 was the implementation of existing entrepreneurship policies. While Nigeria has several robust policies aimed at promoting entrepreneurship, the gap lies in effective implementation. This points to the need for an independent body tasked with monitoring and evaluating how allocated funds for entrepreneurship development are spent. This body would ensure transparency and accountability in the disbursement and use of resources, thus improving the success rate of entrepreneurship programmes. At the state level, educational authorities should also localize EE policies. Different Nigerian areas have different economic and industrial issues. State authorities should collaborate with local universities to customize EE to regional requirements. For example, Agribusiness entrepreneurship should be taught using actual examples and case studies in agricultural regions. This approach is further supported by studies, which shows that aligning EE with local industries not only enhances

student engagement but also leads to more practical and successful entrepreneurial outcomes (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015; Iwu et al., 2019).

6.5 Chapter Summary

The sixth chapter provides a discussion of the data gathered from students, graduates and educators via surveys with open-ended questions based on the study's five objectives. One of the most significant findings is that vocational skills are over-emphasized, without promoting more general entrepreneurial skills. Students said that critical thought, creativity, and problem-solving should get more attention. These are skills needed to initiate and sustain a business in a changing environment. Concerns were also raised by educators about the lack of resources and institutional support, which makes it harder for them to teach these important skills successfully. There was also a clear disconnect between what was taught in the classroom and how entrepreneurial ideas were used in the real world. This was because there were not many chances for experiential education like internships and business incubators.

An additional significant finding was that students did not receive much institutional support. A lot of students thought that universities didn't give them enough access to funds, mentorship, or networks of entrepreneurs. Students didn't have confidence in their business skills because they weren't getting enough help, and many decided not to start their businesses after graduation. In addition, both students and teachers stressed the need to change the curriculum to better match the needs of the business world with entrepreneurship education. These findings led to the development of a framework for assessing the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education programs in Nigeria. The framework is designed to address the specific challenges identified in the study and consists of four key components: Programme design and content, teaching methods and pedagogy, Institutional support, and Stakeholder engagement and feedback.

The originality of this study is its focus on the context-specific challenges that Nigerian universities face when delivering effective entrepreneurship education, particularly from the perspective of stakeholders such as educators, which is often overlooked. While much research focuses on student outcomes, this study emphasizes the critical role that educators play in shaping EE, as well as the institutional barriers they face, such as limited resources, inadequate training, and insufficient support for their entrepreneurial growth. Educators are sometimes disregarded in conversations about enhancing entrepreneurship education, despite their critical role in creating a learning environment that encourages practical entrepreneurial abilities

(O'Connor, 2018). This study addresses institutional inadequacies that impede the success of EE by providing a paradigm that combines both educator and student viewpoints. It calls for a more comprehensive strategy that includes educator training and support, acknowledging that providing educators with entrepreneurial skills and resources is critical to increasing overall educational quality. This study adds to the growing body of literature demonstrating the importance of considering all key stakeholders in EE, ensuring that reforms address the needs of both educators and students to build a more effective and sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem in Nigeria.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSIONS AND RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

7.0 Introduction

This chapter addresses the conclusion derived from the study findings. The conclusions summarize the key insights gained from examining the effectiveness of EEPs in Nigerian universities, particularly about the challenges faced by educators, the skills and capabilities students gain from EEPs, the role of perceived university support and teaching method and lastly the framework developed. In addition, the limitations faced during the research process include the challenges related to data collection, sample size, and the scope of the study will be discussed. These limitations give the necessary background for understanding the results and point out areas that need more study in the future.

7.1 Summary of Study

In a developing economy, this study sought to understand how EE affected students' aspirations to start their own businesses. This broad aim was designed to explore not only the student's intentions to participate in entrepreneurial activities but also to explore certain factors such as university support and teaching methods that affect their subsequent intentions and the perspective of educators on the agenda of EE. As the data gathering procedure moved from one step to the next, the research used a mixed-method approach and an exploratory sequential design. The first stage of data collection was collected through interviews with the educators to identify their challenges, perceptions of EE, and pedagogies used in EE. Having developed surveys to determine student perceptions, and whether different pedagogical approaches foster students' entrepreneurial intention, the second step of the research profited from the initial stage.

The qualitative data in the first stage was obtained from interviews with educators, this informed the design of survey. The qualitative findings by examining the institutional challenges that limit the efficacy of EE. Educators indicated that they encountered resource limitations, such as excessive class numbers, and inadequate, and restricted access to entrepreneurial networks. Moreover, educators perceived that vocational skills were excessively prioritized in numerous programmes, but comprehensive entrepreneurial competencies, including problem-solving, creativity, and risk management, were inadequately

addressed. The interviews highlighted the necessity for curriculum revision to more effectively correspond with industry requirements and the changing economic environment.

The correlation analysis in the Nigerian context suggests that institutional support and engaging teaching methods are essential for fostering entrepreneurial intentions and building confidence among students. However, subjective norms influenced by family and cultural expectations remain a challenge, indicating that educational efforts must be complemented by broader societal engagement. To nurture a robust entrepreneurial culture in Nigeria, universities need to integrate hands-on learning, provide strong institutional support, and work actively with families and communities to reshape cultural perceptions of entrepreneurship. This holistic approach is key to overcoming the barriers posed by deep rooted societal expectations in Nigeria and can help promote entrepreneurship as a viable and respected career path in the country.

The analysis conducted in this study directly aligns with the primary objective of the research, which was to evaluate the effectiveness of EEPs in Nigerian universities and their influence on entrepreneurial intentions. The findings indicate that the entrepreneurial intentions of students are positively impacted by the perceived support from their universities and the quality of teaching methods, in addition it highlights a direct relationship between tangible university support structures and the likelihood of students pursuing entrepreneurial activities. This study highlights the necessity of adopting more interactive and practical approaches in entrepreneurship education. This aligns with the study's objective to enhance the significance and effectiveness of EEPs in equipping students with essential skills for entrepreneurial success in Nigeria.

In addition, the findings of study have resulted in developing a framework for evaluating the effectiveness of EE in Nigerian universities. The researcher's framework emphasizes essential aspects, including teaching methods and pedagogy, institutional support, stakeholder engagement, and the impact and evaluation. The framework has been specifically designed to tackle the challenges identified in the study. It offers universities a structured approach to enhance their EEPs and to better equip students for success in entrepreneurship. The study concludes by highlighting the valuable insights it provides into Nigeria's current state of EE. This provides actionable recommendations for policy reforms and programme enhancements aimed at improving the effectiveness of EE in Nigeria. The findings highlight the necessity of

customising entrepreneurship education to particular contexts, while equally prioritising theoretical understanding and practical application.

7.2 Limitations of Study

The study's scope, data collection methods, and overall direction were all impacted by some research process limitations. These restrictions included things like practical difficulties that come with conducting fieldwork and outside influences that were out of the researcher's control. It is important to recognize and consider these limitations, while not diminishing the significance of results but to put the study's findings in perspective and guide future research efforts.

The challenge of recruiting educators for the initial phase of the study provided a significant limitation, not in terms of the perspectives acquired but rather in terms of the time-consuming process involved. Following several follow-up attempts, some educators who had first consented to participate in the study changed their views. First, many educators were either reluctant or unwilling to take part in the interview. In addition, a sizeable percentage of educators have yet to react to any of the requests made, further complicating the recruitment process. As a result, the research project encountered setbacks, which resulted in an extension of the overall timetable for the collection of data during the initial phase. In addition, the difficulty of engaging educators reflects a more general difficulty in ensuring the participation of stakeholders in research, particularly in the field of entrepreneurship education. Since educators frequently must deal with severe workloads and administrative pressures, it is possible that they found it difficult to set aside the necessary amount of time and effort to participate in the study. During the process of recruitment, this could have been a factor that contributed to the reluctance that was seen. It is important to cultivate stronger ties with educators and identify ways to make involvement simpler and more desirable, as this would help speed future research efforts. The lengthy engagement process underscores the importance of these two initiatives.

The study was limited by geographical constraints, as the universities included were concentrated in specific regions of Nigeria. This regional focus restricts the capacity to completely capture the diverse ways in which entrepreneurship education is delivered and supported across the entire nation, even though data was collected from institutions in the southeast, South-South, and Southeast regions of the country. Nigeria is partitioned into six

geopolitical zones: North Central, Northeast, Northwest, Southeast, South-South, and Southwest. The findings may not account for significant regional differences in economic conditions, institutional support structures, and cultural attitudes towards entrepreneurship due to the exclusion of data from the northern regions specifically, the Northeast, Northwest, and North Central. How students and educators experience entrepreneurship programs can be substantially influenced by the economic and institutional disparities between Nigeria's zones . For instance, the delivery and reception of entrepreneurship education may be influenced by the unique challenges that universities in the northern zones encounter, such as infrastructure, funding constraints, and a lack of access to entrepreneurial networks.

An additional limitation of the research was its emphasis on immediate results; specifically, it evaluated students' opinions of their education and their inclinations towards entrepreneurship soon, but it did not monitor long-term results, such as starting a firm or maintaining it beyond graduation. Although graduates were a part of the study, the study was not focused on their entrepreneurial journeys. A longitudinal study is essential to comprehensively assess the enduring effects of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial journeys. Studies indicate that the impacts of entrepreneurship education frequently require time to materialize, as numerous students initiate enterprises years after their educational completion (Nabi et al., 2017; Rauch & Hulsink, 2015). Moreover, elements such as self-efficacy and resilience, cultivated through entrepreneurship programs, may affect enduring entrepreneurial behaviours (Bae et al., 2014). Future studies should implement a longitudinal strategy to more accurately assess the impact of entrepreneurship education on business success over time .

7.3 Recommendations for Further Studies

The findings of this study and the previously mentioned limitations open a wide range of opportunities for further study. The recommendation recognizes a few directions for further investigation, such as comparative analyses, different stakeholders' viewpoints, longitudinal studies, and evaluation of the university ecosystem.

Future Research should incorporate qualitative interviews with students to obtain a deeper comprehension of their experiences with entrepreneurship education. Although surveys offer valuable quantitative data, in-depth interviews would enable a more comprehensive comprehension of the curriculum, students' motivations, and challenges. This method can reveal the specific obstacles that various types of students encounter and how they vary in their interactions with entrepreneurship programmes, thereby facilitating the development of more

personalized educational approaches (O'Connor, 2018). In addition, these interviews could emphasise the disparities between theory and practice, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how EE affects the entrepreneurial intentions of students.

In future studies, more stakeholders must be involved. Beyond educators and students, policymakers, industry leaders, entrepreneurs, and alumni can bring their perspectives on how EE meets industry and policy demands. Engaging these stakeholders would help institutions understand the entrepreneurial education ecosystem and how to work with external partners to improve learning (Leitch, McMullan & Harrison, 2020). This multi-stakeholder approach would also assist in identifying institutional and policy support gaps and assess how well entrepreneurship programmes prepare students for real-world difficulties.

Graduate entrepreneurs are another relevant area for study. These studies would evaluate the practical application of entrepreneurship skills and knowledge. Tracking graduates who started firms would reveal which parts of their education were most effective and which needed improvement. This research could show how teaching methods and institutional supports like mentorship and funding affect long-term business success (Muofhe & Du Toit, 2019). In addition, longitudinal studies of students' entrepreneurial journeys beyond graduation are also needed. This would reveal the longevity of graduates' firms and the influence of entrepreneurship courses on their careers. Understanding the delayed consequences of entrepreneurship education—such as the time it takes graduates to start their enterprises or the difficulties they confront after graduation—would provide a more complete picture of its success (Bae, Qian, Miao & Fiet, 2014). Longitudinal studies could show how policy changes and economic variations affect graduates' entrepreneurial performance.

In terms of government policy, future research should also examine Nigerian entrepreneurial education policies or barriers. This examines how government policies, university regulations, and public-private partnerships affect entrepreneurship programmes. This research could reveal policy implementation gaps and provide ways to improve educator and student support (Walter & Block, 2016). A comparison of how different Nigerian areas apply these regulations could clarify entrepreneurial education gaps.

Finally, future research should focus on testing the framework developed in this study to assess its practicality and effectiveness. The framework would be implemented in Nigerian universities and measured on student outcomes, institutional performance, and stakeholder involvement. Real-world testing would reveal the framework's strengths and weaknesses,

making it adaptable and effective across institutional contexts. This technique may contribute to the design of context-specific entrepreneurship education models in developing economies

7.4 Conclusion

Overall, the research recommendations for enhancing entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities provide a comprehensive and context-specific plan that has the potential to advance the field. This study emphasizes the uniqueness of the framework created to evaluate the efficiency of entrepreneurship programmes. It specifically examines Teaching methods, University support, and curriculum alignment with industry demands. The framework has been developed to provide guidance for policy reforms and to foster the development of entrepreneurial skills among students. Ultimately, this research lays the groundwork for future studies and policy adjustments aimed at closing the divide between theoretical concepts and real-world entrepreneurial results in Nigeria.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX I: UWS Ethical Approval Letter

08/04/2022

Dear Inimfon Umoren,

Your application 17744: The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Students Entrepreneurial Intention: An Assessment of Nigerian Universities, submission 15164, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

APPENDIX II: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Participant Information Sheet

Research Title: The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Students Entrepreneurial Intention: An Assessment of Nigerian Universities.

Principal Investigator: Inimfon Umoren
Name of Supervisor: Dr. Nicholas Telford

Ethical Approval Number: 17744-15164

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what is involved. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part or not.

Who are we?

UWS is an officially recognised University worldwide. The researcher is a second-year research student undertaking a PhD in the University.

What is the Purpose of this Study?

The aim of this research is to investigate the impact of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) on the mindset and intention of students in Nigerian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Specifically, this study aims to understand how Entrepreneurship Education Programs (EEPs) offered in Nigerian Universities affect the development of students' entrepreneurial mindset and intentions.

To achieve this goal, the research will focus on developing an EE framework that is specific to the Nigerian context. This framework will be informed by an in-depth examination of previous studies on EE and will be used to evaluate the impact of EEPs on students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigerian HEIs. The significance of this study lies in the need for viable solutions to promote economic growth and create jobs. By examining the impact of EE on students' mindset and intentions, this study can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of EEPs in Nigerian HEIs. The findings of this study will also be used in developing a framework that supports EE in Nigeria and other developing countries, and to guide future research on this topic.

Why have I been asked to take part?

We are carrying out surveys to determine how entrepreneurship education programmes affect the entrepreneurial intentions of students. We are particularly interested in the experience of people who are teaching (educators) and learning (Students and Graduates) within Higher Educations in Nigeria and because you are involved in one of these experiences, we are asking you to participate in the study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide. You do not have to take part. If you decide to participate you will be able to withdraw your information from study up to two weeks after completing the interview by contacting the researcher and your information will be destroyed. If you have any questions about the research before deciding. Please contact [REDACTED]

|

What will taking part involve?

If you decide to participate you will be asked to consent to the study by reading the statements on the consent sheet. After consent is given interview questions will be given to you prior to the interview date. You will have to pick a suitable date and time; a zoom meeting will be fixed, and the link will be emailed to you. As an educator, this will involve you taking part in a 40–45-minute interview about your experiences, educational set-up and teaching methods, entrepreneurial skills, barriers and challenges and the perceived impact of entrepreneurship education. As a student, you will be asked to complete a web-based questionnaire which we estimate will take you 20 minutes.

What are the possible risks and benefits of taking part?

First, it is not expected that your participation in this study will cause any distress. However, to reduce the risk of distress to participant, we request any potential participant who feel topic may be upsetting for them to refrain from taking part in the study. Your safety and wellbeing are our primary concerns. Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on how entrepreneurship education can be improved in Nigerian Universities.

Who has ethically reviewed this project?

This project has been ethically approved by the university's ethical committee. The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Research Ethics Committee monitors the application and delivery of the University's Ethics Review Procedure across the University.

Will taking part be confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential by the data controller. The data controller for this study will be the researcher and can be contacted at Inimfon.umoren@uws.ac.uk. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. The researcher will be the only person who knows the participants of study. Any data collected about you during cause of study will be stored online in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies. Data collected will be shared in an anonymised form to allow reuse by the research team and other third parties.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The results of the study will be communicated via published reports and articles in academic journals (e.g., journal of Teaching and Learning, Journal of education, Journal of entrepreneurship Education), conferences and other events. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about research?

Dr. Nicholas Telford

Director of Studies

Thank you for participating.

APPENDIX III: INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR EDUCATORS

INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

PARTICIPANT BACKGROUND

1. Can you tell me a bit about your background?
2. Tell me about your journey to become an Enterprise Educator. How long have you been an educator on the Entrepreneurial learning course?
3. What Entrepreneurship module(s) do you currently teach?
4. How would you define EE?
5. How do you perceive the role entrepreneurship education plays in fostering the intention of students to become entrepreneurs?
6. Can you describe the Entrepreneurship education courses offered at your uni? Can you give a description of the module you teach?
7. Give details of the pedagogical approach you use in teaching Entrepreneurship. Why have you chosen such pedagogies?
8. What are some of the strategies you use to encourage and support entrepreneurial learning and practices among students?
9. As an educator, have you been involved in the development of the curriculum at your institution?
10. Following on from this, have you had any inputs into entrepreneurial education policy at any level (local/National/International)
11. Can you describe your chosen teaching methods in terms of student engagement and skills improvement?- Give examples if any.
12. How effective do you think these methods are? Do you reflect on the chosen methods and adjust?
13. What specific skills do you emphasize when teaching entrepreneurship modules to your students?
14. In your experience, what are some of the most successful types of businesses that emerge from the entrepreneurship education programme in Nigeria?
15. What kind of resources and support does the university provide to students within the entrepreneurial ecosystem to help them develop skills and succeed?
16. In your opinion, what additional support or resources would be beneficial for improving EE and fostering entrepreneurial intention among students?
17. What are some key challenges you face while teaching Entrepreneurship in Nigeria?
Why do you say so? How can these barriers be overcome?
18. How can entrepreneurship teaching be improved in Nigerian higher education? *Any suggestion to the faculty? university? government?*
19. Do you think EEPs are tailored to the Nigerian context and address the unique challenges facing Nigerian entrepreneurs?

20. Do you believe that EEPs developed in the West can be successfully adapted to the Nigerian context? *If so, what modifications are necessary?*

Do you have any questions, or would you like to add anything else to your response?

APPENDIX IV: SURVEY FOR STUDENTS AND GRADUATES

SURVEY FORM FOR NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS/GRADUATES

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Researcher: Nimfon Umoren

Ph.D. Thesis Title: **The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Intentions: An Exploration of Nigerian Universities**

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what is involved. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part or not.

What is the Purpose of this Study?

The aim of this research is to investigate the impact of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) on the mindset and intention of students in Nigerian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Specifically, this study aims to understand how Entrepreneurship Education Programs (EEPs) offered in Nigerian Universities affect the development of students' entrepreneurial mindsets and intentions.

To achieve this goal, the research will focus on developing an EE framework that is specific to the Nigerian context. This framework will be informed by an in-depth examination of previous studies on EE and will be used to evaluate the impact of EEPs on students' entrepreneurial intentions in Nigerian HEIs. The significance of this study lies in the need for viable solutions to promote economic growth and create jobs. By examining the impact of EE on students' mindsets and intentions, this study can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of EEPs in Nigerian HEIs. The findings of this study will also be used in developing a framework that supports EE in Nigeria and other developing countries, and to guide future research on this topic.

Why have I been asked to take part?

The researcher is carrying out surveys to determine how entrepreneurship education programmes affect students' entrepreneurial intentions. We are particularly interested in the experience of people learning (Students) within Higher Education in Nigeria, we are asking you to participate in the study.

Will taking part be confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential by the data controller. The data controller for this study will be the researcher and can be contacted at [REDACTED]. [REDACTED] will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. The researcher will be the only person who knows the participants of the study. Any data collected about you during the course of the study will be stored online in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies. Data collected will be shared in an anonymized form to allow reuse by the research team and other third parties.

* Required

PART A (PARTICIPANT BACKGROUND)

PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT

1. Do you consent to take part in this research? *

Yes

No

2. Age *

- 18 – 25
- 26 – 35
- 36 – 45
- 46 and above

3. Gender *

- Woman
- Man
- Prefer not to say

4. Are you currently enrolled as an undergraduate student or a postgraduate student? *

- Undergraduate Student
- Taught postgraduate student (Master's degree)
- Research postgraduate (Doctorate e.g. PhD)
- No - I am a graduate

5. How long has it been since you graduated? (For graduates only)

- 0 - 2 Years
- 2 - 5 Years
- 5 years and above

6. Could you please identify the ownership structure of your university?

- Public (Federal-Owned)
- Public (State-Owned)
- Private (Individual-Owned)
- Private (Religious-Owned)

7. Which university are you currently attending for your studies?

8. Please indicate the category that best represents the field of your current university course (Programme of Study) *

- Arts and Humanities degree [i.e History, English Literature, Philosophy, Languages, Arts-related disciplines, etc]
- Business management Studies and Law [i.e Business Management, Accounting, Finance, Marketing, HRM, Law, Legal Studies, Entrepreneurship, etc]
- Engineering and Technology [i.e Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Civil Engineering, Computer Science, IT, etc]
- Social Sciences [i.e Sociology, Psychology, Economics, Political Science, Anthropology, Geography, etc]
- Life Sciences and Health Sciences [i.e Medicine, Dentistry, Nursing, Veterinary Science, Biochemistry, Biotechnology, Ecology etc].
- Others - specify in next question

9. If you ticked 'others' in previous question please write your degree title/ area here:

10. Programme Level

- Undergraduate First year
- Undergraduate Second year
- Undergraduate Third year
- Undergraduate fourth year
- Undergraduate Final year
- Postgraduate first year
- Postgraduate second year
- Postgraduate third year
- Postgraduate fourth year

11. Have you ever considered running your own business? *

- Yes - in the near future
- Yes - in the distant future
- No, not at all.
- I already am
- I have in the past but don't currently run a business

12. Does anyone in your family own or run their own business? *

- Yes, my Parents.
- Yes, my siblings
- Yes, my grandparents
- Yes, other relatives
- No, nobody in my family owns a business.

13. Did you have experience in running a business before attending the entrepreneurship educational course or programme? *

- I had no prior experience in running a business
- I had limited experience in running a business
- I had moderate experience in running a business
- I had extensive experience in running a business
- I'm unsure / I don't have enough information to answer

14. Thinking of your experience of running a business, was this your own business or another's business?

- My business
- Another person's business
- Family business
- Both my own business and that of another person/ the family business

16. PERCEIVED UNIVERSITY SUPPORT

This section contains several statements about the support you perceive from the university in your entrepreneurial endeavours. Read each statement carefully and indicate your level of agreement based on your perception. There is no right or wrong answer, and you should respond according to how you perceive the university's support.

*Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements: 1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 Somewhat Disagree, 4 (neither agree nor Disagree), 5 (Somewhat agree), 6 (Agree), and 7 (Strongly Agree) **

	1	2	3	4	5	6
The education in university encourages me to develop creative ideas for being an entrepreneur	<input type="radio"/>					
My university develops my entrepreneurial skills and abilities.	<input type="radio"/>					
My university provides the necessary knowledge about entrepreneurship	<input type="radio"/>					
The University organises idea contests, hackathons and competitions to find and support promising student initiatives	<input type="radio"/>					
If I were to establish a startup business, I think the University would help me to raise the recognition of my company and find potential customers	<input type="radio"/>					
The University helps me find an investor to launch my startup company	<input type="radio"/>					
The university provides adequate resources and facilities for entrepreneurship education.	<input type="radio"/>					

17. TEACHING METHODS AND PEDAGOGY

This section contains several statements about your experiences with teaching methods and pedagogy. Read each statement carefully, and indicate your level of agreement based on your observations. There is no right or wrong answer, and you should respond according to your perception of the teaching methods.

To what extent did your lecturers use the following teaching methods in your entrepreneurship courses? **Rate 1 (Not used at all), 2 (Rarely used), 3 (infrequently used), 4 (Sometimes used), 5 (moderately used), 6 (Often used) and 7 (Mostly used) ***

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Lecturing (Conducting normal lectures)	<input type="radio"/>					
Class participation – (making students participate in class activities during lectures, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
Lecturers using case studies (real or hypothetical) to teach entrepreneurship courses	<input type="radio"/>					
Giving students individual assignments and projects	<input type="radio"/>					
Giving students group projects and assignments	<input type="radio"/>					
Students making oral presentations in the class	<input type="radio"/>					
Role play	<input type="radio"/>					
Asking students to prepare business plans	<input type="radio"/>					
Guest entrepreneurs invited to share their life experiences with the students	<input type="radio"/>					

PART C (ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP)

Attitude Towards Entrepreneurship

Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements: **1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 Somewhat Disagree, 4 (neither agree nor Disagree), 5 (Somewhat agree), 6 (Agree), and 7 (Strongly Agree)**

18. PERSONAL ATTITUDES *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Being an entrepreneur implies more advantages than disadvantages to me	<input type="radio"/>					
I don't find a career as an entrepreneur attractive at all.	<input type="radio"/>					
If I had the opportunity and resources, I would love to start a business	<input type="radio"/>					
Amongst various career options, I would rather be an entrepreneur	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an entrepreneur will give me great satisfaction	<input type="radio"/>					

19. PERCEIVED BEHAVIOURAL CONTROL *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Starting a business and keeping it viable would be easy for me	<input type="radio"/>					
I am able to control the creation process of a new business	<input type="radio"/>					
If I tried to start a business, I would have a high chance of being successful	<input type="radio"/>					
I have no knowledge of the practical details needed to start a business.	<input type="radio"/>					
I have enough self-confidence to start my own business after completing my studies.	<input type="radio"/>					

20. SUBJECTIVE NORM *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
My family thinks that I will become an entrepreneur	<input type="radio"/>					
My friends would approve of my decision to start a Business	<input type="radio"/>					
The opinions of people who are important to me greatly influence my decision to pursue entrepreneurship.	<input type="radio"/>					

21. ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS *

	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am ready to do anything legal and morally acceptable to be an entrepreneur	<input type="radio"/>					
My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur	<input type="radio"/>					
I will make every effort to start and run my own firm	<input type="radio"/>					
I am not determined to create a business venture	<input type="radio"/>					
I have very seriously thought of starting a business	<input type="radio"/>					
I have the firm intention to start a firm someday	<input type="radio"/>					

PART D (OPEN ENDED QUESTIONS)

This section aims to gather valuable insights into your experiences with entrepreneurship education programs and the support provided by your university. Your responses will help us understand how these programs and resources have influenced your learning, skill development, and preparedness for real-world entrepreneurial challenges.

Please take a moment to reflect on your experiences and provide detailed responses to the following questions. Your feedback is crucial for improving entrepreneurship education programs and enhancing support services at our university. Thank you for your participation!

22. In your opinion, how well do you think the entrepreneurship education programmes at your university will [or has] prepare you for real-world entrepreneurial challenges? Please provide examples. (Open-ended)

23. Please describe any specific university support you have received for entrepreneurship education (e.g., incubators, mentorship, resources, entrepreneurship centers).

24. In your own words, describe the skills or abilities you believe you have developed as a result of participating in entrepreneurship education programmes.

25. How can Entrepreneurship Education be improved in your University?
-

APPENDIX V: SAMPLE OF TRANSCRIPT FROM EDUCATORS

INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT – PARTICIPANT EEN02

Interviewer: How would you define EE?

EEN02: Entrepreneurship education if we were to... I like to look at it from the point of the objective of setting up the cost in the first place. One of the reasons why the cost was set up, especially for Nigeria, I don't know about other nations, but because of the challenges we have in terms of development, in terms of employment, entrepreneurship education was introduced to help steer up interest of students within the university environment. For me, entrepreneurship education deals with teaching practical skills or knowledge to students to prepare them for their work of Work. That is the way I consider it. That is how I also check them when I'm in class. It's not just about teaching the theory, it's also about impacting that knowledge to them.

Interviewer: How do you perceive the role entrepreneurship education plays in fostering the intention of students to become entrepreneurs?

EEN02: Yes. From my own experience, it plays a very key role. Because currently in my institution, I have seen more students go into business. They may be small businesses that... They may not count as anything, but many of them are involved in small businesses. For example, selling of footways. Some of them are into programming because programming is also part of the skills we teach. Some of them are involved in programming and they do some graphic designs. Overall, I think the interest of students has or their intention to go into business has increased within this university environment. Yes, I can tell that for sure because I know that many of them, for example, when they come in initially at their first year while you're interacting with them. Not many of them are interested in business. Not many of them have any things that they go doing as far as business is concerned. But by the time they get to their 300 level and then their final year, you score that many of them are involved in so many things. Yes, to a larger extent, I would say it has fostered the interest of students. I also know few of them who are currently feeding based on the skills they learned while they were in school.

Interviewer: Give details of the pedagogical approach you use in teaching Entrepreneurship. Why have you chosen such pedagogies?

EEN02: Yes, for your undergraduate is mainly lectures. Now, I also need to point out a few things. Because of the peculiarity of my institution, one it is a private university. Students are a little bit confined within the university environment. There is little that one can really do. We do more of a lecturing method. But this year, I started something a little bit different. I don't know, I'm still evaluating to see how the impact it would have. One of the things I asked the students to do this year was to go to YouTube and pick any business video and analyse it. That is the closest to reality, I know I can deal with them as far as taking that course is concerned. But largely is the lecture method. largely, yes.

Interviewer: *What are some of the strategies you use to encourage and support entrepreneurial learning and practices among students?*

EEN02: Yes. Apart from sharing my experiences with them occasionally, I call because I know that there are some of them who are doing few things. Sometimes I may just ask who are into businesses within the classroom, and all of them, they'll start pointing to specific students. When they do that, I call up those ones and I want to hear from them. They begin to share some of their experiences within the campus. During that period, I got to learn that there were some of them who were running errands for other students within the school. When they bring up such cases, what we do is to discuss it in class. What are the challenges you're facing? What are the other things you're doing to improve on this? One of the things I've learned from there is that by the time some of these students are graduating, they tend to hand over that business to someone else, so it continues. That's one of the methods I use. Then the other method I also use is that I also host a business radio talk show. I get to bring in some of these students, and sometimes I bring in outsiders, and I get my students to also connect to listing to some of the chains we discussed during the program.

And then other strategies I also engage is I do a form of role-playing. Yes, I think I would call it role-playing. I group the students; I break them into groups. Within that group, you must speak with your CEO, with the company secretary. Though it is for mainly to execute an assignment. But beyond that, I also want to see their ability to think and work like people who are within a company. Those are the few methods I use to steer up their interest. Apart from other personal chains I do, for example, sometimes some of them come to meet me personally, and then we discuss on some of the challenges that they are having in their businesses and how to go about it. But generally, those are the few strategies I adopt.

Interviewer: As an educator, have you been involved in the development of the curriculum at your institution?

EEN02: No, I have not been fully involved in the development of the curriculum. Although on few occasions I have been called to make an impute, but I have not had the opportunity to do it the way I would have loved to do it. Because we are guided by Nigerian University Commission, it's a little bit of a challenge when you want to move outside the curriculum that they prepared for you. The AUCA, which is the regulatory body for all the universities in Nigeria, prepares the curriculum for all courses. Whatever you're teaching must revolve around the curriculum they have prepared. To a larger extent, that is a very big challenge for me. But when it comes to entrepreneurship, there are certain topics I feel should no longer exist, especially as the students are moving to higher levels. I expect some more advanced topics, but I don't really get to see that. Sometimes when you want to introduce it, it becomes a problem. What I do is that I don't discuss it passively while taking other courses. For example, I expect that at a higher level, for example, when getting to the third year or the final year, the focus should be more on innovation, more on developing business models, but you don't get to see that.

The curriculum is more like a repetition of what has been done at the lower level. It's a challenge for me. In fact, there was a time my director, the director at the University Entrepreneurship Center, when I discussed some of the challenges with him, so he told me that I should do a proposal and send that cost to him. By the time I brought some of the topics I felt and what some of the things I felt we should be doing to steer up the interest of today's small entrepreneurship, he has some little doubt. At the end of the day, nothing was done. It was dropped. I have not been fully involved in the development of the curriculum.

Interviewer: Following on from this, have you had any inputs into entrepreneurial education policy at any level (local/National/International)?

EEN02: Yes. Within the university and within the space that we have. Because I am largely involved in our entrepreneurship center, which makes recommendations to the university when it comes to policies and all of that. I'm fully involved in that. To that extent, yes, I'm involved. I participate in a lot of... If there's hardly any issue that deals with entrepreneurship within the university community that I am not involved in hardly any of them. I also don't want to be a

rebel within the system. As much as possible, whatever I need to pass across, I get to pass it across to my individual programs or maybe when I'm meeting with students. There's also a cost they have been given a little bit of freedom to organize. However I still have to work within the framework of the curriculum that NUC is giving to us. To that extent, yes, I'm involved. I also hope I'll be more involved as time goes on. Now that there are some changes going on within the university at the moment, so I believe I will be more involved in the coming days.

Interviewer: What specific skills do you emphasize when teaching entrepreneurship modules to your students?

EEN02: Yes. Because I'm biased to certain skills. Anything that has to do with technology and innovation, that is always my focus. Again, because I also have a business interest in footwear making, in food business, so occasionally I chip those ones in. But generally, what I try doing is to look at how can technology be used to develop your skill or your vocation. I focus on, largely on technology, I focus more on innovation, so digital skills, coding. Those are the things I pay more attention to. I think that was June, I started taking a class in coding. I started teaching myself how to code so that I can also relate with the students involved when they are talking. It made it easier for me. For example, when they come to submit assignment, in my office, I would tell them, okay, write this code for me. It's easier for me to do that because I've gained experience on how to write code. When they come in, they demonstrate to me that, okay, we have learned something within this short period of time.

Interviewer: In your experience, what are some of the most successful types of businesses that emerge from the entrepreneurship education program in Nigeria?

EEN02: Okay. When we talk about that, it's a little bit dicey because-. I wanted to mention certain skills that I feel a lot of people go into. But the problem with that is we have this mentality in Nigeria that has been one of the challenges of vocational training in Nigeria. That, apart from me, it's one of the challenges we face. Now, people are not interested in what the market is looking for. People want what is moving. You've seen one person succeed in a particular skill or vocation, and then everybody jumps into it, and they make a mess of the entire skill. To that extent, one of the things a lot of people are going into now in Nigeria has to do with coding and graphic design. One of the reasons why they do that is because they consider... Because of this idea of remote work. Most people who could not get

a job somewhere feel that, Okay, this is what we need to do in order for us to achieve success. The next one people also jump into is the affiliate marketing team. A lot of people go into affiliate marketing. Though I have my about that line of business, I've seen a lot of people who go into a lot of young people.

And because they make use of social media a lot, on their social media, especially on their WhatsApp platforms, you see them post products from whatever group they belong to. We see a lot of people go into that. Another line of business many people tend to be going into right now is fashion, especially clothing. In Nigeria, we do a lot of parties. If you are a good fashion designer, and this is one thing, again, if we are talking about success, if you're a good fashion designer, it is difficult for you to stay a week without having a handful of clothes to sew, because people always make dresses. So, fashion design is one of the striving businesses. Even the very bad fashion designers or we call them tailors in Nigeria, still have people patronizing them. Then the next one that I've also seen a lot of people go into is Catering. Yes, Catering. Specifically, Catering. I think it's Catering I want to say, not Catering. Catering. A lot of people go into Catering, they also make a lot of money from that. We see many young people... And because the start of capital is very, very, very, very minimal compared to other applications, which let's say we turn 10, 10 pounds or something, or 10,000 naira in Nigeria, you can start learning this. You can buy some of the little things. So many people tend to go into it now. So far, I think those are the skills I would say if you called about 10 people in Nigeria now, at least six to seven of them will mention any of these skills.

***Interviewer:* What kind of resources and support does the university provide to students within the entrepreneurial ecosystem to help them develop skills and succeed?**

EEN02: We have the Entrepreneurship Development Center. Okay. Now, at our center... First, let me confess that our center is not as developed as it's supposed to be. Let me start from there. What we do likely is to facilitate the learning of these vocational skills for students. That's one of the primary reasons the center was set up. Now there was a time we wanted to go into business, full-blown business, but then we had a little challenge with the business arm of the school, which is the consulting arm of the school. We were making certain products that came out from our entrepreneurship center. We wanted to put them into the market. The school came up to tell us that we were not set up to go to the market to go and sell. What we were set up to

do was to train students on what to do. We thought that would have been an avenue for us to generate revenue. But we are still making a move to see if it would be possible to try that angle again and see if the school will allow us to go fully into business. Then the next thing we also do is that any school policy that revolves around entrepreneurship, the center gets to fine-tune it and make sure that it's in alignment with the vision of the school.

Interviewer: In your opinion, what additional support or resources would be beneficial for improving EE and fostering entrepreneurial intention among students?

EEN02: I feel the government needs to play a role. The government cannot be isolated or cannot allow individuals, and private individuals to run the entrepreneurship centers alone. Because we are talking about economic development.

If the government is not involved, that may be a very big challenge because it costs a lot of money to run an entrepreneurship center. If the government, for example, like I told you that our own center, we are still developing. As of now, we've not been able to have a defeating entrepreneurship center where all the vocations are taught within the center, we've not been able to achieve that. Our students go to various locations within the university community to learn some of these skills. Now, if we have a situation where either the private sector or the government comes in to help develop, even though these are privately owned institutions, the product that will come out of it, we are all Nigerians, and for all the students, their parents also pay taxes. So if they come out better in society, it is better for Nigeria as a whole. So government, involvement, I guess, is very important. Then I also feel the collaboration from the private sector will also be a huge support. But sometimes you want to get them in to come and talk to the students about entrepreneurship. At least if they will not bring in money, their experience, we count.

Then also assigning these students to do a form of mentorship, because that is what we have been trying to achieve, and that has been a problem. The private sector can provide a platform for students to have a first-hand experience on how to manage some of these businesses. For example, for our own facilitators, one of the things I tell them whenever we are having a form of meeting or orientation with them is that I'm not just interested in you teaching them the skill. I'm also interested in you teaching them how to run the business. There's a skill aspect of it,

there's a business aspect of it. We are more interested in the business aspect of it. That is what we wanted to teach these students. If you teach them the skill alone, that may not go far. But when you add the business aspect to it, teach them about strategies, teach them where they can get raw materials, it tears up something in them. It makes them feel more committed to it. Then another one, because of the peculiarity of our institution, the religious bodies also need to get involved. They need to get involved because for my institution now, it's a religious organization that is funding it.

They need to devote more time or more resources towards entrepreneurship centers if we are to achieve our goals. So far, I think those are the few support, I think, the center we need. And of course, I mentioned the issue of the alumni earlier, which we are still experimenting. I don't know how far we can go with it, but we are looking at the alumni coming in with support. Because if all of these institutions come in, the stress on the center itself will be reduced drastically and it gives more room for them to do so much within a short period of time.

Interviewer: What are some key challenges you face while teaching Entrepreneurship in Nigeria? Why do you say so? How can these barriers be overcome?

EEN02: Okay, one of the major challenges I've faced so far in teaching, and it's not just me, I think other people as well, is that sometimes you want to demonstrate certain things, but you don't have the resources to do that, and it makes it a little bit difficult. For example, if we are making decisions, I would like to have a simulation where we look at, okay, if we take this step, this is what we are going to get, if we take this step, but we don't have such resources to stimulate those decision making. It makes it difficult. Then another challenge we also have, this time is on the part of the facilitators. Many of them are not really, really, really exposed. They are not exposed. Yes, they know the skill and they are using it to eat. Now, I'm saying they're using it to eat because they are operating at a very subsistent level. Their businesses have not grown to... As small as our communities are, their businesses are not so that when you mention their name, people quickly recon with them. For me, that is not the root. We have that challenge. Sometimes you try to push them.

Interviewer: How can entrepreneurship teaching be improved in Nigerian higher education? Any suggestion to the faculty? university? government?

EEN02: Yes. How can it be improved? One of the ways I feel it can be improved, which is what we are doing in my school at this moment, we have a section, or a semester dedicated to theoretical aspect of it. That is where we have regular university lecturers coming to teach certain aspects of business to the students. Then by the second semester, we then have practicing businesspeople coming to take the class. We opted for that because we felt... Initially, we were just teaching, and we felt that we were not getting the result we wanted. We introduced this aspect to it. So far, I think we have achieved a lot using this method. Then how can it also be improved? The electorals themselves need to go on training. They need to be taught. Yes, the majority don't know anything about business. You can be teaching students about business when you don't know much about it. Even something as simple as being a consultant within your discipline. Not many of the electorals get to practice all these things, and it is a challenge. For example, I was in a particular class some time, and while taking them, I discovered that they were not paying attention to me until I started telling them what I've done and what I'm doing.

That's when they started paying attention. They felt, okay, maybe you have the experience. Then I started telling them, for example, you are telling students who are into nursing, microbiology, some of these other basic medical sciences, you are teaching them about business. One of the questions they get to ask is, what am I going to do with business? I don't have any business with that cost. One of the ways I get their interest is that I start mentioning people who are also finished from the same discipline and who are running a business that is like what they are doing. How can you take nursing out of nursing and then create a business out of it? I begin to demonstrate some of those things and then it goes beyond, oh, okay, nursing is not just about getting a job in a hospital and taking care of people. I can also create an aspect. For example, you talk about taking care of old people. It's a part of their job. You may decide, I don't want to work with anybody, but let me create a company where with my experience, I can take care of elderly people, can take care of children.

By the time you start linking them up with some of the opportunities that exist within their discipline, it helps to improve the teaching. It makes the teaching more interesting, and they

become more involved in the course. I also feel that university management generally should be, especially for developing countries, for developed countries, such as the UK, and the US, they may not take it too seriously because they already have a system working. But for a developing country like Nigeria, investment management should be more involved in entrepreneurship than any other cost. The reason why I say that is that in every course, there's a little bit of entrepreneurship in it. All we need to do is to invest more time and resources to bring it out. For example, if you're a doctor and you are done with your studies, you're not just thinking of, which hospital can I go to and get employed? You are thinking of, okay, what are the opportunities within the medical industry or the medical line that I can explore to provide better service? If you go to, let's say, any of the teaching hospitals in Nigeria, you will cry about the way people are treated. Now that's an opportunity that someone can take and say, okay, how can I turn around this opportunity?

Interviewer: In your opinion, what policies or initiatives could the Nigerian government implement to promote entrepreneurship and economic issues in the country?

EEN02: That is another problem we have because apart from asking everybody, or the institutions to adopt entrepreneurship teaching in Nigeria. There is really nothing much that the government has done. Now, I know we have things like SMEDAN, and we have Empower. Those are lovely policies, but there is still a disconnect between those policies and what we are practicing within our university environment. I don't know. I commend the government for coming up with the idea of getting every school to have an entrepreneurship course. It is very good. But how about we talk about if I'm done with this training, for example, how do I get funding to start? If I'm done with this training, how do I go for a form of a top-up training, an advanced form of that training? Is there a platform for that? There's no platform for that. Most students, once they are done and they come out after two, three months, there's no money to start up the business, there's no employment. The next thing is that they look for the next available job or whatever, and then they forget whatever entrepreneurship skills they have learnt. So, if we have a system in place where even if it is through microfinance banks, students can walk to any of those financial institutions within their community and say, please, this is what I want to do. Can you provide me funding? And then the government, we back up that funding. That will go a very long way to get many people established. Then the government can also, or the private sector now, with the help of the federal government, for example, I love what Tony, who is doing at the moment. The only challenge I have with Tony, who is method, I'm not seeing the impact enough within our communities. I'm not seeing the impact. Yes, he

has sponsored, I think, over 10,000 people with \$5,000, which is a whole lot of money. But the impact, I am not really seeing it. I've also tried to ask questions, at least from... I've seen some people who have won that grant, but I'm not seeing what they are doing with that money. There could be challenges, I don't know. But if we have such grant in place and then we have a support system that can help people both to apply that money correctly and make sure that something comes out of it, it will go a very long way for now. I try to excuse some of the banks or the financial institutions. For me, I've tried to do a little bit of engine investing, and I know the challenges I faced.

Then we have a form of a regulator within each state or within each region or each community, depending on how it goes. The job of the regulator would be to monitor how these guys utilize this money, and if possible, even manage their resources. Because sometimes, not that these guys don't get money, the money comes in. But because many of them don't have a proper bookkeeping skill, so the money gets to fly away to very irrelevant things. So, if we have a situation where there could be a support structure, and that's why I feel that having an innovation hub or an entrepreneurship village where some of these structures can be put in place to assist each local community, will go a long way.

Interviewer: Do you think EEPs are tailored to the Nigerian context and address the unique challenges facing Nigerian entrepreneurs?

EEN02: It's not. Okay. It's not. Like I said earlier, we just do it for the sake of doing it. I mentioned earlier that when you ask question on which of the SKUs are most successful, somebody just came with affiliate marketing and the person probably made money with affiliate marketing and everybody just jumped in or affiliate marketing. Somebody will not come up with, oh, there is cryptocurrency. Everybody will jump into cryptocurrency. Oh, there is money in fashion. Everybody will jump in. We don't have any system in place that we identify our problems and try to solve those problems. We don't have that. That is why it looks like all the entrepreneurship education we receive in our schools makes little or no impact on anybody. Because the problem they are solving are not societal problems. For example, we should not be teaching people how to bake. Anybody can learn how to bake. You can go to YouTube and learn it. Anybody can learn it. What are the new things in the baking industry we need to introduce people to? I can't teach you how to bake and then you come in and then you

are still baking the same type of cake. The woman by myself has been baking for the past 10 years. That is for me, there's nothing entrepreneurial about that. I will not take you to zero. That's the challenge that we have. That is why, honestly, we're not making a lot of impact. We are not.

Interviewer: Do you believe that EEPs developed in the West can be successfully adapted to the Nigerian context? If so, what modifications are necessary?

EEN02: Yeah, I think so. To a large extent, we can only copy a few things because their problems are different from our problems. True. Their vocabularies are different from our vocabularies. If you bring it wholly the way it is, nothing you may not achieve much. In fact, as far as I'm concerned, that's one of the problems we have as far as our entrepreneurship development is concerned because we are copying everything, they give to us. It's not working. It's not working. Now, I don't see the reason why we cannot. We have an entrepreneurship system within our local communities that we are not developing. For example, we have the IBO system of entrepreneurship or apprenticeship. That is an area I feel if we work on, it will do more than what we are doing now. The foreign countries, they may call you VC and all of those things. But this is a system where you take somebody, the person spends some months with you, and then when the person is done, you set up that person and the person continues. Now, that relationship is still maintained. If the person has a problem, the person still comes back to you.

The person still sees you as the boss. Even though he's running his own business, he still sees you as the boss. The person still comes to you for a guide on, okay, I think the challenge I'm having, how am I going to go about it? Those are the things that a regular VC will not do for you. VCs, when they fund you, they take a part of your business. You can't just go to them for advice and all of that, except when they have a very big stake in your business. That's where they get involved in control things. But if we run the entrepreneurship system that we have within our various communities, the Yorubas have this, the Hausas have this, the Igbos have this if our schools should go in... In fact, I'm surprised. It's an embarrassment to me that a school like Harvard is studying the entrepreneurship system in New England, and they are trying to adapt it to what they have, that is what we should be doing. We just copied their own and we're not using it to solve a problem. They will come in and copy what we have and then they will restructure it.

In the next few years, that system will probably be renamed and then it will be exported back to us and you'll see us celebrating over it. We are not solving the problems we are supposed to solve. We are not doing what we're supposed to do, and that is a challenge. I can tell you this, you can make your findings. Most of the businesses that make money in Nigeria, you don't get to see them on the pages of newspapers.

Thank you.